

DOSSIÊ

“Social Engineering and Modernity: The Impacts of Social Darwinism and Eugenics in the Intellectual Context of Brazil and Portugal”

COORDINATION

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Apresentação ao Dossiê Temático “*Engenharia Social e Modernidade: Os Impactos do Darwinismo Social e da Eugenia no Contexto Intelectual do Brasil e de Portugal*”

Presentation of the Thematic Dossier “*Social Engineering and Modernity: The Impacts of Social Darwinism and Eugenics in the Intellectual Context of Brazil and Portugal*”

Welcome to the dossier

Aiming to deepen the understanding of the influences of social Darwinism and eugenics in the Portuguese and Brazilian contexts, the organizers of this dossier started an investigation process during the 9^o *Congresso Internacional de Antropologia da Asociación de Antropólogos Iberoamericanos en Red — AIBR* (9th International Anthropology Congress by the *Asociación de Antropólogos Iberoamericanos en Red*), held at the National Autonomous University of Mexico (UNAM - Universidade Nacional Autônoma do México) in August 2023. The theme panel organized by Daniel Florence Giesbrecht, entitled “Os Limites da Antropologia: Impactos do Darwinismo Social e da Eugenia nas Propostas de Engenharia Social entre os Finais do Século XIX e Meados do Século XX” (The Limits of Anthropology: Impacts of the Social Darwinism and Eugenics in Social Engineering Proposals in the Late 19th and Mid-20th Centuries), aimed to foster an integrated analysis of these issues. The main purpose was to enable the presentation of studies that addressed both transdisciplinarity and interdisciplinarity promoting a broader and fluid approach regarding the consequences of such concepts in their most diverse aspects.

Considering the Panel success, evidenced by the commitment shown by the participant researchers, the quality of the works presented, and the discussions carried out, we concluded that the publication of such contributions is extremely valuable. It also create the possibility of gathering other authors, whose studies are fundamental to the theme proposed. Therefore, we are pleased to present the Dossier “Social Engineering and Modernity: the Impacts of Social Darwinism and Eugenics in the Intellectual Context of Brazil and Portugal”, which has just been published.

To inaugurate this collection, it seems relevant to point out that eugenics influenced the understanding and management of themes such

as childhood, mental “diseases” and criminality, and proposed a focus on genetics linked to racial improvement in several areas of the human life. For this reason, it advocated that the individuals’ health and genetic quality had to be protected from birth, which demanded the implementation of practices and policies aimed at selecting and promoting the development of children that met the requirements set. This is the theme addressed by Joana Vale Guerra in *A Crença na Inferioridade Moral e Intelectual das Crianças Pobres em Portugal: Um Ponto de Viragem* (The Belief in the Moral and Intellectual Inferiority of Poor Children in Portugal: A Crucial Point). According to Joana Guerra, in Portugal, not only was approaching children’s poverty fundamental to fight “social evils” in the light of hygienist principles, but also to promote the improvement of the national race. The moralization of children of poor families was considered a state responsibility, which led to the creation of institutions devoted to education, social, and hygienic care, based on scientific and pedagogical concepts strongly influenced by Darwinism and eugenics. To support her arguments, that author highlights the social, political, and cultural background that resulted in the approval of the Childhood Protection Law of 27th May 1911.

Still looking into eugenicist and hygienic approaches in the Portuguese context, the article co-authored by Jaqueline Moares de Almeida and Daniel Florence Giesbrecht, introduces a strong issue as suggested by its title: “*Criar Cidadãos Perfeitos para uma República Máscula, Forte e Virtuosa*”: *O Primeiro Congresso Nacional Feminista e de Educação em Lisboa (1924) e a Modernização da Desigualdade* (“Bringing up Perfect Citizens for a Masculine, Strong and Virtuous Republic”: The First National Feminist Congress in Lisbon (1924) and the Modernization of Inequality). Taking advantage of the commemoration of the one hundredth anniversary of the First Feminist Congress in Lisbon, organized by the National Council of Portuguese Women (CNMP - Conselho Nacional das Mulheres Portuguesas), those authors explored the connections between a type of feminism and a hygienist nation project aimed at racial improvement. According to those authors, the CNMP institutional feminism that claimed dignity and equality of opportunities for women was inserted in the social reform project based on eugenic principles. The study challenges the conventional idea that the eugenics was a single and diverse movement, mainly developed under the guidance of Anglo-Saxon states and very often associated with conservative and authoritative political projects. Conversely, the study seeks to demonstrate that eugenics also attracted the

adhesion of progressist political groups, such as feminist, liberal and socialist organizations.

It seems relevant to mention that the Catholic church played a crucial role in the opposition to radical eugenic measures (such as sterilization, abortion, and birth control), mainly in countries of Latin origin such as Portugal and Brazil. Regarding this issue, in Portugal, António Rafael Amaro, who wrote *Eugenismo, Higienismo e Racismo em Portugal na Primeira Metade do Século XX* (Eugenics, Hygienist Movement, and Racism in Portugal in the First Half of the 20th Century), highlighted the influence and dissemination of hygienist, eugenicist, and racist conception in the Portuguese society of that time. According to that author, the hygienist tradition, the Catholic opposition, and the low acceptance of eugenics among the conservative liberal and progressist circles in Portugal limited the acceptance of eugenicist theory and practices in that country.

As regards Brazil, the article entitled *Eugenia e Catolicismo no Brasil: Um Estudo a partir da Produção Intelectual Católica do Rio de Janeiro nas Décadas de 1920 e 1930* (Eugenics and Catholicism in Brazil: a Study from the Catholic Intellectual Production in Rio de Janeiro in the 1920s and 1930s), authored by Daniel Florence Giesbrecht, investigates the complex intersection between eugenics, the Catholic church and discourse power. Based on bibliographic and documental sources, including Catholic publications in Rio de Janeiro in the 1920s and 1930s, the study sheds some light on complex power dynamics, discursive control, and resistance between eugenics and religion, thus offering some perceptions of a fundamental period in the history of science and faith relationships.

Despite the Catholic resistance to biopolitical interventions in human reproduction, some Brazilian eugenicists defended openly quite polemical measures that aimed to improve the national “race” characteristics. In the article *Renato Kehl e o Radicalismo Eugênico no Brasil dos Anos 1930: uma Análise a partir da Obra Sexo e Civilização: Aparas Eugênicas (1933)* (Renato Kehl and the Eugenicist Radicalism in Brazil in the 1930s: an Analysis from the Work entitled Sex and Civilization: Eugenicist Trimming (1933)), Vanderlei Sebastião de Souza examines the eugenicist radicalism in Brazil in the 1930s, emphasizing the ideas defended by Renato Kehl in his book *Sexo e Civilização* (Sex and Civilization). Considered the main leadership in the Brazilian eugenicist movement, Kehl expressed extremism in eugenicist practices and defended violent measures of racial segregation and human reproduction control.

By defending that most of the “illnesses”, not only those that affected the body but also the psychological ones, which they believed were genetic, eugenicists justified the implementation of policies such as forced sterilization and institutional segregation of individuals with “mental disorders”, aiming to prevent the transmission of characteristics considered undesirable. However, in many cases, those practices were used to justify the imprisonment and reinforce the punishment of individuals identified as inferior due to other reasons such as gender, ethnicity, political positions, among other characteristics. In his work, *Demolindo Paradigmas da Saúde Mental Brasileira: O Hospital Psiquiátrico de Barbacena e sua Nova Identidade como Museu* (Demolishing Paradigms of the Brazilian Mental Health), Karen Cristina Galletto proposes a reflection upon the useful role of psychiatry in the social construction of “madness” and in the isolation practices that represented power and exclusion structures. Her study examines specifically the Psychiatric Hospital Colônia in Barbacena, Minas Gerais, Brazil, and reveals abusive and dehumanizing practices. That author employs the Dark Heritage concept to explore how the memory of horrors lived in that space might contribute to raise people’s awareness and to the seek social justice.

In relation to criminality, some eugenicists sustained that deviant conducts were genetically predisposed, which enabled the early identification of criminal behavior traits. In such situation, physical anthropology gained a relevant role by employing techniques such as anthropometry and phrenology to measure and analyze physical characteristics that might indicate a criminal behavior. Scholars such as Cesare Lombroso (1835–1909), and his theories about the “born criminal” individual, and Paul Broca (1824–1880), who pioneered craniometric studies, were considered symbols of advancement in that moment.

In *The Identity of Crime: Contributions from Medicine and Physical Anthropology in Portugal (1880–1940)*, Patrícia Ferraz de Matos develops a thorough analysis of how people considered criminals were identified between the late 19th century and the late 1930s in the country, based on theories and practices related to “criminal anthropology”, mainly from medical and legal works, including those by António Mendes Correia (1888–1960).

The co-authored article *O Contexto Político-Científico da Eugenia no Eixo Brasil-Uruguai: Uma Análise Crítica do Quadrante Político Proposto por Maurizio Meloni* (The Eugenics Political-Scientific Context in the Brazil-Uruguay Axis: A Critical Analysis of the Political Framework Proposed by Marizio Meloni),

written by Leonardo Dallacqua de Carvalho and Angelo Tenfen Nicoladeli, examines the use of a political framework developed by the sociologist and professor at the Deakin University, Maurizio Meloni, as an analytical and didactic tool to understand the eugenics policy. Although it was originally conceived based on the European and the United States eugenics, those authors sharply question whether Latin-American experiences can be contextualized within the same methodologies proposed by Meloni. To achieve that aim, they analyze four prominent figures in the eugenics field in Brazil and in Uruguay, namely Renato Kehl (1889–1978), Roquette-Pinto (1884–1954), Paulina Luisi (1875–1950), and Belisário Penna (1836–1906), positioning them in the framework to exemplify the application of such analysis structure.

Currently, issues such as antisemitism and the relations with Jewish communities still generate polemic and heated debates. The prejudice and violence against Jews as well as the extremism defended by Zionist groups show the relevance of a deeper analysis of the historical and social roots of those issues. The trajectory of the Jews and the Marranos (new Christians) is particularly revealing, not only due to the persecution they endured for centuries, but also for the resistance and survival strategies adopted by those communities. The article by João Paulo Avelãs Nunes, entitled *Judeus e Marranos, em Portugal e no Brasil, na Primeira Metade do Século XX: Anti-semitismo e Darwinismo Social?* (Jews and Marranos in Portugal and in Brazil in the First Half of the 20th Century: Social Anti-Semitism and Darwinisms?) firstly seeks to characterize the evolution of Portuguese individuals of Jewish origin from the early 16th century to the early 19th century. Next, it analyzes the specific situation of Portuguese and Brazilian individuals of Marrano origin from 1830 to the period immediately following World War II and the post-Holocaust period. The article also discusses the possibilities and risks of setting patrimonialization and socio-cultural intervention strategies based on historical production and in other social sciences as well as on the memory and post-memory of Jews and Marranos in Portugal and Brazil.

Brazil is a country characterized by mixed-race and ethnic diversity, influenced by a wide variety of peoples, where social Darwinism has generated intense debates, as previously mentioned. If it were true that social evolution depends on the racial composition and that there is a hierarchy among races, Brazilian mixed-race society would be condemned to an “inferior evolution level”. Miscegenation would worsen the situation since the racial mixture would degrade the qualities of races considered superior, thus leading to decadence. In *Tão Bom Como Tão Bom: Discursos Afro-Brasileiros, Racismo e Projeto*

de Nação na Bahia (1889-1937) (As Good as Good: African-Brazilian Discourses, Racism, and Nation Project in Bahia), Flávio Gonçalves dos Santos examines the position of African-Brazilian individuals in relation to racist discourses. Bahia, with its predominant population of African descendant people and as a center of racial ideologies, mainly in the Medical School and by intellectuals such as Nina Rodrigues, is a geographical landmark. The text focuses on the perceptions of African-Brazilian individuals regarding scientific racism and their strategies to fight it.

Closing the Dossier, the analysis focuses on the eugenicist thought production issue, mainly in southern Brazil. In the text entitled *Eugenia, Pensamento Social e Discursos Identitários no Brasil: Entre “Heróis Capengas”, “Urupês de Pau Podre” e “Manchas Loiras”* (Eugenics, Social Thought, and Identity Discourses in Brazil: between stumbling heroes, wood ear mushrooms, and blond spots), written by Maria Julieta Weber, the author explores eugenic debates and their repercussions in the Brazilian social thought, emphasizing national and regional identity discourses. In the first part, Julieta Weber examines the relations between eugenics and social thought, integrating elements of sanitation, hygienist practices, and the national identity construction. Next, she analyzes the intellectual production of identity representation in the South of the country, focusing on the ideas put forward by Bento Munhoz da Rocha Netto (1905-1973) and Wilson Martins (1921-2010), both writers, politicians, and university professors in the state of Paraná. Those intellectuals oppose the regionalist theoretical model of the Brazilian formation elaborated by Gilberto Freyre (1900-1987) and offer a rather intriguing alternative perspective to the regional identity construction.

To sum up, the comparison of the impacts of social Darwinism and eugenics in Portugal and Brazil revealed how scientific concepts were instrumentalized according to the cultural, historical, and religious particularities of each country. Thus, the analysis of each of these complex and multifaceted domains requires interdisciplinary approaches based on the integration of several knowledge areas, including history, social sciences, psychology, medicine, education, and religion. In addition, examining such themes from different analysis scales is necessary, considering both the different regional perspectives and employing comparative studies to recognize the importance of cultural peculiarities in the formation of identities and in the social dynamics over time.

According to René Remond, while history promotes the observation of changes, it also has the mission to propose the history of history seeking to elucidate “the trails of transformations in society” and “great oscillations of the movement of ideas”¹. Therefore, we expect that the eleven articles gathered in this Dossier will contribute significantly to the advancement of knowledge of the history of sciences, thus triggering new discussions and further investigations.

Enjoy the reading!

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(Organizers)

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¹ REMOND, René. “Uma história presente” In REMOND, René (Org.). *Por uma história política*. Rio de Janeiro: FGV Editora, 2003, p. 13.

Renato Kehl and the eugenic radicalism in Brazil of the 1930s:
an analysis based on the work *Sexo e civilização: aparas
eugênicas* (1933)

Renato Kehl e o radicalismo eugênico no Brasil dos anos 1930:
uma análise a partir da obra *Sexo e civilização: aparas eugênicas*
(1933)

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Resumo

O objetivo deste artigo é analisar o radicalismo eugênico no Brasil dos anos 1930, com destaque para as ideias defendidas por Renato Kehl em seu livro *Sexo e civilização: aparas eugênicas*, publicado em 1933. Considerado a principal liderança do movimento eugênico brasileiro, Kehl também foi o eugenista que melhor sintetizou o extremismo das práticas eugênicas, caracterizado pela defesa de medidas violentas de segregação racial e controle da reprodução humana. Busco compreender especialmente o diálogo de Renato Kehl com as ideias e projetos intelectuais e políticos em jogo durante a década de 1930, atentando tanto para o contexto nacional quanto internacional. Neste sentido, analiso a publicação de *Sexo e civilização* como resultado dos diálogos e articulações de Kehl com a eugenia negativa de países como a Alemanha e Estados Unidos, ao mesmo tempo que coloco sua obra em perspectiva com os projetos e as ideologias em disputa durante o governo Vargas. Estes contextos são explorados a partir das discussões promovidas por Renato Kehl em torno de dois paradigmas centrais na história da eugenia: a esterilização eugênica e a miscigenação racial.

Palavras-Chave: Renato Kehl. Eugenia. Brasil. Esterilização Eugênica. Miscigenação Racial.

Abstract

This article aims to analyze eugenic radicalism in Brazil in the 1930s, emphasizing the ideas defended by Renato Kehl in his book *Sexo e civilização: aparas eugênicas*, published in 1933. Considered the main leader of the Brazilian

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Eugenic Movement, Kehl was also the eugenicist who best synthesized the extremism of eugenic practices, characterized by the defense of violent measures of racial segregation and control of human reproduction. I seek to understand Renato Kehl's dialogue with the ideas and intellectual and political projects at play during the 1930s, paying attention to both the national and international context. In this sense, I analyze the publication of *Sexo e civilização* as a result of Kehl's dialogues and articulations with the negative eugenics of countries such as Germany and the United States, at the same time that I place his work in perspective with the projects and ideologies in dispute during the Vargas government. These contexts are explored based on discussions promoted by Renato Kehl around two central paradigms in the history of eugenics: eugenic sterilization and racial miscegenation.

Keywords: Renato Kehl. Eugenics. Brazil. Eugenic Sterilization. Racial Miscegenation.

Introduction

“There is no solution to the social ills outside the laws of biology. There is no rational policy, independent of biological principles, capable of bringing peace and happiness to all peoples. Economic policy, conservative, democratic, socialist, fascist, communist, all these policies and forms of government *fail* if they are not inspired by the dictates of the science of life. That is why politics is per excellence biological politics, politics based on eugenics.”¹

The excerpt above was taken from the epigraph that Renato Kehl produced for his book *Sexo e civilização: aparas eugênicas*, published in 1933. The book presented a set of ideas that reaffirmed the Brazilian eugenicist's adherence to the biological-racial radicalism of the 1930s, characterized by the defense of negative eugenics. The epigraph can be read as a summary of the unwavering belief in eugenics as a way of solving the problems of modern nations. In Renato Kehl's opinion, no national state, government, or political regime, regardless of its ideological position, would be successful if it did not implement a truly biological policy, “a policy based on eugenics.” Politics itself, seen as a rational practice “capable of bringing peace and happiness to all peoples”, was confused with biological principles, since the control of social issues and the future of nations depended on the eugenic capacity of their population. Eugenics thus appeared as a biopolitics par excellence,

¹ KEHL, Renato. *Sexo e civilização: aparas eugênicas*. Rio de Janeiro: Livraria Francisco Alves, 1933.

according to the concept used by Michel Foucault to understand the meanings of managing the lives of populations in the era of modern governmentality².

The epigraph also pointed to the complex international context of the 1930s, marked by the ideological clash between democracy, liberalism, fascism, and communism. Despite the different projects that separated these regimes, Kehl understood that they would all fail if they did not adopt a strict eugenics policy. This statement also signaled the widespread use that both the reactionary right and liberals and the left and social democrats made of eugenics in the first decades of the 20th century, each in their way. As historian Mark Adams points out, eugenics was not just a reactionary movement of the extreme right, only associated with fascism, anti-Semitism, and American racial segregationism. According to the author, this understanding ended up overshadowing the uses that liberal intellectuals and politicians, communists, and left-wing activists made of eugenics in the first decades of the 20th century³. While it is true that the extreme right-wing regimes, especially in Nazi Germany, took eugenics to its ultimate consequences, we should not ignore the spread and use of eugenic ideas among German social democrats and socialists in the Weimar Republic, among communists in Stalin's Soviet Union, or even among doctors and intellectuals. The spread and use of eugenic ideas among German social democrats and socialists in the Weimar Republic, among communists in Stalin's Soviet Union, in Scandinavian social democracies, among English and American feminists, or even among doctors and intellectuals who supported the Mexican Revolution⁴.

In the case of Renato Kehl, it is important to say that his ideas and eugenic projects were in line with the reactionary regimes on the right of the political spectrum. It is no coincidence that his model of eugenics conversed with both American eugenicists and supremacists, as well as eugenicists associated with Nazism and German Aryanism. Kehl even went so far as to enthusiastically praise the eugenics policies implemented during the Third Reich, which he saw as an example that should be followed in the rest of the world⁵. One of the aims of this article is precisely to demonstrate that

² FOUCAULT, Michel. The right to die and power over life. In: _____. *A história da sexualidade: a vontade de saber*. Rio de Janeiro: Ed. Graal, 1997, p.125-149.

³ ADAMS, Mark B. (Org.). *The wellborn science: eugenics in Germany, France, Brazil and Russia*. New York: Oxford University Press, 1990, p. 219-220.

⁴ ADAMS, op. cit., 1990; STERN, Alexandra. *Eugenic nation: faults and frontier of better breeding in modern America*. California: University of California Press, 2005; STEPAN, Nancy. *A hora da eugenia: raça, gênero e nação na América Latina*. Rio de Janeiro: Fiocruz, 2005.

⁵ KEHL, Renato. "Devem ser esterilizados os enfermos incuráveis? (Inquérito entre os cientistas

the book *Sexo e civilização: aparas eugênicas* is the result of a dialog with the German and American eugenics movements, especially regarding adherence to negative eugenics, seen as a more draconian model of eugenic measures. The very desire to employ eugenics as a “biological policy” was in tune with the Nazi obsession with designing the regime’s political architecture from the biological and racial body of the nation⁶.

At the same time, this article aims to analyze Renato Kehl’s book as a response to the internal Brazilian context, marked by heated discussions about the racial question and the future formation of the Brazilian population. This period was experiencing the effects of the so-called “Revolution of 1930” and the rise to the presidency of Getúlio Vargas, a rancher from Rio Grande do Sul who had come to power after a troubled political coup. The first years of his government were marked by strong political instability and a crisis of legitimacy, which served as justification for the formation of an increasingly authoritarian and centralizing government, identified with European fascism and with an anti-communist bias⁷. On the other hand, the Vargas government was characterized by an aggressive nationalist policy, which further fueled discussions about immigration control, the occupation of the interior of the country, racial identity, as well as the future formation of the Brazilian man, topics that eugenicists wanted to intervene in directly.

In this article, I also try to point out that Renato Kehl’s actions in the early 1930s, including the publication of the book *Sexo e civilização: aparas eugênicas*, should be seen as strategies to occupy space in the country’s political and intellectual debate. At the same time, the article also highlights Renato Kehl’s movement to bring eugenics in Brazil into line with the intervention proposals circulating in the United States, Germany, and other northern European countries whose eugenics movements had been more successful in implementing eugenics as a state policy. This gave eugenicists the legitimacy to transform eugenics into a political tool, as an inescapable instrument for perfecting the “national race” and placing Brazil in the concert of eugenic nations.

brasileiros)”. *O Globo*. Rio de Janeiro. 3 Jan. 1934.

⁶ PROCTOR, Robert. *Racial hygiene: medicine under the Nazis*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 1988; WEISS, Sheila Faith. The Race Hygiene Movement In Germany 1904-1945. In: ADAMS, Mark (Org.). *The wellborn science: eugenics in Germany, France, Brazil and Russia*. New York: Oxford University Press, p. 8-68, 1990.

⁷ FAUSTO, Boris. *A história do Brasil*. São Paulo: Edusp, 2019; FERREIRA, Jorge; DELGADO, Lucília de Almeida Neves. *O tempo do nacional estatismo – vol. 2: do início da década de 1930 ao apogeu do Estado Novo*. Rio de Janeiro: Civilização Brasileira, 2019.

Renato Kehl and the eugenic radicalism of the 1930s

In 1933, when he published *Sexo e civilização*, Renato Kehl was already a prestigious author in intellectual circles, especially in the medical field, seen as the great leader of the Brazilian eugenics movement. The writer Monteiro Lobato, with whom he had a very close relationship, considered him the “father of eugenics” in Brazil, such was the recognition of his efforts to promote and institutionalize eugenic science⁸. Born in the interior of São Paulo, a son of German descendants who were already well established in Brazil, Kehl graduated from the Faculty of Medicine of Rio de Janeiro in 1915, when he became interested in the work of Francis Galton, British mathematician and naturalist who created eugenics as the science of racial improvement. Since then, his career has been intertwined with the history of the eugenics movement in Brazil⁹. In 1918, when he was already living in São Paulo, he led the creation of the Eugenics Society of São Paulo, an organization that had more than 140 members. A few years later, when he returned to Rio de Janeiro to take up the post of Sanitary Director of the National Department of Public Health (DNSP), he joined the Brazilian Mental Hygiene League, an institution that played an important and ongoing role in spreading eugenics among Brazilian doctors and psychiatrists.

At the end of the 1920s, when eugenics had become common parlance among intellectuals, Renato Kehl created the *Boletim de Eugenia*, a monthly periodical that circulated between 1929 and 1933. The periodical played an important role not only in spreading eugenic ideas but also in rallying the movement’s supporters around Kehl’s leadership. As a result of the growing interest in eugenics, the First Brazilian Congress of Eugenics was held in 1929, in which Kehl took part as one of the organizers. By this time, Kehl had already distanced himself from the health movement, which he had joined 10 years earlier, and joined the radical eugenics movement that would mark his career from the late 1920s onwards. This rupture became more evident with the release of the book *Lições de Eugenia*, published in 1929¹⁰. The work established

⁸ Letter from Monteiro Lobato to Renato Kehl. São Paulo, (No date) - Renato Kehl Personal Fund. Department of Archives and Documentation of the Casa de Oswaldo Cruz, DAD-COC. In the same correspondence, Monteiro Lobato apologized for having dedicated his “O choque de raças” (The Black President) to Renato Kehl, a book that Lobato defined as a “pro-eugenics war cry”. At the end of the letter, as a way of expressing his identification with Kehl and the theme of eugenics, he wrote: “We need to launch, to vulgarize these ideas. Humanity needs only one thing: pruning. It is like a vineyard.

⁹ SOUZA, Vanderlei Sebastião de. *Renato Kehl e a eugenia no Brasil: ciência, raça e nação no entreguerras*. Guarapuava: Eduni, 2019.

¹⁰ KEHL, Renato. *Lições de eugenia*. Rio de Janeiro: Francisco Alves, 1929a.

a closer conversation with Mendelian eugenics practiced in the United States and Germany, which guided harsher measures of eugenic intervention, such as racial segregation, eugenic sterilization, and marriage control¹¹. Launched during the First Brazilian Congress of Eugenics, the book was harshly criticized by anthropologists Edgar Roquette-Pinto and Alvaro Fróes da Fonseca, who classified the work as a pseudoscience, a set of Aryanist ideologies that were not supported by “modern” anthropological studies¹².

Criticisms of Renato Kehl’s book point to a clear division that would gain even more strength in the intellectual and scientific field in the 1930s. Due to the ideological radicalization in the early years of the Vargas government, the generation of intellectuals formed during the First Republic period was strongly mobilized by the challenge of understanding Brazilian society, its culture, and its political life. Intending to intervene in government discussions and guide the debate on the country’s modernization, these intellectuals constructed different interpretations and diagnoses of Brazil and Brazilians, the reasons for economic and civilizational backwardness, the role of the state and its institutions, racial composition and national identity, among other topics considered key to the country’s development and civilization, the role of the state and its institutions, racial composition, and national identity, among other issues considered key to the country’s development¹³.

It was precisely in the 1930s that essays with profound historical and sociological reflections on Brazil and Brazilian society appeared, works that would become classics of social and intellectual thought. In the artistic and cultural field, modernism also emerged in this context as a critical power capable of transforming art and literature into works of interpretation and denunciation of Brazilian “problems”. Among them, we can highlight authors such as Jorge Amado, Graciliano Ramos, Cecília Meireles, José Lins do Rego, Rachael de Queiroz, and Érico Veríssimo, among other writers who had in common a strong engagement with political and social issues¹⁴.

¹¹ Ibid.

¹² Texts by Roquette-Pinto and Alvaro Fróes da Fonseca can be consulted in the Proceedings of the First Brazilian Congress of Eugenics. PROCEEDINGS OF THE EUGENICS CONGRESS. In: *Actas e Trabalhos do Primeiro Congresso Brasileiro de Eugenia*. Rio de Janeiro, vol. I, 1929, p. 11-42. For more details on Roquette-Pinto and Fróes da Fonseca’s clashes with Renato Kehl, see SOUZA, Vanderlei Sebastião de. *Em busca do Brasil: Edgar Roquette-Pinto e o retrato antropológico brasileiro (1905-1935)*. Rio de Janeiro: Fiocruz; FGV Editora, 2017.

¹³ SCHWARCZ, Lília Moritz. *O espetáculo das raças: cientistas, instituições e questão racial no Brasil*. São Paulo: Companhia das Letras, 1993; STEPAN, op. cit., 2005.

¹⁴ ROSSI, Luiz Gustavo Freitas. *As cores da revolução: a literatura de Jorge Amado nos anos 30*. São Paulo: Annablume, 2009; BUENO, Luís. *Uma história do romance de 30*. São Paulo: Edusp, 2006.

These works pointed to different interpretations of the viability of Brazil and Brazilians on the international stage, especially when considering the country's racial background, which was strongly marked by miscegenation. On the one hand, there were intellectuals, such as Oliveira Vianna, Monteiro Lobato, and Renato Kehl, who projected rather pessimistic readings and diagnoses of Brazilian racial formation, almost always informed by theories and concepts originating from scientific racism. For them, Brazil's great dilemma, the reason for the nation's "ills", was a "race issue". It was on this aspect that intellectuals, science, the state, and its institutions had to act, promoting policies of racial and social selection according to eugenic principles¹⁵. On the other hand, intellectuals linked to the field of emerging social sciences, including Roquette-Pinto, Arthur Ramos, and Gilberto Freyre, promoted more optimistic interpretations of Brazilian racial identity, refuting scientific racism and stigmas about miscegenation. In the view of this generation, the country's problems were not related to race or racial mixing, but to historical and sociological problems, linked to the slave-owning past, public health problems, illiteracy, and political disorganization, in line with the perspective that had already been built up during the First Republic¹⁶.

It was in this intellectual and political context that Renato Kehl projected himself as a prominent eugenicist. Despite the bluntness of the criticism directed at him during the First Brazilian Eugenics Congress, his reputation seems not to have been shaken, as he continued to lead the eugenics movement with great enthusiasm. As well as tirelessly promoting eugenic ideas in the press and on the pages of the *Boletim de Eugenia*, he led a group of eugenicists around the creation of the Central Brazilian Commission of Eugenics (CCBE) in 1931, an organization that aimed to "maintain interest in the study of heredity and eugenics in the country"¹⁷. In essence, the commission had been set up in an interest in occupying a space with the Vargas government, advising on government eugenics policy projects, as Kehl himself had pointed out in the pages of the *Boletim de Eugenia*. At the same time, Kehl recalled that the Commission was the result of "intense correspondence with the main associations that exist in Europe and North America", and

¹⁵ SCHWARCZ, op. cit., 1993; SOUZA, op. cit., 2017.

¹⁶ LIMA, Nísia Trindade; HOCHMAN, Gilberto. "Condenado pela raça, absolvido pela medicina: o Brasil descoberto pelo movimento sanitário da Primeira República". In: MAIO, Marcos Chor; SANTOS, Ricardo Ventura (Org.). *Raça, ciência e sociedade*. Rio de Janeiro: Editora Fiocruz, 1996, p. 23-40.

¹⁷ KEHL, op. cit., 1933, p. 263.

was affiliated with the International Federation of Eugenics Associations¹⁸. Among the members of the Commission was none other than Belisário Penna, Renato Kehl's father-in-law and then Minister of the newly created Ministry of Education and Public Health, seen as a figure who could bring the Vargas government closer to the eugenics movement¹⁹.

The debate on eugenics seemed to have reached its peak at this point in the 1930s. Not by chance, Kehl wrote in 1933 that “the present era is the era of eugenics”, in a reference to the success of eugenics in different countries around the world²⁰. In the case of Brazil, in addition to a well-established institutional network, eugenic ideas were becoming recurrent discussions, as if eugenics' time had come. An example of this could be seen in the debate that the Constituent Assembly of 1933-34 promoted around immigration policy, the application of prenuptial exams, and the inclusion of eugenics education in Brazilian schools. The issue of immigration policy was undoubtedly the one that gave eugenicists the greatest visibility. In the sessions in which the legislation project was discussed, eugenicists were quoted and consulted quite frequently, which contributed to the approval of strict legislation around immigration control²¹. Renato Kehl's name was also recurrently mentioned in parliamentary speeches, as he had also been appointed by the Vargas government to sit on a commission that drew up the pre-project regulating the flow of immigrants. This commission was chaired by none other than Oliveira Vianna, an intellectual well-known for his relations with the eugenics movement and his publications on the Brazilian racial issue²².

In the face of this scenario, Renato Kehl doubled down on his radical eugenics, taking on an agenda increasingly identified with restrictive measures on human reproduction and racial selection. In his view, every effort should be made to prevent the reproduction of individuals considered undesirable. It was in this context, and with this racist perspective, that Renato Kehl published the book *Sexo e civilização: aparas eugênicas*. The work expressed not only the extremism of his ideas but also a convinced optimism about

¹⁸ KEHL, Renato. “Porque se fundou a C.C.B.E”. *Boletim de Eugenia*. Rio de Janeiro, mar 1931, ano III, n. 27, p. 2.

¹⁹ On Belisário Penna's career, his relationship with the Vargas government and his involvement with the eugenics movement, see CARVALHO, Leonardo Dallacqua. *O saneador do Brasil: saúde pública, política e integralismo na trajetória de Belisário Penna (1868-1939)*. Tese (Doutorado em História das Ciências) — Casa de Oswaldo Cruz/Fiocruz, Rio de Janeiro, 2019.

²⁰ KEHL, op. cit., 1933, p. 11.

²¹ PROCEEDINGS OF THE NATIONAL CONSTITUENT ASSEMBLY. *Imprensa Nacional*. Rio de Janeiro, 22 volumes, 1935. Available: <https://bd.camara.leg.br/bd/discover>; accessed: March 10, 2024.

²² SOUZA, op. cit., 2017.

the uses that governments in different countries were making of eugenics, especially in northern Europe. With the collapse of liberalism, Kehl seemed to celebrate the rise of fascism, nationalism, and authoritarian regimes, which were increasingly willing to carry out biological policy as a state project. In the introductory pages to the 1933 book, he pointed out that the present time was an era of “revolutionary transformations”, marked by “a lively ferment of ideas and the violent realization of new facts”²³. In his view, everything was changing overnight, as if modernity had finally found its way. Nations were springing up with force, posing “new problems” and creating doctrines that, in his words, were putting down “deep roots in public opinion”. He celebrated the fact that eugenics was among these doctrines, “the doctrine of regenerating man within the norms of biology”²⁴.

His recent book even seemed to point to events taking place in Europe, especially in Germany, which was then celebrating the rise of Nazism. Renato Kehl’s references to Germany are quite recurrent in this period, even praising the very racial tribunal set up by Adolf Hitler’s government. In his opinion, Germany was the country that best addressed the eugenics issue, seen as a decisive instrument for strengthening the nation²⁵. On the other hand, as he pointed out in his 1933 book, eugenicists doubted universal suffrage and democracy, since they tended to level individuals and undermine the influence of the elites, the only group that would be able to govern. Democratic government was summed up as a government of “mediocre men”, or “inferior men”. Quoting the writer Madison Grant, one of the greatest defenders of Aryan supremacy in the United States, he recalled that “the true republic is governed by the fittest, the best, always represented by a small minority of the population”²⁶.

One of the arguments of this work is that Renato Kehl’s identification with authoritarian regimes and eugenic radicalism is directly linked to the close contact he had with Germany. Since the late 1920s, when he became director of Bayer in Brazil, a German multinational with roots in several countries, Kehl had built a direct connection with the company’s headquarters in Germany. This contact also enabled frequent trips to that country, some of them with extended stays, which allowed time for study, and personal contact

²³ KEHL, op. cit., 1933, p. 9.

²⁴ Ibid., p. 10.

²⁵ KEHL, op. cit., 1934.

²⁶ KEHL, op. cit., 1933, p. 39.

with eugenicists and eugenic associations in Germany, Sweden, Denmark, and Norway. His first trip to Germany was in 1928 when he spent five months traveling around northern Europe. This trip would have stimulated him to expand the dissemination of eugenics in Brazil, as could be seen from the launch of the *Boletim de Eugenia* three months after his return to Brazil. In the second issue of the journal, Kehl highlighted the need to create a Brazilian Institute of Eugenics in Brazil, allowing for “the new era in which Brazilian nationality will be taken care of, as the Berlin Institute of Eugenics does for German nationality”²⁷. In addition, the book *Lições de eugenia* (Lessons in Eugenics), published in June 1929, not only intended to teach the lessons in eugenics that he had learned in Germany but also pointed to the process of radicalizing his eugenics project. His contact with eugenics in that country had even brought him closer to Mendelian genetics, as he had confessed in correspondence with Toledo de Piza Junior, a geneticist at the Luiz de Queiroz Agricultural School and one of the main authorities on Brazilian genetics²⁸.

The book *Sexo and Civilização* should also be read as the result of Kehl’s second trip to Germany. At this time, the Nazis had already come to power and the German eugenics court was beginning to be set up, led by eugenicists who had spearheaded the eugenics movement during the Weimar Republic. Although German eugenics was a much more heterogeneous movement than is generally imagined before Nazism, as historian Sheila Weiss explains, there was a more extremist group identified with the ideologies of Aryan supremacy from the beginning of the 20th century. For them, the power of a nation was essentially a question of racial policy, which meant encouraging the reproduction of the descendants of the “Aryan race” and preventing the reproduction of undesirables, seen as “inferior races”. The German Eugenics Court itself, so praised by Renato Kehl, had the function of rigid racial selection, using policies of marriage control, sterilization, and compulsory hospitalization of the mentally ill, the application of euthanasia, if not mass elimination, as occurred at the end of the Nazi government²⁹.

²⁷ KEHL, Renato. “Instituto Brasileiro de Eugenia”. *Boletim de Eugenia*, Rio de Janeiro, Feb. 1929b, vol. 1, n. 2, p. 1.

²⁸ There are two pieces of correspondence in which Renato Kehl discusses the book *Lições de Eugenia* with Salvador Toledo Piza Junior, especially issues about Mendelian theory. Letter from Renato Kehl to Salvador Toledo Piza Junior. Rio de Janeiro, March 24, 1930; Letter from Renato Kehl to Salvador Toledo Piza Junior. Rio de Janeiro, August 19, 1930 (Fundo Pessoal Renato Kehl. Department of Archives and Documentation of the Casa de Oswaldo Cruz (DAD-COC).

²⁹ PROCTOR, op. cit., 1988; WEISS, op. cit., 1990.

Eugenic sterilization and control of human reproduction

There is no doubt that Renato Kehl was infected by the growing eugenic radicalism of countries like Germany, Norway, Denmark, and Sweden, or even English-speaking countries like the United States and England. It was through dialog with the eugenics movements in these countries that his eugenics project gained strength in the 1930s. In this respect, we differ from historian Nancy Stepan, who includes the eugenics model defended by Renato Kehl as part of the “Latin eugenics” paradigm, linked to the neo-Lamarckist tradition³⁰. In general terms, “Latin eugenics” was characterized by its association with hygiene and environmental reforms, maternal and child care, and sex education, seen as a “softer” model of eugenic intervention. Although the neo-Lamarckist theses were present in Renato Kehl’s early writings, he not only adhered to the Mendelian theses from the late 1920s onwards but also began to refute the theories on the inheritance of acquired characters. It is no coincidence that his 1933 book made a clear case for controlling human reproduction by imposing tougher measures associated with Mendelian theories³¹, as was being implemented in the Nordic countries.

As we will see below, *Sexo e civilização: aparas eugênicas* (Sex and civilization: eugenic trimmings), as its title suggests, had the main objective of promoting a debate on human reproduction based on the conceptions derived from Mendel’s laws of heredity. At least three chapters of the book are dedicated precisely to thinking about the theoretical aspects related to the foundations of eugenics, explicitly connected to the paradigms of Mendelian evolutionism. To carry out the “eugenic trimmings” and prevent the reproduction of undesirables, Kehl advocated the development of studies on the foundations of human heredity, seen as essential for supposed racial improvement and the fight against the factors responsible for human degeneration. It can be said that the book revolves around three main axes: the theoretical aspects involving eugenics and Mendelian genetics; the relations of eugenics with sexuality, marriages, and human reproduction; and the relations between miscegenation, degeneration, and racial selection.

³⁰ STEPAN, op. cit. 2005.

³¹ For Mendelian eugenicists, hereditary characteristics could only be transmitted from father to son through sexual reproduction, without any interference from environmental conditions. Renato Kehl’s famous phrase “the good are born ready” summed up the spirit of Mendelian eugenics. Although it was not a rule, many Mendelian eugenicists believed that only harsher measures stemming from negative eugenics, such as those that prevented the reproduction of undesirables, would have a practical effect on the process of improving future generations. KEHL, Renato. “Aparas médicas: a felicidade do ponto de vista médico e eugênico”. *Correio da Manhã*. Rio de Janeiro, August 30, 1930.

In the first two chapters of the book, Renato Kehl turns to the discussion of human degeneration, a theme that has haunted doctors, intellectuals, and public authorities since the 19th century, especially in Europe. With the growing urban and industrial process, it was feared that contact with poverty and proximity to the poor would hinder the process of natural selection, leading European civilization to moral and biological decadence. In addition, with the imperialist race underway, there was a fear that frequent contact between Europe and its colonies in the southern hemisphere, and the consequent interbreeding with so-called inferior peoples, would threaten Europe's supposed racial purity. This was already a central concern when Galton produced his first reflections on eugenics. From the beginning of the 20th century, this concern gained even more strength among eugenicists, whether due to the effects of the expansion of immigration and miscegenation, or the consequences of the First World War, which produced a mass of poor, sick, and mutilated war victims³².

Renato Kehl analyzes the process of human degeneration based on statistics collected in various countries and from the point of view of different European and North American eugenicists, including figures such as the Aryanist Madison Grant, author of *Passing of the Great Race*, one of the most influential works in the history of scientific racism³³. From these readings, Kehl concludes that human degeneration is an effect of the imbalances produced by modernity itself, between the rapid "growth of human scum", which he defined as the "multiplication of delinquents, amorals, imbeciles, madmen, and mentally retarded people", and the reduction of the "good part of the collectivity", the individuals of "good breeding"³⁴.

In the case of Brazil, Kehl presents an even more pessimistic scenario, as a series of Brazilian writers would have shown, referring to authors such as Nina Rodrigues, Oliveira Vianna, and Paulo Prado, intellectuals whose reflections are recognizably crossed by scientific racism. The Brazilian eugenicist goes so far as to ask, repeating the words of Paulo Prado, if the "extent of the evils that afflict us" is not "a consequence of the mixing of races?"³⁵. Kehl's answer is positive. According to him, in addition to the lack

³² KEVLES, Daniel. *In the name of eugenics: genetics and the uses of human heredity*. New York: Knopf, 1985. ADAMS, op. cit. 1990.

³³ BARKAN, Elazar. *The retreat of scientific racism*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1992.

³⁴ KEHL, op. cit., 1933, p. 15-16.

³⁵ Ibid., p. 19.

of natural selection caused by the forces of modernity, the “decadence of peoples” comes from “heterogeneous crossbreeding”, as is the case in Brazil³⁶.

The biggest dilemma for eugenicists was not that societies were degenerating rapidly, but that degenerate individuals would never produce “healthy offspring” fit for civilization. In Kehl’s view, degenerate parents would beget children who were also degenerate, mentally ill, criminals, delinquents, or incapable, most of them “incurable or incorrigible”³⁷. For Kehl, the determinism of biology taught that man is “a slave to his nature”, a prisoner of heredity, of “a force that inexorably subjugates him biologically, that imprints his temperament, his character”³⁸. This reality forced Kehl to conclude that there is nothing outside of biology. Education, religion, or any form of social policy would not be enough to regenerate humanity or make it more balanced. In many cases, education and the social environment serve only to “provide life resources and to encourage the procreation of undesirables for the species”³⁹. He concluded: “As long as the problem of human degeneration is not viewed from a biological point of view, we will always have to encounter bad social and individual clashes, crises, and threats to the peace of family, society, and between nations.”⁴⁰.

In the face of this scenario, Renato Kehl believed that only the application of restrictive measures would enable the consideration of racial improvement for future generations. It would be up to the state to not only encourage the reproduction of families of “good pedigree”, but also to prevent the reproduction of those supposed to be degenerate or inferior. He also believed that all countries should invest in “rational procreation”, even if this meant implementing a strict *birth control* policy, called birth control, using not only prenuptial examinations and marriage regulations but also harsher measures such as eugenic sterilization, as the United States and northern European countries were already doing. In his opinion, *birth control* was recommended as “an ultra-prophylactic measure against the plethora of mentally deficient people, human waste, and also as a defense for eugenicized couples”⁴¹.

³⁶ Ibid., p. 44.

³⁷ Ibid., p. 41.

³⁸ Ibid., p. 14.

³⁹ Ibid., p. 46.

⁴⁰ Ibid., p. 15.

⁴¹ Ibid., p. 198-199.

Birth control thus appears as one of the issues that most occupied Renato Kehl's attention in his book *Sexo e civilização: aparas eugênicas*. One of the most efficient ways of controlling the eugenic value of a nation was to improve birth control, whether through the practices of sex education and marriage guidance, or harsher measures of sterilization and racial segregation. For many Brazilian eugenicists, marriage guidance practices were ways of carrying out "negative eugenics" in a less radical way, without the need for sterilizing surgeries. In this case, it is understandable that even marriage counseling and female sex education were part of a restrictive reproductive policy, seen as efficient birth control measures⁴². It is no coincidence that Renato Kehl himself published a book in 1925 entitled *Como escolher um bom marido* (How to choose a good husband)⁴³, in which he advised young women on the importance of marriage and the role of female sexual and marital education in the eugenic formation of future generations.

Nancy Stepan points out that this relationship between race and gender was a common concern among eugenicists in the 1920s and 1930s, incorporated as an increasingly central aspect in discourses about the nation. As the social role of women was seen as primarily reproductive, it was women who bore the greatest responsibility for giving birth to healthy offspring. Nancy Stepan goes on to explain that "the desire to 'imagine' the nation in biological terms, to 'purify' the reproduction of populations in order to adapt them to hereditary norms" placed eugenics, race, and gender as aspects closely connected to the very debate on national identity politics⁴⁴. In this context, gender was one of the issues on the agenda of eugenicists and public authorities, above all because eugenics enabled the maintenance of control over female sexuality as well as over the reproductive and maternal role of women. At the same time, historiography has highlighted that more progressive eugenicists, or even women's rights activists, also saw eugenics as a possibility for debating the emancipation of women. For this group, eugenics stimulated female sex education and made it possible to think about the use of contraceptive methods, the debate on divorce, and even the right to abortion, issues that the feminist movement was facing at the time⁴⁵.

⁴² STEPAN, op. cit., 2005, p. 116.

⁴³ KEHL, Renato. *Como escolher um bom marido*. Rio de Janeiro: Livraria Francisco Alves, 1925.

⁴⁴ *Ibid.*, p. 117.

⁴⁵ KEVLES, op. cit., 1985; STEPAN, op. cit., 2005.

With regard to prenuptial exams, Renato Kehl believed that making them compulsory was an effective eugenic policy measure. This explains why eugenicists lobbied for the measure to be approved by the 1933-34 Constituent Assembly, with Kehl at the forefront of this movement. The final result ended up frustrating the expectations of the most radical eugenicists since the constituent assembly only recommended that prenuptial exams be carried out, without the weight of the obligation so desired by the eugenics movement. In Kehl's opinion, all couples should undergo mandatory examinations before getting married, including a thorough analysis of their family history up to the third degree. In the event of any risk to future generations, couples should be prevented from marrying, or submit themselves to sterilization surgery⁴⁶. For the eugenicist, the restriction on marriage should also be indicated in cases involving people of different classes or races, especially "with mestizos of the first generations". According to him, "it has been proven that such marriages are dysgenic, giving rise to physically, psychically and morally inferior types"⁴⁷. In these cases, Kehl also recommended eugenic sterilization.

The idea of sterilization as a way of controlling human reproduction was discussed at length by Kehl in his 1933 book. Although he had already defended sterilization in specific cases in the 1920s, according to an article published in the *Archivos Brasileiros de Hygiene Mental*⁴⁸ In the early 1930s, Kehl not only intensified his campaign to defend this measure but also broadened his understanding of the cases in which it should be indicated. It can be said that Kehl was mobilized by the broad debate that eugenicists were having in the 1930s around negative eugenics programs. It was precisely during this period that human sterilization had become a central theme for eugenicists, seen as one of the most necessary measures in controlling reproduction. Nancy Stepan argues that the introduction of discussions on sterilization was by far "the most dramatic change in the traditional norms that regulated the Western family and individual rights to reproduction"⁴⁹. Examples of this were the thousands of people compulsorily sterilized in the United States between 1907 and 1970, as well as the most violent cases in Germany during the Nazi government.

⁴⁶ KEHL, op. cit., 1933, p. 84-85.

⁴⁷ Ibid., p. 85.

⁴⁸ KEHL, Renato. "A esterilização dos grandes degenerados e criminosos". *Archivos Brasileiros de Hygiene Mental*, n.1, v.2, 1925.

⁴⁹ STEPAN, op. cit., 2005, p. 37.

In the pages of *Sexo e civilização*, Renato Kehl welcomed the fact that some European countries were looking enthusiastically at the recent passing of laws regulating sterilization, especially in Germany, Sweden, Denmark, and Switzerland⁵⁰. However, what caught the Brazilian eugenicist's attention was the sterilization laws underway in the United States, a country that had been carrying out sterilization surgeries as a measure to control human reproduction since 1907. Kehl looked more closely at the initiatives made by eugenicists Harry Laughlin, Ezra Gosney, and Paul Popenoe, eugenicists who led a series of campaigns in defense of *Birth Control* in the state of California, especially compulsory sterilization. In 1928, Gosney and Popenoe founded the *Human Betterment Foundation*, an institution focused on research into human reproduction and the role of sterilization for eugenic purposes⁵¹. In addition to translating articles by these authors for the *Eugenics Bulletin*, Kehl even corresponded with these eugenicists, through which they exchanged institutional information, research interests, and bibliographic material on their medical and scientific productions.

In his 1933 book, Kehl showed great enthusiasm for the benefits of sterilization, from which “the best results are expected”. In his opinion, if this measure “had been enacted by law earlier, its beneficial effects could already be assessed today”, so “it is necessary to look at the racial problem with a broad eugenic view [...] to understand the true usefulness of sterilization”⁵². Kehl argued that such a restrictive measure should be applied in different cases, from the mentally ill, the physically handicapped, criminals, or those with hereditary diseases, to cases in which the poor were unable to economically support their offspring. In his words, this “human waste” was “the cause of the misery, the misfortune of so many families, in whose midst degenerates of all kinds, cretins, idiots, criminals, scoundrels, drunks, and all manner of undesirables breed”⁵³.

In the case of Brazil, although the government never officially legislated on eugenic sterilization, there was a strong desire among eugenicists to regulate this measure. In addition to Renato Kehl's efforts, eugenicists associated with the Brazilian League for Mental Hygiene, including Alberto Farani, Pacheco e Silva, Cunha Lopes, and Ernani Lopes also campaigned

⁵⁰ KEHL, op. cit., 1933, p. 188.

⁵¹ STERN, op. cit., 2005, p. 158-159.

⁵² KEHL, op. cit., 1933, p. 71.

⁵³ Ibid., p. 190.

extensively for sterilization. Like Kehl, they believed that the regulation of this measure in Brazil was only a matter of time.

When the law on compulsory sterilization was passed in Germany by the Nazi government in 1933, these eugenicists welcomed the law with enthusiasm, even publishing it in full in the pages of the *Archivos Brasileiros de Hygiene Mental*⁵⁴. The sterilization law put into practice by Adolf Hitler's government was also covered by the major newspapers of the time, as can be seen in the survey that the newspaper *O Globo* carried out in January 1934 among Brazilian eugenicists. The interviews were also the newspaper's cover story, with one interview a day. Renato Kehl was one of those interviewed, expressing great enthusiasm for the sterilization measure passed in Germany. Others who also spoke in defense of the measure were Pacheco e Silva, Oscar Fontenelle, and Leonídio Ribeiro. Only two interviewees were against or made restrictions on its implementation: the anthropologist Edgard Roquette-Pinto and the doctor Leitão da Cunha, the latter a professor at the Faculty of Medicine in Rio de Janeiro and also a member of the 1933-34 Constituent Assembly⁵⁵.

In his interview with *O Globo*, which was the first in the series and took up the entire front page of the newspaper, Renato Kehl recalled that his opinion was already well known, referring to the lengthy treatment he had dedicated to this subject in his book *Sexo e civilização*, "which I have now published, following my recent trip to the north of the European continent"⁵⁶. By highlighting the publication of his book and his recent trip to Germany, when Nazism had already taken power, Kehl lent credentials that reaffirmed his notorious knowledge of the subject. So much so that he made a point of emphasizing that his opinion in favor of sterilization was "based on the study and observation of many years, an opinion that I believe to be definitive". Kehl not only praised the "judicious law" passed in Germany, a country that, according to him, was taking things seriously, but also pointed out that other countries were already applying this measure. When asked about the possibility of implementing a similar law in Brazil, he was convinced: "Despite

⁵⁴ "A lei alemã de esterilização dos doentes transmissores de taras". *Archivos Brasileiros de Hygiene Mental*, Rio de Janeiro, v.7, n.1. 1934. On the publication of this law in Brazil, see: WEGNER, Robert; SOUZA, Vanderlei Sebastião de. "Eugenia 'negativa', psiquiatria e catolicismo: embates em torno da esterilização eugênica no Brasil". *História, Ciência, Saúde-Manguinhos*, 2013, v. 20, n. 1, p. 263-288.

⁵⁵ O GLOBO. "Devem ser esterilizados os enfermos incuráveis? Inquérito entre os cientistas brasileiros". *O Globo*. Rio de Janeiro, Jan. 1934.

⁵⁶ KEHL, op. cit., 1934.

the routine and the fetishists, sterilization will become a reality in Brazil, in the future”⁵⁷.

By the end of the 1930s, when a wave of criticism of Nazism was beginning to gain momentum in different countries around the world, Kehl once again praised the eugenics policy of the Third Reich. In 1937, in his book *Por que sou Eugenista*, in which he celebrated 20 years of his eugenics campaign, he highlighted the success of that country’s sterilization law, which already had “1500 eugenics tribunals and 77 special appeal boards”. The Brazilian eugenicist made a point of stating that “when a country like this takes such a decision, it is because it is, in reality, an imperative of unquestionable scope”⁵⁸. According to Renato Kehl, the German Eugenics Court, which he defines as “a true code of racial protection”, “has impressed scientists and rulers in several countries, especially in northern Europe, who are gradually adopting the same regulations, only with a few variations”⁵⁹. It is worth remembering that his references to German eugenics were made shortly after another of Renato Kehl’s trips to Germany in 1937 when Nazism was already making strides toward the catastrophe that would explode two years later.

Eugenics, miscegenation, and degeneration

One of the themes that most mobilized Renato Kehl was undoubtedly the relationship between eugenics and racial miscegenation. The debate on miscegenation can be seen as the major paradigm of Brazilian social thought in the first decades of the 20th century. It was through miscegenation that Brazil was formed as a nation, in a process that involved Europeans, indigenous people, and Africans of the most varied racial origins. If in the 1930s there were intellectuals who believed in the myth of racial democracy as a solution for harmonious national integration, or those who saw racial mixing as an optimistic path towards whitening the nation, there were also those who pointed to racial mixing as the biggest obstacle to the formation of a eugenic nation. Renato Kehl was, obviously, in the latter group. Although he stated in the 1920s that Brazil would end up whitening itself “at the expense of a lot of Aryan coconut soap”, from the 1930s onwards he became progressively

⁵⁷ *Ibid.*, p. 1.

⁵⁸ KEHL, Renato. *Por que sou eugenista: 20 anos de campanha eugênica 1917-1937*. Rio de Janeiro: Francisco Alves, 1937.

⁵⁹ *Ibid.*, p. 98.

more pessimistic about the much-vaunted whitening thesis⁶⁰. In his view, it didn't seem admissible to think that the "mixing of all peoples" could lead to homogeneity, as the supporters of the whitening thesis believed⁶¹.

From the late 1920s onwards, his study of Mendelian genetics led him to understand that racial crossbreeding produced inferior or degenerate "hybrid types"⁶². This was a recurring understanding in the anthropological and genetic studies of that period, most of them strongly committed to scientific racism and Nordic Aryanism⁶³. In his book *Sexo e civilização*, the Brazilian eugenicist debated these studies, citing, for example, authors such as Swedish eugenicist Herman Lundborg and Norwegian Alfred Mjöen, whose works were translated by Kehl himself and published in the pages of *Boletim de Eugenia*. Based on these studies, Kehl commented, "It is impossible to deny, in the light of science", that miscegenation does indeed produce "inferior types". In addition, he pointed out that these and other studies, such as the work of Fritz Lentz, Ernest Rudin, and Herman Werner Siemens, internationally known German eugenicists and often cited by Kehl, provided a lucid defense of "Mendelian rigorism". In his opinion, Mendel's genetics made it possible to "predict the hereditary possibilities of a human cross, as well as within an animal cross, given natural exceptions"⁶⁴.

By following the argument of these authors, Kehl explained that no influence of the environment, disease, or any other morbid condition was more responsible for human degeneration than "heterogeneous crossbreeding", such as between whites and blacks, whites and Indigenous peoples, or whites and Asians. He said the excess of biological variation resulting from this crossbreeding was frighteningly taking place becoming the main threat to civilized societies. In a clear reference to Mendelian theories, he stated that hybrid types were responsible for "deviations from the genetic norm", concluding that "life in a society is all the more intense, disordered, full of vicissitudes, crimes, degeneration, the more heterozygous the elements that make it up"⁶⁵.

As a way of combating racial miscegenation, Renato Kehl even defended "racial inbreeding", going so far as to consider "family inbreeding" as a eugenic

⁶⁰ KEHL, Renato. "As questões de Raças". *Gazeta do Povo*, Curitiba, Oct. 1921.

⁶¹ KEHL, op. cit., 1933, p. 206.

⁶² KEHL, op. cit., 1929a; 1933.

⁶³ BARKAN, op. cit., 1992.

⁶⁴ KEHL, op. cit., 1933, p. 202-203.

⁶⁵ *Ibid.*, p. 44.

practice⁶⁶. In *Sexo e civilização*, the author explained that he was not defending incestuous marriages, but understood that marriages between “people of close kinship, of the same race and class, with optimal characters”, were indicated to face the great “evil of the race”, heterogeneous miscegenation⁶⁷. This procedure was called “ultra-eugenics”, a measure which, according to Kehl, could fulfill the “eugenic aims of achieving the utopia of social happiness”⁶⁸.

This “ultra-eugenics” was based on the understanding that the more homogeneous or uniform a society was, the more balanced it would be, whether in terms of psychic temperaments and social coexistence, or morphological or physiological aspects. In Kehl’s view, racial homogeneity would produce not only physical and intellectual superiority but also a political and civilizing order. Kehl recalled the cases of genetic selection carried out by producers of sheep, chickens, or even draft or saddle animals, who always sought “perfect uniformity” to obtain the best strains. In his words, “the breeder strives to maintain homogeneity by keeping choice animals as breeding stock and processing selected inbreeding”⁶⁹. These comparisons or examples from studies of animal and plant genetics were also quite common among eugenicists, especially those who used Mendelian genetics to think about the effects of racial mixing on human reproduction.

Turning to the case of Brazil, considered to be one of the most mixed-race countries in the world, Kehl lamented the fact that studies on “racial crossbreeding” were still incipient in the country. In any case, based on the studies produced by authors such as Nina Rodrigues, Paulo Prado, Oliveira Vianna, and Toledo Piza Junior, Kehl pointed out that there were enough elements to attest to the physical weakness and mental instability of mestizos in Brazil⁷⁰. In his sentence, strongly tempered by scientific racism, “the Brazilian mestizos of white and black (mulattos), are, for the most part, ugly and weak elements, often presenting the vices of their ancestors”. He concluded: “Their character is very unstable and they are therefore elements that disrupt national progress from an ethnic and social point of view.”⁷¹.

⁶⁶ Ibid., p. 240.

⁶⁷ Ibid., p. 241.

⁶⁸ Ibid. p. 247.

⁶⁹ Ibid., p. 242.

⁷⁰ Ibid., p. 200-202. Among Brazilian writers, he especially cited the works of Oliveira Vianna, a writer from Rio de Janeiro with whom he had a very close relationship. Kehl cited above all the book *Populações Meridionais* (Southern Populations), published in 1922, and *Raça e Assimilação* (Race and Assimilation), from 1932.

⁷¹ Ibid., p. 200.

Faced with the findings produced by scholars on the subject, even with the backing of internationally known scientists, Kehl stated that “the great evil of Brazil is an evil of race”⁷². That is why eugenicists could no longer be in favor of racial crossbreeding, especially those involving blacks, indigenous peoples, caboclos, and Asians. In his opinion, it was essential that drastic measures to control human reproduction also took into account the threat that miscegenation posed to the future of Brazil. Kehl believed that one of the most efficient ways of limiting the birth of these “undesirable elements” was precisely to build racial selection measures, whether through marriage control and racial segregation as such, or through eugenic sterilization and immigration selection.

In the 1930s, the debate on immigration was the topic that best summed up the expectations of eugenicists to achieve the much-desired racial selection, especially given the wide repercussion this topic had among the congressmen who took part in the National Constituent Assembly of 1933-34. For the Vargas government itself, the immigration issue was fundamental not only to attract healthy workers and supply the labor that sectors of the economy wanted but also to populate the national territory and contribute to the eugenic formation of the country⁷³. It is important to note that nowhere else in the world have discussions about immigration been more closely identified with the construction of national identity than in Brazil. Since the 19th century, the attraction of European immigrants was seen as an essential alternative to replace Africans, Indigenous peoples, and mestizos with “white people”, leading us to think that, in the future, Brazil would be mostly made up of European descendants.

For the members of the eugenics movement, immigration selection was an essential biological policy, as was already evident during the 1929 Eugenics Congress. In general, the agenda of discussions launched during the event even served as a parameter for the issues promoted during the Constituent Assembly of 1933-34. This was due to the widespread campaign by eugenicists in defense of immigration selection. Led by Kehl, the eugenics movement articulated its institutions, the press, and allied representatives so that eugenics demands were put on the agenda. This articulation gained strength especially because among the representatives some doctors and intellectuals identified with eugenic ideas, among them quite prestigious

⁷² *Ibid.*, p. 204.

⁷³ GERALDO, Endrica. *O 'perigo alienígena': política imigratória e pensamento racial no governo Vargas (1930-1945)*. Thesis (Doctorate in History) - Unicamp: Campinas, 2007.

figures such as Arthur Neiva, Miguel Couto, Pacheco e Silva, and Xavier de Oliveira⁷⁴.

During the discussions that took place in this committee, it was common to see quotes from eugenicists and anthropologists giving warnings of a need to base immigration legislation on eugenic criteria. Among the international intellectual authorities, there were mentions of Aryanists such as Madison Grant and Vacher de Lapouge, as well as allies of German “racial hygiene” such as John Alfred Mjoen, Fritz Lenz, and Herman Lundborg. Among Brazilians, the most mentioned names were Renato Kehl and Oliveira Vianna⁷⁵. Congressman Xavier de Oliveira, one of the representatives who put together the most arguments to justify the ban on undesirable immigrants, read an open letter that Renato Kehl had sent to the Constituent Assembly in session, in which he warned of the danger that the mixing of “heterogeneous races” represented for the future of Brazil⁷⁶. In this document, he repeated the arguments already present in his 1933 book, published precisely in the heat of the discussions promoted by the constituent assembly. In his words, if “an energetic immigration policy” was not approved, Brazil, “which is already a *melting pot* of races, will be dominated by xantho-negroid elements”⁷⁷.

Some representatives even used the issue of miscegenation as an argument to oppose the entry of non-European immigrants. There was an almost general understanding that European immigration was the most desirable since it would guarantee the racial homogeneity of the Brazilian population soon, referring to the whitening process underway. At the same time, the entry of Asians, Arabs, blacks, and Jews should be prevented or avoided. At the end of the discussions, the Constituent Assembly approved strongly racist legislation that, to a large extent, met the demands of the eugenics movement. In general, the Brazilian constitution repeated what US legislation had approved in the controversial *Johnson-Reed Act* of 1924, which created a quota law that favored European immigration by far, restricting the entry of other nationalities⁷⁸.

⁷⁴ SOUZA, Vanderlei Sebastião de. “Eugenia, racismo científico e antirracismo no Brasil: debates sobre ciência, raça e imigração no movimento eugênico brasileiro (1920-1930)”. *Revista Brasileira de História*, Jan-Apr, 2022, v. 42, n. 89, p. 93-115.

⁷⁵ ANNAES DA ASSEMBLEIA..., op. cit., 1935.

⁷⁶ OLIVEIRA, Xavier de. “Discurso”. In: *Annaes da Assembleia Nacional Constituinte*. National Press. Rio de Janeiro, Vol. 6, p. 449-482, 1935, p. 473. Available: <https://bd.camara.leg.br/bd/handle/bdcamara/8128>; accessed: March 10, 2024.

⁷⁷ KEHL, op. cit., 1933, p. 207.

⁷⁸ SERFERTH, Giralda. “Construindo a nação: hierarquias raciais e o papel do racismo na política de

Final considerations

As pointed out at the beginning of this article, the 1930s scenario in Brazil was marked by strong intellectual and political ambiguities. At the same time as the eugenicists were radicalizing their projects towards negative eugenics, an emerging group of intellectuals led by young social thinkers and modernist writers were producing theses and historical and sociological reflections that challenged the scientific racism en vogue among Brazilians. Curiously, the book *Sexo e civilização: aparas eugênicas* (Sex and civilization: eugenic trimmings), which represented a synthesis of racial determinism, was published in the same year that the sociologist Gilberto Freyre released *Casa-grande e Senzala* (1933), a seminal book that celebrated miscegenation as our greatest identity myth. In a way, we can say that these works synthesize the intellectual disagreements and clashes that took place in the 1930s, especially when considering the different national construction projects on the scene.

The simultaneous production of these works also allows us to understand the ambiguities that marked the political ideologies of the Vargas government itself. On the one hand, Vargas' fascist nationalism brought him closer to racism and the ideas defended by the eugenics movement, as if there were a symbiosis of interests around the relationship between race and national identity. The authoritarian way in which the government maintained control over "socially problematic" groups - including undesirable immigrants, the mentally ill, alcoholics, vagabonds, malandros, capoeiras, and street dwellers - was viewed favorably by eugenicists and more reactionary intellectuals, such as Renato Kehl. Like the eugenicists, the Vargas government also believed that a true nationalist policy should involve the homogenization of the population, based as much on the ordering of social life as on biological and racial control. In this context, Vargas created a series of institutions, state apparatuses, and new techniques for controlling, identifying, selecting, and imprisoning those who threatened the ideology of nationality⁷⁹.

On the other hand, as an expression of the ambiguities that characterized his government, Vargas' nationalization policy also incorporated the discourse of valuing mixed-race Brazil, even adhering to the myth of racial democracy. This is why Gilberto Freyre's work became a reference that

imigração e colonização". In: MAIO, Marcos Chor; SANTOS, Ricardo Ventura. *Raça, ciência e sociedade*. Rio de Janeiro: Fiocruz, 1996, p. 41-58; GERALDO, op. cit., 2007.

⁷⁹ CUNHA, Olívia Maria Gomes da. *Intenção e Gesto: Pessoa, cor e a produção cotidiana da (in)diferença no Rio de Janeiro, 1927-1942*. Rio de Janeiro: National Archives, 2002.

supported this positive view of national identity. As Nancy Stepan rightly points out, despite deep racial and social divisions that marked the Vargas government, throughout the 1930s “the notion that racial and cultural fusion was the solution to Brazil’s racial and social composition became the unofficial ideology of the national state”⁸⁰.

Despite the achievements of the eugenics movement, by the end of the 1930s Renato Kehl’s racial radicalism was losing followers and he became an increasingly less expressive figure. At the same time, the vitality with which he had led the eugenics movement since the 1910s was cooling in the face of Brazil’s ambiguous racial ideologies. The winning national identity myths of the late 1930s conversed much more with theses by Gilberto Freyre and more “moderate” versions of eugenics, more common in the 1910s and 1920s, than with Kehl’s negative eugenics and extremism. The most radical measures, such as eugenic sterilization and marriage control, would never be officially approved by the state.

Although the Vargas government, already in the *Estado Novo*, continued its policy of nationalization and persecution of undesirable immigrants, the eugenic measures against miscegenation seemed ineffective for a country that was increasingly opting for the project of whitening the population. Instead of harsh racial segregation, as Kehl wanted, Brazil seemed more and more willing to embrace miscegenation as a deliberate policy of racial homogenization. The elimination of blacks, indigenous peoples, and other “undesirable races” would not follow the path of official segregation, but of a project of racial and cultural fusion with European immigrants. In this sense, it was not a matter of rejecting eugenics, but of adopting it from a perspective more suited to the Brazilian racial ideologies en vogue then, especially those that combined the myth of racial democracy and the whitening of the nation.

This helps to explain the sense of frustration that Renato Kehl seemed to feel at the end of the 1930s. His project to implement a radical biological policy, along the lines of German “racial hygiene” and American racial segregationism, found few supporters in government institutions. Not even the cherished dream of creating a Brazilian Institute of Eugenics, which Kehl wanted as an institution at the service of the state, came to fruition. Although fascism and the allure of authoritarian regimes brought Renato Kehl and the Vargas government closer together, there was a certain distance between them that would never be overcome.

⁸⁰ STEPAN, op. cit., 2005, p. 174.

For all these reasons, Renato Kehl reached the end of the 1930s more isolated, while the eugenics movement lost its institutional strength. An example of this was the closure of the *Boletim de Eugenia* in 1933, which in its last issues no longer had the editorial direction of Renato Kehl, whose functions had been delegated to Octavio Domingues and Toledo Piza Junior, former partners of the eugenics movement⁸¹. Piza Junior himself noted, in a letter written in 1938, that Kehl “was the only true eugenicist in this immense Brazil”, and that despite his efforts “to form nuclei or surround himself with companions, perhaps to share the glory of these 20 years of campaigning, the truth is that you are always alone”⁸².

Toledo Piza Junior’s observation seemed to say more about Renato Kehl’s isolation at the end of the 1930s than about the results of his campaign in defense of eugenics. The book *Por que sou Eugenista*, published in 1937 as a celebratory memoir of his 20 years as a eugenicist, can also be seen as a strategy by Renato Kehl to establish a bridge between the past and the present, as his last effort to remain influential in the intellectual and political field.

In any case, Kehl’s isolation and discouragement were also perceived by Oliveira Vianna, a writer with whom he had a close intellectual affinity. In a letter sent to Kehl in 1938, he asked his friend not to lose heart in his “benevolent work”, referring to the eugenics campaign. He wrote: “I noticed the last time we met before you departed for Germany, that you were a little discouraged and skeptical about your efforts.”⁸³. As a way of motivating his friend not to lose heart, Oliveira Vianna stressed that the dissemination of an idea like eugenics always had a “slow and invisible diffusion, but not null”, meaning that time, in the future, would be responsible for showing the value of his campaigns in defense of eugenics.

⁸¹ For more details on Octavio Domingues and Toledo Piza Junior’s relationship with Renato Kehl and the eugenics movement, see HABIB, Paula Arantes Botelho Briglia. *Agricultura e Biologia na Escola Superior de Agricultura ‘Luiz de Queiroz’ (ESALQ): os estudos de genética nas trajetórias de Carlos Teixeira Mendes, Octavio Domingues e Salvador de Toledo Piza Jr. (1917-1937)*. Thesis (Doctorate in History) - Fiocruz: Rio de Janeiro, 2010.

⁸² Letter from Salvador de Toledo Piza Junior to Renato Kehl. São Paulo, November 19, 1938 (Fundo Pessoal Renato Kehl - Departamento de Arquivo e Documentação da Casa de Oswaldo Cruz - DAD-COC).

⁸³ Letter from Oliveira Vianna to Renato Kehl. Niterói, April 1, 1938 (Fundo Pessoal Renato Kehl - Departamento de Arquivo e Documentação da Casa de Oswaldo Cruz - DAD-COC).

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The political-scientific context of eugenics in the Brazil-Uruguay axis: a critical analysis of the political quadrant proposed by Maurizio Meloni

O contexto político-científico da eugenia no eixo Brasil-Uruguai: uma análise-crítica do quadrante político proposto por Maurizio Meloni¹

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Abstract

This article aims to test the political quadrant developed by Maurizio Meloni as an analytical and didactic tool to understand the political perspective of eugenics. Considering the intricate political and scientific complexity of the eugenics movement, the political quadrant is presented as an analytical structure aimed at delving into different concepts of heredity and eugenic policies defended by different positions in the quadrant. Although it was originally conceived based on cases of European and American eugenics, one must ponder the question of whether or not Latin American experiences can be contextualized within this framework. In this article, we will briefly present four prominent figures in the field of Latin American eugenics in Brazil and Uruguay, namely, Renato Kehl in his different phases, Roquette-Pinto, Paulina Luisi and Belisário Penna, and position them within the quadrant as a way of exemplifying the application of this analytical structure. Lastly, we examine the issue of whether the proposal of Maurizio Meloni's political quadrant is applicable in case studies of Latin American eugenicists or if it is actually an inaccurate tool, given the contextual plurality of eugenics.

Keywords: Eugenics. Brazil. Uruguay. History of Sciences.

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Resumo

Este artigo tem como objetivo testar o quadrante político desenvolvido por Maurizio Meloni como uma ferramenta analítica e didática para a compreensão política de eugenia. Considerando a intrincada complexidade tanto política quanto científica do movimento eugênico, o quadrante político é apresentado como uma estrutura analítica que visa aprofundar diversas concepções de hereditariedade e das políticas eugênicas defendidas por diferentes posicionamentos no quadrante. Embora tenha sido originalmente concebido com base em casos da eugenia europeia e estadunidense, é necessário considerar se as experiências latino-americanas podem ser contextualizadas dentro desse quadro. Neste artigo, apresentaremos brevemente quatro figuras proeminentes no campo da eugenia latino-americana do Brasil e do Uruguai e as posicionaremos dentro do quadrante como forma de exemplificar a aplicação dessa estrutura analítica: Renato Kehl, em suas distintas fases, Roquette-Pinto, Paulina Luisi e Belisário Penna. Ao final, queremos questionar se a proposta do quadrante político de Maurizio Meloni é eficaz para os estudos de caso de personagens eugenistas da América Latina ou se, na verdade, é uma ferramenta imprecisa dada a pluralidade contextual da eugenia.

Palavras-Chave: Eugenesia. Brasil. Uruguai. História das Ciências.

Introduction

What is new in discussions about the political aspect of eugenics? More than three decades ago, literature claimed that eugenics and political projects were inseparable. However, eugenic ideals remain present in public debate and are adopted by certain groups, whose purpose leads to population control policies. Questions arise concerning eugenics-based public policies, such as the possibility of legislation for the abortion of fetuses with congenital anomalies. In the field of contemporary politics, eugenic ideas are endorsed by far-right groups that propose exclusion policies for refugees, immigrants and racial and gender groups. Given this scenario, how does one deal with discussions that cast the political spectrum into the historical past of eugenics, particularly in the first half of the 20th century? Today, the term “eugenics” carries a historical and ideological stigma that serves to link political opponents to their practices and condemn them for acts against humanity. Thus, in the historical sense, eugenics is seen as a science used only by extreme right-wing groups.

The risk of anachronism is practically inevitable when one attempts to project the political past of eugenics into the present in search of ruptures or continuities. Although there are similarities and differences, the historian's role is to contextualize within the scope of a selected past. Hence, the idea is not to disqualify the contemporary appropriations of eugenics associated with far-right groups, for example, but rather to address the connections between eugenics and political ideology from a historical perspective, as proposed by Maurizio Meloni in his analysis of the first half of the 20th century.

In an article published in 1894, Diane Paul² stated that eugenics was widely shared by the left, in the figure of Marxists and Fabians. To exemplify, she mentioned people such as Beatrice Webb, Sidney Webb, George Bernard Shaw, Havelock Ellis, H. J. Laski, Graham Wallas, Emma Foldman, H.G. Wells, Edward Aveling, Julian Huxley, Joseph Needham, Muller, Paul Kammerer, among others.

In the collection *The Wellborn Science*³, Mark Adams examined the political relationships between eugenics and political ideologies. In his historical and conceptual review, he mentions that one of the great myths surrounding eugenics was to characterize it as an exclusive product of a reactionary or right-wing policy. Adams⁴ recalls that geneticists such as Russian geneticist Alexander Sergeevich Serebrovsky, American geneticist Hermann Joseph Muller and British-Indian scientist John Burdon Sanderson Haldane declared themselves communists and defenders of eugenic principles. By pointing out the multiple facets of the political nature of eugenics, Adams sought to distance himself from essentialism and propose a broadening of the investigative and comparative methods of these studies.

Not surprisingly, in the same collection, Adams dedicates a chapter to the study of eugenics in Russia between 1900 and 1940. The example of geneticist Hermann Muller with Soviet eugenics reveals how eugenics and politics were related. Muller was a staunch eugenicist and placed Galton's theory in a social economic perspective. For him, genetic selection represented the final step of the communist revolution.

² PAUL, Diane. Eugenics and the Left. *Journal of the History of Ideas*. [S.l.], v. 45, n. 4, 1984, p. 567-590.

³ ADAMS, Mark. Toward a comparative history of eugenics. In: ADAMS, Mark (org.). *The Wellborn Science: eugenics in Germany, France, Brazil, and Russia*. New York: Oxford University Press, 1990.

⁴ *Ibid.*, p. 220.

In the same vein, Véronique Mottier⁵ maintains that, from the outset, eugenics has been intertwined in society and politics, constituting both a science and a social movement. Following Adams' perspective, the author cites French anthropologist, co-founder of the French Workers' Party and socialist Georges Vacher de Lapouge, whose ideas suggested that men should engage in "selective breeding," that is, a kind of "sexual service" on behalf of the nation. Another case mentioned by Mottier⁶ concerns a Bolshevik movement that emerged in the USA and the United Kingdom in the 1930s, which 'considered the Soviet Union the only country that had favorable conditions for the application of a scientifically based policy for population improvement.

Leo Lucassen⁷ joins this debate to discuss the importance of theories of social reform, from a eugenic standpoint, for Fabians, Marxists and social democrats. This author comments on the divergence of opinions about the meaning of eugenics for the left. According to him, there is a group that considers biological theories in their diffusion through Europe and the Americas in the first half of the 20th century, which strongly appealed to left-wing social reformers. Another group believes that the relationship between eugenics and the left was simply an "opportunistic flirtation" and did not constitute a structural position in the philosophy of these ideologists. Lastly, Lucassen outlines a third group that argued that the Fabians were not "true socialists." The author suggests that in countries such as Germany, Switzerland or Scandinavia, eugenic ideas and programs were easily co-opted within the ideologies of welfare states and in dialogue with social democrats.

The interactions between the eugenics movement and feminisms have been a hotly debated topic among historians. According to Nancy Stepan⁸, some scholars argue that eugenics is explicitly anti-feminist and conservative, for it seeks to control female sexuality and restrict women's roles to the maternal and reproductive sphere. On the other hand, some researchers highlight eugenic initiatives in maternal and child health, sexual hygiene and sexual education, interpreting eugenics as more reformist and associated with the agendas of the political left, even suggesting a proto-feminist attitude.

⁵ MOTTIER, Véronique. Eugenics and the State: Policy-Making in Comparative Perspective. In: BASHFORD, Alison; LAVINE, Philippa Levine (orgs.). *The Oxford Handbook of the History of Eugenics* (Oxford Handbooks). Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2010.

⁶ Ibid.

⁷ LUCASSEN, Leo. A brave new world: the left, social engineering, and eugenics in twentieth-century Europe. *International Review of Social History*. [S.l.], v. 55, n. 2, 2010, p. 269-296.

⁸ STEPAN, Nancy Leys. *The hour of eugenics': race, gender, and nation in Latin America*. Ithaca: Cornell University Press: 1991, p. 104.

However, given the diversity and complexity of the eugenics movement in more than 30 countries, it is possible that eugenicists were anti-feminist in some regions, while in others they adopted a proto-feminist stance.

Upon examining the relationship between feminism and eugenics, Klausen and Bashford⁹ identify two perspectives in historiography. One of them minimizes the genuine interest of many feminists in eugenic ideas and policies aimed at improving the race through selective breeding. It is argued that the relations between feminism and eugenics were strategic, a tactic within the great struggle for the emancipation of women.

In the midst of this debate, we position the quadrant put forward by Maurizio Meloni, who, based on his intellectual actors, intends to create a didactic proposal in the form of a political quadrant for eugenics. To begin with, although the success of his choices can be considered in the analysis of some recognized intellectual and political figures in dialogue with the social engineering of eugenics, the formula cannot be extended to other contexts, such as that of the formation of Latin American eugenics.

Although Meloni recognizes that his quadrant cannot be generalized, it is perilous to suggest a complete and defined eugenics. This hypothesis is in line with the historiography of comparative eugenics, in which the contextual particularities and those of its intellectual actors lend shape to what we call polymorphous eugenics.

In this article, we will briefly present four prominent figures in the field of Latin American eugenics and position them within the quadrant, in order to exemplify the application of this analytical structure: Renato Kehl in his different phases, Roquette-Pinto, Paulina Luisi and Belisário Penna. Lastly, we will ponder whether the proposal of Maurizio Meloni's political quadrant is applicable to case studies of eugenicists from Latin America or whether it is, in fact, an inaccurate tool given the contextual plurality of eugenics.

Eugenics and the Political Quadrant

So far, based on recent historiography, we have sought to demonstrate how broad, complex and diverse the eugenic movement was. As Vanderlei de Souza¹⁰ stated, eugenics is characterized precisely “[...] by its chameleon-like

⁹ KLAUSEN, Susanne; BASHFORD, Alison. Fertility control: Eugenics, Neo-Malthusianism, and feminism. In: BASHFORD, Alison; LEVINE, Philippa. *The Oxford handbook of the history of eugenics*, 2010, p. 109-110.

¹⁰ SOUZA, Vanderlei Sebastião de. Por uma nação eugênica: higiene, raça e identidade nacional no movimento eugênico brasileiro dos anos 1910 e 1920. *Revista Brasileira de História da Ciência*, [S.l.] v. 1, n.

ability to serve different ideological projects.” Thus, the idea is not to downplay eugenic projects historically linked to the right and the extreme right, but rather to expand the scope of analysis of eugenics based on Meloni’s quadrant.

Maurizio Meloni and the significance of his work

Maurizio Meloni is a sociologist and social theorist who studies the relationships between biology and society. He is currently Associate Professor at the Alfred Deakin Institute for Citizenship and Globalization at Deakin University in Australia, and holds a PhD in Social Theory from the University of Catania in Italy and a Master’s in Philosophy from the University of Naples.

Meloni is the author of several books and articles on the history and philosophy of biology and medicine, with emphasis on epigenetics. One of his most important books is *Political Biology: Science and Social Values in Human Heredity from Eugenics to Epigenetics*¹¹, in which he analyzes how conceptions of heredity and biological plasticity have changed over time and how they have been influenced by social and political values. In this book, he proposes a political quadrant for eugenics, based on two axes: the degree of human intervention in inheritance and the degree of social equality sought through intervention. Meloni shows how different forms of eugenics fit into this quadrant and how they relate to dominant political ideologies. The political quadrant appears as a didactic and theoretical tool to frame intellectual actors involved in eugenics and its possible association with certain political spectrums.

Considering the various eugenics that emerged in different contexts, allied to different ideological political-scientific movements, the author creates what he calls a political quadrant (Figure 1) of eugenic movements, which, on the “x axis,” differentiates between political right and left, and, on the “y axis,” illustrates the difference between Mendelians and neo-Lamarckians. In general terms, the author characterizes four possible eugenics: right-wing and left-wing Mendelians, and right-wing and left-wing neo-Lamarckians. Each of the four positions in the quadrant has its own distinct conception of heredity and defends specific eugenic policies, consistent with its worldview and the societal project it believes in, and all of them differ from the others.

2, 2008, p. 146-163.

¹¹ MELONI, Maurizio. *Political biology: Science and social values in human heredity from eugenics to epigenetics*. Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan, 2016.

Although Meloni developed his quadrant by analyzing cases of European and American eugenics, we believe it is essential to bring this formula to Latin American experiences, since its application may be problematic precisely because of the way eugenics developed in those countries.

Figure 1: Maurizio Meloni's Political Quadrant of Eugenics

Source: Meloni¹²

According to Meloni¹³, up to the 1930s, the debate about sociopolitical implications deriving from studies on human heredity was plural and complex. The interpretations of August Weissmann's theories of the continuity of germplasm, Mendelian laws, and acceptance or repudiation of the inheritance of acquired characteristics, or even the scope of the Darwinian theory of evolution, were not at first obvious and indisputable. Although eugenics today is often associated with a right-wing phenomenon whose discourse involves scientific precepts of "hard" or Mendelian heredity, other interpretations of both a scientific-epistemological and political nature were possible in the early days. Over time this plurality was lost; however, in the first half of the 20th century, both the right and the left managed to politicize Mendelian and neo-Lamarckian¹⁴ heredity. By Mendelian heredity we understand the notion of heredity that necessarily excludes any inheritance of acquired characteristics, i.e., inheritance is defined by the content of the germ cells.

¹² Ibid., p. 216.

¹³ Ibid., p. 93.

¹⁴ Ibid.

Neo-Lamarckian heredity recognizes the influence of the environment and the transmission of characteristics acquired throughout the life of an organism to its descendants. In other words, characteristics developed during life can be inherited by descendants.

As Maurizio Meloni¹⁵ points out, before the notion of eugenics became crystallized¹⁶, that is, before this notion was associated with right-wing politics, which is based on Mendelian heredity, conceptions were varied. According to the neo-Lamarckian notion of heredity, both racist and reactionary political beliefs could be mobilized in the name of environmental effects. On the other hand, egalitarian, radical and communist discourses were also defended by eugenicists who adopted Mendelian heredity¹⁷.

In the following sections, we will place greater emphasis on lesser-known eugenic beliefs. Right-wing Mendelian eugenics, or the “crystallized” conception of the movement — the one characterized by the search for racial purity, eternalized in the Nazi Holocaust, in nationalist, anti-communist and anti-Semitic ideology, which resulted in forced sterilizations and genocide in concentration camps, and which banned marriages and carried out horrible experiments on twins in the Auschwitz camp¹⁸ — will be given little space in the following pages.

Part of the objective of this article is to criticize the dimensions of the eugenics movement that fall within three of Meloni’s four quadrants: right-wing neo-Lamarckian Eugenics, left-wing neo-Lamarckian Eugenics and left-wing Mendelian Eugenics.

Right-wing neo-Lamarckian eugenics

Lamarckian ideas are generally associated with social reforms, and are not linked to political radicalism and socialism¹⁹. This apparent affinity of Lamarckism with left-wing notions seems coherent when one examines how Nazi eugenics embraced a completely anti-Lamarckian Weismannian

¹⁵ Ibid.

¹⁶ Using the term “crystallized” coined by science historian Loren Graham, Meloni argues that crystallized eugenics refers to the set of beliefs that became widely known after the end of World War II, which many considered to be the only valid example of eugenics. Crystallized eugenics, represented on the spectrum by right-wing Mendelian eugenics, reflects a particular alignment between science and political values that culminated in the Nazi Holocaust (Ibid., p. 94).

¹⁷ Ibid.

¹⁸ LEVINE, Philippa. *Eugenics: a very short introduction*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2017.

¹⁹ MELONI, op. cit., p. 96.

defense. However, this conception is misleading. Neo-Lamarckism was an important element of a 19th century racist and classist agenda that continued throughout the 20th century²⁰.

However, this should be explained properly, as Meloni points out²¹:

To be fair to Lamarck, however, we must add that his brand of Lamarckism was a truncated version of the inheritance of acquired characters, which emphasized the passive reception and transmission of deleterious characteristics rather than the acquisition of positive characteristics in active response to their environments.

In other words, Meloni's interpretation is that right-wing neo-Lamarckian eugenics focused on how the environment would be a constant source of morbidity, able to permanently alter, weaken and poison heredity. Therefore, to be identified as belonging to this current of eugenics, a person would necessarily have to emphasize the pathogenic properties of the environment, often referred to as "racial poisons," and highlight the hereditary transmission of these acquired deleterious characteristics, believing that this irremediable process prevents the affected groups from fully exercising their citizenship²².

The first school of thought that fits these criteria is medical degenerationism, a belief that circulated widely in medical and social literature in the 19th and early 20th century. Degenerationists assumed the presence of "racial poisons," which included alcohol and venereal disease, in addition to accelerated industrialization, poor hygiene conditions, overpopulation, and the presence of slums, whose inhabitants were considered addicts and ignorant²³.

Another distinct variant of right-wing neo-Lamarckism, which emerged after medical degenerationism, was neo-Lamarckian racism. This ideology was based on the idea that races were formed directly through the inheritance of acquired characters and through environmental influences. Races were believed to develop through the inheritance of locally determined adaptations²⁴.

²⁰ Ibid., p. 97.

²¹ Ibid., p. 97.

²² Ibid., p. 98.

²³ Ibid., p. 98.

²⁴ Ibid., p. 99.

Both medical degenerationism and neo-Lamarckian racism shared the belief that positive habits and benefits of education and moral progress could only be inherited by so-called “superior races” or advanced cultures. As Meloni points out, it was “progress for some, not for all.”²⁵

Left-wing neo-Lamarckian eugenics

Trust in the power of regeneration is the distinctive feature of left-wing neo-Lamarckian eugenics. While right-wing Mendelian eugenics defended the permanence of pure racial lineages and right-wing neo-Lamarckians assumed a certain asymmetry, in which only the “superior races” could progress, left-wing neo-Lamarckian eugenics recognized the remarkable regenerative power of the environment.

Common environments could thus transform distinct races into homogeneous ones. Instead of emphasizing degenerative processes and harmful environmental influences, they focused on environmental regeneration and rejuvenation, which would, thereby, favor a transformation in humanity²⁶.

Meloni²⁷ highlights this eugenicist current through the example of Austrian biologist Paul Kammerer. The author draws attention to the fact that it is important to understand Kammerer’s theory not as a departure from the eugenics movement, but as an alternative form of it, just as eugenic as Davenport in the USA or Pearson in England. According to Meloni²⁸:

... rejuvenation and regeneration would promote the biological transformation of humanity. These were not merely abstract ideas, but also a series of invasive techniques. Steinach’s methods of rejuvenation included testicular transplantation, vasoligation, and vasectomy. Kammerer suggested using testicular implants to influence sexual desire in homosexuals and hermaphrodites and administering mild radiation to women’s ovaries to increase their breastfeeding ability.

In other words, Kammerer’s eugenics may be understood as “productive.” Far from being simply a critique of the selectionist bias of

²⁵ Ibid., p. 100.

²⁶ Ibid., p. 113.

²⁷ Ibid., p. 117.

²⁸ Ibid., p. 113.

right-wing Mendelians, who could only alter the distribution of good or bad genes without creating traits, Kammerer's eugenics could transform political action into an "organic technology," leaving a positive legacy for subsequent generations²⁹.

An intellectual who helps us complexify this distinction between left- and right-wing neo-Lamarckism is Belisário Penna, who can be classified as either right-wing or left-wing, according to Meloni's quadrant. This is because he saw the environment from the standpoint of both degeneration and regeneration. The author of *Saneamento do Brasil* (1918) (*Sanitation in Brazil*) believed that, through the development of a national "awareness about sanitation" aligned with preventive eugenics, the Brazilian race could be transformed by the environment. Thus, health reforms led by the State enabled the regeneration of the Brazilian race. Restrictive measures, in turn, were also an important method to prevent degeneration, as in the case of alcoholism or malaria³⁰.

By choosing awareness about sanitation as a proposal for environmental regeneration, Penna can be seen as flirting with the quadrant on the left. However, this viewpoint disappears when one analyzes his political path and intellectual productions. Penna's political activity and speech condemned left-wing movements, and at the end of his life, he allied himself with the integralists who, on the political spectrum, were antagonistic to what we consider left-wing at that time. His political thinking involved nationalist ideas, so racial regeneration was influenced by this position. According to Castro-Santos³¹, the health movement of the First Republic, led by Penna, occupied itself with an ideological project for the construction of nationality.

At a conference held at the University of Paraná in 1921, Penna explained that he considered his notions revolutionary, admitting that there is no such thing as racial superiority, but rather mindsets that are more advanced than others. In the same lecture, he stated that the human process was moving

²⁹ Ibid., p. 111.

³⁰ CARVALHO, Leonardo Dallacqua de. Sanear é eugenicar: a eugenia "preventiva" de Belisário Penna a serviço do saneamento do Brasil, 1920-1930 [To sanitize is to eugenize: Belisário Penna's "preventive" eugenics in the service of sanitation in Brazil, 1920-1930]. *História, Ciências, Saúde-Manguinhos*, v. 29, n. 3, p. 645-660, 2022. Se also: CARVALHO, Leonardo Dallacqua de. *O saneador do Brasil: saúde pública, política e integralismo na trajetória de Belisário Penna (1868-1939)* [The Brazilian sanitarian: public health, politics and integralism in the trajectory of Belisário Penna (1868-1939)]. Thesis (Doctorate in History of Science) – Casa de Oswaldo Cruz/Fiocruz. Rio de Janeiro: 2019.

³¹ CASTRO-SANTOS, Luiz Antonio de. O pensamento sanitariano na Primeira República: uma ideologia de construção da nacionalidade [Sanitarian ideas in the First Republic: an ideology of nationality construction]. *Dados – Revista de Ciências Sociais*, v. 28, n. 2, p. 193-210, 1985.

towards racial mixing, so that, in the future, there would be a single race³². Any attempt to frame Penna exclusively as a right- or left-wing neo-Lamarckian ignores his own medical and political thinking, as well as the variations that were common in the context of Brazilian eugenics.

Left-wing Mendelian eugenics

The brief experience of Soviet eugenics is perhaps the best example, according to Meloni, of one of the forgotten chapters in the history of eugenics: left-wing Mendelism, which occupies the lower left corner of the political quadrant³³. Left-wing Mendelian eugenicists refer to “a direct and unambiguous commitment to a eugenic project aimed at socialist transformation.”³⁴

Unlike neo-Lamarckians, who prioritized environmental processes, Mendelians argued that germplasm was the most important element³⁵. These eugenicists did not see heredity as slavery to the genetic past, but rather as the ability to shape the future³⁶.

Although hierarchical discourses of racial and social inferiority and superiority were absent from discussions of eugenics in Soviet Russia, compulsory sterilization laws along the lines of American legislation were occasionally proposed³⁷. Throughout the 1920s, Soviet eugenics began to come under open ideological attack.

In the words of Meloni³⁸:

The Nazi seizure of power in 1933, the importance of genetics and biology to Nazi ideology, and the emergence of Lysenkoism after 1934 brought further public disgrace to Soviet eugenics, although genetics somehow survived in disguise.

The cancellation of the International Genetics Congress, which was to be held in Moscow in 1937, represented the final defeat of Soviet genetics and

³² PENNA, Belisário. *Lecture given by Dr. Belisário Penna at the University of Paraná*. (Fundo Belisário Penna, DAD-COC). 2 Aug. 1921, p. 4.

³³ Meloni, op. cit., p. 118.

³⁴ Ibid.

³⁵ Ibid., p. 119.

³⁶ Ibid., p. 121.

³⁷ Ibid.

³⁸ Ibid., p. 122.

eugenics³⁹. The disappearance of this last quadrant of eugenics is symbolized by the departure of Muller and Lysenko from the USSR in 1936⁴⁰. Strictly speaking, the eugenicist intellectuals chosen by Meloni seem to fit his quadrant, but he is perhaps unable to apply a single quadrant as a formula for eugenicists in other contexts.

Hermann Joseph Muller, an American geneticist, is a good example of a left-wing Mendelian eugenicist. Muller was one of the pioneers of classical genetics, a student and collaborator of Thomas Hunt Morgan, between 1912 and 1915, in the famous “fly room” at Columbia University. The two men were fundamental to the development of chromosome theory and to establishing *Drosophila* flies as a model organism for genetic studies: “Against the reactionary tendency of American eugenics, Muller wanted to show how genetics ‘belonged to the political left’”⁴¹.

In Muller’s view, since acquired characteristics were not hereditary, upbringing or education could contribute little to the racial social transformation he dreamed of⁴². In a letter to Stalin, Muller tried to persuade him that genetics would represent the final step of the communist revolution. However, Stalin was not convinced. In fact, he was quite displeased, which culminated in Muller’s unavoidable departure from Communist Russia⁴³. Nancy Stepan⁴⁴ describes Muller as follows:

Herman J. Muller, winner of the Nobel Prize in genetics (for the discovery, in 1927, of the genetic mutation induced by X-rays), was a socialist who, in the 1930s, actively defended a scheme of genetic selection through artificial insemination with the superior sperm of “great men.”

Edgard Roquette-Pinto, in turn, can be considered, in general, a left-leaning Mendelian eugenicist in Brazil, who stood out in the debates of the 1st Brazilian Congress on Eugenics. However, the imprecise and generalized approach of the quadrants does not adequately reflect the diversity of approaches taken by eugenicists in their respective countries, shaping eugenic projects according to specific social, economic, and racial contexts.

³⁹ *Ibid.*, p. 122.

⁴⁰ *Ibid.*

⁴¹ *Ibid.*, p. 125.

⁴² *Ibid.*, p. 127.

⁴³ *Ibid.*

⁴⁴ STEPAN, *op. cit.*, p. 217.

As pointed out earlier, in the Brazilian context, Roquette-Pinto could be placed, somewhat laboriously, within the quadrant of a “left-wing Mendelian.” This is due to the fact that, unlike neo-Lamarckism, the Brazilian anthropologist did not adopt this perspective, making it completely erroneous to classify him as a “right-wing Mendelian.” In fact, he represents a case of an important intellectual who does not easily fit into this quadrant. Roquette-Pinto’s eugenic approach would surprise Meloni with the different variants of eugenics present in Brazil, as specified by the Brazilian intellectual himself. This is evident, for example, in his conclusions that eugenics had become a fashionable theme, with zoologists and botanists writing about it⁴⁵. Even considering the mindset of a “left-wing Mendelian,” it can be argued that his project of human improvement based on eugenics represents a “direct” and “unequivocal” commitment to a socialist transformation.

Roquette-Pinto, according to Vanderlei Sebastião de Souza, used eugenic arguments to oppose the entry of “mentally ill” immigrants, whose condition was considered hereditary. Although he defended public policies such as health and education for the national population, the anthropologist also believed in racial whitening. Souza stated that, in his discussions about crossbreeding between whites and blacks, Roquette-Pinto “[...] usually tended toward the prevalence of the anthropological characteristics of the former”⁴⁶.

Albeit classified as belonging to “left-wing Mendelian eugenics,” Roquette-Pinto is a strange personality in Meloni’s quadrant. His interest focused more strongly on gaining a social and biological understanding of the national population than on adhering to a specific political spectrum. The anthropologist was a Mendelian concerned about the confusion between eugenics and biological inheritance — indeed, it is no coincidence that his references were Charles Davenport and Eugen Fischer. As Souza explains, progress in Roquette-Pinto’s Brazil was much more a problem of “[...] disorganization of national politics, lack of education and health”⁴⁷ than a question of biological inheritance and miscegenation.

Roquette-Pinto exemplifies how the discussion about eugenics should be analyzed within the political, racial and scientific contexts of each country. While Hermann Joseph Muller attempted to persuade Stalin

⁴⁵ SOUZA, Vanderlei Sebastião de. *Em Busca do Brasil: Edgard Roquette-Pinto e o retrato antropológico Brasileiro (1905-1935)*. Rio de Janeiro: FGV Editora e Editora Fiocruz, 2017, p. 365.

⁴⁶ *Ibid.*, p. 334.

⁴⁷ *Ibid.*, p. 378.

that eugenics was the final phase of the communist revolution, there is no evidence that Roquette-Pinto adopted a similar approach in his intellectual output. His analysis of populations, Mendelian eugenics and Brazil is rooted in anthropological and genetic issues, through a militant nationalist discourse typical of the early 20th century in Brazil. The sciences guided his national mission of (re)discovering the country and its population, considered to be at a racial disadvantage.

Right-wing Mendelian eugenics

This current emerged at the early 20th century in Europe and the United States, and was characterized by a conservative and elitist view of society. Supporters of right-wing Mendelian eugenics held the belief that human characteristics were determined by hereditary factors and that it was feasible to improve the human race through reproductive selection and control. They promoted policies such as compulsory sterilization, banning of interracial marriages, and encouraging childbearing among individuals considered superior. Principles such as genetic determinism, racial hierarchy and profound elitism underpinned the ideas of these eugenicists.

This mindset played a significant role in the rise of Nazi fascism in Europe. In Nazi Germany, right-wing Mendelian eugenics was used to justify the persecution and extermination of Jews, Gypsies, and other groups considered inferior. The Holocaust and racial hygiene represent two of the most tragic consequences of right-wing Mendelian eugenics. The Holocaust was the systematic genocide of around six million Jews by the Nazis during World War II. Racial hygiene involved Nazi policies of forced sterilization and euthanasia of people considered genetically inferior, including those with intellectual disabilities, mental illnesses, and congenital disorders. According to Stefan Kühl⁴⁸, more than 1% of Germans were officially sterilized.

On the other side of the Atlantic, the United States, starting in the early 20th century, led a Mendelian program that aimed to sterilize the “incapable.” States such as North Carolina, Michigan, Virginia, and California are among the many that adopted sterilization policies in the name of “eugenic correction” of the incapacitated. Protagonists of American eugenics, such as zoologist

⁴⁸ KÜHL, Stefan. *The Nazi connection: Eugenics, American racism, and German National Socialism*. New York: Oxford University Press, 1994.

Charles Davenport, believed that inferiority was a permanent trait dominant in the Mendelian context⁴⁹.

However, one of the problems pointed out regarding Meloni is his tendency to believe in a single agenda for the quadrants in the context of global eugenics, ignoring the fact that one of the fundamental principles of its success stems from its ability to adapt easily to different contexts.

Renato Kehl's case is even more impactful, as it challenges at least three aspects of the structure proposed by Meloni. An analysis of his trajectory, initially linked to the health movement and later to the Brazilian League of Mental Hygiene, and considering his change in outlook in the late 1920s after a trip to Europe, indicates the implausibility of classifying Renato Kehl in a single way.

Vanderlei Sebastião de Souza's work on Renato Kehl offers a comprehensive analysis of the author's thinking. To avoid repetition, we offer three examples of Kehl's intellectual output: *Eugenia e Medicina Social*⁵⁰ (Eugenics and Social Medicine) (1923 [1920]), *Como escolher um bom marido*⁵¹ (How to Choose a Good Husband) (1935 [1924]), and *Aparas eugênicas*⁵² (Eugenic Cuttings) (1933). Were one to attempt to place them in the proposed quadrants, each one could easily occupy a different position from the others.

Initially, if we look at the "left neo-Lamarckism" quadrant, whose notions suggests that environments can shape different races in a single direction, *Eugenics and Social Medicine* could be a work that fits within this context. In this book, Kehl argues that the Brazilian would be a strong race and representative of resistance, were it not for environmental evils such as diseases, food, organism and climate⁵³. At the time, Kehl saw eugenics and sanitation as similar concepts, aligned with patriotism.

From another perspective, the title *Como Escolher um Bom Marido* may fit if one considers the "right-wing neo-Lamarckian" quadrant, in which the environment is defined as a harmful source that can modify, degenerate and impair heredity. In this case, the eugenic doctor would play a comprehensive

⁴⁹ BLACK, Edwin. *A guerra contra os fracos: a eugenia e a campanha norte-americana para criar uma raça superior*. [War Against the Weak: Eugenics and America's Campaign to Create a Master Race] São Paulo: A Girafa Editora, 2003, p. 101.

⁵⁰ KEHL, Renato. *Eugenia e Medicina Social*. [Eugenics and Social Medicine] 2nd ed. Rio de Janeiro: Livraria Francisco Alves, 1923 [1920].

⁵¹ KEHL, Renato. *Como escolher um bom Marido*. 2ª ed. Rio de Janeiro: Ariel Editora LTDA, 1935 [1924].

⁵² KEHL, Renato. *Sexo e civilização: aparas eugênicas*. Rio de Janeiro: Francisco Alves, 1933.

⁵³ KEHL, op. cit., 1923, p. 223-224.

role involving medical profiles such as sanitarian, clinician, experimentalist and sociologist. His mission, based on modern knowledge of heredity, would consist of “[...] studying defects and vices; concerned particularly with the individual, seeing him from a collective point of view; seeking to resolve his underlying problems for the purpose of ensuring the continuous and safe selection of his offspring”⁵⁴. Therefore, the proposal of a health certificate for marriage falls within the scope of the eugenicist to identify elements that weaken and impair heredity, especially those pertaining to the environment.

Lastly, Kehl also fits the category of “right-wing Mendelism,” especially in view of the uncompromising element of heredity that gave rise to racial and classist agendas. In *Aparas eugênicas*, he recommends “Avoiding marriage with a person of a lower class, and above all, with individuals of a different race and with first generation half-castes. Such marriages are provenly dysgenic, giving rise to physically, psychically and morally inferior types”⁵⁵.

Each of these works corresponds to a phase in Renato Kehl’s life trajectory, so that Meloni’s quadrant would overshadow his understanding of eugenics. Vanderlei Sebastião de Souza points out that Brazilian eugenicists believed that eugenics served different concepts of nation, for “[...] the strength of the eugenic movement gained prominence precisely due to this chameleon-like ability to serve different expressions of ‘biosocial’ knowledge”⁵⁶.

Figure 2 illustrates out how the three main Latin American eugenicists discussed so far herein — Renato Kehl, Belisário Penna and Roquette-Pinto — can be classified.

⁵⁴ KEHL, Renato. *Como escolher um bom Marido*. 1ª ed. Rio de Janeiro: Ariel Editora LTDA, 1924, p. 36.

⁵⁵ KEHL, op. cit., 1933, p. 86.

⁵⁶ SOUZA, op. cit., 2019, p. 303.

Figure 2: Political Quadrant of Eugenics with Brazilian Eugenicists

Source: Adapted from Meloni⁵⁷.

The case study of Paulina Luisi and the Political Quadrant of Eugenics

Paulina Luisi was a distinguished Uruguayan liberal feminist who defended eugenics even in her last book, published in the year of her death in 1950⁵⁸. Considering the political quadrant we described, in what position would this author be located? Luisi is an intriguing character, for she offers significant challenges to the quadrant. She was a prominent Uruguayan feminist leader, involved in the formation of the socialist party and recognized

⁵⁷ MELONI, op. cit., p. 94.

⁵⁸ LUISI, Paulina. *Pedagogia y Conducta Sexual* [Pedagogy and Sexual Behavior]. Montevideo: El Siglo Ilustrado, 1950.

for her fight for women's suffrage. However, she also defended "negative" eugenics practices, such as abortion and sterilization.

The essay *Algumas ideias sobre eugenia*, by Paulina Luisi⁵⁹, fits into the right-wing neo-Lamarckian quadrant, as indicated in Figure 1. Although she aligned herself politically with progressivism and adopted a neo-Lamarckian position about human development, the author also advocates "negative" eugenics policies that highlight the degenerative impact of the environment.

Although the text does not contain direct passages that characterize it as linked to the political left, its conceptions can be inferred indirectly in excerpts, such as when it advocates for the improvement of working conditions for men and women in favor of the race⁶⁰:

It is a vital need for the future of the race that States urgently provide an improvement in professional environments, in order to suppress or reduce all the causes that act extrinsically upon the organisms of parents, weakening or impoverishing them.

⁵⁹ LUISI, Paulina. *Algumas ideias sobre Eugenia* [Some ideas about Eugenics]. Montevideo: El Siglo Ilustrado, 1916; NICOLADELI, Angelo Tenfen. Tradução comentada do artigo de Paulina Luisi publicado em 1916, "Algumas ideias sobre Eugenia". *Revista Brasileira de História da Ciência*, [S.l.], v. 15, n. 1, p. 233-248, 2022; NICOLADELI, Angelo Tenfen. *O pensamento de Paulina Luisi (1875-1950) em "Algumas ideias sobre eugenia": uma análise das potencialidades para discussão de história da ciência na educação científica*. Dissertação (Mestrado em Educação Científica e Tecnológica) PPGECT/UFSC. Florianópolis: 2023.

⁶⁰ NICOLADELI, op. cit., 2022, p. 257.

Figure 3: Political Quadrant of Eugenics with Paulina Luisi

Source: Adapted from Meloni⁶¹

At one point, Luisi argues that men are more harmful to the human species than women⁶²:

Let us note, in passing, that sterilization does not pose equal dangers to both sexes; while it is completely harmless to men, the operation is delicate in women, although the danger is lessened with the progress of modern surgery. We also observe that men are much more harmful to the species than women, given the larger number of beings they can generate.

In another excerpt, Luisi expresses concern for mothers: “It is not uncommon among certain people that a man, under the influence of alcohol, seeks, precisely in this state, to exercise his conjugal rights over his wife, who

⁶¹ MELONI, op. cit., p. 94.

⁶² NICOLADELI, op. cit., 2022, p. 243.

under the pressure of violence surrenders to the reproductive act, dominated by fear”⁶³.

In another text by Paulina Luisi, entitled *Para una mejor descendencia*, published in 1919, her affinity with the political left appears more evident. After discussing the degenerative effects of alcoholism, tuberculosis and syphilis, and presenting possible solutions, the author concludes her essay with the following passage⁶⁴:

In short, all those reforms aimed at tackling the three terrible plagues mentioned, as well as improving the living conditions of the proletarian class, which, worthy of its name, is scanty in resources, abundant in descendants, are appropriate. The electoral platform presented to the people by the Socialist Party in the last elections has courageously faced many of these problems with the height and knowledge worthy of the high purpose pursued by its efforts, nobly oriented towards obtaining the broadest well-being and greatest happiness of our species.

Christine Ehrick⁶⁵ argues that Luisi began to adopt a softer stance on eugenics from 1916 onwards; however, over the decades, this stance dwindled even further. In her 1919 essay, *Para una mejor descendencia*, the author’s analysis reveals a change in perspective, with a more preventive approach to eugenics, emphasizing education, access to health and the improvement of housing and work conditions, instead of supporting practices such as eugenic sterilization and abortion, as in 1916. This change in position becomes evident upon comparing the two texts.

By way of comparison, as we mentioned previously, a preeminent Latin American eugenicist who changed his position in the political sphere of eugenics was Renato Kehl⁶⁶. According to Vanderlei Sebastião de Souza, Renato Kehl, in his first phase (1917–1927), can be classified as a right-wing neo-Lamarckian, since he followed the motto “Sanitizing is Eugenizing,” fighting mainly against the potentially degenerative effects of the environment.

⁶³ Ibid.

⁶⁴ LUISI, Paulina. *Para una mejor descendencia* [For a better descendance]. Buenos Aires: Casa Editora Juan Perrotti, 1919, p. 29, our translation.

⁶⁵ EHRICK, Christine. *The shield of the weak: Feminism and the state in Uruguay, 1903-1933*. New Mexico: University of New Mexico Press, 2005, p. 100.

⁶⁶ SOUZA, Vanderlei Sebastião de. *Renato Kehl e a eugenia no Brasil: ciência, raça e nação no período entreguerras* [Renato Kehl and eugenics in Brazil: science, race and nation in the interwar period]. Guarapuava: Editora Unicentro, 2019.

According to Souza, “Thus, they focused on combating ‘eugenic environments’ and diseases such as syphilis, tuberculosis, hookworm, malaria and leprosy”⁶⁷. In his second phase (1927–1930), Kehl approached the right-wing Mendelian quadrant, starting to defend an innate notion of race, endorsing Mendelism as the basic theory of heredity, and ended up defending more authoritarian, restrictive and radical measures⁶⁸.

However, the suitability of the political quadrant of eugenics proposed by Meloni to the Latin American context is brought into question. It is important to recognize that the author developed this model based on examples of European and American eugenicists, who conceived their eugenic theories and practices in different scientific, political and social scenarios.

Final remarks

The main arguments against Meloni’s political quadrant of eugenics⁶⁹ are as follows: 1 – The quadrant is simplistic and generalizing, dividing eugenics into four categories, each with a set of associated political and scientific characteristics. However, reality is more complex and fluid. 2 – Eugenicists do not always fit perfectly into a single category. 3 – The quadrant does not take into account the historical and political context. Eugenics is a social and cultural phenomenon that develops in specific contexts. Meloni’s quadrant ignores this fact, which may lead to inaccurate interpretations of the history of eugenics. 4 – The quadrant is Eurocentric. Meloni based his model on examples of European and American eugenicists. This may limit its usefulness for understanding eugenics in other contexts, such as the Latin American one.

The examples of Paulina Luisi, Belisário Penna, Roquette-Pinto and Renato Kehl illustrate some of the problems of Meloni’s quadrant. Paulina Luisi, was a liberal feminist and supporter of socialism and social reforms, but she also supported negative eugenics policies such as eugenic sterilization and abortion. Renato Kehl, along his career, changed his stance regarding eugenics. Initially, he could be considered both a right-wing and a left-wing neo-Lamarckian, advocating sanitation as a means of improving the race but also concerned about the dangers of racial degeneration. Later, his stance shifted closer to right-wing Mendelism and he advocated more

⁶⁷ Ibid., p. 87.

⁶⁸ Ibid., 185.

⁶⁹ Ibid.

authoritarian and restrictive measures. An analysis of Belisário Penna's intellectual trajectory indicates that he can be associated with a "left-wing" political spectrum, due to his militant reformist nationalism, although his neo-Lamarckian approach could be seen as aligned with a "right-wing" perspective if considered within a political context.

These examples suggest that Meloni's quadrant may be useful for understanding some general trends in eugenics, but should not be accepted as a single interpretation. It is essential to consider the specific historical and political context in which eugenics appeared, as well as the nuances of the positions of individual eugenicists.

The examples of South American intellectuals who promoted eugenics reveal that the quadrant proposed by Meloni is not universally applicable. This underscores one of the main conclusions of Mark Adams, who emphasized that "[...] eugenics was a single and coherent, mainly Anglo-American movement, with a specific set of common goals and beliefs"⁷⁰. To believe in a single approach to eugenics is to ignore the varied political and cultural context in which it developed and was adopted in different countries. Moreover, it would ignore the actions of institutions and their relationships with a variety of political authorities and sectors of society, including business, industrial and civil society. Therefore, this emphasizes the importance of case studies for the interpretation of eugenics in its political and cultural contexts to enable historical comparisons. Despite the coherence of the model in some specific cases, case studies and comparative analyses of Latin American eugenics reveal that Meloni's quadrant loses its effectiveness.

As discussed, these issues are not new in eugenics studies, and such research problems have been debated for more than three decades. In chapter 4 of his book *Political Biology: Science and Social Values in Human Heredity from Eugenics to Epigenetics*, Meloni demonstrates his clear awareness of this debate. The author does not hesitate to contextualize the experiences of both the Mendelian left and the Lamarckian left within the quadrant's political debate. At the same time, he recognizes that these discussions illustrate how scientific opinions have influenced politics and shaped political agendas⁷¹.

⁷⁰ ADAMS, op. cit., p. 217, free translation.

⁷¹ MELONI, op. cit., p. 131.

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Eugenics, social thought and identity discourses in Brazil: between “heróis capengas” (stumbling heroes), “urupês de pau podre” (wood ear mushrooms) and “manchas loiras” (blond spots)

Eugenia, pensamento social e discursos identitários no Brasil:
entre “heróis capengas”, “urupês de pau podre” e “manchas
loiras”

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Abstract

The study aimed to address the eugenic debates and their repercussions in Brazilian social thought and in national and regional identity discourses. In this sense, it dealt with recurrent conceptualizations around emblematic characters of Brazilian literature, such as Monteiro Lobato’s “Jeca Tatu” (1882-1948) and Mário de Andrade’s “Macunaíma” (1893-1945). In the first part, the relations of eugenics in social thought were discussed, relating elements referring to sanitation, hygiene, and national identity construction; in the second part, the intellectual production of identity representation in southern Brazil was addressed in the arguments of Bento Munhoz da Rocha Netto (1905-1973) and Wilson Martins (1921-2010), both writers, politicians, and university professors from Paraná, who established a counterpoint to the regionalist theoretical model of Brazilian formation elaborated by Gilberto Freyre (1900-1987). Therefore, this article proposes to uproot the past and bring to debate the appropriations of those productions of eugenic principles, in order to discern the historiographical scope of the identity idealizations treated.

Keywords: Eugenics. Social Thought. Identity Discourses. Paraná. Brazil.

Resumo

O estudo teve como objetivo tratar dos debates eugênicos e das suas repercussões no pensamento social brasileiro, especialmente no que diz respeito aos discursos identitários de cunho nacional e regional. Nesse sentido, tratou-se de conceitualizações recorrentes em torno de personagens emblemáticos da

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literatura brasileira como o “Jeca Tatu”, de Monteiro Lobato (1882-1948), e “Macunaíma”, de Mário de Andrade (1893-1945). Na primeira parte, discutiu-se sobre as relações da eugenia no pensamento social, relacionando elementos referentes ao sanitarismo, ao higienismo e à construção identitária nacional; na segunda parte, abordou-se sobre a produção intelectual de representação identitária no Sul do Brasil nas argumentações de Bento Munhoz da Rocha Netto (1905-1973) e Wilson Martins (1921-2010), ambos escritores paranaenses, políticos, professores universitários e que estabeleceram uma contraposição ao modelo teórico de orientação regionalista sobre a formação brasileira elaborada por Gilberto Freyre (1900-1987). A proposição deste artigo foi, portanto, desenraizar o passado e trazer ao debate as apropriações dessas produções aos princípios eugenistas, a fim de discernir sobre o alcance historiográfico das idealizações identitárias tratadas.

Palavras-chave: Eugenia. Pensamento Social. Discursos Identitários. Paraná. Brasil.

Introduction

This article addresses eugenic debates and their repercussions in the Brazilian social thought, mainly regarding national and regional identity discourses. The notion of region considered originates in previous research developed by the author, which analyzed the constitution of a legitimate discourse of the state of Paraná social and historical formation¹, as well as the intellectual production of a blond and European Paraná². Such studies pointed out the production, circulation, and appropriation of ideas around identity idealizations, for example an alleged “blond spot” in southern Brazil or the fact that the state of Paraná was considered a “different Brazil”, which ended up resulting in a noticeably singular regional history writing.

Such arguments have appeared repeatedly in the production of some relevant intellectuals in the political, educational, and scientific spheres, mainly in the Brazilian context of the mid-20th century. Among

¹ WEBER, Maria Julieta. *Tinguiús, pioneiros e adventícios na mancha loira do sul do Brasil: o discurso regional de formação social e histórica paranaense*. Thesis (Sociology Doctoral Program) – Curitiba: Universidade Federal do Paraná, 2009.

² WEBER, Maria Julieta. “Produção intelectual de um Paraná loiro e europeu: o Brasil que nunca foi diferente” In SUASNÁBAR, Claudio; WEBER, Maria Julieta; OLIVEIRA, Natália Cristina de (Orgs.). *Os intelectuais em contextos nacionais e internacionais: educação, intervenções e culturas*. Porto Alegre, RS: FI, pp. 211-237, 2022.

the intellectuals approached, Bento Munhoz da Rocha Netto³ and Wilson Martins⁴ outstood. They were writers, politicians, and university professors from Paraná. Therefore, they were publicly recognized as intellectuals who established opposition to the regionalist theoretical model of Brazilian formation proposed by Gilberto Freyre (1900-1987).

As regards Bento Munhoz da Rocha Netto, he defended that the South was “white” and the state of Paraná was the “blond spot in southern Brazil”. Regarding the mixed-race issue, as addressed by Gilberto Freyre, Bento Munhoz da Rocha Netto thought that there was a contrast in the southern populations, which he considered a diversified region in relation to a supposed Brazilian normality, due to the flow of white immigrants in the south of the country. That author appropriated Gilberto Freyre’s analysis model; however, he twisted the issue by introducing the white European immigration heritage in southern Brazil. In such analytical inversion of Gilberto Freyre’s⁵ theory, he defended, for example, the need to worship the “Blonde Mother” in opposition to the “Black Mother” cult, to honor blond traces against the mixed-race idea. However, he advocated that the criterion should not be racial, but rather cultural, which evidenced the entanglement of conceptual appropriations between race and culture. This means that the intellectual

³ Bento Munhoz da Rocha Netto (1905-1973) was full professor at the University of Paraná (currently UFPR), occupying the chair of American History. In his trajectory, he was linked to the Partido Republicano Paranaense — PRP (Republican Party of Paraná), becoming a Federal Deputy in 1946, Governor of the state of Paraná in the 1951-1954 term, Minister of Agriculture 1954-1955, and Federal Deputy in the 1959-1963 term. The party, PRP, had already been in power with Caetano Munhoz da Rocha, his father, in the 1920-1924 and 1924-1928 periods, in alternation of the family power during the Brazilian First Republic with Affonso Alves de Camargo, also from PRP, who ruled in Paraná in the 1916-1920 and 1928-1930 terms.

⁴ Wilson Martins (1921-2010) was a literary critic and full professor in the literature area at the Federal University of Paraná (UFPR). He was also a professor at the University of New York. In 1943 and 1944, he occupied a position in Manoel Ribas’s office staff (the latter was appointed intervenor of Paraná in 1932, and headed the state government during the 1932-1945 period, outstanding as one of the strongest supporters of Getúlio Vargas). Later, Wilson Martins approached the political current led by Bento Munhoz da Rocha Netto.

⁵ Gilberto Freyre, in the preface initially written in Lisbon in 1931 of the first edition of the book *Casa-grande e senzala: formação da família brasileira sob o regime da economia patriarcal* (Main house and slaves’ accommodation: Brazilian family formation under the patriarchal economy regime) published in 1933, indicated from his contact with the anthropologist Franz Boas (1858-1942), what he considered the “fundamental difference between race and culture” as well as “the effects of purely genetic relationships and those of social influence, cultural heritage, and the environment”. It seems relevant to emphasize that the book was divided into 5 chapters, as follows: I General characteristics of the Portuguese colonization in Brazil: formation of an agrarian, enslaving, and hybrid society; II The indigenous individual in the formation of the Brazilian family; III The Portuguese colonizer: background and predispositions; IV The black slave in the Brazilian sexual and family life; V The black slave in the Brazilian sexual and family life (continued). FREYRE, Gilberto. *Casa-grande & senzala: formação da família brasileira sob o regime da economia patriarcal*. 51. ed. São Paulo: Global, 2006, p. 32.

from Paraná defended the cultural criterion departing from racial criteria for categorizing the argument by the individuals' skin color.

Wilson Martins wrote an essay that achieved great repercussion at the regional level called "A different Brazil: an essay about acculturation phenomena in Paraná". The text defended the idea of "a different Brazil" in the formation of the state of Paraná as an "original civilization" since according to that author, the history of the state had been constituted "without slavery, without Black people, without Portuguese people, and without the indigenous people, in other words, its human definition was not Brazilian"⁶. He evidenced racial aspects by defending a "physical type" from Paraná, in which the white immigrant presence was fundamental in the Brazilian meridional formation.

Regarding the inversion in relation to Gilberto Freyre, both Wilson Martins and Bento Munhoz da Rocha Netto did not question, but rather reinforced the Luso-tropicalism consecration value, a thesis that formulated utterances from cultural assumptions that sometimes soothed, other times romanticized domination and colonization relationships. According to Patrícia Ferraz de Matos, Gilberto Freyre's Luso-tropicalist thesis was supported by the argument that "the Portuguese, for having received several influences, including from Northern Africa, were more inclined to mingle amicably with other peoples". This thesis was elaborated in 1930; however, it was only incorporated in the 1950s by the *Estado Novo* regime in Portugal (1933-1974), aiming to achieve "legitimacy to perpetrate colonial violence based on race,"⁷. It seems relevant to highlight that the study of the alleged Portuguese plasticity provides indication for the denaturalization of intellectual productions whose principle is the cultural differentiation by pigmentation features.

Therefore, the initiative to revisit such conceptions and set a regional perspective is based on the idea of uprooting prejudice. Ideas of a "different Brazil" or a "blond spot" represented, in their production context (mid-20th century) a legitimate language and, therefore, authorized in the definition of guidelines for regional history studies, but also one inserted in a broader project of thinking national formation criteria and framing such parameters within different territorial belongings in the country. An important example of this type of discursive approach was introduced by Oliveira Viana (1883-1951), an author that was highly respected by Bento Munhoz da Rocha Netto

⁶ MARTINS, Wilson. *Um Brasil diferente: ensaio sobre fenômenos de aculturação no Paraná*. 2. ed. São Paulo: T. A. Queiroz, 1989, p. 446.

⁷ MATOS, Patrícia Ferraz de. "As cores do racismo português: do colonialismo à actualidade" In *Público*, 31 January 2021, Ano XXXI, n. 11237, 2021, pp. 16-17.

and Wilson Martins. In *Populações Meridionais do Brasil* (Populations in the south of Brazil), work published in 1918, Viana addressed the historical formation and the land ownership and rural background in the country. When referring to the Brazilian ethnic composition and the “mixed-race individuals” as a historical product of large rural properties”, drawing attention to what he called “genesis” in the “nationality formation”⁸. The “Luso” presence was described as the one that came “alone and single” and found “sexual relief” in “vast and rough gynoecia-like”, or “slaves’ accommodations”, the place of encounter of the “Luso’s licentious lust” and the idyllic figures of the “sweet and slender indigenous women” and the “hot and affectionate black women”.

Among the representatives of the three ethnic groups, competing with land ownership, the Luso (Portuguese individual) was the only one that came alone and single, in his quality of adventurous man. Diving in the wonders of the tropical nature, with hyperexcited nerves due to the effect of our sun, he was attracted, when looking for sexual relief, to those vast and rough gynoecia-like environment that were the accommodations of slaves. They were full of healthy and strong women, and the place where they could find the sweet and slender indigenous women, with their aristocratic and beautiful shape, along with the hot, affectionate, prolific, and seducing black women, who presented excellent host’s abilities, to satisfy the Luso’s licentious lust⁹.

This article aims to desacralize past discourses that were produced and disseminated by intellectuals that represented the Brazilian social thought and were highly acknowledged. It also proposes to investigate how such arguments acted in the formation of prejudice and also uproot conceptualizations around the conflict between “race” and culture. Therefore, it focusses on discriminatory arguments or, more appropriately, prejudiced and disseminators of conceptual confusion.

It seems also relevant to mention that the analysis of some positions of those literate intellectuals might be understood by what Mbembe pointed out, when addressing the black reasoning critique, that is, the “race delirium”¹⁰. Such delirium was made of a type of “codified madness” exactly

⁸ VIANA, Oliveira. *Populações meridionais do Brasil*. (Edições do Senado Federal, v. 27). Brasília: Senado Federal, Conselho Editorial, 2005 [1918], p. 128.

⁹ Ibid.

¹⁰ MBEMBE, Achille. *Crítica da razão negra*. Lisboa: Antígona, 2014, p. 11.

for being a codification that assigned the “skin and the color the status of a biological appearance fiction”. Such codification model also regards the identity characterizations in the south region of the country since when the inhabitants of that state were considered “different” from the inhabitants of other regions of the country, they defined ideally the “blond” aspect of that population. It seems relevant to mention that the arguments put forward by the intellectuals referred to in this article configure as a cultural aspect of the analysis, but in essence they are intrinsically related to the hygienic debates and the eugenicist purposes sedimented by the social thought originated in the sanitizing campaigns in Brazil. This is addressed below.

Eugenics and social thought: an “ill Brazil” in a “Brazilian nature”

The early 20th century was crucial for the production and circulation of the eugenicist thought as well as the ideas and projects about racial, mental, and educational hygiene along with the spread of sanitizing campaigns throughout the country. However, intellectual productions resulting from the movements disseminating eugenicist ideas might gain a new dimension when considering the interconnections between Europe and America since the first decades of the 20th century.

As an illustration of the production and circulation of ideas from eugenicist movements, it seems interesting to think about the places and contexts of creation of eugenicist societies. Those societies would employ approaches related to social selectivity, based on anthropometric analyses that triggered proposals and guidelines of mental prophylaxis and contraceptive methods aiming at genetic improvement, along with eugenicist education teaching projects to provide better education to those considered “gifted”.

For example, in Europe several institutions were created such as the German society for Racial Hygiene (Germany, 1905), the Eugenics Education Society (England, 1907), the French Eugenics Society (France, 1912), the State Institute for Racial Biology (Sweden, 1922) and the Portuguese Society of Eugenics Studies (Portugal, 1937, whose bylaws had been approved in 1934). Several institutions were also created in the American continent, as follows: the Eugenics Record Office (United States of America, 1910), the Eugenics Society of São Paulo (Brazil, 1918); the Brazilian League of Mental Hygiene and the Brazilian Eugenics Institute, in 1931, the Brazilian Eugenics Central Committee (Brazil, 1923 and 1929, respectively); the Mexican Eugenics

Society for the Improvement of the Race (Mexico, 1931), and the Argentinian Association of Biotypology, Eugenics and Social Medicine (Argentina, 1932).

It seems relevant to mention the First International Eugenics Congress held in London in 1912, the creation of the International Federation of Eugenic Societies, and the International Latin Federation of Eugenic Societies, in 1935, whose member countries were part of a so-called Latin cultural and linguistic community, and where the statistician and eugenicist Corrado Gini (1884-1965) outstood. He was also a director of the Italian Committee for Population Problem Studies. Such committee aimed to develop scientific expeditions between 1933 and 1940 and research based on criteria related to the “degeneration” of the human races¹¹.

The actions of the intellectuals involved in the debate of a Latin type of eugenics or eugenicist thought in countries considered of Latin origin refer to the issues related to the political culture consolidated by authoritarianism simultaneous to the modernization process of State-Nations¹². In fact, thinking about eugenics in Latin America also implies taking into account interrelations between race, gender, and nation, as pointed out in Nancy Stepan’s¹³ classical work. For this reason, we considered necessary to relate approaches referring to sanitation and hygiene as well as the echoes of those thoughts in the national identity construction, with the purpose of analyzing possible achievements of those societies and the eugenicist social movements.

Nísia Trindade Lima and Gilberto Hochman called attention to the relations between sanitation, interpretations of the country and social sciences since “the texts by hygienist writers of the three first decades of the 20th century went beyond the health debate limits and disseminated broader representations of society”¹⁴. Those authors mentioned the rural pro-sanitation movement of the First Republic (1889-1930), which “played a central and prolonged role in the construction of the national identity based

¹¹ BERLIVET, Luc André. “A laboratory for Latin eugenics: the Italian Committee for the Study of Population Problems and the international circulation of eugenic knowledge, 1920s-1940s” In *História, Ciências, Saúde – Manguinhos*, Rio de Janeiro, v. 23, 2016, pp. 51-72.

¹² TURDA, Marius; GILLETTE, Aaron. *Latin Eugenics in Comparative Perspective*. Londres: Bloomsbury, 2014.

¹³ STEPAN, Nancy Leys. *The Hour of Eugenics: Race, Gender, and Nation in Latin America*. Ithaca/London: Cornell University Press, 1991.

¹⁴ HOCHMAN, Gilberto; LIMA, Nísia Trindade. “Pouca saúde e muita saúva’: sanitário, interpretações do país e ciências sociais” In HOCHMAN, Gilberto; ARMUS, Diego (Orgs.). *Cuidar, controlar, curar: ensaios históricos sobre saúde e doença na América Latina e Caribe* [online]. Rio de Janeiro: Fiocruz, Coleção História e Saúde, pp. 492-533, 2004, p. 495.

on the identification of illness as a distinctive element in the condition of being a Brazilian”¹⁵.

The idea of an “ill Brazil” indicated the formation of a Brazilian individual whose habits related to laziness, and at this point, the relation and the echoes of the sanitizing ideas can be noticed in the Brazilian social thought. Considering illness or laziness as distinctive features of the national identity found support in the production of intellectuals who represented the Brazilian politics and literature such as Mário de Andrade (1893-1945), who wrote *Macunaíma*¹⁶ (1928) and portrayed allegorically and critically the folk indigenous universe through the narrative of the life of a “hero with no character”; a contradictory individual whose life was characterized by the endless laziness and the prevalence of sexuality. The “stumbling hero” who struggled “on a land without health, but with a lot of ants”: “In the depth of the virgin forest, Macunaíma was born, the hero of our people. He was jet black, the son of fear of the night”¹⁷.

Another reference of that period was Monteiro Lobato (1882-1948). In *Urupês*, written 1918, that author described Jeca Tatu, a “caboclo” who lived in the interior of São Paulo, devoid of a “country feeling”, even if “the most important fact in his life” was “to vote for the government”: “He votes. He does not know exactly for whom, but he votes. He rubs the ink pen on the voting book, drawing some entangled doodles that he calls ‘his signature’”¹⁸. It seems relevant to highlight that 1918 was also the year when the Eugenics Society of São Paulo was created. Monteiro Lobato was a member of that society and exchanged letters with Renato Ferraz Kehl (1889-1978), one of the most representative intellectuals linked to eugenics in Brasil. He was the founder of that society and also of the Eugenics Brazilian Institute, in 1929 (when the First Brazilian Eugenics Congress was held in Brazil), among many other significant activities linked to the eugenicist movement in his intellectual trajectory¹⁹.

¹⁵ Ibid.

¹⁶ Considering the universe of readings available to the intellectuals of the first half of the 20th century, Mário de Andrade inspired his writing of “Makunaimã”, in the studies carried out by the German ethnologist Theodor Koch-Grünberg (1872-1924), who developed relevant research in Amazônia. Some of the results can be accessed, among others, in the book by that researcher entitled *Do Roraima ao Orinoco*, which was thoroughly read by Mário de Andrade.

¹⁷ ANDRADE, Mário de. *Macunaíma: o herói sem nenhum caráter*. 17. ed. São Paulo: Martins Fontes, 1979 [1928], p. 217.

¹⁸ LOBATO, Monteiro. *Urupês*. 2. ed. São Paulo: Globo, 2009 [1918], p. 173.

¹⁹ SOUZA, Vanderlei Sebastião de. *Renato Kehl e a eugenia no Brasil: ciência, raça e nação no período entreguerras*.

The hostile tone used by Monteiro Lobato to contextualize the character Jeca Tatu in matters such as the country’s politics, his daily life, and his relationship with nature around him is quite impressive. When describing the “Brazilian nature” permeated by “blooming ipes” and “rich in shapes and colors”, he portrays Jeca Tatu as follows: “the *caboclo* is the gloomy wood ear mushroom, stagnated in silence at the bottom of caves”, and adds that even surrounded by such “Dionysian life” only the *caboclo* “does not speak, does not sing, does not laugh, does not love. Only he, in the middle of so much life, does not live”²⁰. Later, Monteiro Lobato reconsidered some of Jeca Tatu’s characteristics in relation to his environment and created, in 1947, the character called Zé Brasil, an individual that suffered with the Brazilian land ownership reality. However, the crucial point is that *Urupês* strongly supported ideas and proposals of an eugenicist character and had great national and international repercussion, and an important role in the dissemination of the Jeca Tatu’s image as somebody who liked very little or did not like working at all, that is, the inhabitant of the interior of the country, destined to be lazy and unable to be aware of his own political action.

Even if the degree of respect gained by those authors and the circulation of their work can be measured, it is necessary to highlight that the population mixed-race issue was the central point in the discussions put forward by many intellectuals in the first half of the 20th century. Gilberto Freyre is a referenced author regarding the understanding of the Luso-tropicalism, idea whose contours corresponded, and still correspond, to the fallacy of an alleged Brazilian racial democracy. It seems relevant to emphasize that “in the Luso-tropicalism definitions, associations with the work produced by Gilberto Freyre are very often found. But the readings of his work are several and can be understood in different ways or meanings”²¹. Basically, questioning the abstraction of a hypothetical exceptionality of the Portuguese in the tropics is necessary since “Continuing to reproduce the idea that the Portuguese colonization was different and better than other colonizations neither enriches the present, nor contributes to an understanding of the past”²².

Guarapuava: Editora Unicentro, 2019.

²⁰ LOBATO, op. cit., p. 177.

²¹ CAHEN, Michel; MATOS, Patrícia Ferraz de. “New Perspectives on Luso-tropicalism. Novas Perspetivas sobre o Luso-tropicalismo” In *Portuguese Studies Review*, v. 26, n. 1, pp. 1-6, 2018, p. 4.

²² Ibid.

In the education context, since the National Constituent Assembly (1933-1934), eugenics has been repeatedly evoked. The text of the 1934 Constitution declared that it is the State (nation, state, municipalities) responsibility to stimulate eugenicist education. Taking that into consideration, Giesbrecht and Matos developed a study on the appropriation of the medical-anthropological discourse by the Brazilian Legislative Branch and pointed out the need for “reflecting on the perpetuity of paradigms that permeate the eugenicist movement of the last century”²³.

Therefore, it seems essential to understand eugenics in its contexts of production, considering the scientific discourse essentially supported by medicine and social sciences and even more specifically by anthropology, that is, by intellectuals who used scientific arguments to assign anthropometrically degrees of deficiency or inaptitude (physical and mental) to the collective. They established connections in the realms of science and the political sphere, mainly by means of public health and public education, to devise proposals of school and family education programs based on sanitizing and racial criteria.

Jerry Dávila analyzed how social policies in Brazil in the 1917-1945 period, were structurally marked by racial bias. This is a historical process that advertised a “racially democratic national identity”, by synthesizing racial segregation in the country by means of “discrete and daily mechanisms that reproduced and renewed historical inequalities”²⁴.

In this sense, ideas of heritage and “degeneration” were associated with clinical and pedagogical interventions in the context of the first half of the 20th century in Brazil and Portugal, for example. Relying on the protagonism of a socially and politically well-positioned intellectuality, the production of ideas of improvement of the human race from childhood aimed to “promote a civilization standard, according to which (and also for willing to make it prevail) it was necessary to prevent different or deviant existences”; presumably, those intellectuals were supported by “scientific studies on health (physical and mental) in childhood and by demonstrative practices of the children’s social place in the family, school and institutional environments”²⁵.

²³ GIESBRECHT, Daniel Florence; MATOS, Patrícia Ferraz de. “A apropriação do discurso médico-anropológico pelo poder legislativo brasileiro: a eugenia como utopia regeneradora na Constituinte de 1934” In *Poiésis*, v. 16, n. 29, pp. 37-54, jan-jun, 2022, p. 51.

²⁴ DÁVILA, Jerry. *Diploma de brançura: posição social e racial no Brasil - 1917 - 1945*. São Paulo: Unesp, 2006, p. 16.

²⁵ WEBER, Maria Julieta; MATOS, Patrícia Ferraz de. “Melhorar a espécie humana desde a infância: eugenia e higiene mental no Brasil e em Portugal (primeira metade do século XX)” In *Zero-a-Seis*, v. 25, n. 47, pp. 16-40,

To sum up, there are several issues that might be listed from the scientific proposals and conjectures on the population’s eugenics, hygienic, and educational problems and their correlation with identity idealizations linked to the criteria of formation of an excluding nationalism marked by prejudice. It seems fundamental to uproot such thoughts and reverse the reproduction of practices they originated. One of these practices refers to the appropriations of the eugenicist discourse in regional historiographies.

A “different” and “blond” Brazil: the intellectual production of identity representation in Southern Brazil

The “blond spot” as an analysis category proposed by Bento Munhoz da Rocha Netto was based on historical and sociological arguments supported by the criteria of social and cultural formation of the south region of the country. This category was formed by the populational conformation of specific regions, following cartographic delimitations of what was defined, on the one hand as the “*tingui*” or traditional Paraná, a region that produced mate, and on the other hand as the “pioneer” or new Paraná, where coffee was produced. Regionalism was the central point in Bento Munhoz’s analysis. The idea of the tradition of the elite that produced mate defined, according to him, the political and administrative limits of what corresponded to the formation of the state of Paraná. It seems relevant to emphasize that the economy resulting from the mate production in the state funded a large number of productions with this bibliographic content.

One should consider that the regionality issue for Bento Munhoz da Rocha Netto permeated the idea of nationality from the framing of a European and/or North American civilization, which agreed with other intellectual movements of that time in South America²⁶. Following such perspective, that intellectual was one of the greatest representatives of the discourse of regional identity in Paraná, whose cultural matrix of production and dissemination of ideas called “*paranistas*” focused on the city of Curitiba. The legitimate discourse of idealization of a regional identity in Paraná was produced in the capital of the state²⁷.

Jan/Jun, 2023, p. 35. Universidade Federal de Santa Catarina. Dossiê infância, racismos e educação infantil.

²⁶ WEBER, Maria Julieta. “Bento Munhoz da Rocha Netto e a sua interpretação das Américas” In *Cadernos de História*, v. 18, n. 29, pp. 675-684, 2017.

²⁷ To know more about this topic, see: BEGA, Maria Tarcisa Silva. *Sonho e invenção do Paraná: geração simbolista e a construção de identidade regional*. Thesis (Sociology Doctorate Program) – São Paulo: Universidade de São Paulo, 2001; OLIVEIRA, Ricardo Costa de. *O silêncio dos vencedores: genealogia, classe dominante e Estado*

The book *Presença do Brasil* (Brazil's Presence) by Bento Munhoz da Rocha Netto, published in 1960, showed a mix of praise and opposition to the theoretical model of regionalist orientation by Gilberto Freyre since for the former author, the south of the country was not included in the explanatory approaches of the intellectual from Recife. The miscegenation issue is another factor to be mentioned for being understood as the element that differentiated the idea of mixed race in the Brazilian formation. That author stated: "The south is white. It is the blond spot in the south of Brazil", while "The Brazilian miscegenation establishes a contrast with the Southern populations" and that such "diversification in relation to the Brazilian normality" involved "a vague intuition that the cultural influence necessarily implies in racial influence, as in Europe"²⁸.

This hypothetical diversification of a supposed Brazilian normality suggested that in the south there was a predisposition to "understanding and sympathy toward the foreigner". Even if that author stated that "one cannot confuse race and culture at this level of sociological and anthropological knowledge"²⁹, it was his opposition to Gilberto Freyre's proposal that supported the argument of a different formation in southern Brazil due to the considerable white immigration flow: "The blond individuals are the ones who work from dawn to dusk; the ones running risks in agriculture and earning their money with hard work. White is the blue collar, the servant, the subordinate, the poor, and the humble", and added, "The blond is the one that sets fixed residence and keeps their aspirations and ideals limited to the region"³⁰.

As observed, Bento Munhoz da Rocha Netto also appropriated Gilberto Freyre's model of analysis. However, he reversed the issue by focusing on what he really wanted to emphasize, that is, the European and white heritage in southern Brazil. That author highlighted the importance of regionalism in the "national assimilation process" or by the "regionalism nationalizing

no Paraná. Curitiba: Moinho do Verbo, 2001; PEREIRA, Luís Fernando Lopes. *Paranismo: o Paraná inventado. Cultura e imaginário no Paraná da I República*. Curitiba: Aos Quatro Ventos, 1997; WEBER, Maria Julieta. "O paranismo e o processo de produção historiográfica paranaense: o episódio do Cerco da Lapa" In *Revista de História Regional*, Ponta Grossa, v. 12, n. 2, pp. 151-190, 2007; WEBER, Maria Julieta. *Bento, Brasil e David: o discurso regional de formação social e histórica paranaense*. Curitiba: Ed. UFPR, 2016.

²⁸ ROCHA NETTO, Bento Munhoz da. *Presença do Brasil*. Rio de Janeiro: José Olympio, 1960, p. 73.

²⁹ Ibid.

³⁰ Ibid., p. 62.

function”³¹, supporting his view in the argument that the regional diversity in the south was mainly provided by the white European immigration.

In the south, considering the analytical inversion of Gilberto Freyre’s theory, also resided a “problem of assimilation, of psychological reaction”³². For example, as previously mentioned, the need to worship the “Blonde Mother” as opposed to the cult to the “Black Mother”: “in the south, for some generations, the persistence of the flow of blond currents of immigrants provoked, with the maintenance of the Black Mother, another figure that equaled the former in dedication and affection, that is, the Blonde Mother of clear eyes”³³. Thus, the author insisted that the criterion was not racial, but rather cultural. However, the skin pigment was the predominant element in the cultural differentiation in his analysis. It seems also relevant to notice the assignment of value when considering the loss of “cultural meaning” by the mixed-race individual in opposition to the tradition perpetuated by the “blond spot Brazilian”. According to Bento Munhoz da Rocha Netto:

The conviction that the mixed-race, *mulato* individuals are unarguably Brazilians is rooted in the country. And, in fact, they are. The motivation of such conviction is much more cultural than racial. The Brazilian features of the *mulato* and black individuals are supreme and unquestioned. Even they would not be able to explain their origins in another way. They know about their African origins, but they lost the cultural meaning of such origin and the ability to compare their values with the ones that currently characterize them. This is a different attitude from that of the blond spot Brazilians, who are aware of their origin and compare, by the tradition they experienced and was communicated to them either verbally or in writing, that is, the cultural values of their past and the ones that define them in the present³⁴.

This idea of superiority regarding “cultural meaning” only found in the “blond spot Brazilian” was also rooted in the proposal of *Um Brasil Diferente: ensaio sobre fenômenos de aculturação no Paraná* (A Different Brazil: an essay about acculturation phenomena in Paraná) by Wilson Martins, published in 1955, with a revised edition in 1989, whose first edition was dedicated to Bento

³¹ Ibid., p. 60.

³² Ibid., p. 72.

³³ Ibid., p. 64.

³⁴ Ibid., pp. 72-73.

Munhoz da Rocha Netto. Among the oppositions that the book provoked, there was an article by Cecília Maria Westphalen³⁵ (1927-2004), published in 1997 by the *Revista da Sociedade Brasileira de Pesquisa Histórica* (Historical Research Brazilian Society Journal), whose title already questioned “After all, was there an enslaving regime in Paraná or not?”. It seems relevant to evidence the time lapse between the formulation of that issue by Wilson Martins, 1955 and the response given by Cecília Maria Westphalen, 1997, that is, 42 years after the first publication and 8 years after its reviewed edition. That author limited territorially the analysis to the coast of Paraná and the region called Plateau of Curitiba and Campos Gerais, from a survey carried out in documents that recorded the population of the state of Paraná between 1772 and 1854. Such documents included general maps and lists of inhabitants kept in the Public Archive of São Paulo, a statistical essay by Daniel Pedro Müller, from 1836, and a report by Zacarias de Góis e Vasconcelos, first president of the Province of Paraná, of 1854, where he presented an organized report of the population one year after the political emancipation of Paraná from the State of São Paulo. The Brazilian census of 1772 did not describe the color of the population and, according to Cecília Maria Westphalen did not include data from the place called “*Povoação do Iapó*” (Iapó Village); however, the number that author referred to as the population of Paraná, included the color criterion, which when adding “mixed-race (*mulatos*) and black individuals” or “slaves and their descendants”, should result in an effective percentage that “was never below 40%, and might have reached 46.3%”³⁶.

Mendonça wrote about *Escravidão, africanos e afrodescendentes na “cidade mais europeia do Brasil”* (Slavery, Africans, and African descendants in the “most European city in Brazil”) and reported that the academic production “defining parameters” of a regional history based on the characteristics of the European immigration, ended up minimizing the “importance of slavery in the regional history, and the participation of African individuals and their descendants in the conformation of the local population”³⁷. About the repercussion of Wilson Martins’s book, she mentioned:

³⁵ It seems relevant to highlight that Cecília Maria Westphalen, throughout her academic life, was highly favorable to the consecration of Gilberto Freyre’s work. To know more about this topic, see: WESTPHALEN, Cecília Maria. *A palavra do sul. Cem anos de Gilberto Freyre*. Curitiba: CD, 2000.

³⁶ WESTPHALEN, Cecília Maria. “Afiml, existiu ou não, regime escravo no Paraná?” In *Revista SBPH - Sociedade Brasileira de Pesquisa Histórica*, Curitiba, n. 13, pp. 25-63, 1997, pp. 26-27.

³⁷ MENDONÇA, Joseli Maria Nunes. “Escravidão, africanos e afrodescendentes na ‘cidade mais europeia do Brasil’: identidade, memória e história pública” In *Tempos Históricos*, UNIOESTE, v. 20, n. 1, pp. 218-240, 2016, p. 225.

When studying what he considered acculturation phenomena in Paraná, which he thought resulted from the contact established between foreigners from different European origins, Wilson Martins concluded that the social formation of the region did not result from the interaction between indigenous, Portuguese, and black individuals, as occurred in the social environment studied by Gilberto Freyre. He justified his view by explaining that the history of Paraná was completely different from the history of the rest of the country³⁸.

Therefore, when Wilson Martins defended the idea that Paraná was a “Different Brazil” in his “essay about the acculturation phenomena in Paraná”, he ascribed the formation of the state to an “original civilization built up from pieces of all the others”. That author justified the argument as a “sociological point of view”. He also stated: “Without slavery, without black, without Portuguese, without indigenous individuals, one could say that its human formation is not Brazilian”. “This is Paraná”, he wrote when concluding the work³⁹. Addressing essentially the white immigration in Paraná, he characterized what he thought constituted the “Brazilian from Paraná”. In one of the subtitles of the book called “There was no slavery in Paraná” Wilson Martins was firm in his arguments regarding racial aspects and indicated a specific “physical type” as a result of “acculturation phenomena”:

such handsome physical type, suntanned and with brown hair outstood from other Brazilians, due to a trace of fundamental importance, namely, he did not mix with black individuals, which existed in reduced number in the whole province throughout its history, and for this reason, did not invade sexually the habits of those rustic primitive men⁴⁰.

He also stated that Paraná “suggested advanced projects of social hygiene”⁴¹, and that along with immigration, the “inexistence of large-scale slavery was the most characteristic aspect of the social history in Paraná”, differentiating it “unmistakenly from other Brazilian regions such as Rio de Janeiro and the Northeast, for example”⁴². Wilson Martins differentiated the “miscegenation of the South and the north of the country” and defended a

³⁸ Ibid., p. 224.

³⁹ MARTINS, op. cit., p. 446.

⁴⁰ Ibid., pp. 127-128.

⁴¹ Ibid., p. 135.

⁴² Ibid., p. 128.

type of ideal miscegenation characterized by “white individuals from different origins” as opposed to “white and black individuals”. In short, he characterized a “physical type of the south of the country” exhibiting “noticeable signs of mixture of European bloods, mainly among the different *dólicos* peoples⁴³ among themselves”⁴⁴:

The height, hair and eye color, the blood conformation, are some of the aspects to observe when setting a scientific measure of miscegenation that occurred and still occurs here more among white individuals from several origins (therefore, in a fusion of incalculable proportions) than among white and black individuals, which is the most common type of miscegenation in northern Brazil and its subclasses⁴⁵.

From what that author understood as “miscegenation”, he alleged that there was not a typical mixture of races in the south of the country, that is why he considered it a “different Brazil”:

When talking about mixed-race in the states of Paraná and Santa Catarina, it is difficult to consider the *mulato* or *mameluco*, who are seen in minimal proportion, what must be considered is the mixture of several elements of the white race, which scientifically is not a mixture of races in the strict meaning of the expression⁴⁶.

Defending a “typical foreign cultural influence in the southern populations of Brazil” includes considering what the author classified as an “industrial type of civilization” as opposed to the “agricultural and cattle breeding aptitude” of the “north of the country”⁴⁷, and also something he characterized as the “now sub-race of Paraná”, who “very soon shall dominate

⁴³ Gilberto Freyre, op. cit., 2006, pp. 65-67, defended the thesis of “predisposition of the Portuguese to a hybrid and enslaving colonization in the tropics” or the simulated “aptitude to the tropical life”, and explained what he called “ethnic, or better, cultural past” of the Portuguese colonizers as an “undefined people between Europe and Africa”. Therefore, he refers to a “mass of dark *dólicos*” as the representatives of the formation of such an “unstable population”. He cited, among other authors, Mendes Correia (1888-1960) and his study on “The Portuguese Offenders” (1914), addressing issues related to the “anthropological basis of the Portuguese people”. About Mendes, see: MATOS, Patrícia Ferraz de. *Anthropology, Nationalism and Colonialism: Mendes Correia and the Porto School of Anthropology*. Oxford & New York, Berghhan Books, 2023.

⁴⁴ *Ibid.*, p. 3.

⁴⁵ *Ibid.*

⁴⁶ *Ibid.*

⁴⁷ *Ibid.*

the whole state, a population whose basis is mostly formed by the European immigration current, mainly Polish, German, and Italian”⁴⁸. This reinforced the argument of the “absence of Portuguese people” in the south when compared to what Gilberto Freyre indicated in Northeastern Brazil. He also stated that it was not only “the whiteness of the skin that impressed the observer of the inhabitants of the state of Paraná”, but rather the “set of European physical traces that substituted those of the classical definition of the ‘typical Brazilian’ features”⁴⁹.

Márcio de Oliveira, when addressing biographical elements of Wilson Martins, questioned the “objectives sought by a convinced literary critic”, when writing “a book about sociology and anthropology and the cultural identity of Paraná” He counter-argued Wilson Martins’s appropriation of the sociological proposal presented by Gilberto Freyre, since the objective was to write for the south of Brazil “producing what Gilberto Freyre had presented regarding the country as a whole in *Casa Grande & Senzala*”⁵⁰. In this sense, Wilson Martins “aimed to understand the processes of acculturation of the non-Portuguese European elements in the south of the country” since he “called his work ‘An essay about acculturation phenomena in Paraná’⁵¹. Wilson Martins, when referring to Gilberto Freyre’s thought, mentioned that there were some “details that scaped the shrewdness and erudition of that renovator of the Brazilian sociology”⁵². He established some analogy with astronomy when referring to the “behavior” of planets, and listed “disturbing elements”, “details”, which ascribed “a completely different character from that of the region specifically studied by Mr. Gilberto Freyre”, which apart from the “Brazilian northeast” also included “the vast realms of the Lusotropical culture”. The main factor was, therefore, the immigrant presence first, and then the absence of Portuguese individuals and the inexistence of slavery, in such a way that the second and third factors did not appear as relevant sociological forces” to the “states of the south”⁵³.

Although that author approached the south of Brazil, the emphasis of his work was in the state of Paraná: “I mention southern states due to a

⁴⁸ Ibid., p. 135.

⁴⁹ Ibid.

⁵⁰ OLIVEIRA, Márcio de. “O ‘Brasil Diferente’ de Wilson Martins” In *Caderno CRH - Centro de Estudos e Pesquisas em Humanidades*, Salvador, v. 18, n. 44, pp. 215-221, May/Aug, 2005, p. 217.

⁵¹ Ibid.

⁵² MARTINS, op. cit., p. 5.

⁵³ Ibid.

thoughtless generalization since the studies I carried out focus exclusively on the state of Paraná”⁵⁴. It seems relevant to emphasize elements of comparison with the Luso-tropicalist approach employed by Gilberto Freyre regarding the issue of “plasticity” in the characterization of “Northern-European men” who, inversely, were considered the “Portuguese of the South”. According to Wilson Martins:

The immigrant, in an extraordinarily short time, stopped to feel like a foreigner, and felt completely comfortable in the new land, since they shaped it to their own habits, experiences, and traditions. Therefore, North-European men and, due to “empathy”, those of other ethnic groups, showed in the temperate climate of Paraná the same interesting plasticity Mr. Gilberto Freyre verified in the Portuguese individuals “found” in tropical zones. They were, considering these aspects of the acculturation process, the Portuguese of the south⁵⁵.

Such regional argumentation of territorial occupation sometimes by Portuguese settlers, other times by European immigrants was based on cartographic delimitations of what was called demographic gaps. According to the study by José Rogério Beier, the denomination “Sertão desconhecido” (unknown wilderness) is found in the “*Mappa Chorographico da Provincia de São Paulo*”, the first printed map of that province, by Daniel Pedro Müller. However, the term was not properly introduced or created by him since that expression had been in use to refer to maps in the 18th and 19th centuries, as observed in the “*Mappa da Capitania de São Paulo*”, which is part of the collection of the public archive of the State of São Paulo. Thus, describing an “empty” space as “unknown wilderness” ended up including a vast “well-established and limited area, that is, the Province of São Paulo”, which demonstrated “the interest of the province administration in guaranteeing their possession of an area considered ‘unoccupied’”⁵⁶. At the same time, it considered the need to disseminate the existence of a demographic gap, that is, unoccupied area; therefore, “the importance of printing several copies and sending them to the administrative offices of the Court and other provinces of the Empire”⁵⁷. At this point, it seems reasonable to ask: what were the

⁵⁴ Ibid.

⁵⁵ Ibid., p. 6.

⁵⁶ BEIER, José Rogério. “Daniel Pedro Müller e a trajetória de seu Mappa Chorographico da Provincia de São Paulo (1835-1842)” In *Revista Brasileira de Cartografia*. Rio de Janeiro, n. 67/4, pp. 817-836, 2015, p. 825.

⁵⁷ Ibid.

possible consequences of the idea of an unknown, empty and unoccupied interior area? How much silencing and invisibility resulted from this type of production and dissemination of information?

Nísia Trindade Lima wrote about the interpretations of Brazil and the geographical representations of the national identity and approached regionalism in direct correlation with literary and scientific productions, as observed in her discussions of the “imagined wild areas” and the “(re) discovery” of civilizing expeditions and missions in the interior of the country, which included sanitizing campaigns that adopted a scientific approach in the early 20th century. If the “medical perspective adopted when looking into the *Brazilian wild areas* was transformed into a culture and shared political issue” it is exactly because “for the intellectual scientists of the first Republican period, the term ‘wild’ is in the same semantic field as incorporation, progress, civilization, and conquest”⁵⁸.

Final Considerations

This study was mainly justified by the current political context of racism upsurge and return to the notion of “race” as well as sectarian and selective positions regarding excluding identity propositions at the national or regional level. The idealization of a “blond and European” state of Paraná was achieved by the identity representation that designed a historiography with a production context considered legitimate, authorized, and one that defined the guidelines for the study of the regional history. The analyses of Bento Munhoz da Rocha Netto’s and Wilson Martins’s intellectual production presented in this report, and which were anchored in their own academic and political experiences, refers mainly to the aspect that both ascribed it to a hypothetical inversion of analysis, which did not question that value of the assertive consecration of the so-called plasticity defended by Gilberto Freyre.

The proposal of this article was to investigate those intellectual productions defending that it is fundamental to uproot the past and call to debate the approximations of such productions to eugenicist principles to open a path to other writings of history aiming to understand the effects of such idealizations in current times. If eugenics-related issues used to be treated as scientific principles motivated by the hygiene, social, mental, educational, and racial instigation of the first half of the 20th century, certainly their correlations with social thought regarding identity idealizations still

⁵⁸ LIMA, Nísia Trindade. *Um sertão chamado Brasil*. 2. ed., aumentada. São Paulo: Hucitec, 2013, p. 107; 146.

persist in other formats. They might appear in the regionality views marked by the idea of “stumbling heroes”, either in the representation of a mixed-race population, or in ideas of “regeneration” of the lazy “Jecas Tatus”. Such projects were supported by a type of savior nationalism and, therefore, they were excluding and strongly marked by prejudice and discrimination.

For this reason, analyzing intellectual actions and movements is important to understand historiographic debates of these days correlated to memory issues, including forgotten and silenced details. Moreover, resizing regional differences and historical processes of territorial occupations, to oppose identity representations based on projects of populational “regeneration considered scientific is also fundamental as well as deconstructing ideas intentionally mistaken of demographic gaps, alleged cultural superiority, and fragmented identity positionings.

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Eugenics and Catholicism in Brazil: a study based on Catholic intellectual production in Rio de Janeiro in the decades of 1920 and 1930¹

Eugenia e Catolicismo no Brasil: um estudo a partir da produção intelectual católica do Rio de Janeiro nas décadas de 1920 e 1930

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Abstract

The study examines the intricate intersection between eugenics, the Catholic Church, and discursive power. The clash between radical eugenicists and the Church is analyzed, highlighting rhetorical strategies and forms of expression. This raises whether, in the Brazilian context, the Church has played a role in advocating for a model of Catholic eugenics. To explore this issue, bibliographic and documentary sources were analyzed, including Catholic publications in Rio de Janeiro in the 1920s and 1930s, such as the book *Ensaios de Biologia*, conceived by the Catholic Institute of Higher Studies, and the magazine *A Ordem*, an influential periodical of the Catholic intellectual elite at that time, associated with the Dom Vital Center. A methodological approach emphasizing hermeneutic and qualitative analysis has been chosen. This choice aimed to explore the various perspectives and interpretations present in the selected sources. In summary, the research reveals the intricate dynamics of power, discursive control, and the resistance between eugenics and religion, offering insights into a crucial period in the history of the relationship between science and faith.

Keywords: Eugenics. Catholic Intellectuals. Catholic Press. Church and Modernity. Brazil.

Resumo

O estudo investiga a intrincada interseção entre eugenia, Igreja Católica e poder discursivo. Analisa-se o embate entre os eugenistas radicais e a Igreja, evidenciando estratégias retóricas e formas de expressão. Surge, assim, a indagação sobre se, no contexto brasileiro, a Igreja desempenhou o papel de

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defender um modelo de eugenia católica. Para explorar essa questão, foram analisadas fontes bibliográficas e documentais, incluindo publicações católicas no Rio de Janeiro nas décadas de 1920 e 1930, como o livro *Ensaios de Biologia*, concebido pelo Instituto Católico de Estudos Superiores, e a revista *A Ordem*, um periódico influente da elite intelectual católica da época, associado ao Centro Dom Vital. Optou-se por uma abordagem metodológica que enfatizasse a análise hermenêutica e qualitativa. Essa escolha teve como objetivo explorar as diversas perspectivas e interpretações presentes nas fontes selecionadas. Em síntese, a pesquisa revela as intrincadas dinâmicas de poder, controle discursivo e resistência entre eugenia e religião, oferecendo percepções sobre um período fundamental na história das relações entre ciência e fé.

Palavras-Chave: Eugenia. Intelectuais Católicos. Imprensa Católica. Igreja e Modernidade. Brasil.

Introduction

Eugenics, envisioned by Francis Galton in the late 19th century, became a sort of self-image of modernity. Attracting enthusiasts worldwide, the “science of Galton,” as it became known, became a central concept in scientific, social, and political debates in both European circles and the Americas. Through methodologies of intervention and control over heredity and the environment, eugenic theories promised to improve the genetic quality of human populations while simultaneously preventing societal degeneration. As a result, certain fields of knowledge related to genetics were privileged, leading to the establishment of the model of negative eugenics, which advocated for the adoption of total biopolitical measures — Such as dissemination of contraceptive methods; marital restrictions when necessary; and sterilization of individuals deemed harmful to collective health and race².

In a more particular context such as Brazil, the implementation of the republican regime at the end of the 19th century reflected a time heavily influenced by the positivism of Auguste Comte and the social Darwinism of Herbert Spencer. This conducive environment allowed for the incorporation of new projects of social engineering that promised the improvement of the human condition from the perspective of the bourgeois class, aiming to preserve the lineage of the social elites and, simultaneously, regenerate the lower classes through hygienic and moral measures. Thus, theories of a

² STEPAN, Nancy. *The hour of eugenics: race, gender, and nation in Latin America*. Ithaca: Cornell University Press, 1991.

racist nature, legitimized by the sciences, aligned with notions of progress and evolution³.

As the country progressed towards modernization, the quest for refinement of the racial profile of the population emerged as a central concern to foster national development. Driven by demographic challenges, the complex multiracial structure, and issues in Brazilian healthcare, advocates of eugenics would experience a significant increase in influence during the 1910s⁴.

From this, the concept of Latin eugenics emerges as an approach that reflects European conceptions of human improvement and incorporates distinctive elements of the Latin American reality. The main course of action of the intellectual debate on eugenics in Latin contexts relied on assumptions of national modernization and, consequently, the strengthening of the nation-state⁵.

According to scholar Nancy Stepan's analysis, this framework has provided a viable platform for the development of a form of preventive eugenics in Brazil, strongly influenced by French neo-Lamarckism⁶. Such approach to eugenics was not only limited to the selection of favorable hereditary traits but also encompassed the promotion of hygiene, disease prevention, maternal and childcare, improvement of educational and work conditions, mitigation of social problems such as alcoholism and prostitution. Thus, eugenic engineering aimed not only for collective refinement but also for the promotion of economic progress, based on a perspective adapted to the nation's specificities.

These reformist principles were gradually embraced by the Catholic Church in the early decades of the 20th century. Through the advancement of material life and scientific discourse, a convergence between Catholicism and the modern world was observed, especially after the impacts of the French Revolution in 1789 and the increasing secularization of Western

³ GIESBRECHT, Daniel Florence. "Divus contra Galton: o debate eugênico a partir da produção intelectual católica brasileira na década de 1930" In *Anuario de Antropología Iberoamericana*, pp. 1-6, 2023.

⁴ BONFIM, Paulo. *Educar, higienizar e regenerar: uma história da eugenia no Brasil*. Jundiaí: Paco Editorial, 2017, pp. 42-43.

⁵ WEBER, Maria Julieta. "Eugenia Latina em Portugal e no Brasil (primeira metade do século XX)" In *Trabalhos de Antropologia e Etnologia*, v. 63, pp. 205-217, 2023, p. 208. To learn more, see TURDA, Marius; GILLETTE, Aaron. *Latin eugenics in comparative perspective*. London: Bloomsbury, 2014; SOUZA, Vanderlei Sebastião de. *Renato Kehl e a eugenia no Brasil: ciência, raça e nação no período entreguerras*. Guarapuava: Unicentro, 2019.

⁶ STEPAN, op. cit., p. 92.

states⁷. Additionally, the apparent compatibility between neo-Lamarckism and Catholicism, in contrast to Protestant determinism, is pointed out as one of the fundamental reasons for the adherence of most Brazilian Catholic eugenicists to the approach of preventive eugenics⁸. In this tradition, there was an emphasis on the value of human dignity and freedom, as well as the importance of the pursuit of moral and spiritual excellence, in line with the ideal of regeneration proposed by eugenicists. For example, in the 1910s, the British priest Thomas John Gerrard had already expressed in his book *The Church and Eugenics* that the pursuit of eugenic reform should not be hindered by the Church, but rather promoted by it, on a spiritual basis⁹.

However, the apparent reconciliation between eugenic principles and Catholic precepts have proved to be fragile. During the 1920s and 1930s, the practice of eugenic sterilization, both voluntary and compulsory, as well as the adoption of birth control methods, spread mainly in Protestant tradition countries, especially those of Anglo-Saxon origin¹⁰. Faced with these advancements, a clear and unequivocal concern was demonstrated by the Catholic Church, which condemned all actions that interfered with the natural process of life procreation. The papal encyclical *Casti Connubii*, promulgated on December 31st, 1930, by Pope Pius XI, played a significant role in reaffirming the Church's uncompromising stance regarding birth control, abortion, and sterilization as affronts to the fundamental principles of the Catholic faith¹¹.

Given the proliferation of biopolitical notions of invasive interventions, it is possible to observe that the strategy of expanding the influence of the Catholic Church was intensified out of concern of being marginalized in light of the new values promoted by modern biology. As pointed out by Sérgio Miceli, this process was mainly developed through the establishment of a

⁷ RIBEIRO, Emanuela Sousa. *Modernidade no Brasil, Igreja Católica, Identidade Nacional: práticas e estratégias intelectuais (1889-1930)*. Tese (Doutorado em História)—Recife: Universidade Federal de Pernambuco, 2009.

⁸ TURDA; GILLETTE, op. cit., p. 42.

⁹ WEGNER, Robert; SOUZA, Vanderlei Sebastião de. "Eugenia 'negativa', psiquiatria e catolicismo: embates em torno da esterilização eugênica no Brasil" In *História, Ciências, Saúde-Manguinhos*, v. 20, pp. 263-288, 2013, p. 272.

¹⁰ The implementation of the first compulsory sterilization law occurred in the United States, specifically in the state of Indiana, in 1907. However, it was in California that the program reached the highest number of cases, with an estimated twenty thousand sterilizations performed between 1909 and 1979. These policies received widespread criticism and scrutiny, especially during the 1960s and 1970s, when issues related to individual rights and social justice gained greater prominence. See REILLY, Philip. *The surgical solution: a history of involuntary sterilization in the United States*. Baltimore: Johns Hopkins University Press, 1991.

¹¹ WEGNER; SOUZA, op. cit., p. 273.

series of organizations independent of the ecclesiastical hierarchy¹². Under the leadership of Catholic intellectuals, these institutions sought to react against intellectual currents, religious beliefs, and political measures contrary to the principles of the Holy See, such as radical eugenic practices, now formally condemned in the pages of the encyclical *Casti Connubii*¹³. Thus, the question arises whether, in Brazil, the Church committed itself to defending a paradigm of Catholic eugenics as an alternative to the principles espoused by negative eugenics, aiming to preserve its influence over the bodies and sexuality of the faithful¹⁴. This article aims to reflect on this issue.

To achieve this purpose, bibliographical and documentary sources have been analyzed, including Catholic publications in Rio de Janeiro in the 1920s and 1930s, with emphasis on the book *Ensaio de Biologia* [Essays of Biology], conceived by the Catholic Institute of Higher Studies, and the magazine *A Ordem* [The Order], a relevant periodical printed by the Brazilian Catholic intellectual elite of that time and also linked to the Dom Vital Center, a recognized association of Catholic intellectuals.

In general, a methodological approach emphasizing hermeneutic and qualitative analysis has been chosen. This choice aimed to explore the various perspectives and interpretations present in the selected sources. To compare and analyze the narratives, discourses and concepts present in these sources, efforts were made to investigate the complex relationships between power, religion, and biology in the context of eugenics.

From the foundation of the Catholic Institute of Higher Studies to the publication of *Ensaio de Biologia*.

The implementation of the Brazilian Republic in 1889, heavily influenced by French positivist ideas, resulted in the official rupture between the State and the Church, consecrated by Decree No. 119-A, dated January 7th, 1890¹⁵. This event forced the Church to undergo a process of institutional reorganization

¹² MICELI, Sérgio. *A elite eclesíastica brasileira: 1890-1930*. São Paulo: Companhia das Letras, 2009.

¹³ PIO XI. *Carta encíclica Casti Connubii del Papa Pío XI sobre el matrimonio Cristiano*, Roma, 1930, pp. 15-18. (https://www.vatican.va/content/pius-xi/es/encyclicals/documents/hf_p-xi_enc_19301231_casti-connubii.html), Last consulted 17 June 2023.

¹⁴ This article employs the term “Catholic eugenics” to describe a eugenic approach grounded in the principles and values of Catholicism. This perspective entails preventive, sanitary, and pro-natalist strategies in line with the guidelines and positions established by the ecclesiastical hierarchy.

¹⁵ BRASIL. *Decreto No 119-A, de 7 de janeiro de 1890*. (https://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/decreto/1851-1899/d119-a.htm), Last consulted 20 June 2023.

to adapt to the new circumstances. Additionally, essential structural changes occurred in Latin America in the early 20th century. The rise of the working class, the secularization of culture, and the emergence of new interest groups, coupled with the spread of communism and Protestantism, left the Catholic Church in a state of disorientation¹⁶.

Nevertheless, this new situation created an opportunity for the growing presence of lay religious institutions in various spheres of the social world, especially through the actions of their intellectual elites¹⁷. In this context, in Brazil, the lawyer Jackson de Figueiredo and the literary critic Alceu Amoroso Lima, known by the pseudonym Tristão de Ataíde, stood out. They played a central role in leading lay activities aligned with the interests of the Church, notably through the Dom Vital Center and the magazine *A Ordem*, its main vehicle for scientific publication¹⁸.

After the 1930 Revolution, Getúlio Vargas assumed the leadership of a Provisional Government, committing to restructuring the country until new elections could be held. Due to the lack of constitutional legitimacy of this new government, the Catholic Church seized the opportunity to intervene in the political sphere, emphasizing the necessity of the religious element in the State and arguing that secular society had proven incapable of providing a worthy moral framework¹⁹.

Aware that higher education represented an effective means to promote education based on Catholic ideology, Jesuit priest Leonel Edgard da Silveira Franca collaborated, through his extensive network of contacts, which included Alceu Amoroso Lima, in the founding of the first Catholic higher education institution in Brazil: the Catholic Institute of Higher Studies in Rio de Janeiro, then the Federal Capital of the country²⁰.

¹⁶TODARO, Margareth Patrice. *Pastors, prophets and politicians; a study of brazilian church; 1916-45*. New York: Columbia University Press, 1971.

¹⁷Lay religious institutions are entities or associations belonging to a specific faith, managed and led by lay members, meaning individuals who do not possess clerical ordination, such as priests, pastors, or monks. Such organizations can fulfill various roles within a religious community, including educational, charitable, social, and cultural activities, among others.

¹⁸VELLOSO, Mônica Pimenta. "A Ordem: uma revista de doutrina política e cultura católica" In *Revista de Ciência Política*, v. 21, n. 3, pp. 117-160, 1978.

¹⁹GOMES, Edgar da Silva. "A atualização da hierarquia eclesíástica no Brasil: política e poder na relação Estado/Igreja durante a República Velha (1889-1930)" In *Projeto História: Revista do Programa de Estudos Pós-Graduados de História*, v. 37, pp. 295-303, 2008.

²⁰See OLIVEIRA, Natália Cristina de; CAMPOS, Névio de; SKALINSKI JÚNIOR, Oriomar. "O modelo católico de ensino superior no Brasil" In *Revista Internacional de Educação Superior*, v. 5, pp. 1-26, 2019.

The solemn ceremony marking the inauguration of the Institute took place on May 24th, 1932, in the conference hall of the School of Fine Arts in Rio de Janeiro. It was presided over by Cardinal D. Sebastião Leme and directed by Alceu Amoroso Lima. The event was attended by the Minister of Education, Francisco Campos, as well as ecclesiastical authorities and prominent representatives of the Brazilian intellectual community of that time²¹.

In his speech, Alceu Amoroso Lima expressed his concerns about the advance of materialistic and agnostic culture propagated by modern thinkers, especially those who maintained the incompatibility between science and religion²². By invoking the British philosopher and mathematician Alfred North Whitehead, he highlighted Whitehead's observation that Catholic intellectuals had faced discouragement in the face of significant scientific transformations over the last three centuries. From Amoroso Lima's perspective, "one of the main causes of the disrepute of modern religious thought is the timidity of our initiatives, the lack of direction in our studies, and the perpetual 'defensive' position we have adopted"²³.

Alceu Amoroso Lima criticized the materialist propositions of positivism, evolutionism, and monism, reinforcing the need for a theological restoration as the most viable path for Catholicism to truly reclaim the entirety of Brazilian Catholic thought. To this end, he proposed the resumption of the previously severed relations between the natural sciences and the sciences of the spirit, to demonstrate that "philosophical studies are of fundamental necessity to give formative thought of nationality a secure direction and a constructive discipline"²⁴.

The proposed restoration advocated the idea that the hierarchy between the sciences of the natural order and the sciences of the supernatural order implied the supremacy of the latter over the former. This subordination would not alter the autonomy and methodology of the natural sciences, but rather

²¹ CORREIO DA MANHÃ. *A solene inauguração do Instituto Católico de Estudos Superiores*, 25 maio 1932, p. 3.

²² The lecture by Alceu Amoroso Lima was fully reproduced in issue number 28 of the magazine *A Ordem* in June 1932, of which he was the editor-in-chief, along with Perillo Gomes. See ATAÍDE, Tristão de (pseudônimo). "Instituto Católico de Estudos Superiores" In *A Ordem*, v. 7 (Nova Série), n. 28, pp. 415-425, 1932.

²³ *Ibid.*, p. 417. In Portuguese: "umas das causas principais do desprestígio do pensamento religioso moderno é a timidez das nossas iniciativas, o desgoverno de nossos estudos e a posição de eterna 'defensiva' em que nos colocamos".

²⁴ *Ibid.*, p. 423. In Portuguese: "os estudos filosóficos são de necessidade fundamental, para dar ao pensamento formador da nacionalidade uma orientação segura e uma disciplina construtora".

indicate that the human being cannot be reduced to schemes of thought, as proposed by modern materialism.

This theoretical framework would serve as the foundational basis for the pedagogical philosophy of the Catholic Institute of Higher Studies, evident both in its course offerings and its intellectual productions, such as its first book publication: *Ensaio de Biologia*.

For a Catholic approach to modernity and science

Mr. Tristão de Ataíde and Mr. Hamilton Nogueira, whose intellectual expression in contemporary Brazil is widely recognized, have just begun publishing a very intriguing series of “Essays of Biology”. It is an honest work of scientific guidance that the two leaders of the Catholic movement in Brazil are developing with the collaboration of their young disciples [...] This initiative, which can greatly benefit our cultural development, is worthy of the highest praise, and the published volume deserves the strongest encouragement²⁵.

This is how the Rio de Janeiro daily *O Jornal*, in its edition of November 26th, 1933, reported the release of the book *Ensaio de Biologia*, printed by Livraria Católica in Rio de Janeiro²⁶. The work was supervised by Tristão de Ataíde (Alceu Amoroso Lima) and by the physician Hamilton de Lacerda Nogueira, two renowned Catholic intellectuals associated with both the Catholic Institute of Higher Studies and the Dom Vital Center²⁷.

The responsibility for drafting the introduction of the work fell to Tristão de Ataíde. According to his words, throughout the 186 pages, *Ensaio de Biologia*

²⁵ O JORNAL. “Sem título”, 26 novembro 1933, p. 7. In Portuguese: “Os srs. Tristão de Ataíde e Hamilton Nogueira, cuja expressão intelectual na atualidade brasileira todos reconhecem, acabam de iniciar a publicação de uma série curiosíssima de ‘Ensaio de Biologia’. Trata-se de um honesto trabalho de orientação científica, que os dois líderes do movimento católico no Brasil estão elaborando com a colaboração de seus jovens discípulos [...] A iniciativa, que bons serviços poderão prestar a nossa formação cultural, é digna de mais viva simpatia, e o volume publicado merece os melhores estímulos”.

²⁶ The intellectual recognition and acceptance of the work extend beyond the borders of the daily press. For instance, the artistic-literary journal *Boletim de Ariel*, which boasted contributions from important collaborators such as Afrânio Peixoto, Arthur Ramos, Evaristo de Moraes, Gilberto Freyre, and Sérgio Buarque de Holanda, dedicated a favorable review to it. The reviewer, João de Barros Barreto Filho, described *Ensaio de Biologia* as a thorough work that opposed the exaggerations of hasty pseudoscience, heavily influenced by agnostic materialism. BARRETO FILHO, João de Barros. “Tristão de Ataíde e Hamilton Nogueira – Ensaio de Biologia – Livraria Católica – Rio, 1933” In *Boletim de Ariel*, Ano 3, novembro, 1933.

²⁷ ATAÍDE, Tristão de (pseudônimo); NOGUEIRA, Hamilton (Eds.). *Ensaio de Biologia*. Rio de Janeiro: Livraria Católica (Publicações do Instituto Católico de Estudos Superiores), 1933.

promised to offer readers the opportunity to become acquainted with a “new chapter in the history of our thought”. This would imply demonstrating that, in addition to the close relationships “established between speculative problems and practical problems”, it was necessary to understand the “absence of any incompatibility between religion and science”, contrary to the “anachronistic and tired voices” echoed by modern Biology, which, under a deterministic and positivist approach, had become a dominant doctrine, arrogating itself the power to govern the social and moral sciences by “appropriating the concept of life in its totality”²⁸. This analysis ends up justifying the selection of the title *Ensaios de Biologia* for the book, since, according to the author himself, Biology, like other sciences, would have limitations and, by surpassing the boundaries of pedagogical, sociological, or moral interpretations, transcends the narrow scope of arbitrariness and imagination²⁹.

Ensaios de Biologia openly proclaims its doctrinal nature and its mission to “guide upright will”³⁰. In this sense, the focus on issues such as sexuality, heredity, motherhood, and procreation is confirmed as central aspects that demand careful reflection and approach regarding the principles upheld by Catholicism. The purpose of the work was to investigate these subjects to provide guidance and directives that align with Christian values, in opposition to the determinist scientific materialism manifested by the extremes advocated by some eugenicists. In other words, eugenics (as a theoretical and practical science aimed at promoting the progress of the species without exceeding the methods considered licit and honest by the Church) could be considered. In spite of that, if under the label of eugenics and eugenism there were hidden flawed or perverse doctrines that confronted the designs of the Holy See, then they should be condemned and combated³¹.

²⁸ Ibid., pp. 9-12. In Portuguese: “capítulo novo na história do nosso pensamento”; “estabelecidas entre os problemas especulativos e os problemas práticos”; “ausência de qualquer incompatibilidade entre religião e ciência”; “vozes anacrônicas e cansadas”; “apropriar do conceito de vida em sua totalidade”.

²⁹ In addition to the introductory text written by Tristão de Ataíde, eight other articles were included: *Limites da eugenia* [Limits of Eugenics], also by Ataíde; *Esterilização dos tarados* [Sterilization of the Preverts], by Hamilton Nogueira; *A esterilidade voluntária e sua patologia* [Voluntary Sterility and Its Pathology], by Barbosa Quental; *Crítica geral ao lamarckismo* [General Critique of Lamarckism], by César Girard Jacob; *Biotipologia e suas complicações médico-sociais* [Biotypology and its Medical-Social Complications], by Petrônio Rodrigues Chaves; *Aspecto médico do birth-control* [The Medical Aspect of Birth Control], by Antônio Amarante and, again, by César Girard Jacob; *Eutanásia e Biologia* [Euthanasia and Biology], by Waldyr de Azevedo Franco; and *Energética em Biologia* [Energetics in Biology], by Nelson de Almeida Prado.

³⁰ Ibid., p. 13. In Portuguese: “guiar as vontades retas”.

³¹ The appreciation of the relevance of preventive eugenics had already been expressed by Pius XI himself. This consideration is fundamental for understanding how certain eugenic ideas with an environmentalist orientation were absorbed by confessing Catholic intellectuals, who incorporated them into a variant of

Figure 1: Title page of the book *Ensaaios de Biologia*, published by Editora Livraria Católica in 1933

Source: Author's personal collection.

Eugenics as Deified Theology

In addition to writing the introduction, Tristão de Ataíde authored the first chapter of *Ensaaios de Biologia*, titled *Limites da Eugenia* [Limits of Eugenics], which begins with a provocative epigraph attributed to the Irish playwright

Catholic eugenics of a social nature. This includes initiatives aimed at addressing diseases, alcoholism, and prostitution, as well as the implementation of social protection measures. See ACTA APOSTOLICAE SEDIS. *Commentarium Officiale. Anno XXII - Volumen XXII*. Roma: Typis Polyglottis Vaticanis, 1930, p. 564.

and avowed eugenicist Bernard Shaw: “What can be done with a wolf can be done with a man”³².

As expressed by Ataíde, statements like Shaw’s illustrate the notion that, throughout history, humanity has shown an inclination towards “anthropolatry”, a tendency towards worship—modern man has chosen to venerate, respectively, science and humanity itself.

This phenomenon intensified in the 19th century, driven by evolutionary principles, especially Darwinism, resulting in the formulation of a materialistic philosophy that incessantly sought its own model of “Superman”³³. Ataíde criticized proponents of racial improvement, who saw the methods proposed by eugenicists as the only viable solution for the regeneration of society: “Super-humanism is the philosophical form of eugenics. And the essence of eugenics lies precisely in this equation of man to animal in their origin and the progressive separation of both in their ends through sexual selection”³⁴.

Supported by the findings of the German psychiatrist Iwan Bloch, Tristão de Ataíde argued that Charles Darwin was responsible for laying the ontological foundations that would guide the modern eugenics movement³⁵. Such influence would be consolidated by equating humans with animals and advocating for selective criteria that considered the future qualities of offspring resulting from rationalized marital planning. According to him, this phenomenon represented one of the greatest paradoxes of modernity: science, by rejecting any divine manifestation, paradoxically elevated humans

³² ATAÍDE, Tristão de (pseudônimo). “Limites da eugenia” In ATAÍDE, Tristão de (pseudônimo); NOGUEIRA, Hamilton (Eds.). *Ensaio de Biologia*. Rio de Janeiro: Livraria Católica (Publicações do Instituto Católico de Estudos Superiores), pp. 15-35, 1933, p. 17. Sometime later, in 1939, Tristão de Ataíde, already acclaimed as a member of the Brazilian Academy of Letters since 1935, collaborated with Jacques de Lacreteille and Daniel Rops, both distinguished members of the French Academy, in organizing the book titled *O problema sexual* [The Sexual Problem]. In this work, Ataíde, making slight modifications, republished the fundamental text of *Limites da eugenia*, but under the new title *Será aceitável o eugenismo?* [Is Eugenism Acceptable?]. LACRETELLE, Jacques de; ATAÍDE, Tristão de; ROPS, Daniel (Eds.). *O problema sexual*. Tradução: Frederico De Carvalho. Porto: Livraria Tavares Martins, 1963 [1939].

³³ *Ibid.*, pp. 17-18. Like other Catholic intellectuals of his time, Tristão de Ataíde was influenced by significant ultramontane conservative thinkers such as Joseph de Maistre, Donoso Cortés, and Charles Maurras. These intellectuals identified the materialist philosophy that emerged in the 19th century, represented primarily by the works of philosopher Friedrich Nietzsche, as their main adversary. For them, the pursuit of the “superman” (Übermensch) as the ideal model of humanity proposed by Nietzsche reflected the ontology of modern Western pagan thought.

³⁴ *Ibid.*, p. 20. In Portuguese: “o super-humanismo é a forma filosófica do eugenismo. E a essência do eugenismo está justamente nessa equiparação do homem ao animal em sua origem e na separação progressiva de ambos, em seus fins, por meio da seleção sexual”.

³⁵ *Ibid.*, pp. 21-23.

to the status of divinity by promoting eugenics, as if it became a kind of deified theology³⁶.

In the Brazilian context, according to the author, the first Eugenics Congress, held from June 30th to July 7th, 1929, at the National Academy of Medicine in Rio de Janeiro, was the main event to intensify eugenic propaganda in the country. During the meeting, government officials, medical experts, and foreign visitors debated various eugenic topics such as marriage, education, race, protection of nationality, racial typology, genealogy, immigration, venereal diseases, biometrics, and childcare³⁷. Ataíde acknowledged that these themes involved ethical, philosophical, and religious questions that should not be restricted to eugenicists, as many of the event's participants postulated. Nevertheless, he did not direct specific criticisms at any Brazilian eugenicist, unlike his colleague Hamilton Nogueira, as will be seen later on. The main focus was, above all, the critique of the American Protestant eugenic model, as this was presented by Brazilian eugenicists as a magical and even religious solution to mitigate the nation's potential setbacks.

³⁶ *Ibid.*, p. 23.

³⁷ The titles of the lectures delivered during the 1st Brazilian Congress of Eugenics, as well as their respective authors, were as follows: *A eugenia no Brasil* [Eugenics in Brazil] – Renato Kehl; *Os grandes problemas da Antropologia* [The major issues of Anthropology] – A. Fróes da Fonseca; *O estado atual do problema de hereditariedade* [The current state of the heredity problem] – André Dreyfus; *Biométrica* [Biometrics] – Fernando R. da Silveira; *Educação e eugenia* [Education and Eugenics] – Levi Carneiro; *Nota sobre os tipos antropológicos do Brasil* [Note on the anthropological types of Brazil] – Edgard Roquette-Pinto; *Guiandole sebacee libere della mucosa geniana in varie razze umane* [Guiding the sebaceous glands of the genian mucosa in various human races] – Alfonso Bovero; *Situação do apêndice vermiforme em relação ao céco em diversas raças humanas* [Situation of the vermiform appendix in relation to the cecum in various human races] – R. Lochi; *Considerações em torno do índice radio-pélvico de Lapiçque e túbico-pélvico de Fróes da Fonseca* [Considerations around the radio-pelvic index of Lapiçque and the tibio-pelvic index of Fróes da Fonseca] – Ermiro Lima; *Estado atual da questão dos grupos hemáticos* [Current state of the issue of blood groups] – Roberto F. Hinricksen; *Da aplasia clavicular* [On clavicular aplasia] – Benjamin Vinelli Baptista; *Genética Vegetal* [Plant Genetics] – A. J. de Sampaio; *Contribuição aos estudos dos psicogramas* [Contribution to the studies of psychograms] – Ubirajara da Rocha e Arnauld Bretas; *Estatística dos tarados no Brasil* [Statistics of mental defectives in Brazil] – Bulhões Carvalho; *Quadros demonstrativos das moléstias observadas no hospital de Juqueri, de 1925 a 1928* [Demonstrative charts of the diseases observed at the Juqueri hospital, from 1925 to 1928] – Antônio Carlos Pacheco e Silva; *Herança psíquica intrauterina* [Intrauterine psychic inheritance] – Waldemar E. Coutts; *A procriação voluntária do sexo de acordo com a época da coabitação* [The voluntary procreation of sex according to the time of cohabitation] – Jorge de Lima; *Consanguinidade* [Consanguinity] – Newton Belleza; *Casamento e eugenia* [Marriage and Eugenics] – Joaquim Moreira da Fonseca; *O dispensário psiquiátrico como elemento de educação eugênica* [The psychiatric dispensary as an element of eugenic education] – Gustavo Riedel; *Da educação física como fator eugênico* [On physical education as an eugenic factor] – Jorge de Moraes; *Fatores de degeneração observadas nas praças da Polícia Militar* [Degeneration factors observed in the squares of the Military Police] – Motta Resende; *A idade e o casamento* [Age and marriage] – Leonídio Ribeiro; *Maternidade consciente* [Conscious motherhood] – Castro Barreto; *O problema da imigração* [The immigration problem] – A. J. de Azevedo Amaral. PRIMEIRO CONGRESSO BRASILEIRO DE EUGENIA. *Actas e trabalhos*. Rio de Janeiro: [s.n.], v. 1, 1929, pp. 5-6.

The author of *Limites da eugenia* emphasized the connection between the negative eugenics model and Protestantism in the United States, pointing out that, in this country, eugenics would be playing the role that Galton had predicted twenty years earlier: becoming a “religion of humanity” through the systematization of sexuality. This fact would be evidenced in studies such as that of the American Protestant eugenicist Edward Wiggam and his advocacy of birth control, as well as in works like that of the English writer and eugenicist Anthony Ludovici, according to Ataíde, a more reactionary version of Bernard Shaw.

Unlike Wiggam, who saw eugenics as the path to the Christianization of humanity, Ludovici thought the opposite: Christianization, by encouraging the multiplication of the incapable, would be a complete denial of eugenics. Hence, the need for a religion based on the worship of the body, which would infiltrate power structures to pave the way for regeneration and, consequently, the emergence of a new man³⁸.

Driven primarily by the rejection of negative eugenics, now officially repudiated in the encyclical *Casti Connubii*, it was not only Brazilian Catholic intellectuals who denounced American eugenics. The French Jesuit theologian René Brouillard, in an article titled *L'Engénique et l'eugénisme anglo-saxons devant la morale catholique* [Eugenics and Anglo-Saxon Eugenics in the Face of Catholic Morality], published in June, 1931 in the journal *Études de théologie, de philosophie et d'histoire*, already asserted that, especially in the United States and after World War I, eugenic doctrines, not only in the field of medicine but also in jurisprudence, had deeply rooted themselves, gaining numerous followers in research and propaganda associations, in which Protestant pastors themselves were not strangers³⁹.

According to Brouillard, for radical eugenicists, the majority of the population, unaware of the laws of heredity, multiply at random, following their instincts. Therefore, believing that the mentally deficient would have a prolific potency over superior beings and consume a large portion of social wealth, it would be necessary to correct this imbalance by preventing them from reproducing, and by directing, for the benefit of individuals considered normal, financial resources intended for asylums, prisons, and hospitals,

³⁸ ATAÍDE, op. cit., *Limites da eugenia*, pp. 25-29.

³⁹ BROUILLARD, René. “L'Engénique et l'eugénisme anglo-saxons devant la morale catholique” In *Études de théologie, de philosophie et d'histoire*, pp. 596-597, 1931, p. 596.

thus violating, in a vile and dishonest manner, the Christian principles of compassion and charity⁴⁰.

In Brazil, Renato Ferraz Kehl, one of the fervent advocates and promoters of eugenics, had already expressed on several occasions his opposition to social welfare policies, based on the idea that the process of natural selection would eliminate the less adaptable individuals. According to this perspective, coordinated initiatives of assistance, health, and social security would contradict the principles of a eugenic nation, prolonging the lives of the less fit and generating additional costs for the state⁴¹:

If the inexorable law of the struggle for life still prevailed completely, under which the weak succumb and the strong triumph, most of this residue, which arises clandestinely, violating the precepts of good breeding, would be condemned to perish soon in the early stages of the harsh struggle. Unfortunately, this no longer happens, as one can no longer rely on the selection that once constituted an effective sieve against the undesirable elements, which now survive in great numbers to suffer and to burden the useful and productive elements⁴².

In the same vein as Brouillard, Tristão de Ataíde emphasized that certain practices advocated by some eugenicists mirrored the foundations of modern materialistic revolutionary mentality, contrasting with human and Christian spiritual values. Thus, he urged Catholic intellectuals to discern with precision “a very strict distinction between what is useful in it (eugenics) and what is condemnable”⁴³.

This is what needs to be obvious in the minds of integral eugenicists. There are many points on which we do not yield and will never yield. And precisely for this reason, we must

⁴⁰ Ibid., p. 597.

⁴¹ GIESBRECHT, Daniel Florence; MATOS, Patrícia Ferraz de. “A apropriação do discurso médico-antropológico pelo Poder Legislativo brasileiro: a eugenia como utopia regeneradora na constituinte de 1934” In *Revista Poiésis*, v. 16, n. 29, pp. 37–54, 2022, p. 46.

⁴² KEHL, Renato Ferraz. *Sexo e civilização: aparas eugênicas*. Rio de Janeiro: Editora Francisco Alves, 1933, p. 34. In Portuguese: “Se a lei inexorável da luta pela vida ainda se impusesse, completamente, sob a qual sucumbem os fracos e triunfam os fortes, a maior parte dessa residualha, que vem surgindo clandestinamente, violando os preceitos da boa geração, estaria condenada a perecer logo nos primeiros lances da áspera peleja. Tal, infelizmente não acontece, não mais se podendo contar com a seleção que outrora constituía o crivo eficaz contra os indesejáveis e que agora sobrevivem em grande número para sofrer e para sobrecarregar os elementos úteis e produtivos”.

⁴³ ATAÍDE, op. cit., Limites da eugenia, p. 32. In Portuguese: “uma distinção muito rigorosa entre o que há nela (na eugenia) de aproveitável e o que há de condenável”.

face eugenics within its “limits,” to prevent eugenic overreach that could easily destroy everything that represents for us the essence of our particular freedom⁴⁴.

For us, true eugenics is only achieved in alliance with true reason and true faith. We are not seeking any new religion. Nor will we allow any science or civil power to invade domains that belong to another kind of sciences and another kind of power. We are neither anarchists nor statistes. We do not believe that sexual life is entirely free. But we also do not accept state interference where it should not intervene. For there are realms that only natural law or revealed law, and not positive law, can regulate⁴⁵.

Therefore, it can be inferred that both lay Catholic intellectuals and ecclesiastics were not opposed to eugenics in its entirety, but rather to certain eugenic models that implied specific forms of social engineering interfering with the nature of human reproduction, such as birth control and sterilization. On the other hand, religious leaders endorsed and promoted a eugenic approach of a preventive, sanitary, and pro-natalist nature, as these methods were in line with the positions held by the clergy, in a sort of Catholic eugenics. This stance aligns with the social policy advocated by the Church since the times of *Rerum Novarum*, reflecting the institution’s purported commitment to the protection of human dignity and the promotion of social welfare⁴⁶.

Birth-control

In general, a considerable number of eugenicists in the Anglo-Saxon world, intending to preserve or even strengthen the racial composition

⁴⁴ Ibid., pp. 32-33. In Portuguese: “Isso é que precisa ficar bem claro na cabeça dos eugenistas integrais. Há muitos pontos em que não cedemos nem cederemos nunca. E por isso mesmo é que devemos encarar a eugenia em seus “limites”, para impedir a extralimitação eugênica que facilmente destruirá tudo o que representa para nós a essência da nossa liberdade particular”.

⁴⁵ Ibid., p. 33. In Portuguese: “Para nós, a verdadeira eugenia só se faz em aliança com a verdadeira razão e com a verdadeira fé. Nós não andamos a procura de nenhuma nova religião. Nem consentiremos que nenhuma ciência e nenhum poder civil invada domínios que cabem a outro gênero de ciências e a outro gênero de poder. Não somos nem anarquistas nem estatistas. Não julgamos que a vida sexual seja inteiramente livre. Mas também não aceitamos a ingerência do Estado onde ele não tem que intervir. Pois há recantos que só a lei natural ou a lei revelada, e não a lei positiva, podem regulamentar”.

⁴⁶ The encyclical *Rerum Novarum* is an apostolic letter issued by Pope Leo XIII in 1891, addressing the conditions of workers and the social issues resulting from the Industrial Revolution. LEÃO XIII. *Carta encíclica Rerum Novarum do sumo pontífice Papa Leão XIII sobre a condição dos operários*, Roma, 1891. (<https://www.puc-campinas.edu.br/wp-content/uploads/2016/03/NFC-Carta-Enciclica-rerum-novarum.pdf>), Last consulted 1 February 2024.

of their societies, contributed to the formation of a paradigm of negative eugenics.

This model was based on the coordinated implementation of measures aimed at altering the configuration of the family unit: the legal regulation of marriage, prohibiting it for any individual considered officially dysfunctional or inferior, through the requirement of a prenuptial certificate; divorce, to solve marital incompatibilities and eventually address issues of sterility; preventive sterilization, both voluntary and mandatory, for all individuals incapable of reproducing under satisfactory conditions, whether due to the evident inability to produce superior offspring or due to dangerous physical or moral degeneration, as seen in criminals; and finally, the control or rationalization of reproduction, aiming to improve quality over quantity, a practice commonly known as birth control⁴⁷.

According to historian Regina Marques, from a Foucauldian perspective, these guidelines granted greater authority to doctors, assigning them the role of defining what was considered normal or abnormal in relation to sexual practices. This resulted in the conception of sex as a pathological element of humanity, thus fueling the development of a medico-political project aimed at regulating aspects such as marriages, births, and even the survival of individuals⁴⁸. Therefore, it can be concluded that there is a clear conflict between radical eugenicists and Catholics, both aiming to secure control over human bodies through the manipulation of sexuality.

Regarding Brazilian Catholic intellectuals, Hamilton Nogueira had already positioned himself against biopolitical interventions aimed at controlling birth rates since the 1920s. In the article *O malthusianismo: um sério problema social que é também brasileiro* [Malthusianism: A Serious Social Problem that is also Brazilian], published in the November 1924 edition of *A Ordem*, he presented a scathing critique of the spread of so-called “neo-Malthusian fads”, which he considered degrading practices and real attacks on the nation. For Nogueira, given Brazil’s vast territorial area and small population, the country should prioritize increasing birth rates to avoid the fragmentation of national identity, rather than implementing population reduction policies promoted by advocates of birth control⁴⁹.

⁴⁷ See PICHOT, André. *La société pure: de Darwin à Hitler*. Paris: Flammarion, 2009.

⁴⁸ MARQUES, Vera Regina Beltrão. *A medicalização da raça: médicos, educadores e discurso eugênico*. Campinas: Editora da Unicamp, 1994, p. 75.

⁴⁹ NOGUEIRA, Hamilton. “O malthusianismo: um sério problema social que é também brasileiro” In *A Ordem*, v. 4, n. 37, pp. 239–240, 1924, p. 239. In Portuguese: “modismos neomalthusianos”.

Hamilton Nogueira's stance reflected the conflict between the Church and the rising militancy in favor of birth control, especially in the United States at that time. It is noteworthy that the feminist and nurse Margaret Sanger, one of the main advocates of birth control and abortion rights, wrote a controversial article in 1923 titled *Facing the New Year*, which was published in the periodical *Birth Control Review*⁵⁰. In it, Sanger clearly advocated contraceptive methods based on negative eugenic arguments and encouraged prophylactic abortion in low-income families. At a time when the Church was already cautiously monitoring feminism, views similar to Sanger's were considered a serious affront to life and human dignity.

In turn, *Ensaio de Biologia* incorporated two studies conducted by students under the guidance of Hamilton Nogueira at the Catholic Institute of Higher Studies, which addressed demographic regulation policies: *A esterilidade voluntária e sua patologia* [Voluntary Sterility and Its Pathology] by Barbosa Quental, and *Aspecto médico do birth-control* [Medical Aspect of Birth Control] by Antônio Amarante and César Girard Jacob. Both works share similar objectives, aiming to contest the main arguments presented by proponents of birth control⁵¹.

In the early decades of the 20th century, Brazil showed a significant interest in infant care⁵². Contrary to the notion that reducing birth rates would proportionally decrease infant mortality, disciples of Hamilton Nogueira emphasized the importance of hygiene and maternal and child health care as effective means to promote the health of pregnant women and reduce child mortality.

⁵⁰ SANGER, Margaret. "Facing the New Year" In *Birth Control Review*, v. 7, n. 1, pp. 3–4, 1923.

⁵¹ Barbosa Quental focused on critiquing the studies of the Scottish George Drysdale, while Antônio Amarante and César Girard Jacob took on the task of reproving the works of Margaret Sanger. AMARANTE, Antônio; JACOB, César G. "Aspecto médico do birth-control" In ATAÍDE, Tristão de (pseudônimo); NOGUEIRA, Hamilton. (Eds.). *Ensaio de Biologia*. Rio de Janeiro: Livraria Católica (Publicações do Instituto Católico de Estudos Superiores), pp. 121–147, 1933; QUENTAL, Barbosa. "A esterilidade voluntária e sua patologia" In ATAÍDE, Tristão de (pseudônimo); NOGUEIRA, Hamilton. (Eds.). *Ensaio de Biologia*. Rio de Janeiro: Livraria Católica (Publicações do Instituto Católico de Estudos Superiores), pp. 67–79, 1933.

⁵² The work of the hygienist physician Arthur Moncorvo Filho stood out for advocating the regulation and supervision of activities related to child health, based on medical-scientific knowledge, thus establishing the beginnings of pediatrics in Brazil. See WADSWORTH, James E. "Moncorvo Filho e o problema da infância: modelos institucionais e ideológicos da assistência à infância no Brasil" In *Revista Brasileira de História*, v. 19, n. 37, pp. 103–124, 1999. As Thiago da Costa Lopes and Marcos Chor Maio assert, it is important to emphasize that although the development of pediatrics in Brazil was not entirely influenced by eugenics, significant similarities were observed regarding the terminology and concepts used in both fields, many of which related to racial determinism. LOPES, Thiago da Costa; MAIO, Marcos Chor. "Puericultura, eugenia e interpretações do Brasil na construção do Departamento Nacional da Criança (1940)" In *Tempo*, v. 24, n. 2, pp. 349–368, 2018, p. 350.

In other words, they advocated for combating poverty, adopting comprehensive sanitation policies, protecting children's rights, and providing parental education through prenatal interventions to emerge as fundamental strategies not only to preserve the lives of Brazilian children but also to safeguard the fate of national identity. This alignment with the principles of preventive eugenics underscored the harmonization of Catholic principles with a proactive approach to promote health and well-being, consolidating the strategy of assuming a central role in advocating for these measures.

Therefore, it is not surprising that Amarante and Jacob cited the renowned French obstetrician and neo-Lamarckian eugenicist Adolphe Pinard⁵³ as one of the leading authorities in the field of international infant care. Moreover, Pinard was recognized for emphasizing the importance of maternity in maintaining the organic balance of the female body:

Pinard is right when he states that maternity is a normal and psychological function of woman; it is the natural termination of her sexual cycle; it is necessary for her health and development. To claim, as the advocates of birth control do, that repeated motherhood, successive pregnancies, constitute in themselves a factor of morbidity is a manifest desire to force reality⁵⁴.

Both Barbosa Quental and Antônio Amarante and César Girard Jacob stood out in questioning the notion that successive births caused harm to women's health, basing their arguments on the advances of asepsis in obstetrics at that time. The analysis revealed a close interconnection between obstetrical issues, the nature of childbirth, and female physiology, suggesting that motherhood should not be considered a pathological condition.

However, according to Amarante and Jacob, even more concerning than issues related to the dangers of pregnancy were the lack of mention by neo-Malthusians of the universally damaging effects of contraceptive methods. Based on the analyses of the Catholic Belgian obstetrician Raoul

⁵³ In addition to Pinard, they cited Raoul de Guchteneere, the surgeon Jean-Louis Faure, the French physician Armand Siredey, the Dutch gynecologist Theodoor Hendrik van de Velde, the physician Giuseppe Catani from the Maggiore Hospital in Milan, the French neurologist Joseph Grasset, Hamilton Nogueira, the American nurse Mary Sewall Gardner, the Irish physician and nutritionist Robert McCarrison, and the British surgeon William Arbuthnot Lane.

⁵⁴ AMARANTE; JACOB, op. cit., p. 133. In Portuguese: "Pinard tem razão quando afirma que a maternidade é uma função normal e psicológica da mulher; ela é a terminação natural do seu ciclo sexual; é necessária à sua saúde e ao seu desenvolvimento. Pretender, como fazem os apologistas do birth-control, que as maternidades repetidas, as sucessivas gestações, constituam por si sós um fator de morbidade é vontade manifesta de forçar a realidade".

de Guchteneere, the main aspects of a research report conducted in New York and published in 1924 in the *American Review of Obstetrics and Gynecology* were highlighted, casting doubt on the foundations of reproduction control⁵⁵.

In summary, Guchteneere concluded that data from research on exogenous regulation of fecundity were limited, resulting in a favorable classification by mere assumption, while the investigations lacked recognized scientific and moral methods of value. He initially highlighted the absence of a completely safe and effective contraceptive method to date. Moreover, it was observed that contraceptive methods did not achieve effectiveness when applied to poorer families or less privileged socioeconomic classes. Finally, the divergence of medical opinions was evident due to the lack of proper clinical experimentation and the challenge to data published by clinics in New York and London⁵⁶.

By relying on Guchteneere's statements, Amarante and Jacob seemingly adopted the Galilean method as a strategy to counter proponents of birth control⁵⁷. By challenging the effectiveness of contraceptive methods and highlighting the limitations of research on fecundity regulation, the authors indirectly challenged certain scientific narratives, portraying them as conjectures or assumptions. At the same time, they contradicted them, relying on other scientific evidence, now validated by Catholic medical authorities, such as the eminent Belgian obstetrician.

By doing so, they sought to instill doubts in readers about the validity of scientific discoveries related to reproductive control. This approach questioned established scientific conclusions and weakened the dominant medical discourse on contraceptive methods, suggesting that such conclusions could be mere speculations or subjective interpretations of facts.

In the dispute between the Catholic Church and radical eugenicists, the intricate web of discursive mechanisms in operation was revealed⁵⁸. The Church, relying on its norms of truth and legitimacy, aimed to impose its view

⁵⁵ *Ibid.*, p. 138.

⁵⁶ *Ibid.*, p. 139.

⁵⁷ The author of this article adopted as a basis for naming this strategy the famous case of Galileo Galilei, who faced opposition from the Catholic Church for advocating the heliocentric theory. Part of the tactic against the Florentine physicist and astronomer involved questioning whether what he offered was certain and demonstrated knowledge or merely hypothesis(es). Therefore, the most uncomfortable scientific propositions, from the ecclesiastical standpoint, should be treated more as hypotheses and, therefore, disregarded.

⁵⁸ FOUCAULT, Michel. *A ordem do discurso: aula inaugural no Collège de France, pronunciada em 2 de dezembro de 1970*. São Paulo: Edições Loyola, 2012.

on sexuality and reproduction, sanctioning discourses that were in line with its precepts and excluding those that challenged its moral authority. On the other hand, eugenicists, backed by the alleged objectivity of science, sought to establish their norms of truth, challenging ecclesiastical authority and seeking to legitimize their conceptions within the scientific realm. This struggle for dominance of discourse transcended the realm of ideas and permeated power structures and social relations, highlighting the mechanisms of power, sanction, exclusion, and internalization that shaped the discourses of the time.

Eugenic sterilization

Voluntary and compulsory sterilization were highly controversial topics involving radical eugenicists and the Church, as previously mentioned. During the 1920s and 1930s, eugenic sterilization became relevant in various scientific publications as well as in political debates. In response, the Church expressed concern and unequivocally rejected this intervention in the natural course of the life creation process. It is understandable, for example, as observed in the twenty-fourth session of *Casti Connubii*, that there was a severe condemnation of the imposition of sterilization as a punitive measure⁵⁹.

Robert Wegner and Vanderlei Sebastião de Souza indicate that the attraction exerted by the most extreme eugenic ideas, aimed at preventing the procreation of people considered abnormal, found resonance among certain Brazilian eugenicists, mainly from the late twenties onwards. In *Lições de eugenia* [Lessons of Eugenics], a book published in 1929, Renato Kehl highlighted the relevance of sterilization as a fundamental measure of racial prophylaxis, which, according to him, should be recommended for individuals exhibiting criminal, abnormal, unfit behaviors, or showing any other sign of degeneration⁶⁰.

The sympathy and propaganda promoted by Renato Kehl in favor of sterilization were the target of severe and direct criticism from Hamilton Nogueira in *Educação eugênica* [Eugenic Education], an article in issue number 28 of *A Ordem*, in June 1932⁶¹. The text in question was a reply to the first volume of the bulletin published by the Brazilian Central Commission on Eugenics, an organization inspired by the model of the German Society for Racial Hygiene, founded by Kehl in 1931.

⁵⁹ PIO XI, op. cit., p. 17.

⁶⁰ WEGNER; SOUZA, op. cit., pp. 268-269.

⁶¹ NOGUEIRA, Hamilton. "Educação eugênica" In *A Ordem*, v. 7, n. 28 (Nova Série), p. 408-411, 1932a.

Nogueira judged that those responsible for the bulletin adopted a simplistic and vulgar perspective regarding the understanding of human life by postulating that all activities carried out by men and women, whether physical, intellectual, moral, or social, were intrinsically linked to the biological laws of heredity in the pursuit of improvement. Furthermore, the presentation of eugenics by Renato Kehl as a universal solution and a pedestal of the religion aimed at the integral regeneration of humanity was considered by Nogueira a direct affront to the clergy and Catholics in general⁶².

Hamilton Nogueira's concerns were not merely occasional. In addition to Kehl's eugenic leadership, other Brazilian eugenicists were also interested in negative eugenic measures and, through various forms of communication such as pamphlets, articles, lectures, and interviews, disseminated these convictions. Octávio Domingues, a geneticist who would later share the direction of the Eugenics Bulletin with Renato Kehl and entomologist Salvador de Toledo Pizza Júnior, wrote an article titled "*Birth-control*", *esterilização e pena de morte* ["Birth-control", Sterilization, and Capital Punishment], which illustrated well the reasons for the concerns of Catholic intellectuals about eugenic propaganda:

The compulsory sterilization of delinquents, mentally disturbed individuals, and those with hereditary diseases—though not compulsory in the latter case—is another defensive measure for society. Through such means, society would see a decrease in the proliferation of the caste of natural-born criminals, the caste of the mentally disturbed, the caste of those who transmit bad heritages and fatal afflictions that people receive from birth and disseminate them into other cradles indefinitely⁶³.

⁶² Ibid., p. 408. The criticisms of the eugenic extremism advocated by Renato Kehl were not limited to Brazilian Catholic intellectuals. The respected intellectual and Jesuit priest from Portugal, Domingos Maurício Gomes dos Santos, known by the pseudonym Riba Leça, expressed his criticisms of Kehl's calls for eugenic sterilization in an article published in the Jesuit magazine *Brotéria* in April 1934. In his text, Riba Leça disapproved of the relevance of a lecture given by Kehl, at the invitation of the renowned anthropologist and eugenicist Antônio Mendes Correia, at the headquarters of the Portuguese Society of Anthropology and Ethnology, in the city of Porto, on October 24, 1932: "Dr. Renato Kehl delivered [...] a lecture on eugenic policy. But, to be frank and without disparagement, we consider it exceedingly unfortunate, both in its tendency, intention, and content". In Portuguese: "O Dr. Renato Kehl pronunciou [...] uma conferência sobre política eugênica. Mas, para sermos francos e sem desprimor, reputamos infelicíssima, pela tendência, pela intenção e pelo conteúdo". LEÇA, Riba (pseudônimo). "Esterilização e eugenismo" In *Brotéria. Revista Contemporânea de Cultura*, v. 13, n. 3, pp. 217-226, 1934, pp. 217-218.

⁶³ DOMINGUES, Octávio. "Birth Control", Esterilização e Pena de Morte" In *Boletim de Eugenia*, Ano 3. n. 30, 1931, p. 4. In Portuguese: "A esterilização obrigatória para os delinquentes, tarados mentais, com extensão os portadores de males hereditários, mas neste caso sem caráter compulsório - é outra providência de natureza defensiva para a sociedade que, por tal meio, veria diminuir a proliferação da casta dos

In the October 1932 issue of the magazine *A Ordem*, Hamilton Nogueira revisited his criticisms of advocates for sterilization in an article titled *A esterilização dos inaptos* [The Sterilization of the Useless], once again expressing his direct disapproval of Renato Kehl and his followers: “Men and women, even from a eugenic standpoint, are not merely, as Mr. Renato Kehl defines them, ‘hooks for germ cells’, as if we could do without the other attributes that give them primacy among created beings”⁶⁴.

Since the late 1920s, several studies emerged aimed at questioning the convictions about the absolute accuracy of heredity studies promoted by eugenicists adhering to Mendelian theories. An example is the work titled *La blastotoxie qui crée les dégénérescences individuelles est aussi l’origine de l’hérédité morbide* [The blastotoxia which creates individual degenerations is also the origin of morbid heredity], published in 1928 by the Belgian physician Louis Vervaeck, Director-General of the Belgian Criminal Anthropology Service⁶⁵.

Vervaeck argued that diagnosing the likelihood of familial transmission of the most dangerous characteristics of certain groups of patients and anomalies was difficult, if not impossible, due to the complexity of factors, including the uncertainty of human heredity laws, the possibility of latency of dangerous tendencies in direct descendants, and their possible extinction in subsequent generations, influenced by various factors such as living conditions, appropriate therapeutic interventions, and proper education⁶⁶.

Furthermore, the study suggests that when considering cases of individuals classified as unfit due to factors such as toxins or traumas in the embryonic phase, it was notable that the number of hereditary diseases did not present such an alarming figure when compared to healthy individuals, especially when there was a considerable percentage of people with mental disabilities from parents with no history of genetic diseases⁶⁷.

According to Hamilton Nogueira’s perspective, even in the face of reliable evidence, exemplified by Louis Vervaeck, adherents of “Galtonian

criminosos natos, da casta dos tarados mentais, da casta dos transmissores das más heranças e dos males fatais que o homem recebe do berço, e os dissemina por outros berços indefinidamente”.

⁶⁴ NOGUEIRA, Hamilton. “Esterilização dos inaptos” In *A Ordem*, v. 7, n. 32 (Nova Série), pp. 251–258, 1932b, p. 253. In Portuguese: “O homem e a mulher, mesmo do ponto de vista eugênico, não são apenas, como os define o Sr. Renato Kehl, ‘cabides de células germinais’, como se pudéssemos prescindir dos outros atributos que lhes dão o primado entre os seres criados”.

⁶⁵ VARVAECK, Louis. “La blastotoxie qui crée les dégénérescences individuelles est aussi l’origine de l’hérédité morbide” In *Beuxelles-Med*, v. 9, pp. 61-70, 1928.

⁶⁶ *Ibid.*, p. 63.

⁶⁷ *Ibid.*, pp. 63-64.

science” in Brazil showed considerable interest in the institutionalization of sterilization for punitive and racialistic purposes, as already documented in nations like the United States, England, and Switzerland. These adherents were deeply entrenched in the “rigorous determinism of the biological laws of heredity” and, in an attempt to persuade political authorities, proposed that “for the good of society and the human species, the State authorize the application of processes that prevent the undesirable procreation” of individuals deemed deviant⁶⁸.

In *Ensaio de Biologia*, Hamilton Nogueira would present an expanded version, based on the two previously mentioned texts, titled *A esterilização dos tarados* [The sterilization of Preverts]⁶⁹. In the new version of his study, Nogueira reiterated his previous arguments to challenge proponents of sterilization, expanding his criticisms to the eugenics practiced in the United States. The purpose of this stratagem was to highlight, through the American example, the harms resulting from racial interpretations based on polygenic premises⁷⁰.

According to the author, such ideas neglected the biological phenomenon of adaptation inherent in human beings. Nogueira argued that eugenic practice in the United States, primarily aimed at preserving the American race by reducing the birth rate, was contributing to the emergence of extreme nationalism. This nationalism was characterized by the fanaticism of predominant racism, especially in the southern regions of the country, where white supremacists, influenced by negative eugenics, advocated for the compulsory sterilization of Blacks and immigrants, particularly those of Asian origin⁷¹.

Just like previously observed in the study conducted by Antônio Amarante and César Girard Jacob, Hamilton Nogueira also seemed to adopt the Galilean method, raising uncertainties about the absolute validity of the propositions advocated by American eugenicists. He intended to provoke questioning regarding the infallibility of the postulates presented, especially

⁶⁸ NOGUEIRA, op. cit., *A esterilização dos inaptos*, p. 253. In Portuguese: “rigoroso determinismo das leis biológicas da hereditariedade”; “para o bem da sociedade e da espécie humana, o Estado autorizasse a aplicação de processos que impedissem a procriação indesejável”.

⁶⁹ NOGUEIRA, Hamilton. “A esterilização dos tarados” In ATAÍDE, Tristão de (pseudônimo); NOGUEIRA, Hamilton (Eds.). *Ensaio de Biologia*. Rio de Janeiro: Livraria Católica (Publicações do Instituto Católico de Estudos Superiores), pp. 39-66, 1933.

⁷⁰ The polygenists based their theory on the conception that humanity had multiple origins, resulting in the vast racial diversity observed at different stages of evolution.

⁷¹ *Ibid.*, pp. 39-41.

through the genealogical analyses used by eugenicists, suggesting that such assertions were not incontrovertible truths but rather speculative conjectures, emphasizing, whenever possible, the abuses, and deficiencies observed in places where eugenic sterilization had been previously implemented:

Well, those who devote themselves to these studies (genealogical) know well how much uncertainty, how much unpredictability is observed in the mechanism of heredity. And if this mechanism is already so uncertain in animals, it is even more so in relation to the human person. And it is this very uncertainty that causes certain hygienists and eugenicists to condemn the application of extreme measures such as the one we are considering⁷². According to its public hygiene committee, the New York Academy of Medicine opines that “the question of sterilization of certain types of mental alienates has not made great progress, for two reasons. Firstly, there is a general prevention against sterilization because of the difficulties and possible abuses that inevitably accompany its application; on the other hand, opinions concerning the heredity of mental disturbances are very divergent; there is no agreement on this subject among specialists” [...] Moreover, these abuses have already been verified even in some states of North America, which hastily adopted the opinions of radical eugenicists, and contributed to the repeal, in some of these states, of the laws that supported sterilizing interventions. Thus in New Jersey, in Nevada, in New York, in Colorado, in Ohio⁷³.

With the clear intention of strictly endorsing social interventions of environmental and educational nature, Hamilton Nogueira’s work, as well as the other texts in *Ensaio de Biologia*, aimed to overcome the ambiguities

⁷²Ibid., p. 46. In Portuguese: “Ora, aqueles que se dedicam a esses estudos (genealógicos) sabem bem quanto de incerto, quanto de imprevisível se observa no mecanismo da hereditariedade. E se esse mecanismo já é tão incerto nos animais, muito mais o é com relação à pessoa humana. E é essa incerteza mesma que faz com que certos higienistas e eugenistas condenem a aplicação de medidas extremas como a que estamos considerando”.

⁷³Ibid., pp. 56-57. In Portuguese: “Pela sua comissão de higiene pública, opina a Academia de Medicina de New-York, que “a questão da esterilização de certos tipos de alienados mentais não fez grandes progressos, por duas razões. Primeiramente, existe uma prevenção geral contra a esterilização por causa das dificuldades e dos abusos possíveis que acompanham fatalmente sua aplicação; por outro lado as opiniões concernentes à hereditariedade das perturbações mentais são muito divergentes; não há, sobre esse assunto, nenhuma espécie de acordo entre os especialistas” [...] Aliás, esses abusos já foram verificados mesmo em alguns Estados da América do Norte, que adotaram, apressadamente, as opiniões dos eugenistas radicais, e concorreram para revogação, em alguns desses Estados, das leis que amparavam as intervenções esterilizadoras. Assim em New Jersey, em Nevada, em New York, no Colorado, em Ohio”.

caused by the spread of modern scientific thought. In other words, it sought to address, through science itself, the problems arising from the transgression of ethical and moral boundaries by advocates (in this case, radical eugenicists) of materialistic conceptions opposed to the Christian perception of the human being. This debate was not limited only to sterilization, but also, for example, to euthanasia, neo-Malthusian birth control, and abortion, especially regarding the intervention of the State in these matters.

Conclusion

The analysis of the controversies between radical eugenicists and Catholic intellectuals in Brazil during the early decades of the 20th century reveals a complex and multifaceted landscape, permeated by heated debates and deep ideological divergences. At the heart of these discussions lies the clash between distinct worldviews that were reflected not only in conceptions of eugenics but also in perceptions of human nature, the role of the state, and the ethical limits of scientific intervention.

The emergence of a kind of Catholic eugenics represents one of the most striking points of this period, highlighting the influence of the Catholic Church in formulating and disseminating preventive eugenic measures. By advocating for eugenics based on the principles of Latin eugenics, the Church positioned itself as a voice in the search for solutions that reconciled scientific advances with the moral and ethical values of Catholicism.

The use of the Galilean method by Catholic intellectuals as a strategy to question the certainties defended by radical eugenicists proves to be a shrewd approach. By raising questions about the full validity of eugenic propositions and emphasizing the importance of uncertainty and inquiry in the context of scientific research, Catholics sought to undermine the thesis propagated by radical eugenicists, exemplified by those advocated by Renato Kehl, considered a grave affront to human life and dignity.

The clash between radical eugenicists and Catholics also revealed fundamental differences in the conception of human nature and the role of the state in society. While eugenicists grounded their proposals in a utilitarian and deterministic view of humanity, Catholics emphasized the importance of morality and ethics in guiding public policies, rejecting any form of instrumentalization of the human being for supposed collective objectives.

These ideological and ethical divergences shed light on the challenges faced by Brazilian society in seeking solutions to complex issues such as eugenics. By confronting the limits of science and technology, as well as the ethical, discursive, and moral dilemmas associated with state intervention in the lives of citizens, debates on eugenics in Brazil offer important lessons for the present and the future.

In summary, the study of the history of eugenics in Brazil prompts deep reflections on fundamental issues related to human nature, morality, and ethics in science and society. By exploring the controversies and complexities of this historical period, we are prompted to consider how eugenic ideas shaped both scientific thought, public policies and social relations.

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To create perfect citizens for a masculine, strong, and virtuous Republic]: the First National Feminist and Education Congress in Lisbon (1924) and the modernization of inequality¹

“Criar cidadãos perfeitos para uma República máscula, forte e virtuosa”: o Primeiro Congresso Nacional Feminista e de Educação em Lisboa (1924) e a modernização da desigualdade

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Abstract

Organized by the Conselho Nacional das Mulheres Portuguesas [National Council of Portuguese Women – CNMP], the Primeiro Congresso Feminista e de Educação [First Feminist and Education Congress] took place between the 4th and 9th of May 1924, in Lisbon. On the occasion, some theses were presented and discussed on topics related to political and civic rights, education, social assistance, hygiene, and women’s health. Taking advantage of the centenary of this Congress, we propose a historicized analysis of the event, especially some of the theses, which mobilizes reflections on the intrinsic relationships between a certain feminism and a hygienist nation project, focused on improving the race. Without wanting to reduce feminist expressions from the beginning of the 20th century to a rigid definition – even because the conflicts within the CNMP point to various positions regarding the emancipation of the female sex –, we intend to draw attention, as Susan Besse well outlined in the study the Brazilian case, for a “modernization of inequality”. For this historian, marriage, sexuality, motherhood, and female education – themes recurrently present in feminist discussions in the late 19th century and in the first decades of the 20th century – acquired enormous importance, since “clean reproduction” was considered a way to overcome the backwardness and degeneration of certain

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nations. Our hypothesis is that the institutional feminism represented by the CNMP, by claiming dignity and equality of opportunity for women, found a place in the ingenious project of social reform based on eugenic precepts, supported mainly through medical-anthropological discourse. In this, “the woman” was called upon to carry the heavy burden of civilizing her family, assuming a fundamental role for the State, although conservative: that of wife and mother, educated to manage the home and to create “perfect citizens for a masculine, strong, and virtuous Republic” – words by Julieta Ribeiro, author of the thesis *A mulher naturista* [The naturist woman].

Keywords: Feminism. National Council of Portuguese Women. Eugenics. Biopower. Lisbon/Portugal.

Resumo

Organizado pelo Conselho Nacional das Mulheres Portuguesas (CNMP), o Primeiro Congresso Feminista e de Educação ocorreu entre os dias 4 e 9 de maio de 1924, em Lisboa. Na ocasião, foram apresentadas e discutidas teses que versaram sobre temáticas relacionadas aos direitos políticos e cívicos, à educação, à assistência social, à higiene e saúde da mulher. Aproveitando a efeméride, propomos uma análise historicizada do evento, especialmente de algumas das teses, que mobilize reflexões sobre as relações intrínsecas entre certo feminismo e um projeto de nação higienista, focado no aprimoramento da raça. Sem querer reduzir as expressões feministas do início do século XX a uma definição engessada – mesmo porque os conflitos no interior do CNMP apontam para uma variedade de posturas relativamente à emancipação do sexo feminino –, pretendemos chamar a atenção, tal qual Susan Besse bem delineou ao estudar o caso brasileiro, para uma “modernização da desigualdade”. Para a historiadora, o casamento, a sexualidade, a maternidade e a educação feminina – temáticas recorrentemente presentes nas discussões feministas do final dos Oitocentos e nas primeiras décadas do século XX – adquiriram enorme importância, uma vez que a “reprodução limpa” foi encarada como forma de superar o atraso e a degeneração de determinadas nações. Assim, nossa hipótese é a de que o feminismo institucional representado pelo CNMP, ao reivindicar dignidade e igualdade de oportunidade às mulheres, encontrou lugar no engenhoso projeto de reforma social fundamentada em preceitos eugênicos, sustentados, principalmente, através do discurso médico-anropológico. Neste, “a mulher” foi convocada a carregar o pesado fardo de civilizar sua família, assumindo um papel fundamental ao Estado, embora conservador: o de esposa e mãe, educada para administrar o lar e criar “cidadãos perfeitos para uma República máscula, forte e virtuosa” – palavras de Julieta Ribeiro, autora da tese *A mulher naturista*.

Palavras-chave: Feminismo. Conselho Nacional das Mulheres Portuguesas. Eugenia. Biopoder. Lisboa/Portugal.

Introduction

In issues 2 and 3 of *Alma Feminina* [Feminine Soul], the official bulletin of the Conselho Nacional das Mulheres Portuguesas [National Council of Portuguese Women], corresponding to the months of January and February 1924, a call was published for an event that would be held for the first time in Portugal, in the capital city of Lisbon: the Primeiro Congresso Feminista e de Educação [First Feminist and Education Congress]². The aim of the endeavor, according to the Organizing Committee, was “to discuss and explore feminist and educational principles, which are so closely related”³. The same bulletin also published the names of the members of the Organizing Committee, a set of regulations, and a list of the titles and respective authors of the theses already submitted—all related to the event that, in principle, would take place in March of that same year⁴.

On the centenary of the Primeiro Congresso Feminista e de Educação, we propose a historicized analysis of the event that seeks to foster reflections, particularly on the intrinsic relationships between a certain type of feminism and a hygienist nation-building project, with a focus on the improvement of the race. To this end, we will draw on sources related to the event, such as the *Relatório* [Report] and the *Homenagem às Relatoras das Teses do Primeiro Congresso Feminista e de Educação* [Tribute to the Rapporteurs of the Theses of the First Feminist and Education Congress], written by Arnaldo Brazão; the special issues of *Alma Feminina* dedicated to the congress; as well as the brochures of the theses that we are most interested in highlighting.

This article, developed in co-authorship, is also the result of portions of two ongoing doctoral theses that interact in aspects particularly related to the intersection between feminism and eugenics in the context of the first half of the 20th century. Thus, we take advantage of the dialogic potential of the previously referenced sources, giving special attention to the theses that were explicitly developed based on eugenic principles. These include: *Abolicionismo* [Abolitionism], by Arnaldo Brazão; *Educação Sexual* [Sexual Education], by

² CONSELHO NACIONAL DAS MULHERES PORTUGUESAS. “Sem título” In *Alma Feminina: Boletim Oficial do Conselho Nacional das Mulheres Portuguesas*, Lisboa, V. VIII, n. 2 e 3, p. 5, 1924.

³ *Ibid.* In Portuguese: “discutir e ventilar princípios feministas e educativos e que tão intimamente se relacionam”.

⁴ The Organizing Committee postponed it until May following several requests from teachers to hold it during the Easter holidays”. COSTA, C. Rosa. *História do Conselho Nacional das Mulheres Portuguesas (1914-1947)*. Lisboa: Tinta da China, 2021, p. 144. In Portuguese: “em virtude de ter recebido ‘vários pedidos de professoras da província para se transferir a realização para as férias da Páscoa”.

Paulina Luisi; *A luta Anti-Alcoólica nas Escolas* [The Anti-Alcohol Struggle in Schools], by Adelaide Cabete; *A Mulher Naturista* [The Naturist Woman], by Julieta Ribeiro; and *Educação dos Indígenas nas Colônias e suas Vantagens* [The Education of Indigenous Peoples in the Colonies and Its Advantages], by Domingas Lazary do Amaral. From this selection, we also incorporate into our analyses other publications by the aforementioned rapporteurs, in an attempt to more consistently understand their respective arguments.

Although feminism has never been a homogeneous movement, expressing in various ways its discomfort with the limitations and inconsistencies of a liberal model consolidated by the development of capitalism, it was revolutionary, even in its liberal form, especially in the context of the last decades of the 19th century through the early decades of the 20th century. It sparked reflections on the possibilities afforded to women in society, demanding dignity and certain rights. However, as Fabíola Rohden aptly noted, “the relations between the genders constitute a fundamental knot around which a series of indispensable precepts for life in society are articulated”⁵, feminism was perceived as a threat, especially when represented by women who linked gender oppression to other forms of violence, such as those related to class and race.

This movement, therefore, prompted various attitudes, some of an antifeminist character—more overt and, perhaps, easier to identify and analyze—and others more complex, which seemingly aimed to reconcile women’s political demands with the collective needs of the period. Theologians, jurists, and physicians were actively involved in theorizing about feminism while also striving to reaffirm the foundations of the difference between men and women⁶. Furthermore, these “translators of natural designs”⁷ insisted heavily on the idea of the complementarity of the sexes—and thus, on heterosexuality—which they deemed fundamental to the proper progress of both individual and national development. As a result, some feminists, whether for strategic reasons or due to their belief in a more individualistic

⁵ ROHDEN, Fabíola. *Uma Ciência da Diferença: Sexo e Gênero na Medicina da Mulher*. Rio de Janeiro: Editora da FIOCRUZ, 2001, p. 13. In Portuguese: “as relações entre os gêneros constituem um nóculo fundamental em torno do qual se articula uma série de preceitos indispensáveis para a vida em sociedade”.

⁶ Below, we list some examples authored by Portuguese theologian, jurist, and physician, respectively: SILVA, M. Abúndio da. *Feminismo e Ação Feminina: Cartas à uma Senhora*. Braga: Cruz & Cia, 1912; MOURA, Carneiro de. *A Mulher e a Civilização*. Lisboa: Seção Editorial da Companhia Nacional Editora, 1900; ALMEIDA, Jaime Pereira de. *Elementos para o Estudo da Condição Física e Intelectual da Mulher*. Porto: Tip. Do Porto Médico de Magalhães & Figueiredo, 1907.

⁷ ROHDEN, op. cit., p. 15. In Portuguese: “tradutores dos desígnios naturais”.

definition of feminism—focused on individual achievements, for instance—became involved in this proposal, which ultimately dressed inequality in a modern guise. We draw this idea from Susan Besse, a Brazil specialist who, in studying gender relations in Brazil during the first half of the 20th century, observed that:

Increasingly secular in their thinking, urban modernizers imagined that progress was achieved through the application of modern scientific theories [...]. The enormous influence of eugenics—both a “science” and a social movement concerned with the improvement of the “race”—was focused on reproduction as a mean to overcome the supposed “backwardness” and “degeneration” of the country. Thus, marriage, sexuality, motherhood, and female education [expensive topics to the feminism of those time] took on huge importance from their point of view⁸.

Despite certain advances, particularly related to access to education and professional careers experienced by a fraction of predominantly affluent women, the essential social role of women was maintained: reproduction. Moreover, and perhaps as a way to grant women a civic responsibility that would remove them from the position of eternal wards, they were burdened with the heavy task of sanitizing their homes, aiding in the fight against alcoholism, so-called venereal diseases, sexual perversions, etc. Thus, while there was an effort to uncover the scientific nature of women’s role in the evolutionary progress of the race, feminist movements were placed under masculine surveillance and guidance. As Anne McClintock aptly summarized in her analysis of the Men and Women’s Club, a Darwinist English group founded by the statistician and mathematician Karl Pearson, “Feminism was considered a product of evolution, necessary but dangerously volatile”⁹.

⁸ BESSE, Susan K. *Modernizando a Desigualdade: Reestruturação da Ideologia de Gênero no Brasil, 1914-1940*. São Paulo: EDUSP, 1999, p. 3. In Portuguese: “De pensamento cada vez mais secular, os modernizadores urbanos imaginavam que o progresso se realizava mediante a aplicação das modernas teorias científicas [...]. A enorme influência da eugenia — ao mesmo tempo “ciência” e movimento social preocupado com o aperfeiçoamento da “raça” — concentrava-se na reprodução como forma de superar os supostos “atraso” e “degeneração” do país. Assim, casamento, sexualidade, maternidade e educação feminina [temas caros ao feminismo da altura] assumiram, a seus olhos, enorme importância”.

⁹ MCCLINTOCK, Anne. *Couro Imperial: Raça, Gênero e Sexualidade no Embate Colonial*. Campinas: Editora da Unicamp, 2010, p. 413. In Portuguese: “O feminismo era visto como criado da evolução, necessário, mas perigosamente volúvel”. An example of a similar club is the Heterodoxy Club in the United States, founded in 1912 in Greenwich Village, New York. This club included prominent feminists, activists, and intellectuals, promoting debates on women’s rights, suffrage, education, sexuality, and social reforms. Some of its members, like many feminists and social reformers of the early 20th century, were sympathetic

The Primeiro Congresso Feminista e de Educação, 80 and 100 years later

Organized by the Conselho Nacional das Mulheres Portuguesas (CNMP), then chaired by the physician Adelaide Cabete, the Primeiro Congresso Feminista e de Educação was held from May 4 to 9, 1924, at the premises of the Associação de Socorros Mútuos dos Empregados no Comércio de Lisboa [Association of Mutual Aid for Employees in Commerce of Lisbon]¹⁰. Finally, imitating a gesture popularized at least since the early days of feminist associativism, the members of the organization and some of their supporters intended, with this event, to celebrate the tenth anniversary of the CNMP—an organization considered by Arnaldo Brazão, Cabete’s nephew, as the only Portuguese women’s association to debate the feminist issue¹¹. It is important to note that the initiative was, in the words of the lawyer, “crowned with great success and applauded by figures of the highest social standing”, receiving commendations from the Chamber of Deputies and the Senate¹². The Congress featured well-known public figures as session presidents, including Bernardino Machado, Magalhães Lima, Abranches Ferrão, and Barbosa de Magalhães. The President of the Republic himself, Manuel Teixeira Gomes, presided over the inaugural session, concluding it with a speech:

to eugenic ideas, believing in the improvement of the human race through the conscious selection of desirable traits. This belief was common among those advocating for birth control, reproductive health, and women’s rights, seeing eugenics as a way to improve the social and biological conditions of the population. See: WITTENSTEIN, Kate. E. *The Heterodoxy Club and American Feminism (1912-1930)*. Dissertation (Doctor of Philosophy)—Boston: Boston University, 1989.

¹⁰ Issues related to the regeneration of the Portuguese race constituted a central motivator for the implementation of projects during the first decades of the 20th century. A notable example occurred a hundred years ago, in 1924, when the Portuguese Liga Portuguesa de Profilaxia Social [League of Social Prophylaxis] was founded in Porto by Dr. António Emílio de Magalhães, along with Drs. Cândido Henrique Gil da Costa and Arnaldo Cândido Veiga Pires. This civil association, which is still active, initially committed itself to spreading hygiene principles, combating venereal diseases, alcoholism, cancer, and tuberculosis, promoting proper care for the mentally ill, ensuring workplace hygiene, and fostering childcare. VIEIRA, Ismael Cerqueira. “Em prol do bem comum”: o contributo da Liga Portuguesa de Profilaxia Social para a Educação Higiénica no Porto (1924-1960)” In *CEM Cultura, Espaço & Memória*, n. 5, 2014, p. 20. In its programs, the use of terminologies such as “improvement”, “healthy constitution”, and the fight against “physical degeneration”, including syphilis and alcoholism, as well as the emphasis on childcare, reveals the almost eugenic nature of this institution. Although eugenics was not explicitly mentioned in the founding statutes, these objectives reflect a concern with the enhancement and health of the population, aligning with the eugenic ideals of the time. PROGRAMA DA LIGA PORTUGUESA DE PROFILAXIA SOCIAL In *Boletim da Liga Portuguesa de Profilaxia Social*, n. 1. Porto: Empresa Industrial Gráfica do Porto, p. 6-9, 1929.

¹¹ BRAZÃO, Arnaldo. *O Primeiro Congresso Feminista e de Educação (Relatório)*. Lisboa: Edições Spartacus, 1925, p. 1.

¹² *Ibid.*, p. 11. In Portuguese: “coroadada do melhor êxito e teve a aplaudi-la figuras da mais alta representação social”.

I believe it was wise to choose the title Feminist and Education Congress for this women's assembly. For a long time now, women have played a more direct role in guiding societies; since they became the educators of men, they have been earning the respect of all of us. The women entrusted with the education of our children have the right to participate in the public life of their country.

[...] Do not worry about what is happening abroad. Reforms must be subordinated to the spirit of our nationality, and we must shape the great Feminist movement within the bounds of Portuguese traditions¹³.

Dozens of national and foreign organizations supported and congratulated the CNMP's initiative, as did individuals such as Carolina Michaëlis de Vasconcelos, Norton de Matos, Fernão Boto Machado, and the physicians Célia and Ambrosina de Almeida Leite. During the Congress, twenty-five theses were discussed, which, according to Brazão's interpretation, "explored issues of Law, Hygiene, Education, Sociology, and Criminology"¹⁴.

¹³ Ibid., pp. 43–44. In Portuguese: "Acho que fizeram bem em escolher o título do Congresso Feminista e de Educação para esta assembleia feminina. Há muito tempo que as mulheres têm uma ação mais direta na orientação das sociedades; desde que passaram a ser a educadora do homem se vêm impondo à consideração de todos nós. As mulheres a quem está confiada a educação dos nossos filhos têm o direito de intervir na vida pública do seu país. [...] Não se preocupem com o que se passa lá fora. As reformas têm que ser subordinadas ao espírito da nossa nacionalidade e acomodamos a grande jornada do Feminismo no limite dos moldes portugueses".

¹⁴ Ibid., p. 15. In Portuguese: "ventilaram questões de Direito, Higiene, Educação, Sociologia e Criminologia". Titles of the theses and their respective authors, in order of presentation, according to the Report by Arnaldo Brazão: *Reivindicações políticas da mulher portuguesa* [Political Demands of Portuguese Women], Aurora de Castro Gouveia; *Bibliotecas infantis* [Children's Libraries], Ilda Pinto de Lima; *As pensões de estudantes* [Student Scholarships], Tito de Sousa Larcher; *A mulher na administração dos municípios* [Women in Municipal Administration], Isabel Correia Manso; *Assistência e educação à infância desvalida* [Assistance and Education for Underprivileged Children], A. C. Amaral Frazão; *Nacionalidade da mulher casada* [Nationality of Married Woman], Jaime Gouveia; *Assistência às delinquentes* [Assistance to Delinquents], Angélica Porto; *A educação dos anormais* [Education of the Abnormal], Deolinda Lopes Vieira; *Assistência e trabalho* [Assistance and Work], Maria O'Neill; *A influência da mulher na extinção da mendicância* [The Influence of Women in the Eradication of Begging], Jorge das Neves Larcher; *A luta anti-alcoólica nas escolas* [The Anti-Alcoholism Campaign in Schools], Adelaide Cabete; *Escolas ao ar livre* [Open-Air Schools], Regina do Carmo; *A mulher como educadora* [Women as Educators] Albertina Gambôa; *Situação da mulher casada nas relações matrimoniais dos bens de casal* [The Status of Married Woman in Marital Property Relations], Aurora Gouveia; *Educação dos indígenas nas colônias e suas vantagens* [Education of Indigenous in the Colonies and Its Advantages], Domingas Lazary Amaral; *Abolicionismo* [Abolitionism], Arnaldo Brazão; *Educação sexual* [Sexual Education], Paulina Luisi; *As ligas de bondade* [The Kindness Leagues], Maria O'Neill; *A influência dos espetáculos públicos na educação* [The Influence of Public Performances on Education], Victória Pais Freire de Andrade; *Proteção à mulher grávida e à criança* [Protection of Pregnant Woman and Children], Adelaide Cabete; *A mulher e a alimentação vegetariana* [Women and Vegetarian Diet], António Carvalho Brandão; *A mulher naturista* [The Naturist Woman], Julieta Ribeiro; *Solução biológica do problema educativo e Solução biológica do problema da assistência* [Biological Solution to the Educational Problem and Biological Solution to the Assistance Problem] Bentes Castel-Branco.

Analyzing the event's report, historian Zília Osório de Castro, who greatly contributed to the development of women's studies in Portugal, observed that,

[...] of the 25 theses presented, 17 were authored by women, demonstrating the existence of a determined and pioneering group of feminists in Portugal, although this reality had its downside. The analysis of the debates reveals, as a whole, a majority of male participants, 26 compared to 16 feminists. In other words, of the total names mentioned, about 60% were men, which carries its own significance, pointing to what I call "male feminism" of intervention and action¹⁵.

Castro, Anne Cova¹⁶, João Esteves and other scholars of feminism in Portugal participated, in May 2004, in the "Seminário Evocativo do I Congresso Feminista e da Educação em Portugal" [Evocative Seminar of the First Feminist and Education Congress in Portugal]. Eighty years later, in recalling the event, the aim was to give "face and life to the Portuguese feminists [...] who remained faithful to the feminist ideal"; to inscribe feminism into the history of Portugal, "through the evocation of its different forms of action in response to political contexts and its ongoing contribution to the modernization and democratization of Portuguese society throughout the 20th century"; and to develop an assessment of feminist thought and action in the country"¹⁷. Published in book form, some of the works that more directly referenced the 1924 Congress reflect a celebratory attitude that was also shared by the organizing committee of the 2004 Seminar:

By deciding to hold that Congress in 1924, the same year as its 10th anniversary, the National Council of Portuguese Women

¹⁵ CASTRO, Zília Osório de. "Seminário Evocativo do I Congresso Feminista e da Educação em Portugal" In *O Longo Caminho das Mulheres. Feminismos 80 Anos Depois*. Lisboa: Publicações Dom Quixote, 2007, p. 21. In Portuguese: "[...] das 25 teses apresentadas, 17 eram assinadas por mulheres, demonstrando a existência de um grupo aguerrido e pioneiro de feministas em Portugal, embora esta realidade tivesse a sua contraface. A análise dos debates revela, no seu conjunto, uma maioria de intervenientes masculinos, 26 para 16 feministas. Ou seja, no total dos nomes mencionados, cerca de 60% são de homens, o que não deixa de ter o seu significado próprio, apontando para o que chamo 'feminismo masculino' de intervenção e ação".

¹⁶ COVA, Anne. "O Primeiro Congresso Feminista e da Educação em Portugal numa Perspectiva Comparada" In *O Longo Caminho das Mulheres. 80 Anos Depois*. Lisboa: Publicações Dom Quixote, 2007, pp. 27-43.

¹⁷ AMÂNCIO, Lígia et al. *O Longo Caminho das Mulheres. 80 Anos Depois*. Lisboa: Publicações Dom Quixote, 2007, pp. 15-16. In Portuguese: "rosto e vida às feministas portuguesas [...] que se mantiveram fiéis ao ideal feminista"; "através da evocação das suas diferentes formas de ação em função dos contextos políticos e da sua permanente contribuição para a modernização e democratização da sociedade portuguesa ao longo do século XX; e desenvolver um balanço sobre o pensamento e a ação feministas no país".

marked an important milestone in the history of Portuguese feminism, promoting, for the first time in Portugal, an event aimed at “discussing and propagating feminist ideas”. Feminism was then embraced in both word and action by the first women who, at the beginning of the 20th century, fought for women’s rights in Portugal. Courageously, they challenged prejudice and conservatism, as highlighted in one of Adelaide Cabete’s remarks at that Congress: “To those timid souls who ask where Feminism will lead, we will respond: Feminism will end where all ideas of Progress and all generous hopes end, where all just aspirations end”¹⁸.

It is important to note, however, that João Esteves, a scholar of Portuguese feminist associations during the First Republic, took a more critical stance regarding the CNMP and republican feminists in general. He recalled the actions of women who, years before the foundation of the aforementioned association, were already advocating for women’s dignity—actions that were sometimes contrasting. Furthermore, by highlighting how the Uruguayan doctor Paulina Luisi was presented in one of the issues of the *Alma Feminina* bulletin, the historian critiqued “the tendency of Portuguese feminists to overly value the legislative advances achieved with the Republic, at the expense of a realistic analysis of their weaknesses, both in organizational terms and in concrete responses to their demands”¹⁹.

¹⁸ *Ibid.*, p. 458. In Portuguese: “Ao decidir realizar aquele Congresso [de 1924], no mesmo ano do seu 10º aniversário, o Conselho Nacional das Mulheres Portuguesas marcou uma etapa importante na história do feminismo português, promovendo, pela primeira vez, em Portugal, uma realização que visava ‘discutir e propagar as ideias feministas’. O feminismo era então assumido na palavra e na ação das primeiras mulheres que lutaram, no início do século XX, pelos direitos das mulheres em Portugal. De forma corajosa, desafiando o preconceito e o conservadorismo, como se destaca de uma das frases da intervenção de Adelaide Cabete naquele Congresso: ‘Àqueles timoratos que perguntam onde irá o Feminismo parar responder-lhes-emos: o Feminismo terminará onde acabam todas as ideias de Progresso e toda a esperança generosa, terminará onde acabam as aspirações justas’”.

¹⁹ ESTEVES, João Gomes. “Os Anos 20: a Afirmação de uma Nova Geração de Feministas” In *O Longo Caminho das Mulheres. 80 Anos Depois*. Lisboa: Publicações Dom Quixote, 2007, p. 78. In Portuguese: “tendência das feministas portuguesas em valorizar em demasia os avanços legislativos obtidos com a República, em detrimento de uma análise realista das suas debilidades, quer no plano organizativo, como nas respostas concretas às suas reivindicações”. In the aforementioned edition of the bulletin, Paulina Luisi was honored by the CNMP: “At the Kristiana Congress [Denmark], particularly when discussing the situation of illegitimate children within the family, Dr. Paulina Luisi demonstrated to the select feminist assembly how Portuguese legislation on this matter was much more advanced than that of many other countries. This brought about a great wave of sympathy for our country, as many women were unaware that it was at such a developed level of civilization”. CONSELHO NACIONAL DAS MULHERES PORTUGUESAS. “Dr^a Paulina Luisi” In *Alma Feminina: Boletim Oficial do Conselho Nacional das Mulheres Portuguesas*, Lisboa, V. V, n. 5 e 6, 1921, p. 22. In Portuguese: “No congresso de Kristiana [Dinamarca], principalmente, quando se tratava de discutir a situação dos filhos ilegítimos na família, a Dr^a Paulina Luisi mostrou à seleta assembleia

Recently, a master's thesis supervised by Anne Cova was published in book format, *History of the National Council of Portuguese Women (1914-1947)*. In this work, Célia Rosa Costa presents—much like the previously referenced works of Castro, Cova, and Esteves—data on the 1924 Congress, based on sources such as Arnaldo Brazão's report, while also offering pertinent reflections. First, the author notes that the very title of the event, which differed from most similar gatherings abroad by incorporating the word “education”, revealed the cautious stance of the CNMP, “since feminism was still a ‘misunderstood cause’ among the general Portuguese population” and also because “it was not in the feminists’ interest to confront the established power, given that the majority identified with the republican regime”²⁰. Additionally, Costa draws attention to the strategic effort of the organizing committee in inviting prominent male political figures and publicizing their participation in the Congress through the mainstream press—actions that lent a certain credibility to the CNMP. Finally, she clarifies it that the content of the theses presented, as well as the very definition of feminism upheld by those involved, aligned with a moderate current, “as it reconciles the traditionally assigned social roles of women—as mothers and wives—with the demand for participation in political and social activities”²¹.

As Mark Adams rightly pointed out, much of the historiography has established the idea that eugenics was a singular and coherent movement, primarily developed under the aegis of Anglo-Saxon states, guided by genetic heredity theories (especially of a Mendelian nature), and often associated with conservative and authoritarian political projects²². The ideas analyzed here contrast with this historiography, which, on various occasions, has overlooked the temporal, spatial, and social diversity in which eugenics spread, ignoring, for example, in the Portuguese case, the strong Christian and neo-Lamarckian tradition. Moreover, this historiography often fails to account for the fact that,

feminista como a legislação portuguesa neste ponto era muito mais avançada que a de muitos outros países. Valeu isto uma grande corrente de simpatia para o nosso país que muitas senhoras desconheciam estar num grau de civilização bastante desenvolvido”.

²⁰ COSTA, op. cit., p. 145. In Portuguese: “uma vez que o feminismo era ainda uma causa ‘mal compreendida’ do quadro geral da população portuguesa”; “às feministas não interessava confrontar o poder instituído, em virtude de ser o regime republicano aquele com que a maioria se identificava”.

²¹ Ibid., p. 151. In Portuguese: “uma vez que faz conciliar o papel social tradicionalmente atribuído às mulheres — de mãe e esposa — com a reivindicação do exercício das atividades política e social”.

²² ADAMS, Mark. B. “Toward a Comparative History” In ADAMS, Mark B. (Ed). *The Wellborn Science: Eugenics in Germany, France, Brazil, and Russia*. New York: Oxford University Press, 1990.

in the early 20th century, eugenics also attracted supporters from progressive political groups, such as feminists, liberals, and socialists²³.

Although the formalization of eugenics as a concept in Portugal occurred only in the early 1910s, the evolutionary discussions that began in the late 19th century laid the groundwork for questions about the future of the Portuguese race²⁴. Social problems such as alcoholism, prostitution, crime, juvenile delinquency, as well as mortality rates caused by poverty and endemic diseases, were on the rise. All these factors clearly obstructed, from the perspective of policymakers, national development and demanded the implementation of preventive and therapeutic measures to mitigate conditions that seemed to contribute to the weakening of the Portuguese people²⁵. After the Proclamation of the Republic in 1910, the regenerative discourse was thus incorporated into political rhetoric.

Recognizing that historiography itself is subject to historicization²⁶ and that, today, feminist theory increasingly questions major milestones²⁷ and the limits of certain feminist expressions²⁸, this study aims to interrogate precisely

²³ About the influence of eugenics within the progressive sphere, see: CLEMINSON, Richard. *Anarchism and Eugenics: an Unlikely Convergence, 1890-1940*. Manchester: Manchester University Press, 2019; LAVRIN, Asunción. *Women, Feminism, and Social Change in Argentina, Chile, and Uruguay, 1890-1940*. Lincoln: University of Nebraska Press, 1995; NADKARNI, Asha. *Eugenic Feminism: Reproductive Nationalism in the United States and India*. Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press, 2014.

²⁴ According to José Manuel Sobral, since the late 19th century, contemporary observers frequently resorted to racial explanations to justify Portugal's disappointing development. This context motivated anthropologists and social scientists, with an evolutionary mindset, to conduct statistical studies in an attempt to map degeneration in the country. SOBRAL, José Manuel. "O Norte, o Sul, a Raça, a Nação — Representações da Identidade Nacional Portuguesa (séculos XIX-XX)" In *Análise Social*, V. 39, n. 171, pp. 255- 284, 2004.

²⁵ GIESBRECHT, Daniel Florence. "Trabalhos de Antropologia e Etnologia: o Movimento Eugênico Português a partir da Perspectiva da Antropologia Histórica" In *Revista Científica do Centro Universitário do Rio São Francisco*, n. 30, pp. 361-384, 2021, p. 368.

²⁶ BARROS, José D'Assunção. *A Historiografia como Fonte Histórica*. Petrópolis: Vozes, 2022.

²⁷ LAUGHLIN, Kathleen A. et al. "Is It Time to Jump Ship? Historians Rethink the Waves Metaphor" In *Feminist Formations*, Baltimore, V. 22, n. 1, pp. 76-135, 2010; FRACCARO, Glaucia Cristina Candian. *Os Direitos das Mulheres: Feminismo e Trabalho no Brasil (1917-1937)*. Rio de Janeiro: FGV, 2018; ALVES, Iracélli da Cruz. *Feminismo Entre Ondas: Mulheres, PCB e Política no Brasil*. Tese (Doutorado em História)—Universidade Federal Fluminense, Niterói, 2020.

²⁸ In response to Nancy Fraser's text, *How Feminism Became Capitalism's Handmaiden*, Brenna Bhandar and Denise Ferreira da Silva noted that Fraser's observation—that feminism would have been co-opted by capitalism—had already been felt and problematized by Black and Third World feminists for decades. In this sense, we reference only a few of the classic works that address intersections of gender and race, for example: DAVIS, Angela. *Mulheres, Raça e Classe*. São Paulo: Boitempo, 2016; hooks, bell. *Não serei eu mulher?*. Lisboa: Orfeu Negro, 2018; GONZALEZ, Léila. "Por um Feminismo Afro-Latino-Americano" In *Pensamento Feminista Hoje — Perspectivas Decoloniais*, Rio de Janeiro: Bazar do Tempo, 2020. Texts cited in the note: FRASER, Nancy. "How Feminism Became Capitalism's Handmaiden — And How to Reclaim It" In

some of those limits present in Portuguese institutionalized feminism of the 1920s²⁹. In response to this initiative, some might argue that there is a degree of anachronism here or that, given the conditions of the past, things could not have been otherwise. Despite evidence that other forms of contemporary feminism existed alongside that represented by the CNMP, our intention is primarily to highlight how certain movements, despite being distinct and seemingly contradictory (such as feminism and eugenics), could, given the historical circumstances, converge and even blend into larger and more complex projects or as a strategy for survival. If we cannot question past situations and their celebratory narratives, then we are doomed to repeat attitudes that, today, are no longer comprehensible.

Discourses on Sex

To develop his concept of biopolitics, Michel Foucault posed several questions, including the following: “[...] at a time when labor power is systematically exploited, could one tolerate it dissipating in pleasures, except for those, minimized to the utmost, that allow it to reproduce itself?”³⁰. With this in mind, let us move on to a brief consideration of the treatment of prostitution in the 19th and early 20th centuries in Portugal. In the mid-1800s, legislation related to the activity—such as the *Regulamento Policial das Meretrizes e Casas Toleradas da Cidade de Lisboa* [Police Regulation of Prostitutes and Tolerated Houses in the City of Lisbon], promulgated in 1858—aimed to remove prostitutes from visible public spaces “in order to safeguard the respectability and apparent decency of ‘respectable’ women”³¹. José Pais, who studied the issue in Lisbon, argued that the moralistic discourse condemning prostitution, which circulated among both supporters of the

The Guardian, 2013, e BHANDAR, Brenna; SILVA, Denise Ferreira da. “White Feminist Fatigue Syndrome” In *Critical Legal Thinking*, 2013. Nancy Fraser herself, along with other feminist theorists, issued a manifesto in favor of a feminism capable of necessarily articulating race and ethnicity, class and gender, in dialogue with ecosocialist agendas. ARRIZZA, Cinzia; BHATTACHARYA, Thiti; FRASER, Nancy. *Feminismo para os 99%*. Lisboa: Objectiva, 2019.

²⁹ Regarding the problem, see also: ALMEIDA, Jaqueline Moraes de. “Limites e Possibilidades do Feminismo Português na Primeira Década do Século XX, a Partir da Análise de ‘Alma Feminina’” In *Revista de História das Ideias*, Coimbra, V. 41, pp. 141–164, 2023.

³⁰ FOUCAULT, Michel. *História da Sexualidade: a Vontade de Saber*. São Paulo: Paz & Terra, 2014, p. 10. In Portuguese: “[...] na época em que se explora sistematicamente a força de trabalho, poder-se-ia tolerar que ela fosse dissipar-se nos prazeres, salvo naqueles, reduzidos ao máximo, que lhe permitem reproduzir-se?”.

³¹ PAIS, José Machado. *A Prostituição e a Lisboa Boémia do Século XIX a Inícios do Século XX*. Lisboa: Ambar, 2008, p. 43. In Portuguese: “de maneira a salvaguardar a respeitabilidade e a decência aparente das mulheres ‘de bem’”.

regulation of the activity and the so-called abolitionists, was driven, among other reasons, by concerns about the spread of venereal diseases, especially among those of productive and reproductive age³². However, the project that sought to confine sexuality, entrusting the family with the “seriousness of the reproductive function” while simultaneously tolerating male pleasures restricted “to the bedroom or the brothel”³³, faced difficulties in sustaining itself in the face of the visible advancement of the contradictions within the capitalist system, including the development of feminism, for example. By the end of the 19th century, the failure of regulatory policies—those that broadly aimed at controlling the practices of prostitution—gave way to the abolitionist movement. This movement was championed by individuals—including a significant number of feminists—who “rejected the legalization of prostitution, as they saw it as a measure of repression and control over public women”³⁴.

In *Do Cabaré ao Lar* [From the Cabaret to the Home], Margareth Rago clearly explains the criticisms developed by abolitionists against the regulatory model. For them,

[...] the old method of monitoring prostitution had numerous flaws: first and foremost, it targeted only the woman, pursuing her for a type of relationship in which the man was equally involved. She was seized and confined in isolated, special houses, registered by the police as a professional prostitute, strictly monitored by both the police and doctors, accused of transmitting syphilis and other venereal diseases, and subjected to all the repression for practices deemed intolerable by society, while the man remained free from any responsibility. Furthermore, the result of the regulatory system then adopted was the opposite of what it had intended: clandestine prostitution had visibly increased, both here and in other countries. [...] But the point on which abolitionist criticism of the regulatory system most vigorously focused was that the legal registration of prostitutes trapped them and hindered their potential rehabilitation. The vice police were seen as a machine that transformed “occasional

³² Ibid., p. 46.

³³ Ibid., p. 47. In Portuguese: “seriedade da função reprodutora”; “à alcova ou ao bordel”.

³⁴ RAGO, Margareth. *Do Cabaré ao Lar: a Utopia da Sociedade Disciplinar e a Resistência Anarquista, Brasil (1890-1930)*. São Paulo: Paz & Terra, 2014, p. 145. In Portuguese: “recusavam a legalização da prostituição, pois viam neste ato uma medida de repressão e de controle sobre as mulheres públicas”.

whores” into “eternal whores”: the registered prostitute ended up becoming a perpetual prisoner of the police³⁵.

Broadly speaking, the same shift in understanding and treatment of prostitution observed in Portugal and other European countries also occurred in Brazil, Uruguay, and very likely in other countries, especially during the early decades of the 20th century. The international associations and congresses, which were so common during this period, played a crucial role in this convergence of ideas and practices.

***Abolicionismo*, by Arnaldo Brazão (1890–1968)**

On the fourth day of the Feminist and Educational Congress, Arnaldo Brazão, who also took on the role of secretary for the event, presented the thesis titled *Abolicionismo*. According to the report, this thesis was discussed by Angélica Porto (President of the Moral Section of the CNMP), Domingas Lazary do Amaral (Secretary of the Interior of the Council), and Jaime de Gouveia, a lawyer. “The regulation of prostitution is a hygienic error, a social injustice, a moral monstrosity, and a legal crime”—this was the epigraph chosen by Brazão for his thesis, recalling the words of the International Abolitionist Federation³⁶.

His work follows a typical format, segmented into an introduction—which immediately synthesizes abolitionism as “moral education”—and a justification based on the supposed scarcity of studies on the subject in Portugal³⁷; a literature review; the development of arguments capable

³⁵ *Ibid.*, pp. 144–145. In Portuguese: “[...] o antigo método de vigilância da prostituição comportava inúmeras falhas: em primeiro lugar, visava apenas à mulher, perseguindo-a por um tipo de relação em que o homem também estava envolvido. Ela era sequestrada e confinada em casas isoladas e especiais, fichada na polícia como prostituta profissional, vigiada severamente pela polícia e pelos médicos, acusada de ser transmissora de sífilis e de outras doenças venéreas, sofrendo sozinha toda a repressão de práticas intoleráveis para a sociedade, enquanto o homem ficava isento de qualquer responsabilidade. Além disso, o resultado do sistema regulamentarista então adotado foi o oposto do que se propusera: a prostituição clandestina aumentara a olhos vistos, tanto aqui quanto em outros países. [...] Mas o ponto sobre o qual incidia mais vigorosamente a crítica abolicionista aos regulamentaristas era que o registro legal das prostitutas prendia-as e impedia sua possível recuperação. A polícia de costumes era vista como uma máquina que transformava ‘putas ocasionais’ em ‘putas eternas’: a prostituta inscrita acaba se tornando uma prisioneira perpétua da polícia”.

³⁶ BRAZÃO, Arnaldo. *Abolicionismo*. Lisboa: Tip. da Casa Garrett, 1924, p. 3. In Portuguese: “A regulamentação da prostituição é um erro higiênico, uma injustiça social, uma monstruosidade moral e um crime jurídico”. The International Abolitionist Federation was founded in 1875 in Liverpool by the English feminist Josephine Butler.

³⁷ Among Portuguese feminists, the topic of prostitution or “white slavery traffic” has appeared recurrently since at least the 1910s, in line with debates held abroad. Below, we list some articles on the subject that

of supporting his claims; and the proposition of alternative measures to regulationism. The explicitly feminist nature of the thesis is evident in the account of the process of consolidating an association focused on defending abolitionist arguments. “When they saw their efforts were in vain”—related to opposing the regulationist law of 1864 in England—doctors, lawyers, and “other people of high social standing” turned to Josephine Butler who, after the invitation,

[...] embarked on the crusade by founding the National Association of English Ladies and saw figures such as Florence Nightingale, Mme Lucas, sister of Stuart Mill, Mrs. Bright, daughter of Dr. Bright, the renowned doctor Inés Mac Laren, who even took her advocacy to Pope Leo XIII, the Duchess of Manchester, Crestina Alsop, Herbert Spencer, Stuart Mill, James Stansfeld, George Russell, Drs. Wood, Hodgson, Bell Taylor, and many others, stand by her side³⁸.

In addition to Josephine Butler and other English women, Brazão recalls the involvement of feminists such as Maria Deraismes (France) and Concepción Arenal (Spain) in the abolitionism. He also references the studies of Paulina Luisi, then a permanent member of the International Commission on White Slave Traffic of the League of Nations, who viewed the regulation regime as hateful, “because it is both favorable to vice and a relentless enemy of the fallen woman, entirely opposed to its mission as a repressive social law”³⁹. With this stance, the author conveyed that the arguments of a woman, Dr. Luisi, held the same impact and value as those put forth by male physicians, such as Ângelo da Fonseca, Silvio Rebelo, and Félix Renault—also referenced in the thesis.

Regarding the argumentation in favor of abolitionism, in addition to citing a body of literature developed by medical professionals, Arnaldo Brazão

were published in *A Madrugada* [The Dawn], the journal of the Liga Republicana das Mulheres Portuguesas [Republican League of Portuguese Women]: PEREIRA, Avelina Correia. “A Prostituição” In *A Madrugada*, Ano II, n. 13, 1912, p. 3; FAZENDA JÚNIOR. “A Prostituição”, *A Madrugada*, Ano II, n. 15, 1912, p. 2; LIGA REPUBLICANA DAS MULHERES PORTUGUESAS. “Escravidura Branca” In *A Madrugada*, Ano II, n. 15, p. 3; SERPA, Maria P. Bastos. “A Prostituição” In *A Madrugada*, Ano II, n. 19, 1913, cover page.

³⁸ BRAZÃO, op. cit., Abolicionismo, p. 4. In Portuguese: “[...] empreende a cruzada fundando a Associação Nacional de Damas Inglesas e vê colocarem-se a seu lado Florência Nightingale, M.me Lucas, irmã de Stuart Mill, Mrs. Bright, filha do dr. Bright, a célebre médica Inés Mac Laren que levou a sua propaganda até junto ao Papa Leão XIII, duquesa de Manchester, Crestina Alsop, Herbert Spencer, Stuart Mill, James Stansfeld, George Russel, os drs. Wood, Hodgson, Bell Taylor e tantos outros”.

³⁹ Ibid., p. 11. In Portuguese: “porque ao mesmo tempo é favorável ao vício e implacável inimigo da mulher caída, é completamente oposto à sua missão de lei social repressiva”.

presents a table containing English statistical data “concerning syphilis, extracted from the Army Medical Reports and published by [Abraham] Flexner”, an American physician⁴⁰. Brazão’s idea was to demonstrate that the number of people infected with syphilis significantly decreased after the abolition of the regulatory laws on prostitution.

In his book *Catholicism, Race and Empire: Eugenics in Portugal (1900–1950)*, Richard Cleminson emphasizes that the sanitary problems faced by Portugal during the period from the late 19th century to the early 20th century, such as the spread of venereal diseases, allowed for the alignment with the principles of reformist eugenics⁴¹. This essentially environmentalist eugenic model was characterized by its emphasis on public health measures aimed at preventing the transmission of diseases and improving the genetic quality of the population. The Portuguese psychiatrist Miguel Bombarda, for example, was one of the first to advocate that the dangers arising from acquired conditions were significantly greater than those originating from cases of hereditary degeneration, once again highlighting the considerable influence of Neo-Lamarckian ideas in the country: “Various intoxications, multiple infections, play a predominant role here. An alcoholic, a syphilitic, is much more dangerous for the offspring than, I know, a simple lunatic”⁴².

In the conclusions of his thesis, Arnaldo Brazão asserts that prostitution was not a crime, thus distancing himself from criminologists like Cesare Lombroso, who claimed that prostitutes were characterized “by their small cranial capacity and much heavier jaws than those of honest women”⁴³, or, to cite a Portuguese example, the anthropologist Mendes Correia, who believed that “Among prostitutes, as among criminals, degeneracy, neuroses, psychoses—especially moral insanity, hysteria, and mental deficiency—abound

⁴⁰ Ibid., p. 8. In Portuguese: “respeitantes à sífilis, extraído dos Army Medical Reports e publicado por [Abraham] Flexner”. The statistical data used by Brazão were also published in the book *Prostitution in Europe*: ABRAHAM FLEXNER. *Prostitution in Europe*. New York: The Century Co., 1919, pp. 372–373.

⁴¹ CLEMINSON, Richard. *Catholicism, Race and Empire: Eugenics in Portugal (1900-1950)*. Budapest: Central European University Press, 2014, pp. 62-65.

⁴² BOMBARDA, Miguel. “A Esterilização dos Degenerados” In *A Medicina Contemporânea*, V. 13, n. 5, 1910, p. 34. In Portuguese: “As várias intoxicações, as múltiplas infecções, representam aqui um papel preponderante. Um alcoólico, um sífilítico, é muito mais perigoso para a progênie do que, eu sei, um simples alienado”.

⁴³ RAGO, op. cit., p. 138. In Portuguese: “por sua fraca capacidade craniana e por mandíbulas bem mais pesadas que as das mulheres honestas”.

in stigmatizations”⁴⁴ ⁴⁵. In his conclusions, Brazão also suggested a social prophylaxis that would provide free medical assistance to venereal disease patients and function parallel to the widespread dissemination of individual hygiene knowledge.

Arnaldo Brazão’s thesis was approved and praised by Angélica Porto and Domingas Lazary do Amaral. In the motion of the latter, we draw attention to the following statement, which, among others, legitimized the approval of the thesis by the commentator: “Considering that exceptional measures based on sex differentiation are inequitable and infringe upon individual freedom”⁴⁶ – we will revisit this argument at an appropriate time. Contrary to the position of these feminists, Jaime de Gouveia expressed some disagreements with the content of the thesis. Firstly, he argued that “If it is impossible to abolish prostitution, if it persists and develops despite all prohibitions and punishments, it is because it is part of our social environment, because it is an evil, a necessary evil as Saint Augustine said”⁴⁷. With such an argument, the commentator concluded that “if prostitution is a necessary evil, its regulation may not aggravate the situation but rather alleviate it”⁴⁸. The thesis rapporteur countered Gouveia’s comments by invoking the data borrowed from Flexner’s study, concluding that, “Even if abolitionism cannot reduce the number of prostitutes, it at least visibly decreases the number of syphilitics,

⁴⁴ CORREIA, Mendes. *Os Criminosos Portugueses: Estudos de Antropologia Criminal*. Coimbra: Tip. França Amado, 1914, p. 77. In Portuguese: “Entre as prostitutas, como entre os criminosos, a degenerescência, as nevroses, as psicoses, especialmente a loucura moral, a histeria e a debilidade mental, espalham abundantes estigmatizações”.

⁴⁵ In the same study, however, Mendes Correia considers the relevance of the social environment for the development of certain criminals. For him, some prostitutes would be victims of conditions such as “family abandonment, mistreatment, poverty, seduction, unhappy love, poor or nonexistent education, etc.”. *Ibid.*, pp. 77-78. In Portuguese: “o abandono de família, maus tratos, miséria, sedução, amores infelizes, má ou nula educação, etc.”. According to the studies by Patrícia Ferraz de Matos, Mendes Correia was one of the pioneers in linking eugenics with Lombrosian degeneration theory and neolamarckism. Although he did not agree with all of Lombroso’s assertions, Correia fully accepted the notion of inherited criminal predisposition. At the same time, he highlighted the benefits of education for those deemed deserving, arguing that it would stimulate civic consciousness, good work habits, and ultimately, a healthy and eugenic lifestyle. MATOS, Patrícia Ferraz de. *Anthropology, Nationalism and Colonialism: Mendes Correia and the Porto School of Anthropology*. New York: Berghahn Books, 2023, pp. 182-195.

⁴⁶ BRAZÃO, op. cit., O Primeiro Congresso Feminista..., p. 181. In Portuguese: “Considerando que as medidas de caráter excepcional baseadas na diferenciação dos sexos são iníquas e atentatórias da liberdade individual”.

⁴⁷ *Ibid.*, p. 182. In Portuguese: “Se é impossível abolir a prostituição, se ela apesar de todas as proibições e castigos subsiste e se desenvolve, é porque faz parte do nosso meio social, é porque ela é um mal, um mal necessário como o disse Santo Agostinho”.

⁴⁸ *Ibid.* In Portuguese: “se a prostituição é um mal necessário a sua regulamentação talvez o não agrave, antes o minore”.

which is something”⁴⁹ 50. Furthermore, Brazão, in a courageous move—given that the Feminist and Educational Congress was, as previously mentioned, legitimized by republican authorities—seized the opportunity to lament that the Republic’s legislation not only “maintained what was humiliating” but also made “the already existing measures” regarding prostitution in the country “even more oppressive and hateful”⁵¹.

Educação Sexual, by Paulina Luisi (1875–1949)

In dialogue with Brazão’s thesis, particularly in his concern about venereal diseases, Paulina Luisi presented the paper *Educação Sexual*, whose conclusions, as explicitly stated by the doctor herself, were debated and approved in previous congresses — 1st American Congress of the Child, Buenos Aires, 1916; 2nd Congress of Medicine, Montevideo, 1921; 3rd American Congress of the Child, Rio de Janeiro, 1922; and the International Congress of Social Hygiene, Paris, 1923. In the thesis in question, Luisi defines and repeatedly emphasizes what she understands by sexual education: “it is the pedagogical action that aims to subject the sexual instinct to the action of the will under the control of an educated, conscious, and responsible intelligence”⁵². Based on this conceptualization, she establishes a methodology that integrates the “knowledge of things” — that is, knowledge of life and its respective laws, made possible through disciplines such as Natural History, Botany, Zoology, Anatomy, and Physiology — and the “moral knowledge of sexual issues”. Although she does not provide detailed explanations about this latter type of knowledge, she references a study, also authored by her, where

⁴⁹ Ibid., p. 184. In Portuguese: “Se o abolicionismo não consegue diminuir o número de prostitutas, daqui ressalta logo à primeira vista, que pelo menos, faz diminuir o número dos sífilíticos o que já é alguma coisa”.

⁵⁰ In 1912, Avelina Pereira regretted: “But there are women who disdain the poor lost souls and there are men (men? no: monsters!) who even say that *prostitution is necessary!* It is difficult to believe, but it is true. Therefore, any effort against prostitution is not enough. Let us work for the emancipation of our sisters, let us fight for women’s independence, for a free woman through thought and independent through work will never descend to the vile profession of a prostitute”. PEREIRA, op. cit., p. 3. In Portuguese: “Mas há mulheres que desprezam as pobres extraviadas e há homens (homens? não: monstros!) que até dizem que a prostituição é necessária! Custa a crer mas é verdade. Por isso toda a guerra à prostituição é pouca. Trabalhem para a emancipação das nossas irmãs, lutemos pela independência da mulher, pois que a mulher livre pelo pensamento e independente pelo trabalho, jamais descerá ao vil mister de prostituta”.

⁵¹ BRAZÃO, op. cit., O Primeiro Congresso Feminista..., p. 183. In Portuguese: “deixou ficar o que era humilhante”; “ainda mais opressivas e odientas as medidas já existentes”.

⁵² LUISI, Paulina. *Educação Sexual*. Lisboa: Tip. da Casa Garrett, 1924, p. 3. In Portuguese: “é a ação pedagógica que pretende submeter o instinto sexual à ação da vontade sob o domínio da inteligência instruída, consciente e responsável”.

the issue was more thoroughly addressed. Following these leads, from the article “Plan y Métodos de Enseñanza Sexual”, published in *Acción Femenina* [Female Action], a periodical of the *Consejo Nacional de Mujeres del Uruguay* [National Council of Women of Uruguay], we recover a brief summary in which Luisi distinguishes between the concepts of instruction — equivalent to what she termed as knowledge of life in the thesis — and sexual education:

It is necessary, then, to establish two major chapters in what is called sexual education: sexual instruction, which pertains to scientific knowledge on the subject, and sexual education, which, penetrating into the realms of ethics, encompasses within its lessons the gospel of a new morality based on human respect and individual responsibility within collective life. This education should develop, as fundamental to fulfilling the morality it teaches, two great and powerful virtues within the strength of will: character and a sense of responsibility⁵³.

In the 1916 text *Algunas ideas sobre Eugenia* [Some Ideas on Eugenics]⁵⁴, Paulina Luisi already expressed her affinity for the French eugenic model, particularly that promoted by the vice president of the French Eugenics Society, Adolphe Pinard, an obstetrician recognized as one of the pioneers of childcare in Europe and one of the world’s leading experts in prenatal pediatric care⁵⁵:

Eugenics, in one of its practical applications, seeks precisely to civilize this generative instinct, directing it towards the production of descendants who represent progress over their predecessors. These words also encapsulate the concept of Eugenics as understood by Pinard, the old champion of puericulture, who could not limit his work to the care of the child during gestation and after birth⁵⁶.

⁵³ LUISI, Paulina. “Plan y Métodos de Enseñanza Sexual” In *Acción Femenina*, Año IV, n. 27, 1920, p. 14. In Spanish: “Hay que establecer, pues, dos grandes capítulos en la llamada Enseñanza sexual: la instrucción sexual que corresponde a los conocimientos científicos relativos a la materia, y la educación sexual que, penetrando en los dominios de la ética encierra en sus lecciones el evangelio de una nueva moral, basada en el respeto humano y en la responsabilidad individual dentro de la vida colectiva, educación que debe desarrollar como fundamentales para el cumplimiento de la moral que enseña, dos grandes y poderosas virtudes en la fuerza de la voluntad: el carácter y el sentimiento de la responsabilidad”.

⁵⁴ LUISI, Paulina. *Algunas Ideas Sobre Eugenia*. Montevideo: El Siglo Ilustrado, 1916.

⁵⁵ DUNN, Peter M. “Adolphe Pinard (1844–1934) of Paris and Intrauterine Paediatric Care” In *Archives of Disease in Childhood: Fetal and Neonatal*, n. 91, pp. 231–232, 2006.

⁵⁶ PAULINI, op. cit., *Algunas ideas sobre eugenia*, p. 7. In Spanish: “La Eugenia en una de sus aplicaciones prácticas trata, precisamente, de civilizar este instinto de la generación, encaminándolo a la producción

Pinard argued that maternal protection and monitoring during pregnancy were essential for the health of the fetus (intrauterine puericulture) and later for the newborn (extrauterine puericulture). However, the French physician sought to extend puericulture beyond maternal prenatal and postnatal care. In his 1899 text, *De la Conservation et de l'Amélioration de l'Espèce* [On the Conservation and Improvement of the Species], he outlined a broad program of medical eugenics based on “preconceptional puericulture”⁵⁷. This strong emphasis on the health and hereditary value of parents was expressed through traditional pro-natalist and neo-Lamarckian language, encapsulated in the concepts of “Eugênica” (the study of eugenic practices, focusing on understanding their methods) and “Eugenética” (the dissemination of ideal reproductive conditions for effective application, aiming to conserve and improve the human species). These concepts were especially valued among eugenicists in Latin countries⁵⁸.

For Adolphe Pinard, the mission of puericulture was to determine the means to preserve and improve the human species, both through the selection of parents before conception and through proper care of the mother and child. In October 1922, responding to an invitation from the Belgian Society of Eugenics, Pinard delivered a lecture in which he emphasized that the goals of puericulture could only be achieved through a campaign of “rational sexual education”⁵⁹. This perspective was equally shared by Paulina Luisi.

In the conclusions of the thesis presented at the Lisbon Congress, Luisi proposed pedagogical guidelines for the implementation of sexual education in schools:

II

Sexual Education should begin with the awakening of a child's intelligence and continue from the maternal school through the entire duration of their school years.

de descendientes que señalen un progreso sobre sus antecesores. Estas palabras también sintetizan el concepto de la Eugénica de Pinard, el viejo campeón de la puericultura, que no podía limitar su tarea al cultivo del niño durante la gestación y después del Nacimiento”.

⁵⁷ PINARD, Adolphe. “De la Conservation et de l'Amélioration de l'Espèce” In *Revue Scientifique*, V. 1, pp. 167-174, 1899.

⁵⁸ Regarding Latin eugenics, see: TURDA, Marius; GILLETTE, Aaron. *Latin Eugenics in Comparative Perspective*. London: Bloomsbury, 2014.

⁵⁹ APERT, Eugène. “Les Journées Eugéniques Internationales de Bruxelles et la Fondation de la Ligue Nationale Belge Contre le Péril Vénérien” In *Paris Médical*, n. 46, pp. 322-333, 1922.

III

Sexual Education is the work of both the family and the school. [...]

VII

Sexual Education should not exist as a special subject in school curriculum [...]. The concepts it includes should be integrated into the subjects to which they belong, blended, so to speak, with the rest of the related analogous subjects, distributed across the disciplines of Natural History, Physiology, Anatomy, Hygiene, Prophylaxis, and Moral Education. [...]

X

No distinction should be made in the education of both sexes. Boys' and girls' schools should have the same curriculum as far as possible to achieve the *desideratum* of rational education: the Coeducation⁶⁰.

Analyzing Paulina Luisi's work on the topic of sexual education, Fernanda Cedrani and Santiago Zemaitis highlighted that it was based on medical knowledge that the introduction and recommendation of behavioral norms to populations were justified⁶¹. They highlight how the biological sciences, eugenics, and morality were intertwined in the discourse of the Uruguayan physician:

According to Luisi, the concern for hygiene and morality was considered “the need for physical and mental health”, and it was in defense of health that moral principles were established. She expressed that “morality must be based on science”. Again, sexuality, morality, and reproduction were strongly associated in her proposal⁶².

⁶⁰ LUISI, op. cit., Educação sexual, pp. 5-7. In Spanish: “II A **Educação Sexual** deve começar desde o despertar da inteligência da criança e deve prosseguir, a partir da escola maternal, durante toda a duração da vida escolar. [...] III A **Educação Sexual** é ao mesmo tempo a obra da família e da escola [...]. VII A **Educação Sexual** não deve existir como uma matéria especial nos programas escolares [...]. As noções que compreendem devem confundir-se nas matérias à quais pertencem, amalgamadas por assim dizer, com o resto das nações [sic] correlativas análogas, disseminadas nos programas de História Natural, Fisiologia, Anatomia, Higiene, Profilaxia e Moral. [...] X Não deve estabelecer-se nenhuma diferença no ensino de ambos os sexos [...]. As escolas masculinas e femininas devem ter os mesmos programas enquanto o seja possível alcançar o *desideratum* da educação racional: A Coeducação”.

⁶¹ CEDRANI, Fernanda Sosa; ZEMAITIS, Santiago. “Educación sexual, eugenesia y moral en el pensamiento de Paulina Luisi. La experiencia de la cátedra de Higiene Social (Uruguay, 1926-1930)” In *Mora*, Buenos Aires, n. 27, pp. 7-26, 2021, p. 14.

⁶² Ibid, p. 14. In Spanish: “Según Luisi, la preocupación por la higiene y la moral eran ‘la necesidad de la salud física y psíquica’ y en defensa de la salud es que se dictaminaban principios de orden moral. Expresaba que ‘La moral debe fundarse en la ciencia’. Nuevamente sexualidad, moral y reproducción quedaban fuertemente asociadas en su propuesta”.

Thus, despite appearing disruptive to some at the time—due to its public treatment of traditionally private matters and its advocacy for projects such as coeducation—Luisi, ultimately, did not abandon the idea of a “natural function”, which, since Rousseau⁶³ at least, had been associated with the feminine role in reproduction. Instead of liberating women from this condition, she and other intellectuals of the period attempted, particularly through their discourses, to subject men as well to the dictates of nature, focusing on the preservation and improvement of the race. In revisiting Foucault’s inquiry, we note that the period which systematically exploited labor—considering labor broadly and diversely, encompassing workers in factories, monoculture farms, colonial mines, domestic spaces, etc.—coincided with advancements in the technologies of sex, particularly represented by medicine and eugenic programs. As Foucault observed, the analysis of heredity from the second half of the 19th century “placed sex (sexual relations, venereal diseases, marital alliances, perversions) in a position of ‘biological responsibility’ regarding the species”⁶⁴. By merging the useful—the need for healthy and disciplined bodies—with the pleasurable—the control of women’s movement—the sciences of the period helped legitimize a discourse that, on the surface, elevated women to the status of emancipated beings, as they were entrusted with the most important mission in that context: ensuring the future and improvement of the race.

A Luta Anti-Alcoólica nas escolas, by Adelaide Cabete (1867–1935)

The thesis of Adelaide Cabete, *A Luta Anti-Alcoólica nas Escolas*, points to several of the arguments she had previously developed⁶⁵. Following a

⁶³ ROUSSEAU, Jean-Jacques. *Emílio ou Da Educação*. Rio de Janeiro: Bertrand Brasil, 1995.

⁶⁴ FOUCAULT, op. cit., p. 128. In Portuguese: “colocava o sexo (as relações sexuais, as doenças venéreas, as alianças matrimoniais, as perversões) em posição de ‘responsabilidade biológica’ com relação à espécie”.

⁶⁵ It is important to highlight that Adelaide Cabete was a Miguel Bombarda’s student in the Physiology and Histology courses at the Lisbon Medical-Surgical School. As previously mentioned, Bombarda was aligned with theories about acquired states and saw alcohol as one of the primary agents of degeneration. In an article published in 1904, he even advocated for legislation that would be forbidden marriage between individuals considered “defective”, including alcoholics, syphilitics, and people with mental disorders. BOMBARDA, Miguel. “Degenerescência das Raças” In *A Medicina Contemporânea*, V. 7, n. 32, 1904, p. 254. In 1910, in the Chamber of Deputies, the topic was discussed by Duarte Gustavo de Roboredo Sampaio e Mello, who defended the prohibition of marriage between individuals considered degenerate. He argued that the State should not allow the marital union of syphilitics, tuberculars, lepers, chronic alcoholics, epileptics, and those with heart diseases. Although the proposal was not approved, it demonstrates the concern with the physiological decline of the Portuguese race and, simultaneously, the mobilization of biopower mechanisms aimed at regenerating future generations. SERRADO, Ricardo Fernando Fontes Jesus. *O Problema Corpo-Mente no Portugal Contemporâneo: para uma Epistemologia do Desporto (1870-1910)*. Tese

structure similar to the works of Brazão and Luisi, Cabete's work presents a medical definition of alcoholism, followed by a listing of the main harms caused by the disease. According to the reporter, the greatest of these harms is the transmission of various conditions to the offspring of alcoholics, "such as the propensity for diseases, pauperism, and atavistic lesions so severe that the descendants end up as "human abortions or social monsters"⁶⁶. To legitimize her point, the doctor presents statistics developed by Charrin [sic], who found that in a children's hospital, 80% of the patients were kids of "alcoholics"⁶⁷. Like her nephew, Cabete adopts a liberal stance, rejecting direct State intervention in solving the problem of alcoholism. For her, the solution would involve expanding access to treatment for the afflicted, improving the conditions of the working class (raising wages, providing hygienic housing, promoting leisure activities, etc.), and, fundamentally, implementing an educational project aimed at school-aged children:

It is necessary to engrave in the minds of children the harmful effects of alcohol because the outcomes we seek are more certain than those achieved through propaganda among adults. Many adults are so accustomed to alcohol that they cannot live without it; it has become a physiological necessity for them. In contrast, a child, still free from such a vice, is an excellent field in which to cultivate a fear of alcohol.

This underscores the great mission of the Educator in this relentless battle, in which thousands upon thousands of good wills and kind hearts are engaged⁶⁸.

Knowing that the late 19th century saw a process of feminization of primary education in various countries, including Portugal⁶⁹, it will once

(Doutorado em História)—Lisboa: Universidade Autónoma de Lisboa, 2021, p. 192.

⁶⁶ CABETE, Adelaide. *A Luta Anti-Alcoólica nas Escolas*. Lisboa: Tip. da Casa Garrett, 1924, p. 3. In Portuguese: "condições várias de receptividade de doenças, como o pauperismo e lesões atávicas de tal gravidade que os descendentes acabam por serem uns abortos humanos ou uns monstros sociais".

⁶⁷ Ibid, p. 4. It is likely that "Charrin" is actually Élisée Charra, the author of the study *Contribution à L'Étude de L'Alcoolisme Héritaire* [Contribution to the Study of Hereditary Alcoholism], published in 1906.

⁶⁸ CABETE, op. cit., p. 6. In Portuguese: "É preciso gravar no cérebro das crianças os malefícios do álcool, porque os resultados que nós temos em vista são mais seguros do que a propaganda feita entre os adultos. Nestes, muitos há que estão tão habituados ao álcool que não podem passar sem ele, é para eles uma necessidade fisiológica, enquanto que a criança, ainda livre de tal vício, é um excelente campo para nela se desenvolver o medo pelo álcool. Daqui a grande missão do Educador nesta luta sem tréguas em que andam empenhados milhares e milhares de boas vontades, milhares de corações bondosos".

⁶⁹ ADÃO, Áurea. "A História da Profissão Docente em Portugal: Balanço da Investigação Realizada nas Últimas Décadas" In *Encontros Ibéricos de História da Educação*, Porto, V. 1, pp. 123–135, 1992, p. 125.

again be women who are tasked with solving the problems associated with the “destruction of the home” and the generation of “deformed offspring”. Cabete herself, when historicizing the anti-alcohol movement, highlights the involvement of women, “not because they [women] are more prone to vice, but because they directly suffer and feel the intemperance of men to whom they have tied their life”⁷⁰.

A mulher naturista, by Julieta Ribeiro (s/d)

The thesis developed by Julieta Adelina Menezes Rodrigues Ribeiro, author of the book *Culinária Vegetariana, Vegetalina e Menús Frugívoros* [Vegetarian Cooking, Plant-Based Cuisine, and Frugivore Recipes], presents a format that differs from the others analyzed, as it is a compilation of propositions. Despite this, her work strongly resonates with the theses of Brazão, Luisi, and Cabete, as it suggests that a natural diet⁷¹, without the consumption of meat, could prevent social ills such as alcoholism and syphilis. However, the majority of the author’s propositions establish a connection between the feminine element, the regeneration of the race, and the moralization of society: “Human happiness can only be the work of women, who hold the conquests of knowledge, building the modern home on the ruins of the past”, “From daughters, sisters, mothers, and wives should come the cry for universal redemption”, etc.⁷².

⁷⁰ CABETE, op. cit., p. 4. In Portuguese: “destruição do lar”; “frutos disformes”; “não porque ela [a mulher] seja mais viciosa, mas porque ela que mais diretamente sofre e sente as intemperanças do homem a quem ligou a sua vida”.

⁷¹ O *Vegetariano* [The Vegetarian], a periodical founded and edited by Julieta’s husband, Jerónimo Caetano Ribeiro, published a list of the advantages of plant-based diet, which included the following points: “8 – Overcomes drunkenness; 10 – Clarifies the mind; 11 – Strengthens the will; 12 – Softens the character; 13 – Prevents crimes; 15 – Frees the kitchen wives; 16 – Brings joy to the family; 17 – **Prevents divorce**; 18 – Prevents all social evils”. ANGELATZ Y ALBORNA, Juan. “Ventagens da Alimentação Natural” In *O Vegetariano*, Porto, V. 13, n. 9 e 10, 1922, p. 178. In Portuguese: “8 – Vence a embriaguez; 10 – Clarifica a mente; 11 – Fortifica a vontade; 12 – Suaviza o caráter; 13 – Evita o crime; 15 – Liberta a mulher da cozinha; 16 – Provoca a alegria na família; 17 – **Impede o divórcio**; 18 – Impede todos os males sociais”. The disclosure of an advantage related to the maintenance of marriage, underlined by us, highlights the recurrence of one of the moral values of the period which, ruffle speaking, associated divorce with a woman’s lack of commitment to safeguarding her family, even if made up of a husband alcoholic and violent.

⁷² Julieta Ribeiro’s thesis was also published in the journal *O Vegetariano*: RIBEIRO, Julieta. “Defesa da Tese Naturista” In *O Vegetariano*, V. 15, n. 9 e 10, pp. 19–23, 1924, p. 1. In Portuguese: “A felicidade humana só pode ser obra da mulher, detentora das conquistas do saber, edificando o lar moderno nas ruínas do passado”; “Das filhas, irmãs, mães e esposas deve partir o grito de redenção universal”.

The focus on female knowledge and education, expressed in the idea that human happiness can only be achieved when women possess the fruits of knowledge, echoes eugenic proposals that saw educated and healthy women as fundamental elements for the strengthening of the nation. This perspective also aligns with the European hygiene movement, which advocated for individual hygiene as a means of improving public health. Additionally, vegetarianism, by advocating a natural diet, aimed to prevent social problems such as alcoholism and syphilis, reflecting the principles of reformist eugenics⁷³.

In the thesis presented, Julieta Ribeiro praises the qualities of her sex, contrasting them with the “ferocity of war” and the “disordered ambition for power” — characteristics associated with the manhood — but does so without questioning a supposed essence or feminine nature, based on attributes like kindness, sensitivity, and compassion. Furthermore, her naturalist discourse, seemingly opposed to any form of barbarism and imbued with a civilizing morality, becomes starkly inconsistent with the glorification of colonial violence. At one point in her thesis, she writes:

In the expansion of nationality, men always need to seek the indispensable support of women. How can Portugal colonize the Alentejo plain and the vast African colonial empire? Certainly, by finding steadfast support from Portuguese women, who have so often demonstrated their patriotism and social value⁷⁴.

To conclude, we present another inconsistency, perhaps the most evident, present in the naturalist’s thesis: despite women being persistently identified as the primary agents of physical regeneration and social moralization, the ultimate desirable outcome was a “masculine, strong, and virtuous” Republic—masculine attributes—resulting from the ingenious conception of biologically perfect citizens⁷⁵.

⁷³ To understand the history of vegetarianism and its connections with eugenics and hygiene movements, see: BRAGA, Isabel Drumond. “Em Busca do Novo Éden no Século XX: os Portugueses e a Fundação de Colônias Naturistas no Brasil” In *História, Ciências, Saúde - Manguinhos*, Rio de Janeiro, V. 25, n. 3, pp. 659-678, 2018; BERNARDINO, Maria Gabriela; CARVALHO, Leonardo Dallacqua de. “Sociedade Vegetariana Brasileira: Tópicos sobre Eugenia, Moral e Higiene por Meio da Trajetória de Francisco Jaguaribe (1917-1923)” In *Outros Tempos: Pesquisa em Foco - História*, V. 21, n. 37, pp. 10-32, 2024.

⁷⁴ RIBEIRO, op. cit., p. 2. In Portuguese: “Na expansão da nacionalidade tem sempre o homem de solicitar o auxílio indispensável da mulher. Como poderá Portugal colonizar a planície do Alentejo e o vasto império colonial africano? De certo, encontrando apoio decidido na mulher portuguesa, que tantas vezes tem afirmado o seu patriotismo e o seu valor social”.

⁷⁵ Ibid, p. 3. In Portuguese: “máscula, forte e virtuosa”.

Educação dos Indígenas nas Colônias e suas Vantagens, by Domingas Lazary do Amaral (1883–1954)

We intentionally left the analysis of the thesis authored by Domingas do Amaral until the end, because its content reveals: I) that some advocates of women’s emancipation—including, evidently, some feminists—ended up entangled in discussions about biological determinism, falling into contradictions⁷⁶; II) and that some of these individuals, by participating in certain negotiations, contributed to the promotion of an apparently modern and hygienic domesticity that, in addition to keeping women in a social role related to their physiological function, seems to have been fundamental to the consolidation of a national identity that, in the Portuguese case, had colonialism as an important element.

Before we address the main points of the thesis, we need to contextualize it: simultaneously with the implementation of new republican legislation, which, among other aspects, defined the rules of colonial administration and established the legal status of so-called indigenous people, there was a prevalent “modern colonialist ideology, based on the work of the Geographical Society [...] and which spread throughout Portuguese society”⁷⁷. José Luís García, a scholar of the intellectual output of journalist and anti-colonial activist Mário Domingues⁷⁸, argued that the fundamental vectors of this

⁷⁶ Using a definition of feminism— “the resistance of women to accept roles, social, economic, political, ideological situations, and psychological characteristics that are based on the existence of a hierarchy between men and women, from which there is discrimination against women”—Lélia Gonzalez proposes to replace the terms “men” and “women” with “whites” and “blacks”, respectively, to achieve a good definition of the anti-racist struggle. She explains that this correspondence in meaning occurs because both racism and sexism stem from biological differences to establish themselves as ideologies of domination. GONZALEZ, op. cit., p. 55. In Portuguese: “resistência das mulheres em aceitar papéis, situações sociais, econômicas, políticas, ideológicas e características psicológicas que tenham como fundamento a existência de uma hierarquia entre homens e mulheres, a partir da qual a mulher é discriminada”. Recall that, in commenting on Brazão’s thesis, Domingas Lazary argued that “exceptional measures based on the differentiation of the sexes are inequitable and infringe upon individual freedom”. BRAZÃO, op. cit., O Primeiro Congresso Feminista..., p. 181. In Portuguese: “medidas de caráter excepcional baseadas na diferenciação dos sexos são iníquas e atentatórias da liberdade individual”.

⁷⁷ DOMINGUES, Mário. *A Afirmação Negra e a Questão Colonial. Textos, 1919-1928*. Lisboa: Tinta da China, 2022, p. 51. In Portuguese: “ideologia colonialista moderna, baseada nos trabalhos da Sociedade de Geografia [...] e que se disseminou por toda a sociedade portuguesa”.

⁷⁸ Mário Domingues (1899–1977) was a journalist, a columnist, a translator, and a writer who advocated for black empowerment and anti-colonialism. He and Domingas do Amaral share common identity elements: both were born in colonial territories—he in São Tomé and Príncipe, and she in Angola; in addition, they were both children of African mothers and Portuguese fathers. See: ROLDÃO, Cristina et al. *Tribuna Negra: Origens do Movimento Negro em Portugal (1911-1933)*. Lisboa: Orfeu Negro, 2023, p. 127. As a “mixed-race” individual, it is likely that Domingas do Amaral have occupied different positions on the power hierarchy of human relations: superior to the indigenous people of the colonies, and, at the same time, insufficiently

ideological construction “were the idea of the civilizing colonial vocation of the Portuguese people, altruistically carried out towards the Africans, and the humanitarian paternalism towards blacks”⁷⁹.

“Resulting from her experience as an educator in Angola”⁸⁰, Domingas do Amaral’s thesis advocates for an education project for the indigenous peoples of the Portuguese colonies led by a well-prepared contingent that could serve as a good example to the colonized. For this reason, the educator, in the conclusions of her thesis, calls for the Depósito Geral de Degredados de Angola [General Deposit of Exiles in Angola] to be replaced by agricultural colonies situated away from Luanda. In line with this modern colonialist ideology, Amaral urges that soldiers should not be sent to subdue the colonized, as they, instead of being called to reason

[...] with deadly weapons that devastate their huts, excite their warrior instincts, and at the same time, while the sword seemingly annihilates them, it fosters a new feeling of revenge, which sooner or later becomes a terrible weapon against its victor. This is a matter of history. The Motherland should seek to gain a friend in every indigenous person, not an enemy whose unleashed wrath it must fear⁸¹.

Except for a brief part of the thesis where she describes, almost in the manner of a European traveler or Jesuit of the 16th and 17th centuries, the excessive indolence of the indigenous people⁸², Domingas do Amaral pays little attention to the colonized women. Regarding them, she states that despite working harder than men – “The indigenous mother is solely

white to, for example, deal with other themes recurrently discussed among feminists in the metropolis.

⁷⁹ DOMINGUES, op. cit., p. 51. In Portuguese: “foram a ideia da vocação colonial civilizadora dos portugueses, altruisticamente levada aos africanos, e o paternalismo humanitário em relação aos negros”.

⁸⁰ CASTRO, Zília Osório de; ESTEVES, João. *Dicionário no Feminino (Séculos XIX-XX)*. Lisboa: Livros Horizonte, 2005, p. 283. In Portuguese: “Resultado da vivência de educadora em Angola”.

⁸¹ AMARAL, Domingas Lazary. *Educação dos Indígenas nas Colônias e suas Vantagens*. Lisboa: Tip. da Casa Garrett, 1924, pp. 13-14. In Portuguese: “[...] com arma mortífera que arrasa as suas cubatas, excitam o seu instinto guerreiro, e ao mesmo tempo que a espada, aparentemente o aniquila vai dando vida a um novo sentimento de vingança, que, cedo ou tarde, se torna em arma terrível contra o seu vencedor. Isto é da História. A Mãe Pátria deve procurar conquistar um amigo em cada indígena, e não um inimigo de quem tenha a temer as iras desencadeadas”.

⁸² bell hooks draw attention to this: “When discussing black people, the focus often falls on black men; when discussing women, the focus tends to be on white women. This is particularly evident in the vast corpus of feminist literature”, hooks, bell. *Não Serei eu Mulher?*. Lisboa: Orfeu Negro, 2018, p. 26. In Portuguese: “Quando se fala de gentes negras, a atenção tende a recair nos *homens* negros; quando se fala de mulheres, a atenção tende a recair nas mulheres *brancas*. Isto é particularmente flagrante no vasto corpus da literatura feminista”.

responsible for supporting her sometimes numerous offspring” — they do everything “without the slightest shadow of criteria”⁸³. Besides, differences related to family organization, the author reveals other distinctions, always establishing hierarchies. For example, she makes distinctions between those who do domestic work and those who give orders, and between the clean and the dirty: “[...] I remember, we would talk about the struggle we had to endure to ensure that the servants dried the dishes with appropriate towels: they would use the first rag, dirty and tattered, that they came across on the floor”⁸⁴.

In *Couro Imperial* [Imperial Leather], Anne McClintock proposes the development of a social history of soap—until then obliterated due to its association with the female domain of domesticity—in order to reflect on the domestic value of women in industrial capitalism. Studying the English case, she observed that, in the last decade of the 19th century, soap sales surged, while “advertising emerged as a central cultural form of mercantile capitalism”⁸⁵. In one of the advertisements analyzed by McClintock, from the “Pears Soap” brand, divided into two parts and featuring two boys, a bar of soap, and a mirror, the upper part shows a white boy, dressed in a white apron, offering a bar of soap to a black boy who, from within a bathtub, looks at the water in fear. In the lower part of the advertisement, the black boy is outside the bathtub, with his genitalia covered by a white towel, and he looks in a mirror held by the other character: his face, the place of identity, remains black, but the rest of his body has changed color, becoming white. According to McClintock’s interpretation,

The white boy appears as the agent of history and the male heir of progress, showing the reflection of his “inferior” brother in the European mirror of self-awareness. In the Victorian mirror, the black boy witnesses his predetermined fate of imperial metamorphosis but remains a passive racial hybrid, part white and part black, brought to the brink of civilization by the twin mercantile fetishes of soap and mirror⁸⁶.

⁸³ AMARAL, op. cit., p. 11. In Portuguese: “À mãe indígena cabe exclusivamente o pesado encargo de sustentar a sua, por vezes, numerosa prole”; “sem a mais leve sombra de critério”.

⁸⁴ Ibid., p. 12. In Portuguese: “[...] lembro-me, íamos dizendo da luta que tínhamos que sustentar para conseguir, das criadas, que enxugassem a louça às toalhas competentes: sendo apropriado para elas, o primeiro farrapo sujo e esburacado que se lhe deparava no chão”.

⁸⁵ MCCLINTOCK, op. cit., p. 311. In Portuguese: “propaganda surgira como forma cultural central do capitalismo mercantil”.

⁸⁶ Ibid., p. 317. In Portuguese: “O menino branco aparece [...] como agente da história e o herdeiro masculino

In her thesis, Domingas do Amaral describes the habits of Africans who, she claims, lived in a “complete state of primitive eras”:

They live in a filthy hut, without light, without air, and without the slightest comfort, even for the most basic needs [...]. Everything is in a revolting promiscuity; and they are absolutely unaware of even the most rudimentary rules of hygiene. [...] For clothing, the indigenous person wears nothing; and instead of the fig leaf with which old Adam from the Bible covered himself after sinning, the black person wears a rag or the skin of the last deer they killed!⁸⁷

It is true that, from such a report, the author sheds light on the incompetence of the secular Portuguese colonial enterprise (or on the resistance of African peoples), but what interests us is to understand and reflect, as McClintock does, on what were the agents and mechanisms essential to imperialism, or why a thesis like that of Domingas do Amaral, which did not even attempt to address the specifics of colonized women, found space and relevance in an essentially feminist congress. In this sense, a social history of soap, in Portugal, seems useful to us.

Domingas do Amaral, in advocating for an educational project for the indigenous peoples of the Portuguese colonies, reflects a mindset that not only seeks domination but also a supposed “civilization” of the colonized. However, when we analyze this issue through the ideas of anthropologist Ann Laura Stoler, we see that this “civilization” is not merely an educational effort but also a way to exert colonial power over all spheres of the lives of the dominated populations, including their sexual practices and racial identities. Stoler argues that the discursive management of these activities, between colonizer and colonized, is crucial for maintaining the “colonial order of things”⁸⁸. Additionally, whiteness and its preservation, as exemplified in soap advertisements, are fundamental elements of colonial power, not only as

do progresso, mostrando o reflexo de seu irmão “inferior” no espelho europeu da autoconsciência. No espelho vitoriano, o menino negro testemunha seu destino predeterminado de metamorfose imperial, mas continua um híbrido racial passivo, parte branco, parte negro, levado à beira da civilização pelos fetiches mercantis gêmeos do sabão e do espelho”.

⁸⁷ AMARAL, op. cit., p. 9. In Portuguese: “em completo estado das primitivas eras”; “Tem por habitação uma cubata infecta, sem luz, sem ar, sem o menor conforto, mesmo para as mais exíguas necessidades [...]. Vive tudo numa promiscuidade revoltante; e ele desconhece, em absoluto, as mais rudimentares regras de higiene. [...] Por vestuário, usa o indígena, o corpo nu; e em vez da parra com que se cobriu o velho pai Adão da Bíblia, depois de haver pecado, o negro traz um farrapo ou a pele da última corça que matou!”.

⁸⁸ STOLER, Ann Laura. *Race and the Education of Desire: Foucault’s History of Sexuality and the Colonial Order of Things*. Durham: Duke University Press, 1995, p. 5. In Portuguese: “ordem colonial das coisas”.

part of bourgeois identity but also as expressions of European biopower. Racial and sexual differences are maintained and reinforced through a “grammar of difference” that is symbolic, material, and discursive⁸⁹. Therefore, we can see that colonial education is embedded within a broader context of power and domination, where the management of social practices is an integral part of the imperialist project.

Conclusion

In 1872, *Harper's Weekly* published a cartoon by Thomas Nast: in the foreground, a demonic female figure holds a sign that reads “Be saved by free love”; she looks back towards another female figure in the background, who struggles up a rocky mountain carrying a drunk man and two small children on her back⁹⁰. The image is accompanied by the text: “GET THEE BEHIND ME, (MRS.) SATAN! – [see page 143]. Wife (with heavy burden) ‘I’d rather travel the hardest path of matrimony than follow your footsteps’”.

Victoria Woodhull, cartoon, by Thomas Nast.

⁸⁹ Ibid., pp. 39-41. In Portuguese: “gramática da diferença”.

⁹⁰ GET THEE BEHIND ME, (MRS.) SATAN!, *Harper's Weekly*, V. XVI, n. 790, 1872, p. 140.

The purpose of the publication, according to a note from the newspaper itself (“page 143”), was to convey a moral lesson to those who might be tempted to accept the pernicious doctrines of the free love movement⁹¹. The note further explains that the satanic figure, “Mrs.,” was inspired by a prominent leader who advocated for women’s rights and was traveling across the United States giving lectures at the time. In addition to supporting divorce, “Mrs. Satan”, according to *Harper’s Weekly*, declared in these meetings her choice for free love: “Yes, I am a free-lover. I have an inalienable, constitutional, and natural right to love whom I may; to love as long or as short a period as I can; to change that love every day if I please”⁹². In response to such a stance, the author of the note questioned: “If this mischievous talk does not emanate from Satan, whence does it come?”⁹³.

Thomas Nast’s cartoon is titled “Victoria Woodhull, Caricature”—the “Satan” figure, who was also portrayed in the Brazilian press as a speaker advocating before an audience largely composed of women that marriage was a form of slavery^{94 95}. We revisit this caricature, published approximately half a century before the *Primeiro Congresso Feminista e de Educação* because it can visually highlight and encapsulate a long-term project that materialized, for example, in several of the theses defended in Lisbon and discussed here. This project was based on a superficial social valorization of women willing to take on, according to the directives of the “masters of knowledge”, the heavy burden of family life. It is worth noting that the post-First World War context highlighted the radicalization of old institutions in response to the development of new forms of organization and understanding of the world, exemplified by the Russian Revolution and anti-colonial movements. Thus, the project of female emancipation based on deeper transformations—sketched at least since the 1890s in Portugal and focused, for example, on women’s financial emancipation through socially valued work, which was *sine qua non* to obtaining other freedoms—was replaced, at least within institutionalized feminism, by a retrogressive perspective where women, despite a modern facade, remained bound to their merely biological condition.

⁹¹ Ibid., p. 143.

⁹² Ibid.

⁹³ Ibid.

⁹⁴ Sem título, *Diário de Notícias*, Ano III, nº 416. p. 3, 1872.

⁹⁵ Victoria Woodhull (1838–1927) was the first woman to run for President of the United States and the first female stockbroker on Wall Street. See: BRANDMAN, Mariana. “Victoria Woodhull” In *National Women’s History Museum*, 2022. Available in: <www.womenshistory.org/education-resources/biographies/victoria-woodhull>. Last consulted June 2024.

In the European case, accounting for the particularities of each country, while the white man took on the burden of the neocolonial venture “No tawdry rule of kings / But toil of serf and sweeper — / The tale of common things”⁹⁶, the white woman, his complement, bore the burden of civilizing, first, the family (the micro-State), and then the other “children”, namely, minors in the metropolis and indigenous peoples in the colonies. And how could they do this? Through the “soap”, this also a metaphorical tool used to refer to hygienic and eugenic techniques and practices. In a context marked by the increasing importance given to the influence of the environment, especially concerning acquired characteristics, the female role was considered crucial in forming a national state of “strong race”. Women, considered guardians of morality and family health, were encouraged to adopt rigorous hygienic practices and to educate their children according to these principles, reinforcing the idea that national regeneration began at home. This approach elevated women’s civic responsibility, seemingly removing them from the position of mere wards and giving them an active role in building a healthy nation.

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To create perfect citizens for a masculine, strong, and virtuous Republic: the First National...

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Demolishing paradigms of Brazilian mental health: the Barbacena Psychiatric Hospital and its new identity as a museum¹

Demolindo paradigmas da saúde mental brasileira: o Hospital Psiquiátrico de Barbacena e sua nova identidade como museu

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Abstract

This article examines the evolution of psychiatry in the 19th and the 20th centuries. It emphasizes treatment and isolation of individuals considered mentally ill. The aim is to understand how the social construction of madness and isolation practices reflect structures of power and exclusion. It also examines the evolution of psychiatric institutions, and the reforms aimed at humanizing the treatment of the mentally ill. The work culminates with an analysis of the Colônia Psychiatric Hospital in Barbacena, Minas Gerais, Brazil, highlighting the abuses and dehumanization that occurred, using the concept of *Dark Heritage* to explore how the memory of horrors can promote awareness and social justice. The Museum of Madness, established in the former Colônia, exemplifies this concept, transforming a place of suffering into a space of learning and memory. Methodologically, this investigation is based on bibliographic and qualitative research, in addition to incorporating recent studies on the history of psychiatry.

Keywords: Evolution of Psychiatry. Social Construction of Madness. *Dark Heritage*. Psychiatric Hospital Colony. Barbacena.

Resumo

O artigo analisa a evolução da psiquiatria nos séculos XIX e XX, com ênfase no tratamento e isolamento de indivíduos considerados mentalmente alienados. O objetivo é compreender como a construção social da loucura e as práticas de isolamento refletem estruturas de poder e exclusão. Examina-se também a evolução das instituições psiquiátricas e as reformas destinadas a humanizar o tratamento dos doentes mentais. O trabalho culmina com uma análise do

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Hospital Psiquiátrico Colônia, em Barbacena, Minas Gerais, Brasil, destacando os abusos e a desumanização ocorridos, utilizando o conceito de *Dark Heritage* para explorar como a memória dos horrores pode promover conscientização e justiça social. O Museu da Loucura, estabelecido no antigo Colônia, exemplifica o referido conceito, transformando um local de sofrimento em um espaço de aprendizado e memória. Metodologicamente, esta investigação se baseia em pesquisa bibliográfica e qualitativa, além de incorporar estudos recentes sobre a história da psiquiatria.

Palavras-Chave: Evolução da Psiquiatria. Construção Social da Loucura. *Dark Heritage*. Hospital Psiquiátrico Colônia. Barbacena.

Introduction

The aim of this study is to analyse the evolution of psychiatry in the 19th and 20th centuries, focusing on the treatment and isolation of individuals considered mentally ill. At the beginning of this period, people with mental disorders were often perceived as dangerous or out of control, and institutionalization was a common practice to regularize their condition. This approach revealed a utilitarian vision, in which society benefited from the isolation of these individuals, who, in turn, were deprived of freedom due to the social and economic order.

The research aims to understand how the social construction of madness and the isolation practices of mentally ill patients reflect structures of power and exclusion. In addition, it analyses the evolution of psychiatric institutions and the reforms that aimed to make the treatment of mentally ill patients more humane. The transition to the 20th century brought new criticisms and movements for change, such as antipsychiatry and Democratic Psychiatry, which questioned traditional methods and proposed more inclusive and compassionate approaches.

The historical trajectory ends with an analysis of a Brazilian case, focusing on the Colônia Psychiatric Hospital in Barbacena, Minas Gerais, Brazil. This hospital is an example of the abuse and dehumanization suffered by patients admitted to psychiatric institutions. The work is also connected to the concept of *Dark Heritage*, analysing how the memory of the horrors committed in institutions such as Colônia can be preserved and used to promote awareness and social justice. The analysis of the Colônia Psychiatric Hospital, from this perspective, allows us to reflect on how these spots can be reconfigured as spots of memory and education, contributing to a more

conscious and empathetic society. The Museum of Madness, located in the former Colônia, is an example of *Dark Heritage*, by transforming a place of pain into a tool for learning and memorialization.

Methodologically, we opted for bibliographical and qualitative research, in addition to using recent studies on the history of psychiatry. Qualitative analysis provides a more profound understanding of the social, cultural and institutional dynamics that shaped the treatment of patients in the 19th and 20th centuries.

From Pinel to Basaglia: The Development of Psychiatry and the Transformation of Treatment Models

The emergence of psychiatry as a scientific subject occurred during the 19th century. Initially, it was characterized by questions about the representation of individuals with mental disorders as dangerous or uncontrolled. Commitment regularized a state of affairs, since it was not possible to deprive someone who did not have freedom. For society, there were only benefits, since the individual remained ignorant, while the community profited both socially and economically². However, with the conception of madness as a problem of a social nature, it began to be recognized and studied as a pathological condition.

These recurrences become more evident from Michel Foucault's analysis, which goes back to the "structure of exclusion". This concept was established at the time when leprosariums began to be emptied at the end of the Middle Ages, considered dark places full of "rites"³. At that time, only those considered "undesirable madmen", such as drunkards and debauchees, were confined on ships. For this reason, Foucault sought in his studies to identify the moment when madness began to be seen as a pathology. It is worth remembering that the history of madness was the object of study of his doctoral thesis, defended in 1961 and published a few months later with its original title, *História da Loucura: Na Idade Clássica*⁴.

According to Foucault, the era of mass internment, which occurred throughout the 19th century, represents a crucial point in which madness was

² PEREIRA, Ana Leonor. "A institucionalização da loucura em Portugal" In Revista Crítica de Ciências Sociais, v. 21, pp. 85-100, 1986.

³ FOUCAULT, Michel. *História da Loucura: Na Idade Clássica*. São Paulo: Perspectiva, 2017 [1972].

⁴ FREITAS, Fernando Ferreira Pinto de. "A história da psiquiatria não contada por Foucault" In *História, Ciências, Saúde - Manguinhos*, Rio de Janeiro, v. 11, n. 1, pp. 75-91, 2004, p. 77.

considered part of the social spectrum, associated with poverty, incapacity for work and difficulty in community integration. In this context, madness emerged as an urban problem, standing out from other social conditions. This period witnessed a significant change: while poverty was no longer automatically confined, madness became an object of incarceration. At the end of the 18th century and during the 19th century, asylums emerged, designed for therapeutic purposes⁵.

Madness is then conceptualized as “mental alienation,” as proposed by Philippe Pinel, integrating itself into the medical domain. In France, Pinel frees the inmates of Bicêtre from their chains, advocating for their reeducation through social and more, especially, moral control⁶. In England, simultaneously with Pinel’s efforts, Samuel Tuke stands out as a central figure in mental health reform, promoting the recovery of the disease, especially women, in rural settings free from physical restraints such as bars and chains. A notable example is the Ticehurst House Asylum in East Sussex, an elite establishment that received some of the most affluent patients in the 19th century of the Victorian society (Figure 1). However, Pinel’s therapeutic method involved procedures such as cold water baths (Figure 2) and the use of straitjackets, which, according to Foucault, only perpetuated the notion of judgment and punishment in the context of the patients⁷.

⁵ See also: FOUCAULT, Michel. *Problematização do sujeito: Psicologia, psiquiatria, psicanálise (Ditos e Escritos, Vol. I)*. Rio de Janeiro: Forense, 2010.

⁶ In 1793, during his time at the Bicêtre Asylum, Pinel implemented the groundbreaking decision to remove the chains that restrained the inmates. This emblematic gesture represented a major transformation in the approach to mental health, promoting a more humanitarian and less punitive perspective towards psychiatric patients. The reform led by Pinel was decisive in the development of more compassionate and therapeutic practices in the treatment of the mentally ill, leaving a significant impact on the evolution of modern psychiatry. See: PEREIRA, Mario Eduardo Costa. “Pinel - a mania, o tratamento moral e os inícios da psiquiatria contemporânea” In *Revista Latinoamericana de Psicopatologia Fundamental*, v. 7, n. 4, pp. 113-116, 2004.

⁷ FOUCAULT, op. cit., “História da Loucura...”, pp. 55-57; 97-99.

Figure 1: Ticehurst House Asylum.

Source: Wellcome Collection.

Figure 2: The shower, a method to “calm down” violent lunatics.

Source: Wellcome Collection.

At that time, prognoses indicated that the best option would be to keep the “mad” in an asylum, where they would be “safe”. This place would

function as a place for supervision and work, the last one being considered the main method of treatment. Work was seen as an element that dignifies the human being, converting the insane into a useful and obedient individual. This Pinelian model, based on the triad of isolate/know/treat, in which the hospital appears as the epicenter of medical power and knowledge, continues to arouse both criticism and defense nowadays.

Western psychiatric hospitals, characterized by long-term or full-time admissions, were overcrowded and understaffed in the 1950s to meet demand. Furthermore, these institutions were frequently the target of allegations of abuse. Criticism of this model led to significant reforms in these sector. Prominent among the reformers were those who advocated internal restructuring of institutions to make them truly therapeutic, as demonstrated by the adoption of the therapeutic community in England, and institutional psychotherapy in France⁸. Other groups proposed the expansion of psychiatry into the public sphere, promoting community psychiatry, which sought to integrate mental health care into the community rather than isolating them in institutions. At the same time, advocates emerged for a radical break with the established psychiatric model. Among these, the supporters of antipsychiatry, stood out a movement that began in England in the 1960s and criticized the repressive and dehumanizing nature of traditional psychiatric treatments⁹. In addition, there were the proponents of Democratic Psychiatry, led by the Italian Franco Basaglia, who advocated a more humanistic and liberating approach to the treatment of mental disorders, emphasizing the deinstitutionalization and social reintegration of patients¹⁰.

These changes and movements reflect a period of intense debate and transformation in the approach to mental health, marked by a constant search for more effective and humane methods of treatment¹¹. The changes implemented during this period were also influenced by the ideas of Michel

⁸ See: PASSOS, Izabel Friche. "Duas versões históricas para a Psicoterapia Institucional" In *Cadernos Brasileiros de Saúde Mental*, v.4 , n. 9, pp. 21-32, 2012; COUTO, Richard; ALBERTI, Sonia. "Breve história da Reforma Psiquiátrica para uma melhor compreensão da questão atual" In *Saúde em Debate*, v. 32, pp. 49-59, 2008.

⁹ See: COOPER, David. *Psiquiatria e anti-psiquiatria*. Rio de Janeiro: Zahar, 1970; SPOHR, Bianca; SCHNEIDER Daniela Ribeiro. "Bases epistemológicas da antipsiquiatria: a influência do Existencialismo de Sartre" In *Revista Abordagem Gestáltica*, v. 15 n. 2, pp. 115-125, 2009.

¹⁰ See: BASAGLIA, Franco. *A instituição negada: relato de um hospital psiquiátrico*. Rio de Janeiro: Graal, 1985.

¹¹ BASAGLIA, op. cit.; JUNQUEIRA, Anamélia Maria Guimarães; CARNIEL, Isabel Cristina. "Olhares sobre a loucura: os grupos na experiência de Gorizia" In *Revista da SPAGESP*, v. 13, n. 2, pp. 12-22, 2012.

Foucault, who in his works, such as *História da loucura...*, criticized the medicalization and incarceration of the mentally ill, proposing a reflection on the mechanisms of power and social exclusion present in psychiatric practices. These reform and criticism movements contributed to the continuous evolution of psychiatry, promoting the need for a more inclusive and compassionate mental health system.

Franco Basaglia's proposal was not limited to the abolition of mental hospitals in Italy, a process that began in 1973, but also involved the deconstruction of psychiatric knowledge, practices and discourses. He argued that institutions such as the family, schools, prisons and mental hospitals are "institutions of violence". According to Basaglia, "paternal authority is oppressive and arbitrary; schools are based on blackmail and threats; exploiters exploit the workers; mental hospitals destroy people with mental illness"¹². He also questioned clinical diagnoses, identifying in them a "deep discriminatory meaning". He observed that a rich schizophrenic patient admitted to a private clinic received a different prognosis than a poor schizophrenic one and sent to a psychiatric hospital. The rich patient has never been decontextualized or completely separated from his reality, facilitating his reintegration into society. On the other hand, the poor already suffered from the violence of the social system, which "pushes them out of production, to the margins of associative life, until they are locked up within the walls of the hospital"¹³.

For him, the core of the problem did not lie in the disease itself, but in the dynamics established around it. The rejection of the asylum model implied not only the rejection of any nosological classification, but also the need to restore the patient's freedom, understood as the core part of therapy. Upon assuming the direction of the Provincial Psychiatric Hospital of Gorizia in 1961, Basaglia introduced the concept of therapeutic community, influenced by the ideas of the British David Cooper and Ronald Laing¹⁴. He aimed to transform the asylum into a true treatment hospital, a transitory phase in the healing process, which would eventually be overcome and replaced by an alternative system of services. According to Izabel Passos, these changes were considered bold and radically innovative by those who still defended the paradigms of an old-fashioned asylum psychiatry. These

¹² BASAGLIA, Franco. "As instituições da violência" In AMARANTE, Paulo (Org.). Escritos selecionados em saúde mental e reforma psiquiátrica. Rio de Janeiro: Garamond, pp. 91-149, 2005, p. 91.

¹³ Ibid.

¹⁴ COOPER, op. cit.; LAING, Ronald David. *The Politics of Experience*. New York: Pantheon Books, 1967.

were the true elements of disturbance in the society. The exclusion of the insane from the world of the sane only confirmed and sanctioned the validity of the norms established by society itself¹⁵.

The Italian Parliament enacted Law No. 180, known as the Basaglia Law, which represented a significant milestone in the history of mental health¹⁶. This legislation included mental illness into the scope of health legislation, removing it from the connotation of particular dangerousness, as advocated by the advocates of Democratic Psychiatry. A crucial step forward was the regulation of compulsory treatment, which was no longer limited to hospitalization, allowing such treatment to be carried out in community services rather than in psychiatric hospitals. Consequently, these hospitals were gradually decommissioned. In addition, the law eliminated custody measures over the person and their assets, and restored the constitutional right to vote for patients with mental disorders.

In the context of sectoral psychiatry, which began in France in 1945 and was officially incorporated as a mental health policy in 1960, the main focus was on treating patients within their own community. Multidisciplinary teams, composed of psychiatrists, psychologists, nurses and social workers, were created to prevent and treat mental disorders with no need for confinement. The hospital began to play a secondary role, only to provide treatment assistance. The French reform aimed to replace the exclusionary and isolationist model, which was based on repression, with a model that promoted the emancipation of mental patients and their reintegration into society¹⁷. These reforms reflect a paradigmatic shift in the approach to mental health, where the focus shifted from institutionalization and confinement to community integration and patient autonomy. This new paradigm sought not only to treat mental disorders, but also to combat the stigma and marginalization associated with these conditions, promoting a more humanistic and inclusive approach.

¹⁵ PASSOS, Izabel C. Friche. Reforma psiquiátrica: as experiências francesa e italiana. Rio de Janeiro: Ed. da Fiocruz, 2009.

¹⁶ ITÁLIA. Legge 13 maggio 1978, n. 180. Accertamenti e trattamenti sanitari volontari e obbligatori. Gazzetta Ufficiale, Roma, n. 133, 16 maio 1978.

¹⁷ PASSOS, op. cit., Duas versões históricas para a Psicoterapia Institucional, 2008.

Psychiatric Hospitals in Brazil

In the 19th century, “madness” was considered as an integral part of social coexistence, but it gradually came to be seen as a manifestation of disorder and disturbance of collective peace. During this period, madness began to be appropriated by religious discourse¹⁸. The origins of mental hygiene are deeply rooted among theorists of Psychiatry, and this current became one of the main themes in intellectual circles. The terms eugenics, initially introduced by anthropologists and historians, became part of Brazilian culture in the early 20th century, before being widely adopted by doctors¹⁹.

Individuals considered insane were progressively removed from society and confined to the basements of hospitals or public prisons. However, for doctors at that time, this approach did not effectively solve the problem of insanity. Segregation, combined with poor hygiene and the absence of adequate physical and moral treatment, made the cure practically impossible. During the First Republic, the concept of insanity was detached from religious discourse and adopted by scientific medical-psychiatric discourses. This changing allowed inhumane approaches to be replaced by humanitarian principles, implementing the process of medicalization of insanity and its reconceptualization as a mental illness²⁰. As a result, there was an expansion of the public network of psychiatric hospitals. Isolation in these institutions was justified by the need to separate the individual from the supposed causes of the illness, mainly the family, and by the viability of effective therapeutic interventions, believing that the cure would not be possible without this isolation.

In Brazil, psychiatric hospitals emerged as a response to this need to deal with mental disorders from a predominantly medical and segregationist perspective. Influenced by the European model of asylum treatment, these institutions sought to isolate individuals considered “insane” from society. Despite this, it is essential to preserve memory and value the fight against oblivion. It is not only the effort of memory that is important, but mainly the fear of negligence²¹. So that the past is not forgotten in

¹⁸ VECHI, Luís Gustavo. “Introgenia e exclusão social: a loucura como objeto do discurso científico no Brasil” In Estudos de Psicologia, v. 9, n. 3, 2004, pp. 489-495.

¹⁹ COSTA, Jurandir Freire. História da Psiquiatria no Brasil. Ed. Garamond Ltda. 2007.

²⁰ FONTE, Eliane Maria Monteiro da. “Da institucionalização da loucura à reforma psiquiátrica: as sete vidas da agenda pública em saúde mental no Brasil” In Estudos de Sociologia, v. 1, n. 18, 2012.

²¹ See: RICOEUR, Paul. A memória, a história, o esquecimento. Campinas: Editora da Unicamp, 2007.

the present, it is essential that the events that occurred are systematized and analyzed²². Therefore, from now on, this study aims to highlight the importance of the historical analysis of the Barbacena Psychiatric Hospital, where the experiences of patients left deep scars, compared to the Nazi concentration camps traumas. Opened on October 12, 1903, the hospital was one of the seven psychiatric establishments built in the city and became known as the “Brazilian Holocaust”.

The Colony of the “crazy”

The Colônia Psychiatric Hospital, located in Barbacena, Minas Gerais, Brazil, represents a dark and disturbing chapter in the country’s history. Established in 1903 as part of a group of psychiatric institutions in the city, Colônia over the years transformed from a treatment center for mental disorders into a place of despair and anguish for thousands of people. The founding of Colônia marked the beginning of an era of indescribable suffering for those interned in its facilities. Over the decades, the hospital became a symbol of inhumanity, where patients were often subject to subhuman conditions and brutal treatments. Such intensity is essential to produce studies on the events that occurred at Colônia, in addition to analyzing the crucial role of dissonant memories in preserving history and promoting a more empathetic and just society²³.

²² See: FERRO, Marc. *A Cegueira – Uma Outra História do Nosso Mundo. Cem anos de guerra, política e religião*. Lisboa: Cavalo de Ferro, 2017.

²³ Regarding dissonant memories, see: FESTINGER, Leon. *A theory of cognitive dissonance*. Stanford: University Press, 1957.

Figure 3: Colônia Psychiatric Hospital, opened in 1903, in the mining town of Barbacena.

Archive: Minas Gerais Public Collection.

By discussing the role of dissonant memories, we propose a reflection on how knowledge and awareness of the horrors of the past can inform present actions and shape a more inclusive and compassionate future. Recognizing the importance of confronting the darkest aspects of our collective history, it is essential to be able to learn with the mistakes from the past and work together to create a society where everyone is treated with dignity and respect. By confronting our collective past, we can strive to build a future in which humanity and compassion are the pillars of our existence. This approach is corroborated by historical studies that highlight the relevance of preserving memory for the construction of more just and humane societies²⁴.

Since its founding in the early 20th century, the Colônia Psychiatric Hospital has demonstrated a worrying pattern of arbitrary admissions, in which approximately 70% of patients did not present symptoms of mental illness and were simply categorized as undesirable by society²⁵. The influence of eugenic theories deeply permeated the medical and

²⁴ RICOEUR, op. cit.; IRON, op. cit.

²⁵ ARBEX, Daniela. *Holocausto Brasileiro: Vida, Genocídio e 60 Mil Mortes no Maior Hospício do Brasil*.

social practices to be adopted at the hospital. The notion of social cleansing and purification of humanity fostered the idea that individuals considered “undesirable” should be segregated and subjected to inhumane treatment²⁶. This ideology, widely disseminated at that time, justified the abuses committed at the Colônia and perpetuated in a cycle of discrimination and suffering.

Overcrowding was a chronic condition at the Colony, further exacerbating the already precarious living conditions of the patients. Initially designed to hold a limited number of people, the hospital quickly found itself overwhelmed, resulting in unsanitary conditions, lack of proper hygiene, and a shortage of medical resources. This overcrowding contributed significantly to the physical and psychological deterioration of inmates, perpetuating a cycle of suffering and despair²⁷.

Furthermore, the lack of strict medical criteria for admissions made the Colony a destination for those deemed inconvenient to society but not necessarily mentally ill. Individuals marginalized by their sexual orientation, socioeconomic status, race, or political views were often admitted to the hospital, deprived of their freedom, and subject to a regime of terror and oppression²⁸. This phenomenon can be understood within what Foucault called the “structure of exclusion,” as mentioned earlier, a concept that highlights how certain populations are systematically marginalized and isolated by society²⁹.

São Paulo: Geração Editorial, 2013.

²⁶ See: SOUZA, Vanderlei Sebastião de. Renato Kehl e a eugenia no Brasil: ciência, raça e nação no período entreguerras. Guarapuava: Unicentro, 2019.

²⁷ “In 1930, with the overcrowding of the unit, a story of extermination began to be drawn. Thirty years later, there were 5 thousand patients in a place initially designed for 200. The replacement of beds with grass was then officially suggested by the head of the Department of Neuropsychiatric Assistance of Minas Gerais, José Consenso Filho, as an alternative to the excess of people. The intention was clear: to save space in the pavilions to fit more and more unfortunate people”. ARBEX, op. cit., pp. 21-22.

²⁸ Ibid.

²⁹ FOUCAULT, op. cit., História da loucura...

Figure 4: Patients “incarcerated” in Colônia.

Photo: Luiz Alfredo (1961), for the magazine “O Cruzeiro” [the Cruise].

The combination of these factors created an environment where suffering and despair were endemic. Patients at the Colony faced not only the hardships inherent in their mental conditions, but also institutional cruelty and neglect. Their voices were silenced and their lives devalued, as society continued to perpetuate the myth of madness and marginalize those who did not fit in its established norms.

When examining the cruel reality of the Colônia Psychiatric Hospital, it is possible to perceive the complexity of the social and medical issues that contributed to its tragic history. Understanding the depth of suffering experienced by those who passed through its doors raises the need to recognize the importance of preserving these dissonant memories and confronting the injustices of our collective past. Shock therapy, a controversial technique, became routine practice at the Colônia, highlighting the lack of scruples and medical ethics that permeated psychiatric institutions at that time. Applied indiscriminately and often without anesthesia or adequate care, this form of treatment resulted in more suffering than healing for patients. Disturbing accounts of abuse include cases of death and severe fractures resulting from these brutal procedures, casting an even darker shadow over the already

sinister environment of the hospital. In addition to shock therapy, other forms of abuse were commonplace at the hospital³⁰. In addition to shock therapy, other forms of abuse were commonplace at the hospital. Hunger and thirst were constant realities for inmates, who often faced shortages of food and clean water. The hospital's unsanitary conditions, including a lack of basic sanitation and proper hygiene, contributed to the suffering and despair of patients, who were forced to live amid filth and decay³¹.

The Colony also became a center for illegal trafficking of bodies to medical schools, adding another dark side to its already tragic history. The bodies of deceased patients were often sold without the consent of their families, violating their dignity and privacy even after death. This inhumane practice not only violated the rights of the deceased, but also perpetuated the devaluation of patients' lives. As John Lennon and Malcolm Foley point out in their article entitled *Dark Tourism: The Attraction of Death and Disaster*, this dehumanization culminated in the commodification of human suffering³².

In short, the Colônia Psychiatric Hospital was a literal Hell on Earth, where patients were subject to a series of abuses and human rights violations. Shock therapy, lack of basic living conditions, and illegal trafficking of bodies are just a few examples of those horrors that occurred within its walls. Confronting this dark side of our collective history is essential to acknowledge the suffering of those who were affected, and to give voice to those who have been silenced until now.

Dark Heritage and the “Museum of Madness”

The inhumane conditions at the Cologne Psychiatric Hospital were finally brought to light by complaints and criticism from mental health activists and professionals. Notable among these whistleblowers was the aforementioned Italian psychiatrist Franco Basaglia, who compared the facility to a Nazi concentration camp³³. Basaglia, renowned for his role in psychiatric reform in Italy, visited the Cologne in 1979 and was deeply shocked

³⁰ ARBEX, op. cit.

³¹ Ibid.

³² LENNON, John; FOLEY, Malcolm. *Dark Tourism: The Attraction of Death and Disaster*. London-New York: Continuum, 2000.

³³ MATOS-DE-SOUZA, Rodrigo; MEDRADO, Ana Carolina Cerqueira. “Dos corpos como objeto: uma leitura pós-colonial do ‘Holocausto Brasileiro’” In *Saúde Debate*, v. 45, n. 128, pp. 164-177, 2021.

by the inhumane conditions and abuse to which patients were subject to, and denouncing them publicly³⁴.

Despite decades of neglect and abuse, Colônia was finally closed in the 1980s, ending a dark chapter in the history of mental health in Brazil³⁵. However, the hospital's legacy lives on in the memories of those who suffered its atrocities and in the public recognition of the impact of its existence. Today, the place has been transformed into a Museum of Madness [Museu da Loucura], representing an example of *Dark Heritage*, a heritage associated with suffering and pain, that is, places that bear a negative emotional burden due to the traumatic events that occurred there³⁶.

On August 16, 1996, the Colônia Psychiatric Hospital, which was known for its outrageous practices, such as cold showers used for torture, was restored as the Museum of Madness. This museum, which now opens its doors and rooms filled with memories to the public, symbolizes not only a new historical milestone, but also a significant discursive event. It is a reinterpretation of the past, a break with the dominant institutional discourse, and a connection between memory and the present.

The inauguration of the Museum of Madness is not only a historical milestone, but also a painful but necessary archive that plays a crucial role in the process of identity of the city of Barbacena. The process of reconfiguring the "City of Madmen" occurs through the valorization of a memory that persists in reinventing itself, transforming the museum into a space of memory, remembrance and even oblivion. This phenomenon is related to the concept of archive, according to Michel Foucault, who considers the archive as a guarantee of the future, influencing the way in which one lives and understands the past³⁷. Furthermore, the narrative of the Museum of Madness establishes a constant dialogue between change and permanence, disappearance and reconstruction, seeking new meanings for the model of psychiatry represented by the hospital. The Anti-Asylum

³⁴ Ibid.

³⁵ It was only in 1994 that the last cell in the Colônia was destroyed. The implementation of therapeutic workshops and extramural activities only began in the late 1990s. See: GODOY, Ana Boff de. "Arquivos de Barbacena, a Cidade dos Loucos: o manicômio como lugar de aprisionamento e apagamento de sujeitos e suas memórias" In Revista Investigações, v. 27, n. 2, 2014.

³⁶ LENNON; FOLEY, op. cit.; LOGAN, William; REEVES, Keir. Places of Pain and Shame: Dealing with 'Difficult Heritage'. London: Routledge, 2009; GALLETTO, Karen Cristina. Dark tourism: patrimônio, memória e contos. Rio de Janeiro: Letras e Versos, 2022.

³⁷ FOUCAULT, Michel. A arqueologia do saber. Rio de Janeiro: Forense Universitária, 2008.

Movement³⁸ and the Psychiatric Reform were fundamental in transforming the hospital into a museum, a place of memory that aims to preserve the traces of a dark past and promote a new approach to madness³⁹. This transformation is an example of how cultural heritage can be a political expression, using collective memory to express the injustices of the past and propose a more humane future.

In the context of *Dark Heritage*, the Museum of Madness represents an exemplary case study. As mentioned, according to Foley and Lennon, *Dark Heritage* involves visiting places marked by catastrophes, genocides and other forms of human suffering, which, although painful, are essential for memory and historical education⁴⁰. The Museum of Madness, inserted in this context, transforms the pain and suffering experienced in the former hospital into an educational and collective memory tool. Through the museum's exhibitions and collection, visitors are confronted with the reality of the atrocities committed and encouraged to reflect on the relevance of not repeating such acts. This process of patrimonializing suffering not only preserves the memory of the victims, but also serves as a constant reminder of the need for empathy and social justice.

The opening of psychiatric hospitals to the press allowed news reports to publicly denounce the atrocities suffered by inmates. In this sense, the Museum of Madness is a metaphor for the discourse of Psychiatric Reform, created to reveal a painful memory and reveal a little-known history. The transformation of a "hospice" into a place of memory and cultural heritage demonstrates the expansion of the notion of heritage in recent decades, including not only physical monuments but also intangible and identity-related elements of communities and groups⁴¹.

³⁸ The Anti-Asylum Movement in Brazil, which began in the 1980s, seeks to reform the mental health system, criticizing the asylum model of hospitalization, which often resulted in inhumane conditions and social exclusion. Advocating deinstitutionalization and defending the human rights of psychiatric patients, the movement promotes the replacement of psychiatric hospitals with community services, such as Psychosocial Care Centers (CAPS). It influenced significant legislation, such as Law No. 10,216 of 2001, which establishes guidelines for the protection of people with mental disorders and encourages social reintegration, highlighting the importance of the active participation of patients and their families in the management of mental health policies. MACHADO, Cristiani Vieira. "A Reforma Psiquiátrica Brasileira: caminhos e desafios" In *Saúde em Debate*, v. 44, pp. 5-8, 2021.

³⁹ LÜCHMANN, Lúgia Helena Hahn; RODRIGUES, Jefferson. "O movimento antimanicomial no Brasil" In *Ciência & Saúde Coletiva*, v. 12, pp. 399-407, 2007.

⁴⁰ LENNON; FOLEY, op. cit.

⁴¹ GODOY, op. cit.

Cultural heritage can be a political discourse that aims to establish the relevance of certain assets, whether material or symbolic. Thus, the analysis of the Museum of Madness collection is essential to understanding the society that created it, considering it as a historical object that reflects a collective memory. In the archive-asylum, individual memories are often forgotten, but in the museum, these scattered memories are rescued and recontextualized in a large mosaic, a document of the collective memory of the “City of Madmen”⁴². However, this memory can only be maintained and updated if there is a constant effort to keep it alive and relevant.

Final Considerations

The conclusions of this work, which aimed to briefly analyze the historical trajectory of psychiatry and its social and human implications, highlight the complexity and progress of this field over time. From a religious perspective to a scientific and medical-psychiatric focus, the conception of madness has undergone significant transformations. However, this path has not been free of controversy, abuse and violations of patients’ rights, as it was clearly demonstrated in the case of the Colônia Psychiatric Hospital in Brazil.

Preserving dissonant memories, such as those associated with Colônia, is essential raising awareness of past wrongs to prevent future tragedies. Understanding and confronting the dark aspects of our collective history is essential to healing and building a more just and compassionate society. Remembering and honoring the victims of Colônia acknowledges, the importance of all lives and reaffirms our commitment to human dignity and rights. The exposure of these atrocities by activists and mental health professionals, including prominent figures such as Franco Basaglia, was crucial in exposing the inhumane conditions and pushing for change. Closing the hospital and transforming it into a museum represents an attempt to confront the dark past and educate the public about the horrors of psychiatric history. By confronting the injustices of the past, future generations will recognize the signs of oppression and discrimination and advocate for the values of social justice and equality.

The Museum of Madness not only protects the memory of victims, but also provides an in-depth reflection on past injustices and their effects

⁴² Ibid.

on today's society. Analyzing the Museum of Madness as a site of political memory and patrimonialization reveals the importance of preserving and confronting the traumatic events of the past, allowing for a more in-depth understanding of the social and medical injustices that shaped our society. The concept of *Dark Heritage* reinforces the relevance of confronting the past, not only as a form of memory, but also as a way to educate and raise awareness about the atrocities committed and their consequences for the present and future.

It is crucial to recognize those tragedies such as the “Brazilian Holocaust” occurred in a context of unfair social and political systems that marginalized and dehumanized certain social groups⁴³. Therefore, when designing a more promising future, we must commit to eliminate these oppressive structures and create a culture of mutual respect and inclusion.

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Jews and marranos, in Portugal and in Brazil, in the first half of the 20th century: anti-Semitism and social Darwinism?¹

Judeus e marranos, em Portugal e no Brasil, na primeira metade do século XX: anti-semitismo e darwinismo social?

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Abstract

This article seeks, on the one hand, to characterise the evolution of the Portuguese of Jewish origin from the beginning of the 16th century until the first quarter of the 19th century and, on the other hand, to analyse the specific situation of the Portuguese and Brazilian citizens of Marrano origin from the 1830s until the immediate post-World War II and post-Holocaust period. The aim is also to reflect on the possibilities and risks of defining patrimonialisation and socio-cultural intervention strategies that are based either on historiographical production and other social sciences, or on memory and post-memory about Jews and Marranos, in Portugal and Brazil, in the first half of the 20th century. To this end, we will use theoretical categories such as anti-Judaism and anti-Semitism, philo-Semitism and Zionism; nationalism, social Darwinism, racism and xenophobia, eugenics, religious fundamentalism and secularism; discrimination, mass violence and genocide, transitional processes. I recall how, during the centuries of systematic persecution (16th-18th centuries) and the decades of more or less aggressive tolerance (1820s to 1970s), Portuguese and Brazilian citizens of Marrano origin were both targets of discrimination by their fellow citizens of Catholic culture and of Jewish descent, and were marked by the consequences of their own strategy of survival and resistance during the centuries of systematic persecution (16th to 18th centuries) and in the decades of less or more aggressive tolerance (1820s to 1970s).

Keywords: Jews. Marranos. Anti-Judaism. Anti-Semitism. Social Darwinism.

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Resumo

Procura-se neste artigo, por um lado, caracterizar a evolução dos portugueses de origem judaica do início do século XVI ao primeiro quartel de oitocentos; por outro lado, analisar a situação específica dos cidadãos portugueses e dos cidadãos brasileiros de origem marrana da década de 1830 ao imediato pós-Segunda Guerra e ao pós-Holocausto. Visa-se, ainda, reflectir sobre as possibilidades e sobre os riscos da definição de estratégias de patrimonialização e de intervenção sociocultural que tenham como fundamento, quer a produção historiográfica e outras ciências sociais, quer a memória e a pós-memória acerca dos judeus e dos marranos, em Portugal e no Brasil, na primeira metade do século XX. Utilizar-se-ão, para o efeito, categorias teóricas como as de anti-judaísmo e anti-semitismo, filo-semitismo e sionismo; nacionalismo, darwinismo social, racismo e xenofobia, eugenia, integrismo religioso e laicismo; discriminação, violência de massas e genocídio, processos transicionais. Lembro que cidadãos portugueses e cidadãos brasileiros de origem marrana foram, tanto alvo de discriminação por parte de concidadãos de cultura católica e de origem judaica, como marcados pelas sequelas da sua própria estratégia de sobrevivência e de resistência nos séculos de perseguição sistémica (séculos XVI a XVIII) e nas décadas de tolerância menos ou mais agressiva (décadas 1820 a 1970).

Palavras-chave: Judeus. Marranos. Anti-judaísmo. Anti-semitismo. Darwinismo social.

Introduction

Probably less well known than the words Jews and New Christians, the word Marranos was used specifically as a pejorative for New Christians in the 16th to 18th centuries. These were Portuguese subjects of Jewish origin who had been forced to convert to Catholicism after 5 December 1496, and who, living in the metropolis or in their non-autonomous territories, and whether they wanted to or not, secretly maintained Hebrew religious experiences and cultural practices in general.

This allegedly almost universal tendency to “Judaise” would have different causes, depending on one’s ideological perspective. For the mainly anti-Jewish view, the New Christians or Marranos were an attack on the “virtuous monopoly of Catholicism” through temporary (individual and family) attachment to previous religious habits. For the mainly proto-anti-Semitic readings that legitimised the long existence of the Tribunal of the Holy Office of the Inquisition, the “religious crimes” committed by New Christians

or Marranos had a global scope and resulted from the “permanent evil nature” of the Jews as a people².

The term Marranos, on the other hand, referred to Portuguese, Brazilian, and perhaps other non-autonomous countries and territories in the 19th to 21st centuries. They were the descendants of Portuguese of Jewish origin and New Christian Portuguese who had little contact with Hebrew culture and who had lost contact with other segments of the Jewish Diaspora in general, and with other parts of the Sephardic re-Diaspora in particular. Such a break would be the result of an attempt at disguise –resistance and survival – sustained for almost five centuries of systemic persecution, followed by lesser or more aggressive toleration.

While traditional forms of anti-Jewish and anti-Semitic discrimination continue to exist in the surrounding societies, the Marranos have also experienced (and will continue to experience) other forms of marginalisation in the modern era. Of particular importance were the phenomena resulting from individual and collective traumas caused by long-term exposure to discrimination and mass violence, religious fundamentalism or defensive xenophobia on the part of Jewish leaders or sections of Jewish communities, and the fact that most Marranos live in “precarious” socio-cultural contexts, i.e. those characterised by the hegemony of peripheral socio-economic relations, popular cultures and/or mass culture³.

Given the intense changes that took place in Portugal and Brazil in the first half of the 20th century, the aim of this article is, first, to systematise the results of the research already carried out on Jews and Marranos, anti-Judaism/anti-Semitism and philo-Semitism in these countries and during this period, and then to reflect on the potential and the risks of strategies of patrimonialisation and socio-cultural intervention, whose object of study and intervention is the remembrance, the post- remembrance and the contemporary reality of the Jews and the Marranos in Portugal and Brazil.

² See, in particular, ALVES, Francisco Manuel (Reitor ou Abade de Baçal), “Preâmbulo”. *Os judeus no distrito de Bragança, Memórias Arqueologico-Historicas do Districto de Bragança*, Bragança: s.e., Tomo V, 1925, p. 7-18 [...]; NUNES, João Paulo Avelãs, “Anti-judaísmo e anti-semitismo, em Portugal, no Antigo Regime e na Época Contemporânea”, forthcoming; REMÉDIOS, Joaquim Mendes dos. *Os judeus em Portugal*, vol. II, Coimbra: Coimbra Editora, 1928.

³ See, inter alia, GARCIA, Maria Antonieta. *Os judeus de Belmonte. Os caminhos da memória*. Lisboa: UNL, 1993; MEA, Elvira Cunha de Azevedo. *O Porto judaico*. Porto: Evo Luna Edições, 2021; MILGRAM, Avraham. “Crypto-Jews, Sephardim, Ashkenazim, and Refugees from Nazi Europe in Early twentieth-century Portugal: Together and Apart”, *Contemporary Jewry*, 2020, p. 607-626; SCHWARZ, Samuel. *Os cristãos-novos em Portugal no século XX*. Lisboa: [loose-leaf of the journal *Arqueologia e História*, Associação dos Arqueólogos Portugueses, “Prefácio do Dr. Ricardo Jorge”], 1925.

At the risk of oversimplifying, I would say that, in Portugal, both aspects of the defined universe (Jews and Marranos in the present) have reached a similarly average level of depth since the 1980s – the dictatorship of the Estado Novo, which severely limited research in historiography/other social sciences and the technologies derived therefrom, was only interrupted in 1974. In Brazil, on the other hand, the evolution of citizens of Jewish origin has been studied more extensively than that of the Marranos, whose mere existence is still little known⁴. This has involved reconstructing and analysing both the contexts of their origin as settlers, immigrants, exiles or refugees, and their international contacts.

Epistemological, theoretical-methodological, and deontological assumptions

In my opinion, historiography in general, and the historiographic analysis of problems related to forms of discrimination in particular, are important enough in contemporary societies to merit both a debate on the proposed conclusions and an evaluation of the epistemological, theoretical-methodological, and deontological choices made so far. I believe that the same reasoning largely applies to technologies derived from historiography, such as scientific communication and heritage journalism, history teaching and didactics, organisational culture and territorial differentiation, heritage and museology, leisure and heritage tourism.

I also suggest that one of the causes of the diminished standing and social influence of historians and specialists in technologies derived from historiography as a professional group is both the precariousness of the epistemic and methodological debate and the inadequacy of deontological self-policing. Most importantly, the knowledge generated may become less objectified and operational, or, through critical reception, may not be included in challenging processes of qualifying civic intervention and professional activity.

In this article, I outline the epistemological, theoretical-methodological, and deontological assumptions that I, as a historian (in other words, as a researcher, teacher, and communicator), have tried to make about the problem of the Portuguese of Jewish origin and the Marranos, anti-Judaism

⁴ On the survival of the Marranos in Peru until the second half of the 20th century, cfr. WACHTEL, Nathan. *Sous le ciel de l'Eden. Juifs portugais, métis & indiens. Une mémoire marrane au Pérou?* Paris: Éditions Chandeigne, 2020.

and anti-Semitism, philo-Semitism and Zionism. These assumptions structure my work as a researcher and consultant in the fields of history teaching and didactics, organizational culture and territorial differentiation, cultural heritage and museology, leisure and heritage tourism.

In terms of epistemology, I share the views of the founders and proponents of the neo-modernist paradigm that emerged in the 1930s. I argue that the most that historians, as scholars, can produce and disseminate is knowledge that is as objective as possible about reality (reconstruction and analysis of specific objects of study, including their contextualisation and comparison). I believe that this effort of objectification is important to improve the living conditions of all individuals and the degree of sustainability of human societies; that science depends on the mobilisation and control of each researcher's structuring ideology, the operational use of complex concepts and methodologies, inter- and transdisciplinary dialogue, the willingness to listen and, finally, to incorporate different proposals for reconstitution and/or interpretation.

I share the idea that science (an attempt to know reality as objectively as possible) is not the same as science-based technology (a rationalised attempt to transform reality in a direction previously chosen on the basis of civic or ideological criteria); that it is up to individuals, civil society organisations and public institutions to decide what to do with the results of scientific and technological research. I also support the idea that historians, like researchers in other sciences, should be involved in the production of technological knowledge derived from their field of expertise, and should

contribute to the development, application and evaluation/improvement of technological solutions.

I am therefore at odds with many of the core assumptions of the modern and post-modern paradigms. As for the modern paradigm, which is responsible for the decisive process of the autonomous affirmation of science and science-based technologies, it affirms the objective and definitive character of scientific knowledge; the superiority of science over other knowledge – humanities, arts, ideology, common sense – as well as the increased rigour of “exact sciences” over natural sciences and even more so over social sciences. It also proclaims the epistemological identity between science and science-based technology, and the obligation for individuals and human societies seeking to promote progress to adopt the unquestioned conclusions/determinations of science and science-based technology.

With regard to the post-modern paradigm, consolidated in the 1960s, it makes an absolute distinction between scientific knowledge and science-based technologies (resulting from the reconstruction and analysis of those parts of reality that can be approached through mathematical models) and ideological narratives about reality and the consequent proposal for its transformation. The most radicalised post-modern sectors – on both the far left and the far right – even claim that the monopoly of the ideological approach also applies to those segments of reality that have hitherto been studied and transformed through the application of mathematical models (“exact sciences”, natural sciences and the technologies derived therefrom).

Given that ideologies – value systems that enable us to ‘critique’, ‘evaluate’ and ‘act upon’ reality – are almost exclusively a form of knowledge accessible to people, it would be up to researchers to produce and promote the most just and mobilising narratives of reality. Since the degree of fairness attributed to each reading/intervention strategy would depend on the conceptions espoused, and the sub-universe of recipients would be associated with the identity of each subject of knowledge (the respective “place of speech”), we would inevitably be faced with a space of permanent confrontation between ideologies, identity groups and complementary and/or opposing powers.

From a theoretical and methodological point of view, I have opted for a syncretic use of contributions from historiographical currents such as new historiography, structuralist historiography and critical Marxist historiography, by combining the priority given to empirical with the recognition of the centrality of the conceptual structuring of analysis, by interdisciplinarity and the simultaneous use of different scales and temporalities, and by comparing different periods and societies. Finally, I would like to argue that the technologies derived from historiography – scientific dissemination and cultural heritage journalism, didactics and history teaching, organisational culture and territorial differentiation, cultural heritage and museology, leisure and cultural heritage tourism – should consist above all in disseminating the most objective and up-to-date proposals for the historiographical interpretation of the issues under consideration⁵.

⁵ See, in particular, BALIBAR, Étienne; WALLERSTEIN, Immanuel, *Raça, nação, classe. As identidades ambíguas*. São Paulo: Boitempo, 2021; BLOCH, Marc. *Apologia da história ou o ofício de historiador* (trad. do francês) Rio de Janeiro: Jorge Zahar Editor, 2002; BRAUNSTEIN, Jean-François. *A religião Woke*. Lisboa: Guerra & Paz, 2023; CATROGA, Fernando. *Memória, história e historiografia*. Coimbra: Quarteto Editora, 2001; HESPANHA, António Manuel. “História e sistema: interrogações à historiografia pós-moderna”, *Ler História*, n. 9, 1986; NEIMAN, Susan. *A esquerda não é woke*. Belo Horizonte: Editora Âyiné, 2023; NUNES, Adérito Sedas,

Jews, New Christians and Marranos in Modern and Contemporary Portugal and Brazil

After 5 December 1496, in Portugal and its empire – including Brazil –, the members of the existing Jewish communities were forced to convert to Catholicism or leave their territories. Throughout the 16th to 18th centuries, these Portuguese and their descendants were formally identified as New Christians by the Portuguese State and the Catholic Church. The target of various forms of legal and institutional discrimination, they were also inherently victims of the Tribunal of the Holy Office of the Inquisition. As former Jews or descendants of Jews, they were false Catholics and maintained an irrepressible tendency to “Judaize” (to think and act in accordance with the cultural and religious precepts of Judaism).

In terms of informality, i.e. in terms of diffuse socio-cultural relations, the New Christians were effectively seen by many of the Old Christians as Jews in disguise, or at least as Jews forced to simulate a Catholic lifestyle. One of the traces of this identification and of the corresponding hostility or alienation is the fact that the New Christians were referred to, both collectively and individually, by the term “Marranos”. Since ‘Marrano’ was synonymous with pig, it was clearly a double insult. Humans were relegated to the status of non-humans, using a species that had a very negative image in Jewish culture.

If, on the one hand, the initial choice of forced conversion could be characterised as the fruit of an anti-Jewish worldview – the only problem for the Jews would be the practice of a “false religion” – on the other hand, the creation and long existence of both the category of New Christians and the Tribunal of the Holy Office of the Inquisition are indicative of the presence of at least embryonic anti-Semitic ideas (the danger would be the insurmountable “Jewish blood”). The New Christians adopted several strategies in trying to integrate themselves into a forcibly Catholic State and society, and in trying

“Questões preliminares sobre as ciências sociais”, *Análise Social*, v. VIII, n. 30/31, 1970; NUNES, João Paulo Avelãs Nunes. “História e historiografia, património cultural e museologia, lazer e turismo culturais: uma abordagem deontológico-epistemológica e teórico-metodológica”, *Revista de Teoria da História*, v. 17, n. 1, Julho de 2017; _____, “Historiografia e tecnologias derivadas: relevância social, epistemologia e deontologia”. In: VAQUINHAS, Irene Maria et. al. (Coords.). *História, empresas, arqueologia industrial e museologia*. Coimbra: IUC, 2021; PAIS, José Machado. *Consciência histórica e identidade*. Oeiras: Celta Editora, 1999; PLUCKROSE, Helen; LINDSAY, James. *Teorias cónicas* (translated from English). Lisboa: Guerra & Paz, Editores, 2021; ROUDINESCO, Elisabeth. *O eu soberano. Ensaio sobre as derivas identitárias* (translated from French). Rio de Janeiro: Zahar, 2022; VARGAS LLOSA, Mario. *O apelo da tribo* (trad. do castelhano). Lisboa: Quetzal, 2018; VATTIMO, Gianni. *O fim da modernidade. Niilismo e hermenêutica na cultura pós-moderna*. Lisboa: Editorial Presença, 1987; WOOD, Ellen Meiksins. *Democracy against capitalism. Renewing historical materialism*. Cambridge: CUP, 1996.

to avoid or at least survive the brutal and constant violence perpetrated by the Tribunal of the Holy Office of the Inquisition.

Among the main methods of acculturation or disguise used by the New Christians between the 16th and 18th centuries, I would highlight the migration from small villages in the interior of Portugal to cities on the coast and to colonies, protectorates or trading posts (namely Brazil). I would also emphasise the renunciation of forms of Jewish social, religious and cultural life which might be more easily identifiable by possible informers, the adoption of some Catholic religious and cultural practices, the pursuit of professional activities not associated with Jews, mixed marriages with Old Christians, and the almost complete renunciation of Jewish religious and cultural traditions.

Even those New Christians who, until the early 19th century, chose either to go into exile or to immigrate to countries that were less intolerant of Jews (while returning to Jewish cultural and religious life) faced numerous constraints. In addition to the obstacles posed by the Portuguese administrative and ecclesiastical authorities, and the manifestations of anti-Judaism and proto-anti-Semitism that existed in these other societies, the host Jewish communities were confronted with several situations: the trauma and post-trauma resulting from the threat of violence and/or the violence suffered in Portugal and in their respective non-autonomous territories; the accusations or distrust associated with the partial, temporary and even imposed abandonment of Judaism and Jewish culture; with the difficulties and stigma of having had an explicitly syncretic upbringing (Jewish and Catholic); the rivalries between Sephardim, Ashkenazim and Oriental Jews, and between Jews from different countries.

Perhaps this will make it easier to understand why, even in modern times, Portuguese subjects of Jewish origin – those who recognised themselves as such and were identified as such by third parties – were divided into two increasingly separate sub-universes. First, the group of those who, as Jews in other countries or as New Christians in Portugal and its non-autonomous territories, maintained contact with the basics of Jewish culture, including religion, and with other segments of the Jewish diaspora (primarily the Sephardic re-diaspora). There were also those who, as New Christians in Portugal and its non-autonomous territories, knew only a small part of Jewish culture; they were not aware that there were many branches of the Jewish Diaspora⁶.

⁶ See, inter alia, BENBASSA, Esther (Dir.). *Mémoires juives d'Espagne et du Portugal*. Paris: Éditions Publisud,

At least since the beginning of the modern era⁷ and until the establishment of republican political systems, both Portugal (from 1820 to 1910) and Brazil (from 1822 to 1889), as constitutional monarchies, saw the arrival of Jewish exiles, refugees and immigrants – with the consequent creation of community structures in some cities – and of processes in which Portuguese or Brazilian citizens, formerly crypto-Jews, publicly returned to a Jewish cultural and religious tradition. Although small (both in absolute and relative terms), these communities ensured, on the one hand, that they were recognised by civil societies, state apparatuses and political systems, and, on the other, that they resumed regular contacts with other sectors of the Jewish diaspora.

Consumed by the fear of being once again persecuted by the state, by the Catholic Church and by their former Old Christian neighbours, many of the small groups of Portuguese and Brazilian former New Christians – locally self- and hetero-identified as Jews or Marranos – continued to live in secrecy and isolation, losing contact with much of the Jewish culture and links with the publicly resettled Jewish communities in Portugal and Brazil. The fact that the majority of these Marranos lived in rural areas in the interior of the country, and that they mainly practised forms of popular culture, increased the likelihood that they would remain unknown in other regions of the countries and non-autonomous territories in question, as well as in other countries.

Neither the Jewish communities nor the groups of Marranos in 19th century Portugal and Brazil saw the establishment and deepening of contacts and bilateral relations as something positive, due to their own peculiarities and the tensions that arose in their relationship with the surrounding non-Jewish cultural majorities. Among the Marranos, this attitude may have stemmed from fear of the possible future consequences of a public embrace of Judaism, even in a conservative liberal regime, from the difficulty of accepting

1996; DIMONT, Max I. *Jews, God and History*. Nova Iorque: Mentor, 1994; MUCZNIK, Esther et. al. (Coords.). *Dicionário do judaísmo português*. Lisboa: Editorial Presença, 2009; MUCZNIK, Esther. *Judeus portugueses. Uma história de luz e sombra*. Lisboa: Manuscrito, 2021; REIS, Maria de Fátima; PINTO, Paulo Mendes (Coord.). *Identidade e memória sefardita: história e actualidade. Terra(s) de Sefarad 2017. Encontros de Culturas Judaico-Sefarditas*. Bragança: CMB/Ideias Emergentes, 2019; TAVARES, Maria José Ferro. *Os judeus em Portugal no século XV*, 2 volumes. Lisboa: INIC, 1982-1984; J.A.R.S. TAVIM, José Alberto R. Silva et. al. (Org.). *As diásporas dos judeus e cristãos-novos de origem ibérica entre o Mar Mediterrâneo e o Oceano Atlântico. Estudos*. Lisboa: CH, 2020.

⁷ In this regard, I would like to remind you that, since the reign of King José I (1750-1777), the Portuguese State had abolished most of the formal forms of discrimination and repression specifically directed against its subjects of Jewish origin.

the radically piecemeal and syncretic nature of their experience of Judaism and Jewish culture in general, and from the near impossibility of grasping the real complexity and dimension of the Jewish diaspora.

Faced with the initiatives of Marranos who wanted to contact the Portuguese and Brazilian Jewish communities in order to be supported in their return to more structured practices of Judaism and Jewish culture, several organisations initially refused to promote both these individual processes and joint strategies for reaching out to groups of surviving Marranos in each of the aforementioned countries. The explanation for this may be related to a failure to recognise the socio-cultural reality of the Marranos as part of the Jewish diaspora, a degradation of ways of life that are essentially based on popular cultures, and a concern not to provoke violent reactions from the more anti-Jewish and/or anti-Semitic sectors of civil society, political systems and state apparatuses in Portugal and Brazil.

Since the establishment of the republican political-institutional experience (i.e. from 15 November 1889 to the present day), Brazil has seen a significant increase in its Jewish community, an increase of its internal diversity – Brazilian citizens, exiles, refugees and immigrants, Sephardim, Ashkenazim and Oriental Jews with different attitudes towards Judaism, Zionism, the political alternatives that exist in Brazil or in other countries, including, since 1948, the State of Israel –, and the increasing intensity of debates about and by people of Jewish origin who are more or less members of the community in question. Conversely, the reality of Brazil's Marrano centres remains little known.

Given the size and intellectual strength of the Jewish community, and the particular intensity and explicitness of multiculturalism in Brazil since at least the beginning of the 20th century, the isolation that will essentially continue to characterise the majority of Brazilian Marrano nuclei is nevertheless surprising. This peculiarity is all the more striking when compared with the development of the surviving Marrano nuclei in Peru until the second half of the 20th century. Also descendants of Portuguese and Brazilian New Christians, the Peruvian Marranos went through a common process of reconstructing their memory, reintegrating into the Jewish diaspora and then, in part, immigrating to Israel.

In Portugal, from 5 October 1910 to the present day, there has been both a relative increase in the Jewish community and a significant increase in public awareness and knowledge of the Marrano nuclei. There has also been

an increase in controversies concerning Jews, an increased public presence of people of Jewish origin, and some growth in the number and internal diversity of the Jewish community living in Portugal (Portuguese citizens, including some of Marrano origin, exiles, refugees and immigrants, Sephardim and Ashkenazim, with different attitudes towards Judaism, Zionism, the political alternatives existing in Portugal and in the respective non-autonomous territories or in other countries, namely the State of Israel since 1948).

As a result of the not necessarily concerted action of three unusually dynamic heterodox individuals – Father Francisco Manuel Alves, Captain Artur de Barros Basto and Engineer Samuel Schwarz – and many other individuals and organisations (national and foreign), the first phase of the process of hetero- and self-characterisation of the Marrano nuclei, which included the debate on their relationship with the Jewish diaspora in general and the Sephardic re-diaspora in particular, took place in Portugal between the 1920s and 1940s. A second phase of this process began in 1974, with the end of the Estado Novo dictatorship, the establishment of a democratic regime and the establishment of diplomatic relations with the State of Israel.

Led by Artur Barros Basto, one of the founders of the Porto Israelite Community and himself a Marrano who had returned to Judaism in Tangier (Morocco) after being rejected by the Lisbon Israelite Community, the first phase of the process in question (known as the “Save the Marranos”) lost momentum from the second half of the 1930s onwards due to the negative reaction of the Estado Novo and the Church/“Portuguese Catholic Action”, among other factors: conflicts within the Jewish community of Porto, the reservations of the Jewish community of Lisbon, the indirect consequences of the rise of radical anti-Semitism, the Second World War and the Holocaust. The subsequent fate of the majority of Portuguese citizens who identified themselves as Marranos in the 1920s and 1930s remains to be seen⁸.

After the coup d'état/revolution of 25 April 1974, an effort was made to reconstruct, analyse and disseminate information about Samuel Schwarz, Artur Barros Basto and the “Save the Marranos” movement, on the one hand, and the development of the Portuguese Marranos from the beginning of the 19th century to the immediate post-World War II and post-Holocaust period, on the other. In the case of the Marranos in the municipality of Belmonte (in Beira Baixa), there has been an attempt to characterise the community

⁸ On this subject, it is both possible and essential to consult the collection of the Porto Israeli Community Newspaper (*Ha-Lapid (O Facho)* [1927-1958]).

as it was in the 1970s and 1980s, in anthropological and historiographical terms, with a view to the patrimonialisation and touristification of their lives and memories, with the intervention of the City Council, and a process of rapprochement with Jewish culture and Judaism, with the intervention of the State of Israel⁹.

Portugal, Brazil, the Jews and the Marranos from 1820 and 1822 to the present

Above all, it is worth remembering something that is obvious, but still worth emphasising. Between 1820 or 1822 and the present day, both Portugal and Brazil have experienced different political regimes, during which the attitude towards Jews (national and foreign), the Marranos, the memory of the former Jews – forced to convert to Catholicism or expelled – and then the New Christians varied. Individuals and organisations from both civil societies and political systems, individuals and entities from both state apparatuses, also took different positions. Until 1974, referring to Portugal meant taking into account the “continental territory” and the “adjacent islands”, as well as the respective non-autonomous territories (protectorates or colonies).

Since the beginning of the modern era, Portugal has experienced a liberal-conservative regime with authoritarian overtones (Constitutional Monarchy, 1820-1891) and a demoliberal regime with authoritarian overtones (Constitutional Monarchy, 1891-1910), both of which were monarchical in nature; a demoliberal regime with authoritarian overtones (First Republic, 1910-1926), an extreme right-wing authoritarian regime (Military Dictatorship, 1926-1933), an extreme right-wing and tendentially totalitarian

⁹ See, in particular, ALVES, Francisco Manuel (Reitor ou Abade de Baçal). *Memorias Arqueologico-Historicas do Districto de Bragança*. 11 tomos, Bragança: s.e., 1910-1947; SCHWARZ, Samuel. *La découverte des marranes. Les crypto-juifs au Portugal* [“Préface de Israël Levi”]. Paris: Éditions Chandeigne, 2015 — Préface de Nathan Wachel, Introduction & Notes de Livia Parnes; FIGUEIREDO, Ana Gabriela da Silva. “The Portuguese Marranos Committee. A contribution to a unknown history”. In: TAVIM, José Alberto R. Silva et. al. (Org.). *As diásporas dos judeus e cristãos-novos de origem ibérica entre o Mar Mediterrâneo e o Oceano Atlântico*. Estudos. Lisboa: CH, 2020; FRANCO, Manuela. “Judeus em Portugal”. In: MÓNICA, Maria Filomena; BARRETO, António (Coord.). *Dicionário de História de Portugal. Suplemento*, Porto: Livraria Figueirinhas, v. 8, 1999 p. 314-324; GREEN, Abigail; SULLAM, Simon Levis (Eds.). *Jews, Liberalism, anti-Semitism. A global history*. Londres: Palgrave Macmillan, 2021; MARTINS, Jorge. *A República e os judeus*. Lisboa: Nova Vega, 2010; MEA, Elvira de Azevedo; STEINHARDT, Inácio. *Ben-Rosh. Biografia do Capitão Barros Basto, o “apóstolo dos marranos”*. Porto: Edições Afrontamento, 1997; PARNES, Livia. *Présences juives dans le Portugal contemporain (1820-1939)*, 2 volumes, Paris, 2002 (policopiado); VITAL, David. *A People Apart. The Jews in Europe (1789-1939)*. Oxford: OUP, 2009.

regime (Estado Novo, 1933-1974), a revolutionary process (1974-1976) and a democratic regime (1976-...), always under the guise of republicanism.

Brazil, for its part, has experienced a liberal-conservative monarchical regime with authoritarian overtones (Empire, 1822-1889); a demoliberal regime with authoritarian overtones (First Republic, 1889-1930), authoritarian right-wing governments (New Republic, 1930-1937) and a tendentially totalitarian right-wing regime (Estado Novo, 1937-1945)¹⁰, an openly demoliberal regime but with authoritarian overtones (1946-1964), a tendentially totalitarian right-wing regime (Military Dictatorship, 1964-1985) and a democratic regime (1985-...), also always under the guise of republicanism.

With regard to the Jews and Marranos of today, on the one hand, and the memory of the Jews and New Christians of the Middle Ages and the Modern Age, on the other, I believe that in both countries it is possible to identify anti-Jewish, anti-Semitic, philo-Semitic, Zionist or pro-Zionist attitudes and actions. Although most anti-Jewish and anti-Semitic attitudes are associated with conservative and/or right-wing worldviews, there have also been manifestations of anti-Judaism and anti-Semitism based on left-wing values. I would also argue that, as a result of both the choices made by their respective elites and the pressures exerted by the dominant powers in the spheres of influence into which they were integrated, neither the Portuguese nor the Brazilian states pursued radical anti-Semitic policies, much less genocidal anti-Semitic policies from the 19th to the 21st centuries.

Both the Portuguese constitutional monarchy and the Brazilian empire, while claiming to be Catholic, allowed the practice of other religious denominations – including Judaism – as long as they were not openly practiced in public. Most of the intellectuals and political leaders of both conservative-liberal regimes even defended a philo-Semitic interpretation of the past and future of both countries: the persecution of Jews and New Christians would explain some of the blockages accumulated in the modern era; overcoming this “backwardness” (economic, social, scientific and technological) would depend

¹⁰ Assuming that the characteristics of dictatorial, authoritarian and/or totalitarian governments and regimes, which seek to legitimise and consolidate themselves on the basis of predominantly right-wing ideologies, essentially define ideologies, symbol and actions that are typical of the far right. A similar logic would apply to dictatorial governments and regimes – authoritarian and/or totalitarian – that seek to legitimise and consolidate themselves on the basis of mainly left-wing ideologies. See NUNES, João Paulo Avelãs. “Sobre a utilidade da teoria na historiografia: o exemplo da história dos regimes políticos no século XX”. In: DOCKHORN, Gilvan Veiga et. al. (Coords.). *Brasil e Portugal: ditaduras e transições para a democracia*. Santa Maria e Coimbra: Editora UFSM e IUC, 2020a, p. 47-71.

in particular on the reconstitution and full integration of the respective Jewish communities, preferably of Sephardic tradition.

Symbolised by the “Dreyfus Affair” (France, 1894-1906) and the publication of several editions of the *Protocols of the Elders of Zion* (1903-1905 and later), moderate and/or radical anti-Semitism became part of the arguments of Portuguese and Brazilian personalities and organisations, both on the right and far right and on the left and far left, at least since the last decade of the 19th century. Although several of the aforementioned ideological and political actors presented themselves as Catholics, what was to become the dominant current of organised Catholicism (conservative Christian democracy) opted for moderate anti-Semitism, anti-Judaism or even the absence of hostile references to Jews, New Christians and Marranos.

It was during this period – the last quarter of the 19th century and the first quarter of the 20th century – that the myths of anti-Semitism reached their highest expression in Europe and America, relevant to the subsequent viability of the years of mass violence against people of Jewish origin and, later, genocide (the Holocaust). The Jews would be an Asian people who wanted to dominate the world by destroying the superior “Western civilisation” (Christian, monarchical and corporatist). Loyal to their nation, they would try to blend in and disguise themselves, but would refuse to integrate effectively into any other state. The creators of a despotic dictatorship, they would promote liberalism and democracy, anarchising communism and wars.

As fanatical believers in their Eastern religion, they would advocate secularism and religious freedom, atheism and the desecration of Christian places of worship, the ritual murder of children and the elderly. As economic and social parasites, they would propagate capitalism and collectivism. Hostages to an animalistic male sexuality, they would spread feminism and divorce, contraception and abortion, prostitution and paedophilia, alcohol and drug abuse. Supposedly incapable of subtlety and aesthetic grandeur, they favoured subjectivism and what many anti-Semitic activists and individuals called or saw as “degenerate art”.

Faced with the proclaimed indisputability of this characterisation – supposedly validated by theology, philosophy and/or science – the anti-Jews advocated the relentless pursuit of converting every single Jew to what they called “the true religion” (in other words, one of the forms of Christianity). Moderate anti-Semites proposed to demonstrate the danger posed by Jews by segregating them preventively, limiting the number of Jews in each country

and monitoring the links between each national Jewish community and a mythical “Jewish International”. The radical and genocidal anti-Semites demanded that priority be given to denouncing the absolute evil of the Jews, to their dispossession and expulsion, and to the cultural and physical elimination of all Semites who resisted the so-called “racial hygiene” measures (presented as legitimate and indispensable).

Both the First Brazilian Republic and its Portuguese counterpart formally legalised the public practice of the Jewish religion, claiming, with varying degrees of accuracy, to be secularist and to promote religious freedom. Much of the criticism levelled at the two authoritarian regimes, from both the far right and the far left, referred to alleged links between the republican leadership and the “Jewish International”, namely through Freemasonry, “capitalist plutocracy” and “Russian Bolshevism”, the “surrender” of parts of “national territory” (including the non-autonomous territories) and the defence of multilateralism.

After the establishment of authoritarian and/or totalitarian right-wing governments or dictatorial regimes – the military dictatorship and the Estado Novo in Lisbon, the New Republic and the Estado Novo in Rio de Janeiro – in the 1930s and until immediately after the Second World War, the Portuguese and Brazilian states returned to an informal Catholic confessionalism. Although legislation and institutional practice generally preserved the basic principles of the secularisation of both state apparatuses and civil societies (including individuals of Jewish origin), some of the “organic intellectuals” and political leaders of these dictatorships adopted radical anti-Semitic discourses and moderate anti-Semitic practices.

According to the same ideologists, Catholicism was the defining force in Portugal and Brazil. Both countries had been victims of “Jewish aggression” since the end of the Western Roman Empire (support for the Muslim invasion, constant provocation of Catholics, the practice of usury and hoarding, ritual murders of children and the elderly, sexual violence against Catholic women, the clandestine spread of Judaism, support for the Dutch invasions, support for the Napoleonic invasions). Hence the undeniable necessity and legitimacy of the outbreaks of “popular justice” against the Jewish quarters in the Middle Ages, the forced conversion to Catholicism or the expulsion in the late 15th/early 16th centuries, and the activity of the Holy Office of the Inquisition from the 16th to the 18th centuries.

They also proclaimed that, after the 1820 and 1822 ruptures, it had become essential to keep the Portuguese and Brazilian Jewish communities small, as assimilated as possible and under surveillance, to prevent the Marranos from abandoning Catholicism and returning to Judaism; to prohibit the entry of more people of Jewish origin – as immigrants, refugees or exiles – or to guarantee their exit; to support the “governments of order” of countries that, “belatedly” compared to Spain and Portugal, were alleviating or resolving their “Jewish problems”. Despite unequivocally recognising the scale and brutality of the Holocaust, the creation of the State of Israel and the conclusions of the Second Vatican Council, the Portuguese Estado Novo, at least until the end of António de Oliveira Salazar’s term of office (1968), remained firmly committed to the above assumptions and practices. Lisbon did not establish diplomatic relations with Tel Aviv until May 1977, three years after the coup d’état/revolution of 25 April 1974.

Before and after the beginning of the Second World War and, later, the outbreak of the Holocaust, after the end of this generalised military conflict and the Estado Novo under Getúlio Vargas, the evolution of the Brazilian case was quite different. Although some of the leaders of the dictatorship, high-ranking members of the state apparatus and individuals/organisations from civil society defended the above-mentioned anti-Semitic and hegemonic ideology and practice, other regime leaders, members of the state apparatus and individuals/organisations from civil society (including most representatives and members of the Jewish community) voiced alternative perspectives and interventions in the opposite direction.

Due to the differences between the two dictatorships, to the two civil societies and the two Jewish communities between the mid-1930s and the immediate aftermath of the World War II and the Holocaust, many people of Jewish origin ended up in Brazil as immigrants or refugees. A significant proportion of these people ended up staying in Brazil and acquiring Brazilian citizenship. Conversely, the Marrano nuclei continued to receive little recognition. Brazil became a belligerent state on the side of the Allies, adopted an openly demolitionist regime with authoritarian overtones (1946-1964), critically revisited the anti-Judaism and proto-anti-Semitism present during the colonial period, condemned the genocidal anti-Semitism of Germany under the Nazi regime, and established diplomatic relations with Israel in February 1949. The situation was largely maintained during the military

dictatorship (1964-1985) and largely resumed after the establishment of a democratic regime (1985-...)¹¹.

Possible strategies for patrimonialisation and socio-cultural intervention

I agree with those who argue that the concepts, policies and practices related to cultural heritage – technological knowledge derived from historiography and other social sciences – have been introduced in each country since they were first structured as contemporary states (i.e. nation states or nation states with civil societies, political systems and state apparatuses). They consist of the more or less integrative or exclusionary,

¹¹ See, inter alia, J. AMEAL, João. *História de Portugal*. Porto: Livraria Tavares Martins, 1940; J AZEVEDO, João Lúcio de. *História dos cristãos novos portugueses*. Lisboa: Livraria Clássica Editora, 1921; CARNEIRO, Maria Luiza Tucci. *O anti-semitismo na Era Vargas*. São Paulo: Perspectiva, 2001; FRANCO, Manuela. “Uma influência portuguesa no Levante? A diplomacia ao serviço da propaganda do prestígio da República”, *Política Internacional*, 2002, p. 187-206; “Diversão balcânica: os israelitas portugueses de Salónica”, *Análise Social*, n. 170, 2004, p. 119-147; HAWKINS, Mike. *Social Darwinism in European and American Thought (1860-1945)*. Cambridge: CUP, 1998; LIMA, Joaquim Alberto Pires de. *Mouros, judeus e negros na história de Portugal*. Porto: Livraria Civilização, 1940; LOFF, Manuel. *As duas ditaduras ibéricas na nova ordem eurofascista*. Florença: 2004, vol. 3 (policopiado); LOUÇÃ, António; PACCAUD, Isabel. *O segredo da Rua d’O Século*. Lisboa: Fim de Século, 2007; MARTINS, Jorge. “O moderno anti-semitismo em Portugal”, *Vária Escrita*, n. 11, 2004, p. 291-336; A.G. Mattoso, 1939; MEA, Elvira Cunha de Azevedo (Coord.). *Amílcar Paulo: o delfim do Capitão Barros Basto*. Colectânea da sua obra. Porto: CIP, 2018; MILGRAM, Avraham (Ed.). *Entre la aceptación y el rechazo. América Latina y los refugiados judíos del nazismo*. Jerusalém: Yad Vashem, 2003; _____, *Portugal, Salazar e os judeus*. Lisboa: Gradiva, 2010; NUNES, João Paulo Avelãs Nunes. “Neo-darwinism and politico-ideological concepts in Portugal during the first half of the 20th century”. In: PEREIRA, Ana Leonor et. al. (Ed.). *Darwin, evolution, evolutionisms*. Coimbra: IUC, 2011, p. 151-155; _____, “Darwinismo social e antisemitismo: o caso português”, *Cultura, Espaço & Memória*, n. 5, 2014, p. 117- 132; _____, “A memória histórica como instrumento de controlo durante o Estado Novo português: o exemplo do antisemitismo”. In: CARNEIRO, Maria Luiza Tucci; MONTEIRO, Maria Elizabeth Brêa (Org.). *O controle dos corpos e das mentes. Estratégias de dominação dos regimes fascistas e autoritários*. Rio de Janeiro e São Paulo: Arquivo Nacional e LEER/USP, 2019, p. 87-113.; _____, “Sobre a utilidade da teoria na historiografia: o exemplo da história dos regimes políticos no século XX”. In: DOCKHORN, Gilvan Veiga et. al. (Coords.). *Brasil e Portugal: ditaduras e transições para a democracia*. Santa Maria e Coimbra: Editora UFSM e IUC, 2020a, p. 47-71; _____, “Antijudaísmo e antisemitismo moderado, em Portugal, nas décadas de 1930 e 1940”. SENKMANN, Leonardo; MILGRAM, Avraham (Eds.). *Cultura, ideología y fascismo. Sociedad civil iberoamericana y Holocausto*. Madrid: Iberoamericana Vervuert, 2020b, p. 305-342; PEREIRA, Ana Leonor. *Darwin em Portugal: filosofia, história, engenharia social (1865-1914)*. Coimbra: Livraria Almedina, 2001; PHAYER, Michael. *The Catholic Church and the Holocauste (1930-1965)*. Bloomington: Indiana University Press, 2000; PIMENTEL, Irene Flunser. “O anti-semitismo português na primeira metade do século XX: marginal e importado”. *História*, 3ª Série, n. 15, 1999, p. 42-53; REMÉDIOS, Joaquim Mendes dos. *Os judeus em Portugal*. Coimbra: F. França Amado — Editor, vol. 1, 1895; SAA, Mário. *A invasão dos judeus*. Lisboa: Libanio da Silva, 1925; SCHAEFER, Ansgar. *Portugal e os refugiados judeus provenientes do território alemão*. Coimbra: IUC, 2014; SEQUEIRA, Francisco Pereira de; PEIXOTO, José de Lemos. *Os planos da autocracia judaica: Protocolos dos Sábios de Sião*. Porto: Livraria Portuguesa, 1923; TURDA, Marius e GILLETTE, Aaron. *Latin eugenics in comparative perspective*. Londres: Bloomsbury Academic, 2016; WASSERSTEIN, Bernard. *On the Eve. The Jews of Europe Before the Second World War*. Londres: Profile Books, 2012.

consensual or violent management of memories and identities (based on sites, buildings, structures, objects and rituals of remembrance), and aim at the construction and intensification/dissemination of feelings of belonging to a nation and of difference – superior or otherwise – in relation to other nations or populations/territories.

At the traditional cultural heritage level, the hegemony of unitary, essentialist and historicist nationalist readings is almost universal, especially after the Second World War/Holocaust and in countries with democratic/multilateralist regimes. Attempts have been made to reconcile identification with the lowest common denominators, which are essential for the self-critical reproduction of national or federal patriotism, and the recognition of identities/memories upstream and downstream identities/national memories (new cultural heritage). It may be possible to consider that this approach corresponds to the recognition of the structuring multiculturalism of all individuals and all communities (different and similar characteristics, characteristics to be abandoned, maintained and introduced).

In terms of identity/memory vectors upstream of the national scale, I would mention those associated with different territorial scales (sub-local, local and regional), as well as with different criteria: ethnic and/or religious, socio-economic, socio-cultural and socio-professional, political-ideological, sex, gender and the experience of sexuality, and age. With regard to identity/memory vectors downstream of the national scale, I would mention the affirmative spaces of civilisational complexes, the subcontinental and global or world spheres. In this context, I would mention the central role played by UNESCO and its journal, *The UNESCO Courier*, from the 1950s to the 1980s.

With the exception of the State of Israel (where we are dealing with history, memory and national identity), the study and subsequent preservation of memory and representation - through the dissemination of historiography, organisational culture, history teaching, cultural heritage, leisure and heritage tourism - of Portuguese and Brazilians of Jewish, Neo-Christian and Marrano origin, in the context of the Jewish diaspora and the Sephardic re-diaspora, will ultimately make more sense and has only become possible with this new historiography, this new cultural heritage and this new teaching of history. This is particularly true in terms of representation (through cultural heritage, organisational culture, leisure and heritage tourism, the dissemination of historiography and the teaching of history). This progress may be taking place, but at the same time it is not taking place, either in Portugal or in Brazil.

At least since the beginning of the 21st century, various Portuguese localities have seen the foundation of cultural heritage initiatives – routes to places, buildings, structures and socio-cultural practices; museums, museum centres and interpretation centres – whose main stated aims have to do with safeguarding memory and representing Portuguese of Jewish, New Christian and Marrano origin¹². Most of these projects are the work of local councils or Jewish communities, and to some extent incorporate the results of objective historiographical research and are linked to the project “Sephardic Routes: valuing Portuguese Jewish identity in intercultural dialogue” – Network of Jewish Quarters of Portugal. Several schools are organising activities on the subject, some of which are supported by Memoshoá - Associação Memória e Ensino do Holocausto [Holocaust Memory and Teaching Association].

However, it is also possible to identify less positive aspects. Some of the initiatives in question are excessively marked by ideological and/or religious proselytism, organisational promotion, territorial differentiation, the promotion of tourism as a mass culture, which ultimately leads to less historiographical rigour and to civic reductionism or Manichaeism. Some of these projects may not respect the privacy and wishes of the members of the Marrano groups. The Portuguese State has not yet assumed the responsibility of creating a heritage and museum offer (ideally with multiple centres) that continuously disseminates objective historiographical knowledge, promotes the multilateral transfer of knowledge and seeks to contribute to qualifying the civil debate on the Jews in the territory that is now Portugal, from Classical Antiquity to the end of the Middle Ages, on the New Christian Portuguese and the Tribunal of the Holy Office of the Inquisition in the modern age, and on Jews and Marranos in contemporary Portugal.

Like many others, the so-called “minority issue” – or “divisive issue” or “difficult memory” – of the Portuguese of Jewish, Neo-Christian or Marrano

¹² E.g. the Sephardic Culture Interpretation Centre of the Northeast of Trás-os-Montes (Bragança), the Jewish Museum (Carção, Vimioso, Bragança), the Jewish Museum of Porto, The Holocaust Museum (Porto), the “Vilar Formoso Fronteira da Paz” Interpretation Centre (Almeida, Guarda), the Isaac Cardoso Jewish Culture Interpretation Centre (Trancoso, Guarda), the Jewish Museum (Belmonte, Castelo Branco), the House of Remembrance of the Jewish Presence (Castelo Branco), the Jewish Remembrance Centre (Vila Cova à Coelheira, Vila Nova de Paiva, Viseu), the future Aristides de Sousa Mendes Museum (Cabanas de Viriato, Carregal do Sal, Viseu), the “Jews of Coimbra” section of the Coimbra City Council Municipal Museum, the Abraão Zacuto Hebrew Museum (Tomar, Santarém), the Damião de Góis and Victims of the Inquisition Museum (Alenquer, Lisbon), the Jewish Community Interpretation Centre (Torres Vedras, Lisbon), the future Tikva – Jewish Museum (Lisbon), the Exiles Remembrance Space (Cascais, Lisbon), the House of the Inquisition – Jewish History Interpretation Centre (Monsaraz, Reguengos de Monsaraz, Évora), the Castelo de Vide Synagogue (Portalegre), the House of Jewish History (Elvas, Portalegre), the Jewish Historical Centre (Faro), the Hebrew Museum Ponta Delgada, São Miguel Island, Azores).

origin is not sufficiently addressed in the Portuguese non-tertiary education system, which continues to be primarily committed to preparing students for tests and exams, which by definition focus on the subjects and curricula considered to be the most important. There are no systemic incentives for schools to regularly organise extracurricular initiatives or activity clubs. The career statute, performance appraisal and in-service training do not encourage history teachers to make frequent use of links with local history and heritage, extra-curricular initiatives and activity clubs.

With regard to Brazil, despite the considerable size of its current Jewish community and the importance of Jews and New Christians in its historical development from the 16th century to the present day, there appear to be fewer initiatives in the areas of cultural heritage¹³ and non-higher education. While the weight of Brazilians of Ashkenazi or Oriental Jewish origin (who arrived since the second half of the 19th century) compared to Brazilians of Sephardic Jewish origin helps to explain the possible lower involvement of Brazilian Jewish organisations, the precariousness of the intervention of state and federal governments would require further contextualisation. The lack of knowledge and representation is even greater for Brazilians of Marrano origin.

To conclude this part of the article, I would like to draw attention to the ethical issues raised by historiographical research, scientific dissemination, heritage and the promotion, through leisure and heritage tourism, of the results of research on victims of discrimination, mass violence or genocide in general and, in particular, on individuals belonging to Portuguese or Brazilian Marrano groups (transitional processes). While the right to research is unquestioned and the subject matter is of great importance, the collection and use of oral history can only be carried out with the express consent of the people concerned.

There is also the question of the dissemination of research and, in particular, of the cultural heritage and the way in which it can be exploited, in the form of leisure and cultural heritage trips, to promote the experience and memory of individuals and groups of Portuguese and Brazilian Marranos. I would like to remind you that what is at stake is, first and foremost, the right to self-management of memory and privacy of individuals who are heirs to

¹³ I have identified the Kabal Zur Israel Synagogue (Recife, Pernambuco), the Abradjin Museum of the History of the Inquisition (Belo Horizonte, Minas Gerais), the Jewish Museum of Rio de Janeiro, the Jewish Museum of São Paulo, the Memorial of Jewish Immigration and Museum of Jewish Immigration (São Paulo), the Holocaust Museum (Curitiba, Paraná), the Marc Chagall Jewish Cultural Institute (Porto Alegre, Rio Grande do Sul).

experiences of resistance and survival, but also of suffering, fear and disguise; of people who are perhaps immersed in syncretic and local popular cultures, less willing to be involved in global debates and sometimes characterised by a strong religious fundamentalism¹⁴.

Conclusion

After defining and attempting to demonstrate the contemporary relevance of the subject of this text, I began by explaining and substantiating my perspectives on the epistemological, theoretical-methodological and deontological aspects that frame current historiography in general and research on Portuguese and Brazilian Jews, New Christians and Marranos in particular. I then tried to summarise the information that has already been reconstructed and the perspectives of analysis that have already been put forward regarding the Jews, New Christians and Marranos who lived in Portugal and Brazil in modern and contemporary times. I drew attention to the possible presence of both anti-Judaism and proto-anti-Semitism from the 16th to the 18th centuries and to the actions of the Tribunal of the Holy Office of the Inquisition.

This was followed by a summary of the characterisations and interpretations that have been made of the ways in which Portugal and Brazil and their civil societies, political systems and state apparatuses have viewed and related to Jews and Marranos from 1820 and 1822 to the present day, both as representations of the past and the future and as individuals (citizens, exiles, refugees or immigrants). I have argued that the use of the theoretical categories of philo-Semitism, radical anti-Semitism and/or moderate anti-Semitism, social Darwinism and positive eugenics, religious fundamentalism

¹⁴ See, in particular, ARENDT, Hannah. *Homens em tempos sombrios* (translated from English). Lisboa: Relógio D'Água Editores, 2021; FRACAPANE, Karel; HASS, Mathias (Eds.). *Holocaust education in a global context*. Paris/Berlim: UNESCO Publishing/Topography of Terror Foundation, 2014; GUTERMAN, Marco. *Holocausto e memória*. São Paulo: Editora Contexto, 2020; GUTTERMAN, Bella; SHALEV, Avner (Eds.). *To bear witness. Holocaust remembrance at Yad Vashem*. Jerusalém: Yad Vashem, 2005; JESUS, Carlos Gustavo Nóbrega de. *Anti-semitismo e nacionalismo, negacionismo e memória. Revisão Editora e as estratégias da intolerância (1987-2003)*. São Paulo: Editora UNESP, 2006; LACAPRA, Dominick. *History and memory after Auschwitz*. Ithaca: Cornell University Press, 1998; NUNES, João Paulo Avelãs Nunes. "Modalidades de intolerância no passado e no presente: o exemplo do anti-semitismo", *Trabalhos de Antropologia e Etnologia*, v. 63, 2023, p. 167-188; SEN, Amartya. *Identidade e violência* (translated from English). Lisboa: Edições Tinta-da-China, 2007; TRAVERSO, Enzo. *O passado, modos de usar* (translated from French). Lisboa: Edições Unipop, 2012; WHIGHAM, Kerry. *Resonant violence. Affect, memory, and activism in pós-genocide societies*. Londres: Rutgers University Press, 2022.

and Zionism is appropriate for producing more objective knowledge about the subject in question.

Finally, the use and non-use of history and heritage education, organisational culture and leisure and heritage tourism in Portugal and Brazil to disseminate knowledge about Jews, New Christians and Marranos was reviewed and assessed. Despite the developments that have taken place in recent decades, which are primarily the responsibility of Jewish communities, local councils and higher education institutions, I have highlighted the precarious presence or absence of the Portuguese and Brazilian states (federal and state) in this area of transitional processes and memory and identity policies.

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The identity of crime: contributions from medicine and physical anthropology in Portugal (1880–1940)¹

A identidade do crime: contribuições da medicina e da antropologia física em Portugal (1880–1940)

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Abstract

The aim of this article is to contribute to understanding how people who were considered criminals were identified between the end of the nineteenth century and the end of the 1930s (the heyday of eugenics theories) in Portugal. It begins by presenting some examples of theorization and practices associated with the so-called “criminal anthropology”. The examples presented refer to the Porto School of Medicine and Surgery, the University of Porto, hospitals and scientific societies, such as the Carlos Ribeiro Society and the Portuguese Society of Anthropology and Ethnology. Authors connected to other institutions and hospitals in Coimbra and Lisbon were also analysed. In the process of identifying people, anthropometric posts played an important role, as did “criminal anthropology” courses at universities and the publications that appeared. All these examples ended up contributing to disseminating proposals for recognition, but also forms of control and surveillance. The article analyses the work carried out by doctors and legal doctors. Among the various examples given, the work which António Mendes Correia (1888–1960) produced on the subject stands out, taking into account his theoretical and methodological, but also moral and ethical conceptions and his interest in psychiatry in the 1910s and 1920s, which would later lead him to the field of anthropology. At the end of the article, an explanation is sought of how intellectual elites, when trying to identify and understand deviant behaviour, also ended up producing and reproducing prejudices.

Keywords: crime; eugenics; physical anthropology; medicine; Portugal.

Resumo

Este artigo pretende trazer um contributo sobre o entendimento de como era feita a identificação das pessoas consideradas criminosas, entre os finais

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do século XIX e o final dos anos 30 do século XX (período auge das teorias eugénicas) em Portugal. Começa por apresentar alguns exemplos de teorização e práticas associadas à então chamada “antropologia criminal”. Os exemplos apresentados reportam-se à Escola Médico-Cirúrgica do Porto, à Universidade do Porto, a hospitais e a sociedades científicas, como a Sociedade Carlos Ribeiro e a Sociedade Portuguesa de Antropologia e Etnologia. Foram também analisados autores ligados a outras instituições e hospitais, em Coimbra e em Lisboa. No processo de identificação de pessoas, os postos antropométricos tiveram um papel importante, assim como os cursos de “antropologia criminal” nas universidades e as publicações que foram surgindo. Todos estes exemplos acabaram por contribuir para disseminar propostas de reconhecimento, mas também formas de controle e vigilância. O artigo analisa o trabalho realizado por médicos e médicos legistas. Entre os vários exemplos dados, é destacado o trabalho de António Mendes Correia (1888–1960), produzido sobre o tema, tendo em conta as suas concepções teóricas e metodológicas, mas também morais e éticas e o seu interesse pela psiquiatria nos anos 10 e 20 do século XX, que haveria de o conduzir mais tarde para os domínios da antropologia. No final, procura-se explicitar como as elites intelectuais, ao tentarem identificar e compreender comportamentos desviantes, acabaram também por produzir e reproduzir preconceitos.

Palavras-chave: crime; eugenia; antropologia física; medicina; Portugal.

Introduction

Between the late nineteenth century and the first half of the twentieth century, some experts conceived anthropology as a science with practical applications. Such applications were considered to exist, for example, within what was defined as “criminal anthropology”. From the second half of the nineteenth century, we can find images, representing individuals from the lower social classes, individuals considered criminals, the mentally ill and women, as well as works on groups considered different or which had deviant behaviour. Often, it was the elites, or the most knowledgeable individuals, who appropriated the power to classify and compare human groups. However, those classifying were often following models of development and retardation – present, for example, in the reports of universal and colonial expositions²

² On the phenomenon of world fairs and exhibitions, and its importance to the history of anthropology, see: MATOS, Patrícia Ferraz de; BIRKALAN-GEDIK, Hande; BARRERA-GONZÁLEZ, Andrés; VAIL, Pegi (eds). *World Fairs. Special Issue of Anthropological Journal of European Cultures*, 2022, vol. 31, no. 2, pp. 1–132.

– denouncing the prejudices of those who elaborated them³. In this context, the so-called primitive peoples, for example and above all Africans, were compared with less intellectually gifted groups.

Darwinist thinking, and the foundations of social hierarchy and eugenics⁴ relied heavily on anthropometric measurements. From that point until Cesare Lombroso (1835–1909) and his disciples considered the mentally ill and criminals as comparable to the so-called primitive peoples was a short step. In this context, it was mainly physicians and specialists in physical anthropology, but also in other scientific or disciplinary areas, who had the task of classifying and weaving considerations about humanity, and in their works we can find remnants of Darwinian thought.

The intention of this article is to make a precise analysis of some of these works on “criminal anthropology”. The examples that will be presented were linked to institutions such as the Porto School of Medicine and Surgery, the University of Porto, hospitals and scientific societies, such as the Carlos Ribeiro Society and the Portuguese Society of Anthropology and Ethnology, all of these in the city of Porto, but also other institutions that played a fundamental role in this process in Coimbra and Lisbon. The authors analysed will be mainly doctors, or legal doctors, or people with training in medicine who later dedicated themselves to other areas. This is precisely the case of the anthropologist and archaeologist António Mendes Correia (1888–1960)⁵, whose work produced in the field of “criminal anthropology” will be analysed in more detail. The period of analysis is between 1880 (the year of what is considered the first dissertation on crime) and the end of the 1930s. The examples presented throughout the article will seek to highlight how, behind processes of identification and possible treatment or monitoring of deviant

³ On the relations between anthropology, colonialism and eugenics, see: LEVINE, Philippa. “Anthropology, Colonialism, and Eugenics” In BASHFORD, Alison; LEVINE, Philippa (eds), *The Oxford Handbook of the History of Eugenics*. Oxford, Oxford University Press, pp. 43–61. For the Portuguese case, see: MATOS, Patrícia Ferraz de. “Aperfeiçoar a ‘raça’, salvar a nação: Eugenia, teorias nacionalistas e situação colonial em Portugal” In *Trabalhos de Antropologia e Etnologia*, 2010, vol. 50, pp. 89–111.

⁴ On the history of eugenics in the international context, see: BASHFORD, Alison; LEVINE, Philippa (eds). *The Oxford Handbook of the History of Eugenics*. Oxford, Oxford University Press, 2010. KÜHL, Stefan. *For the Betterment of the Race: The Rise and Fall of the International Movement for Eugenics and Racial Hygiene*. New York, Palgrave Macmillan, 2013 (1997). On the history of Latin eugenics in comparative context, see: TURDA, Marius; GILLETTE, Aaron. *Latin Eugenics in Comparative Perspective*. London & New York, Bloomsbury. For a history of eugenics in Portugal, see: CLEMINSON, Richard. *Catholicism, Race and Empire: Eugenics in Portugal (1900-1950)*. Budapest & New York, Central European University Press.

⁵ On the life and work of Mendes Correia, mentor of the Porto School of Anthropology, see: MATOS, Patrícia Ferraz de. *Anthropology, Nationalism and Colonialism: Mendes Correia and the Porto School of Anthropology*. Oxford & New York, Berghahn Books, 2023.

behaviours, there were often also prejudices, the justification of which could not come from the health or merely biological domain, but rather from social and cultural factors and which, therefore, deserve a deeper reflection.

“Criminal anthropology” in Portugal (first incursions: 1880s–1900s)

The tradition of “criminal anthropology” studies in Portugal dates from the late nineteenth century. The 1880s and 1890s saw the rise and establishment of means to control crime and individuals considered criminals, and the improvement of techniques and instruments for measurement. At that time, anthropology was also seen as anthropometry⁶.

At the Porto School of Medicine and Surgery (*Escola Médico-Cirúrgica do Porto*) some dissertations were on crime and prisons⁷. The first of them, entitled *O Crime: Apontamentos para a sua sistematização* [Crime: Notes for its systematization] by Roberto Frias, in 1880, appeared four years after *L'uomo delinquente* (1876)⁸ by Cesare Lombroso (1835–1909), an Italian criminalist who linked the physical aspect with behaviour and a tendency for criminal activity⁹.

In 1885, with the lead of the doctor Luís Bastos de Freitas Viegas (1869–1928), the anthropology laboratory in the Hospital Conde de Ferreira at Porto initiated its activity with the objective of implementing official teaching of criminal anthropology. Freitas Viegas was also professor of anatomy at the Porto School of Medicine and Surgery, founder and first president of the Portuguese Society of Anthropology and Ethnology (SPAÉ) in 1918. The *Revista de Ciências Naturaes e Sociaes* [Journal of Natural and Social Sciences] (1889–1898), of the Carlos Ribeiro Society (1888–98), also published works on

⁶ MADUREIRA, Nuno Luís. “A Estatística do Corpo: Antropologia Física e Antropometria na Alvorada do Século XX” In *Etnográfica*, 2003, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 283–303.

⁷ FRIAS, Roberto. *O Crime: Apontamentos para a sua sistematização* (degree dissertation in medicine). Porto, Escola Médico-Cirúrgica do Porto, 1880. PEREIRA, João António. *As prisões* (degree dissertation in medicine). Porto, Escola Médico-Cirúrgica do Porto, 1881. FONSECA, Sérgio Moreira da. *O crime: Considerações gerais* (degree dissertation in medicine). Porto, Escola Médico-Cirúrgica do Porto, 1902. BASTOS, Álvaro Teixeira. *A tatuagem nos criminosos* (degree dissertation in medicine). Porto, Escola Médico-Cirúrgica do Porto, 1903. OLIVEIRA, Manuel José de. *O problema de Lombroso: Estudo crítico de bio-sociologia sobre a teoria atávica do crime* (degree dissertation in medicine). Porto, Escola Médico-Cirúrgica do Porto, 1904.

⁸ LOMBROSO, Cesare. *L'uomo delinquent*. Milano, Hoepli, 1876.

⁹ On the work of Lombroso, see: SANSONE, Livio. *La Galassia Lombroso*. Roma, Editori Laterza, 2022. This book results from several years of research, taking Lombroso's network into account, not only in Italy, but all around the world, especially in Europe and South America.

criminology. In volume II of this journal, the doctor Júlio de Matos (1856–1922) analysed the work *Crime et criminel*¹⁰ [Crime and criminal] (1892) by Francisco Ferraz de Macedo (1845–1907).

According to the doctor and ethnologist José Leite de Vasconcelos (1858–1941), Ferraz de Macedo “diligently devoted his efforts to criminal anthropology”, having published not also the already mentioned *Crime et criminel* (1892), but also *Bosquejos de Antropologia Criminal*¹¹ [Essays on Criminal Anthropology] (1900) and *Os criminosos “evadidos do Limoeiro em 1847”*¹² [The criminals “escaped from Limoeiro in 1847”] (1901)¹³. Ferraz de Macedo born in Portugal (Águeda), but graduated in medicine in Brazil (Rio de Janeiro), where he led his clinical practice for some years. He attended the Paris School of Anthropology and eventually settled in Lisbon.

Another example came from António Augusto da Rocha Peixoto (1866–1909), one of the founders of the Carlos Ribeiro Society in Porto, who had the work “A tatuagem em Portugal”¹⁴ [Tattoos in Portugal], published in the volume II of *Revista de Sciencias Naturaes e Sociaes* (1893), influenced by Lombroso and “criminal anthropology”¹⁵. António Aurélio da Costa Ferreira (1879–1922), a “close friend of Ferraz de Macedo”, according to Leite de Vasconcelos,¹⁶ also contributed to this area with the work *La capacité crânienne chez les criminels portugais*¹⁷ [Cranial capacity in Portuguese criminals], published in 1905 by the Société d’Anthropologie de Paris. Costa Ferreira graduated at the University of Coimbra Faculties of Philosophy (1899) and Medicine (1905). Following several periods in Paris, he settled in Lisbon in 1907. He was minister of internal development (1912–13) and in 1914 he created the Medical-Pedagogical Institute for the teaching of the mentally disabled. He

¹⁰ MACEDO, Francisco Ferraz de. *Crime et criminel: essai synthétique d’observations anatomiques, physiologiques, pathologiques et psychiques sur des délinquants vivants et morts selon la méthode et les procédés anthropologiques les plus rigoureux*. Paris, Belhate & Thomas, 1892.

¹¹ MACEDO, Francisco Ferraz de. *Bosquejos de Antropologia Criminal*. Lisbon, Imprensa Nacional, 1900.

¹² MACEDO, Francisco Ferraz de. *Os criminosos “evadidos do Limoeiro em 1847”*. Lisbon, Tipografia da Papelaria Palhares, 1901. From the seventeenth to the nineteenth century, Limoeiro was the main prison in Lisbon and also the central prison of the Portuguese penal system.

¹³ VASCONCELOS, José Leite de. “A Antropologia portuguesa como fonte de investigação etnográfica” In *Boletim de Etnografia*, 1928, no. 4, p. 9.

¹⁴ PEIXOTO, António Augusto da Rocha. “A tatuagem em Portugal” In *Revista de Sciencias Naturaes e Sociaes*. Porto, Typographia Occidental, 1893, vol. 2, pp. 97–111 and 145.

¹⁵ See, for example: CORREIA, António Mendes. *A Escola Antropológica Portuense*. Lisbon, Bertrand, 1941, p. 11.

¹⁶ VASCONCELOS, “A Antropologia portuguesa como fonte...”, 1928, p. 9.

¹⁷ FERREIRA, António Aurélio da Costa. “La capacité crânienne chez les criminels portugais” In *Bulletins et Mémoires de la Société d’Anthropologie de Paris*, 1905, vol. 6, pp. 357–361.

was a founder of SPAE and a local correspondent of the Royal Anthropological Institute of Great Britain and Ireland from 1910.

Anthropometric Posts

On August of 1899, legislation was published creating the Anthropometric Posts, to undertake “anthropometric measurements of all prisoners” who entered the Central Prison or were dispatched by police commissioners or criminal investigation judges (article 81)¹⁸. According to the Decree-Law of November of the same year, the anthropometric posts should be equipped with the Bertillon system¹⁹.

The Decree-Law of September 1901 established the creation of posts for the collection of photographs, physical measurements and fingerprints in the civil prisons of Lisbon, Porto and Ponta Delgada²⁰. According to this decree (article 77), prisons should have an anthropometric post for the study of criminal anthropology and to assist police and court services “to verify, as precisely as possible, of the identity of individuals who entered therein”²¹.

This method, which was based on “the principle that there are no persons who exactly resemble each other and that the dimensions of certain bones, unchanged from adulthood, differ considerably from one specimen to another”, would allow individuals to be identified via particular distinguishing marks and measurements of height, length of feet and the middle toe. The colour of the iris, hair, beard and skin must also be observed and placed on the prisoner’s identification card with other specifics, together with front and profile photographs, to which a serial number was assigned²².

On March 2, 1902, the Central Anthropometric Post was created next to the Civil Prison and the Tribunal da Relação do Porto [Porto Court of Appeal], under the direction of Luís de Freitas Viegas. The *Revista de Antropologia Criminal* [Journal of Criminal Anthropology] was published from this post; it was directed by António Ferreira Augusto (1851–1907) and Freitas

¹⁸ <http://digitarq.cpf.dgarq.gov.pt/details?id=39150>, accessed December 2011.

¹⁹ System developed by French anthropologist Alphonse Bertillon (1853–1914), in 1879, to identify and describe individuals using measurements of specific parts of the body (such as head, face, ears, nose, hands and feet) and frontal and profile photographs. The techniques used in this system were used to identify individuals with deviant behaviour or those considered criminals.

²⁰ <http://www.redeconhecimentojustica.mj.pt/Category.aspx?id=78>, accessed December 2011.

²¹ <http://digitarq.cpf.dgarq.gov.pt/details?id=39150>, accessed December 2011.

²² <http://digitarq.cpf.dgarq.gov.pt/details?id=39150>, accessed December 2011.

Viegas, and two issues were published²³. This post also gave rise to the work *A Tatuagem nos Criminosos [Tattoos on Criminals]*, in 1903, by Álvaro Teixeira Bastos (1879–1945)²⁴. The post was succeeded by the Department of Criminal Anthropology, Experimental Psychology and Civil Identification and by the Porto Institute of Criminology. The Anthropometric Post collected “thousands of anthropometric and fingerprint records, in addition to photographs” and tattoos²⁵. The documentary background of this post, currently under the auspices of the Portuguese Photography Centre, consists mostly of portraits of prisoners.

At the beginning of the twentieth century, at the University of Coimbra, the discipline of anthropology, created by Bernardino Machado (1851–1944), in 1885, also had a component regarding the Course in Criminal Anthropology, approved in academic year 1908/09, with the designation of Course of Anthropometry.

Creation of the identity card in Portugal

The identity card emerged with the republican regime, after 1910. In 1912, the first attempt was made to create an archive with the identification data of citizens, using scientific knowledge and the techniques used in criminal identification. The previously mentioned Aurélio da Costa Ferreira, as minister of internal development, proposed creating an identity card for all civil servants in ministries and general directorates. The document was supposed to include fingerprints of the five fingers of the right hand, particular signs and a photograph, but few employees requested the aforementioned card.

In the beginning, the creation of identification archives and identity cards raised suspicions. Some citizens feared that such initiatives were a way for the state to control citizens²⁶ and some working-class people were afraid of being seen as criminals. A curiosity is that the first identity card to be issued in Portugal, in 1914, was that of Manuel de Arriaga (1840–1917) – the first president of the Portuguese Republic between 1911 and 1915.

²³ PESSOA, Alberto. “História da introdução em Portugal dos métodos científicos de Identificação Criminal” In *Congressos do Mundo Português: Congresso da História da Actividade Científica Portuguesa, Ciências Físico-Matemáticas e Militares, Ciências Naturais e Biológicas*. Lisbon, Comissão Executiva dos Centenários, 1940, vol. 12, pp. 709–722.

²⁴ BASTOS, *A tatuagem nos criminosos...*

²⁵ CORREIA, *A Escola Antropológica Portuense...*, p. 14.

²⁶ MADUREIRA, “A Estatística do Corpo...”.

Only in 1918 was the Lisbon Identification Archive created, replacing the Central Criminal Identification and Statistics Archive, and civil identification began. In 1919, the identity card was instituted by a Decree-Law (no. 5266, of 16 March), which stipulated that it was mandatory for “all persons (...) who were appointed to any civil public office in Lisbon”. For the remaining people, of both sexes, it was optional. The document had four pages, on which were inscribed the name, name of parents, place of birth, date of birth and profession, particular physical signs, a photograph, fingerprint and signature (if the person in question could write).

In 1927, the identity card became mandatory for the exercise of any profession and for enrolment in any secondary or higher education establishment. In that year, civil identification services were distributed among three archives in Lisbon, Porto and Coimbra²⁷. In 1957, the identity card had two pages and in 1970 only one page. From 1986 onwards, it became mandatory to use colour photographs. In 1992, plastic was introduced around the card and a security strip above the photograph. From 2008 onwards, the identity card began to be gradually replaced by the citizen’s card.

“Criminal anthropology” in Portugal (second incursions: 1910s–1930s)

“Criminal anthropology” was also one of the subjects of attention at the SPAE). The purpose of this society was to:

Stimulate and promote, in Portugal, the study of anthropological methods, of zoological anthropology, ethnic anthropology, prehistoric anthropology and archaeology, experimental psychology, ethnography, and of its derived or applied scientific branches, such as military, pedagogical, clinical, criminal, judiciary, etc. anthropologies²⁸.

The SPAE, which published *Trabalhos de Antropologia e Etnologia* [*Works on Anthropology and Ethnology*] exchanged its journal with others on anthropology, physical anthropology, archaeology and criminology, like the journal *Archivio de Antropologia Criminale* [*Criminal Anthropology Archive*], from Turin, from 1920.

²⁷ <https://www.jn.pt/nacional/bilhete-de-identidade-nasce-com-a-republica--1535340.html>, accessed in August 2022.

²⁸ *Estatutos da Sociedade Portuguesa de Antropologia e Etnologia*. Porto, SPAE, 1918, p. 3.

Works on “criminal anthropology” were also presented at the scientific sessions held by this society. This was the case of the lectures: “Antropologia criminal integral” [Integral Criminal Anthropology] (1925); “Fórmulas e perfis individuais em Antropologia Criminal” [Formulas and individual profiles in Criminal Anthropology] (1933); and “Novas directrizes de antropologia criminal” [New guidelines for criminal anthropology] (1936), all presented by Mendes Correia.

Despite that, “criminal anthropology” was mainly the charge of doctors and legal doctors. In some academic years, criminal anthropology was taught as an independent subject. In the case of Porto, there was “a Department of Criminal Anthropology as a dependency of the Ministry of Justice” and this branch constituted “one of the subjects in the course for coroners” (legal doctors)²⁹. In addition to the works of anthropology produced at the University of Porto Institute of Anthropology (IAUP), others emerged from the Criminal Anthropology and Civil Identification Department, then Criminology Institute (directed first by Joaquim A. Pires de Lima [1877–1951], who succeeded Freitas Viegas, and then by Luís de Pina [1901–1972], all of whom were doctors).

In the reports prepared by physicians, the inclusion of medical terms in expressions which were more appropriate to other contexts, such as “social parasites”, to classify people whose behaviour was considered deviant, is notable. Homosexuals, for example, long classified among the mentally ill, received harsh criticism from doctors: men were supposed to be virile, not effeminate, and specialists attempted to correct these tendencies³⁰.

Between 1912 and 1939, Mendes Correia published several articles and books on criminal anthropology³¹, both in Portugal and abroad, as is

²⁹ CORREIA, *A Escola Antropológica Portuense...*, p. 16.

³⁰ Only in 1973 were they withdrawn from the American Psychiatric Association’s list of mental illnesses.

³¹ CORREIA, António Mendes. “Instrução e Criminalidade em Portugal” In offprint of *Porto Médico*, 1912a, vol. 1, pp. 1–7. CORREIA, António Mendes. “A Situação dos Médicos Legistas e os Progressos da Antropologia Criminal” In *Porto Médico*, 1912b, vol. 2, pp. 46–53. CORREIA, António Mendes. *Os Criminosos Portugueses: Estudos de Antropologia Criminal*, 1st ed. Porto, Imprensa Portuguesa, 1913; 2nd ed. Coimbra, França Amado, 1914. CORREIA, António Mendes. “Um Delinquente Habitual: Exame Médico Antropológico” In offprint of *Gazeta dos Hospitais do Porto*, 1913b, vol. 9, pp. 1–14. CORREIA, António Mendes. “A Criminalidade Precoce” In *A Tutoria*, 1913c, vol. 11, pp. 179–81. CORREIA, António Mendes. *Crianças Delinquentes: Subsídios para o Estudo da Criminalidade em Portugal*, Coimbra, Typ. França Amado, 1915a. CORREIA, António Mendes. “Antropologia Criminal Integral: O Normal Delinquente e a Crise Moral” In offprint of *Boletim do Instituto de Criminologia*, 1925, vol. 5, pp. 1–25. CORREIA, António Mendes. “Le Normal Délinquant et la Crise Morale” In *Revue Anthropologique*, 1926, vol. 7–9, pp. 1–22. CORREIA, António Mendes. *A Nova Antropologia Criminal*. Porto, Imprensa Portuguesa, 1931a. CORREIA, António Mendes. “Inquérito sobre as Ideias Morais em Criminosos e Não Criminosos” In offprint of *Arquivo da Repartição de Antropologia Criminal, Psicologia Experimental e Identificação Civil do Porto*, 1931b, vol. 1, no. 2, pp. 101–5. CORREIA, António Mendes. “O Prof.

the case of the conference at Brussels Law Courts on 11 May 1931, under the auspices of the Belgian Union of Criminal Law and the Royal Belgian Society of Anthropology and Prehistory³². Taking this extensiveness of Mendes Correia's work on criminal anthropology into account, the next section will be dedicated to this author's analyses.

Genius and Talent in Pathology (1911)

Mendes Correia's interest in studying individuals with deviant behaviour began in the dissertation for his medical course – *O Génio e o Talento na Patologia [Genius and Talent in Pathology]* (1911) – in which he drew up a critical overview of the doctrines that establish the pathological roots of genius and talent.³³ He sought to find traces of genius and talent in patients in the Hospital de Rilhafoles and in the Hospital Conde de Ferreira, analysing their musical and poetic compositions, drawings, paintings and portraits. Lombroso's work seems to inspire his dissertation, but mainly in criticism of it.

According to Correia, in the work *L'uomo delinquente* (1876), Lombroso's intention was to site crime as an atavistic concept.³⁴ However, many behaviours³⁵ were not explained by atavistic regression, but by mesological

Carrara e 'A Nova Antropologia Criminal'" In offprint of *Arquivo da Repartição de Antropologia Criminal, Psicologia Experimental e Identificação Civil do Porto*, 1931c, vol. 1, no. 3, pp. 181–90. CORREIA, António Mendes. "Ideias Morais em Jovens Criminosos e Não Criminosos" In *Asociación Española para el Progreso de las Ciencias*. Madrid, Huelves y Compañía, 1932a, pp. 55–8. CORREIA, António Mendes. "La Nouvelle Anthropologie Criminelle" In offprint of *Scientia: Revue Internationale de Synthèse Scientifique*, 1932b, vol. 51, pp. 357–65. CORREIA, António Mendes. "L'Étude du Criminel en Portugal" In offprint of *Revue de Droit Pénal et de Criminologie*, 1932c, vol. 2, pp. 1–28. CORREIA, António Mendes. "La Nuova Antropologia Criminale" In offprint of *Giustizia penale*, 1936a, vol. 1, pp. 1–35. CORREIA, António Mendes. "La Nuova e la Vecchia Antropologia Criminale" In offprint of *Giustizia penale*, 1936b, vol. 7, pp. 1–50. CORREIA, António Mendes. "A Nova e a Velha Antropologia Criminal" In offprint of *Arquivos de Medicina Legal e Identificação*, Rio de Janeiro, Imprensa Nacional, 1937, vol. 13, pp. 1–30. CORREIA, António Mendes. "Les 'Profils' en Anthropologie, Biotypologie et Criminologie" In *Bolletino del Comitato Internazionale per L'Unificazione dei Metodi e per la Sintesi in Antropologia Eugénica e Biologia*, 1939, vol. 9, pp. 1–6.

³² CORREIA, "Étude du Criminel en Portugal"...

³³ CORREIA, António Mendes. *O Génio e o Talento na Patologia*. Porto, Imprensa Portuguesa, 1911.

³⁴ LOMBROSO, Cesare. *L'uomo delinquent*. Milano, Hoepli, 1876.

³⁵ The relationship between bodies and behaviour and between bones and other physical elements is explicitly suggested in: STOCKING, George W. Jr. (ed.). *Bones, Bodies, Behaviour: Essays on Biological Anthropology*. London, University of Wisconsin Press, 1988, vol. 5. On attempts to correlate morphological characters with behavioural parameters, particularly in the North American and French tradition during the nineteenth century, see: STOCKING, George W. Jr. *Race, Culture and Evolution: Essays in the History of Anthropology*. Chicago, University of Chicago Press, 1968. GOULD, Stephen Jay. *The Mismeasure of Man*. New York, Norton & Company, 1981. STEPAN, Nancy Leys. *The Idea of Race in Science: Great Britain 1800–1960*. London, MacMillan Press, 1982. On the Brazilian case, see: CORRÊA, Mariza. *As Ilusões da Liberdade: A Escola Nina Rodrigues e a Antropologia no Brasil*. 3rd ed. Rio de Janeiro, Fiocruz, 2013 (1998). SCHWARCZ,

conditions of a social nature, that is, “it was necessary to recognise the place of moral madness, misery, alcoholism, political tyranny, mental alienation and finally other social and individual causes of human criminality”³⁶. For Correia, if Lombrosian exclusivism prevailed, the penal system’s only need would be to eliminate criminals, “once the impossibility of correcting their atavism was proven”; however, in criminal matters, “the principle of *reparation* for crime” had already been established, “the *penal substitutes*” (suggested by Enrico Ferri’s doctrines)³⁷ and the suggested “systems for *correction* of criminals, especially minors”³⁸. According to Correia:

The social value of geniuses is enormous and invaluable. They have been the vanguard of civilization, true agents of social progress. And modern humanity relegates them, summarily and with barely no defence, to the field of mental pathology! If this is not indeed an injustice, as we suppose, it is at least ingratitude³⁹.

Phrenological positions and the prejudices underlying them ended up discredited, not only because they were inconclusive, but because they were to be found at the origin of atrocities carried out on innocent people. As well as refuting the identification of genius and madness, Correia rejected Max Simon Nordau’s ideas (published in *Entartung*⁴⁰ (1892–1893)), referring to the case of Friedrich Nietzsche as evidence. Correia, then a medical finalist, believed that although Nietzsche was a genius, his madness only appeared at an advanced stage of his life⁴¹. Correia furthermore claimed that both in hygiene and in forensic medicine, a doctor “is not an ancient physicist”, a “remote surgeon” or an “archaic healer”, but “a true sociologist, who brings social facts into play and intervenes powerfully in the collective life of human societies”⁴². From his studies in hospitals, Correia concluded that: “the mentality of the alienated does not reach the limits of genius”; “among the alienated who have

Lilia Moritz. *O Espectáculo das Raças: Cientistas, Instituições e Questão Racial no Brasil: 1870-1930*. São Paulo, Companhia das Letras, 2007 [1993]. SOUZA, Vanderlei Sebastião de. *Renato Kehl e Eugenia no Brasil: Ciência, Raça e Nação no Período Entreguerras*. Guarapuava, Editora Unicentro, 2019.

³⁶ CORREIA, *O Génio e o Talento...*, pp. 3–4.

³⁷ Enrico Ferri (1856–1929), founder of modern criminology, attributed biological e social causes to crimes.

³⁸ CORREIA, *O Génio e o Talento...*, p. 5.

³⁹ CORREIA, *O Génio e o Talento...*, p. 6.

⁴⁰ *Entartung* is a German word whose meaning is degeneration. NORDAU, Max Simon, *Entartung*, 2 vols, Berlin, Carl Duncker, 1892–1893.

⁴¹ CORREIA, *O Génio e o Talento...*, p. 101–102.

⁴² CORREIA, *O Génio e o Talento...*, p. 7.

artistic tendencies, painters predominated, followed by poets”; the alienated who were authors of appreciable works of art, “were already artists ... before their illness”⁴³.

The Portuguese Criminals: Studies in Criminal Anthropology (1913, 1914)

Subsequently, Mendes Correia wrote on individuals with deviant behaviour, the “delinquent”, and “delinquent children”. He wrote specifically on criminal anthropology and it was in this area that he passed his public exams to be named second tenured assistant professor of anthropology at the University of Porto Faculty of Sciences in 1913, with the dissertation *Os Criminosos Portugueses: Estudos de Antropologia Criminal*⁴⁴ [*Portuguese Criminals: Studies in Criminal Anthropology*]. In the same year, he worked as associate judge and as a doctor at the Porto Central Youth Detention Centre, where he issued medical opinions.

Correia divided the criminals into “random” or “occasional” offenders, and “habitual” offenders. This division suggests that he believed there were false criminals – the occasional ones, like most murderers – and true ones – the habitual ones (with a congenital or acquired habit), such as thieves and vagrants. Occasional criminals were those who were free from:

profound and particular criminal tendencies, they accidentally commit a crime, moved by a powerful momentary factor, such as misery, hunger, drunkenness, passion, an emotional state, love, honour, anger, hate, revenge, or a political or religious ideal⁴⁵.

The anthropologist João Fatela, who analysed violence in Portugal between 1926 and 1946, also concluded that “homicide is a practice of adult men with no criminal past, and occurs in a context of strong relational proximity” and that, “despite the absence of global statistics by cause, everything indicates that homicides resulting from serious pathological

⁴³ CORREIA, *O Gênio e o Talento...*, p. 179. Correia’s interest in psychiatry and mental illness is contemporary with the work of eminent figures in medicine and psychiatry in Portugal, such as the nineteenth-century alienists and Miguel Bombarda, Júlio de Matos and Sobral Cid. On the work of these doctors, see: QUINTAIS, Luís. *Mestres da Verdade Invisível: No Arquivo da Psiquiatria Forense Portuguesa*. Coimbra, Imprensa da Universidade de Coimbra, 2012.

⁴⁴ CORREIA, António Mendes. *Os Criminosos Portugueses: Estudos de Antropologia Criminal*. 1st ed. Porto, Imprensa Portuguesa, 1913a.

⁴⁵ CORREIA, António Mendes. *Os Criminosos Portugueses: Estudos de Antropologia Criminal*, 2nd ed. Coimbra, França Amado, 1914, p. 52.

anomalies are rare, as are, in fact, homicides associated with organized crime”⁴⁶.

The photographs included in the book *Os Criminosos Portugueses* [*Portuguese Criminals*], by Correia⁴⁷ (1914), were taken in prisons, or places that Michel Foucault would call surveillance spaces, in which the power of resistance is denied⁴⁸. Analysing the cases portrayed in photographs, we can see that men were mainly associated with crimes such as manufacturing counterfeit currency, forgery of documents, drunkenness and rape, while women were criminalized for infanticide or for having caused an abortion. Another interesting aspect is that beggars (*mendigos*) were considered vagrants (*vadios*), or that they could not be integrated into society and therefore were close to criminals or grouped with them in this type of analysis.

Limits of classification and determination

Mendes Correia considered that “it is premature to intend to establish an exclusively endocrinological classification of offenders”⁴⁹. According to him, the environment, although it was not omnipotent, was the “breakthrough condition”, thus emphasizing the neo-Lamarckist influence on his work. In many cases the environment acted as a factor of stimulus and advantage, and although “tendencies” may be inherited, it is “education and the environment” that complete the individual constitution⁵⁰. Correia included prostitutes in an “anthropological and social category” close to that of the criminal, as “degeneration, neurosis, psychosis, especially moral madness, hysteria and mental weakness, spread abundant stigmatization” among them; just as criminals were victims of their social environment, prostitutes were influenced by “deplorable social conditions, such as abandonment by their

⁴⁶ FATELA, João. *O Sangue e a Rua: Elementos para uma Antropologia da Violência em Portugal (1926-1946)*. Lisbon, Dom Quixote, 1989, pp. 52, 58.

⁴⁷ CORREIA, *Os Criminosos Portugueses...*, 1914.

⁴⁸ For a comparative study on the functioning of Brazilian prisons between 1930s and 1960s, based on the case study of a Penitentiary in Florianópolis, see: BORGES, Viviane. “O arquivo e a prisão: a premissa de inferioridade dos indivíduos incômodos (Brasil, 1930 – ao tempo presente)” In *Revista Brasileira de História*, 2023, vol. 43, no. 94, pp. 123–144.

⁴⁹ CORREIA, António Mendes. *Introdução à Antropobiologia*. Coimbra, Imprensa da Universidade, 1933, pp. 69, 75.

⁵⁰ CORREIA, *Introdução à Antropobiologia...*, p. 83.

family, abuse, misery, seduction, unhappy love affairs, bad or no education”; so, for Correia, there was a parallelism with criminality⁵¹.

Although Correia recognized the existence of individuals with greater predisposition to deviant and criminal behaviour, he denied that there was a “type” of born delinquent, since any individual can be a delinquent. Correia suggested the possibility of finding an index of Portuguese value based on the study of criminality, as there was a lower percentage in Portugal than that of countries considered more cultured and progressive⁵². Homicides, for example, were more frequent than in France and northern countries, but less so than in Austria, Spain, Hungary and Italy; in the case of theft, Portugal had the lowest numbers and “given the poor economic conditions of the Portuguese population, their family, legal and political disorganization and the poor educational environment..., more advanced delinquency would be expected”, according to Correia⁵³.

Besides, the real numbers of violence for the period analysed are not in fact known. João Fatela suggests that violence was hidden in Portugal as a cultural practice and that this occurred not only in this country, or during the António de Oliveira Salazar (1889–1970) dictatorship, but throughout the West, “as it became a delinquent practice”.⁵⁴ According to Fatela, this concealment cannot be separated from the legal-criminal movement that, from the nineteenth century onwards, began to hide it in the delinquent’s body and hide it in prison in order to correct it and “the legal definition of crime or tort” was the basis for bounding a field of investigation that determines the logic of violence⁵⁵.

The history of anthropology was thus linked to the history of criminology. Various anthropologists (including Correia) were involved in this criminalization; perhaps this is the reason behind Correia’s need to isolate himself from these intentions when he stated in *A Nova Antropologia Criminal* that his work was the testimony of an anthropologist⁵⁶ and that it was the jurists who should establish prophylaxis and therapies for the individual factors of crime. For this reason, except on incidental occasions, Correia set

⁵¹ CORREIA, *Os Criminosos Portugueses...*, 1914, p. 77–8.

⁵² CORREIA, *Os Criminosos Portugueses...*, 1914.

⁵³ CORREIA, António Mendes. *Raça e Nacionalidade*. Porto, Renascença Portuguesa, 1919, p. 162.

⁵⁴ FATELA, *O Sangue e a Rua...*, p. 14.

⁵⁵ FATELA, *O Sangue e a Rua...*, p. 14.

⁵⁶ CORREIA, *A Nova Antropologia Criminal*, p. v.

aside penal problems, the penitentiary issue and the social reforms related to the fight against crime; he also separated himself from any association with potential schools⁵⁷.

The criminal's morals

Mendes Correia's originality also lies in the idea of the criminal's moral, or psycho-moral, individuality. This idea opened new horizons for the study of the causes of crime, which interested both medical examiners (who could treat them) and jurists (who could punish them). The idea of observing (by the doctor) and punishing (by the lawyer), present in institutions where Correia exercised his duties, recalls Michel Foucault⁵⁸ and his analyses in similar institutions. The idea of morality, in part inspired by Nietzsche⁵⁹, was a constant theme for Correia and is present in several of his works. According to Correia, although some authors still defended Lombroso's old concept in the 1930s, it was no longer acceptable to consider criminals as morphologically distinct. Thus, it was necessary to research not only descriptive or somatological characteristics, but above all their "moral individuality"⁶⁰. Correia argues that often it was the environment, or a fortuitous situation, that triggered the crime⁶¹. Both in Portuguese prisons and in the *Refúgio*⁶², an annex of the Porto Youth Detention Centre (*Tutoria*)⁶³, Correia says that he encountered:

A large mass of delinquents whose criminal acts cannot be considered the product of degenerative flaws or pathological defects, but are essentially the consequence of a deplorable

⁵⁷ CORREIA, *A Nova Antropologia Criminal*, p. vi.

⁵⁸ FOUCAULT, Michel. *Surveiller et Punir: Naissance de la Prison*. Paris, Gallimard, 1975.

⁵⁹ Correia states that it was António Emílio de Vasconcelos, a fellow student and future doctor at the Porto military hospital, who, around 1910, advised him to read this philosopher, whose *Thus Spoke Zarathustra* he had on his bedside table (CORREIA, António Mendes. *Em Face de Deus: Memórias e Confissões*. Porto, Fernando Machado, 1946, p. 61). Although Correia searched for this work, he only found *Twilight of the Idols*, i.e. the philosopher's penultimate work (1888) written shortly before his loss of lucidity and which, according to its author, constitutes a declaration of war on Christian morality, the misconceptions of philosophy and some "modern" trends.

⁶⁰ CORREIA, *A Nova Antropologia Criminal...*, p. 57.

⁶¹ CORREIA, *A Nova Antropologia Criminal...*, pp. 54-5.

⁶² While the *Refúgio* was the place where minors were collected until the court decision, the detention centres (*Tutoria*) were where disadvantaged children who were considered criminals or at risk were examined.

⁶³ On this institution between the 1930s and 1960s, i.e. after the publication of Correia's main works on delinquency and criminality, see: LOPES, João Teixeira (ed.). *A Tutoria do Porto: Estudo sobre a Morte Social Temporária*. Porto, Afrontamento, 2001.

earlier education. Some were absolutely *ignorant* of certain moral ideas. Were they insusceptible to acquiring these ideas? In general, no⁶⁴.

The *Tutoria* (Youth Detention Centre) collective court⁶⁵ consisted of a magistrate, a doctor and a teacher. As a doctor and assistant judge at the Porto Youth Detention Centre, established in 1912, Correia issued opinions on children and young people⁶⁶ from that year until the mid-1920s. The *Tutoria* was a republican project of social regeneration that aimed to eliminate crime and youth felonies, but also to watch over and protect the most disadvantaged social classes.

From previous observations, recorded in publications⁶⁷, and from those carried out in the *Tutoria*, Correia drew his conclusions: criminal behaviour was mainly associated with social and economic conditions, linked to aspects of moral order, education and training, hygiene and mental health rather than individuals' physical components⁶⁸. Elsewhere, he stated that crime does not decrease with education, but it can bring a reduction in the most violent occurrences⁶⁹ and he argued for the development of measures to combat social deprivation. A few years earlier, geographer Gérard Péry (1835–1893) also considered that serious crimes had decreased not because of the abolition of the death penalty in the mid-nineteenth century, but because of the increased educational level of the people⁷⁰.

For Correia, examining children and young people contributed to an understanding of the roots of crime and criminality in adults⁷¹. The instruction referred to by Correia was part of education; education was a whole which was related to the morals that must be part of the family. For Correia, “moral imperfection ... is the fulcrum of the criminal problem”⁷². It was because the

⁶⁴ CORREIA, “Antropologia Criminal Integral...”, p. 3.

⁶⁵ The youth detention centres were instituted by the decree of 27 May 1911.

⁶⁶ Studies on delinquent children were initiated by Ferreira Augusto and Luís de Freitas Viegas.

⁶⁷ CORREIA, *O Génio e o Talento na Patologia....* CORREIA, *Os Criminosos Portugueses...*

⁶⁸ CORREIA, *Crianças Delinquentes...*

⁶⁹ CORREIA, “Instrução e Criminalidade em Portugal”.... CORREIA, “A Criminalidade Precoce”...

⁷⁰ Péry, Gérard. *Geografia e Estatística Geral de Portugal e Colónias*. Lisbon, Imprensa Nacional, 1875, p. 284.

⁷¹ CORREIA, *Crianças Delinquentes....* CORREIA, “Antropologia Criminal Integral”... CORREIA, *A Nova Antropologia Criminal...*

⁷² CORREIA, “Antropologia Criminal Integral”..., p. 21.

children⁷³ were in “moral danger”⁷⁴ that they should be under the tutelage of the state, with the state replacing the family; they were the institutions that exercised pedagogical and social reintegration functions.

From medicine (psychiatry) to anthropology

From the analysis of the work produced by Mendes Correia, one of the conclusions that can be drawn is that he took a path from medicine (especially in the domain of psychiatry) to anthropology. These two areas – medicine and psychiatry – garnered the interest of Mendes Correia in anthropology, and he saw “criminal anthropology” as one of the possible practical uses of anthropology.

In the anthropology course he taught at the University of Porto Faculty of Sciences⁷⁵, he included references to: Ferraz de Macedo (*Crime et criminel* [*Crime and criminal*]); Alfredo Luiz Lopes (*Estudos de antropologia criminal* [*Studies on Criminal Anthropology*]); Basílio Freire (*Os degenerados* [*The degenerated*] and *Os criminosos* [*The Criminals*]); and Álvaro Teixeira Bastos (*A tatuagem nos criminosos: estudo feito no posto antropométrico da Cadeia da Relação* [*Tattooing on criminals: a study carried out at the anthropometric post of the Relação Jail*]). His interest in this area made him a member of the Society of Criminology and Forensic Medicine in Sao Paulo (Brazil), for example. He published in journals dedicated to criminology, such as: *Arquivo da Repartição de Antropologia Criminal, Psicologia Experimental e Identificação Civil do Porto* (*Archive of the Department of Criminal Anthropology, Experimental Psychology and Civil Identification of Porto*);

⁷³ On measures to improve the human species from childhood, within the assumptions of eugenics, in a comparative perspective between Brazil and Portugal (first half of the 20th century), see: WEBER, Maria Julieta; MATOS, Patrícia Ferraz de. “Melhorar a espécie humana desde a infância: Eugenia e higiene mental no Brasil e em Portugal (primeira metade do século XX)” In *Zero-a-Seis*, 2023, vol. 25, no. 47, pp. 16–40.

⁷⁴ According to the Decree-Law of 27 May 1911, the “minors in moral danger” were those who “had no fixed abode or means of subsistence (due to the absence of parents, guardians, relatives, etc., due to illness or imprisonment of the children themselves), those whose parents or guardians were recognized as incapable or powerless to fulfil their parental or guardian duties, as well as those who lived in the company of parents or guardians who ‘severely neglected their duties to watch over and educate their children’, who they had ‘notorious and scandalous behaviour’, who were ‘known as being habitually idle, beggars, strays, alcoholics, burglars, ruffians, prostitutes or other immoral beings’, who habitually deprived their children of food and other essential health care, physically abused them in a habitual or excessive manner, made them to ‘steal’, beg or prostitute themselves, were employed in ‘banned, dangerous or inhuman’ professions, and/or had been convicted for certain crimes” (BASTOS, Susana Pereira. *O Estado Novo e os Seus Vadios: Contribuição para o Estudo das Identidades Marginais e da sua Repressão*. Lisbon, Dom Quixote, 1997, p. 201).

⁷⁵ CORREIA, António Mendes. *Antropologia: Resumo das Lições Feitas pelo Assistente, Servindo de Professor da Cadeira*. Porto, Imprensa Portuguesa, 1915b.

Boletim do Instituto de Criminologia (Bulletin of the Institute of Criminology) (in Lisbon); and *Revue de droit pénal et de criminologie (Journal of Criminal Law and Criminology)* [in Brussels]). In 1934, he visited Brazil⁷⁶ and presented a conference at the Congresso Nacional de Identificação (National Congress of Identification). His conference was entitled “*O indivíduo, realidade biológica*” [The individual, biological reality], and included the topics of criminology and criminal anthropology⁷⁷. During the same visit, and at the Institute of Lawyers, he presented the lecture “*Os criminosos em Portugal*” [Criminals in Portugal].

Correia wrote about various deteriorations – linguistic, moral or behavioural – defined from the starting point of norms and deviations, or from the establishment of deviant behaviour in the later terminology of Erving Goffman (1922–1982)⁷⁸. Correia wrote “The slang of delinquent children”, where he explored the vocabulary used by minors admitted to the Youth Detention Centre⁷⁹. On the other hand, he analysed the slang used by “Portuguese criminals”⁸⁰; he pointed out that some vocabulary was not exclusive to delinquent children and was in common use in criminal circles in Porto⁸¹. The analysis of his work allows us to conclude that it was the distortion of a certain norm (which could be invented or idealized) that could reveal the deviation. According to Correia, “slang and certain tattoos pull down the morally regular people who use them, to some extent”; it does not matter that tattoos are religious emblems, such as crucifixes, as the “delinquents” who used them often did not know their meaning, or adopted them out of subservience or imitation, and they could be side by side with “obscene representations” such as “naked women in lubricious positions” (Figure 1). On the other hand, manifestations of religiosity of criminals and prostitutes had a tenuous moral value, as they do not “guide their conduct by the norms established by religion”⁸².

⁷⁶ On this visit, see: MATOS, Patrícia Ferraz de. “Um olhar sobre as relações entre Portugal e o Brasil a partir da obra de Mendes Correia: desafios, pontes e interações” In *População e Sociedade*, 2013, vol. 21, pp. 53–69.

⁷⁷ Abstract of the lecture: “Diferenças individuais, nos aspectos morfológico, bioquímico e psíquico. Os fundamentos genéticos da desigualdade. A importância da definição da individualidade em medicina clínica, pedagogia, criminologia, etc. Fórmulas e perfis individuais em Antropologia Criminal” [Individual differences, in morphological, biochemical and psychic aspects. The genetic foundations of inequality. The importance of defining individuality in clinical medicine, pedagogy, criminology, etc. Formulas and individual profiles in Criminal Anthropology].

⁷⁸ Goffman, Erving. *Stigma: Notes on the Management of Spoiled Identity*. New York, Simon & Schuster, 1963.

⁷⁹ CORREIA, *A Nova Antropologia Criminal...*, pp. 57–169.

⁸⁰ CORREIA, *Os Criminosos Portugueses...*, 2nd ed., pp. 244–7.

⁸¹ CORREIA, *A Nova Antropologia Criminal...*, p. 159.

⁸² CORREIA, *A Nova Antropologia Criminal...*, pp. 166, 168–9.

Figure 1. “Tatuagem erótica” [Erotic tattoo]

Source: Taken from CORREIA⁸³

Conclusion

In conclusion, it can be said that often, it was the elites, or the most knowledgeable individuals, who appropriated the power to classify and compare human groups. However, those who classified were often following models of development and retardation denouncing their prejudices. In the analysed context, it was mainly physicians and specialists in physical anthropology who had the task of classifying and weaving considerations about humanity, and in their works we can find remnants of Darwinian thought. The context of analysis was also influenced by eugenic theories and proposals for the improvement of the human species.

On the work of Mendes Correia, to which I have given special emphasis, it can be concluded that unlike Lombroso, Correia considered that “criminals” were not necessarily pathologically abnormal. And while Correia did not exclude biological factors, he placed great importance on the psychological, moral and social factors of crime. Correia analysed different types of crime and how they can be relative, taking into account the context in which they occur, as well as different types of criminals. However, at the same time as criticizing Lombroso and giving rise to the task of the anthropologist by promoting the importance of individuality and knowledge of its context, Correia ended up typifying the Portuguese by attributing psychological characteristics to them, such as being: “excessive and unstable as authentic southerners”; “aggressive and intelligent”, not possessing “the cruelty of

⁸³ CORREIA, *Os Criminosos Portugueses...*, 2nd ed., p. 86.

the Calabrian or the Neapolitan”; these characteristics also led him to the conclusion that the Portuguese were those who had the lowest percentages of homicides and crimes against property in the statistics⁸⁴.

Thus, although he criticized Lombroso and correctly argued that crime is relative and that the individuals who commit it can be normal beings at the outset, Correia ended up not following his misgivings to their ultimate consequences. By considering that there are social and national reasons for certain behaviours, he ended up diminishing the importance of this individuality; that is, by replacing the biological determinism proposed by Lombroso, the result, in a way, is social determinism. In some situations, however, Correia sought to analyse the sociocultural context in which the crime occurred.

Currently, there are, at least, still two theses that support the possible correlation between biology and deviant behaviour: by the doctor (neurologist) António Damásio, who highlights the role of the orbitofrontal cortex as a sensitive area in psychopaths; and the neurologist James Blair for whom the amygdala (the area between the orbitofrontal cortex and the hippocampus) is the zone which is the focal point for the study of individuals considered criminals.

This issue is not closed. Although the technical means of the past, and their consequent determinisms, are no longer in force, today there are other techniques, which are more sophisticated but which demonstrate the power to identify, such as biometric technologies. Biometric surveillance, for example, is at the intersection of migration and crime control and can also be influenced by racism⁸⁵. On the other hand, biometric data, with avatars able to identify people who could create problems in the future, can be powerful tools to protect people, but also to control citizens.

⁸⁴ CORREIA, *Os Criminosos Portugueses...*, p. 39. The first statistical study of criminality in Portugal, given its efforts in interpretation and its systematic character, is the “Statistical Study of Crime in Portugal from 1891 to 1895”, by A. Luís Lopes, which was prepared at the request of the organizing committee of the National Congress of Medicine in Lisbon, in 1897 and published by the Imprensa Nacional de Lisboa (FATELA, *O Sangue e a Rua...*, p. 26).

⁸⁵ AMELUNG, Nina. “‘Crisis’, control and circulation: Biometric surveillance in the policing of the ‘crimmigrant other’” In *International Journal of Police Science & Management*, 2023, vol. 25, no. 3, pp. 297–312.

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Hygienism, Eugenics and Racism in Portugal in the first half of the twentieth century

Eugenismo, Higienismo e Racismo em Portugal na primeira metade do século XX

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Abstract

This article aims to highlight the influence and dissemination of eugenicist, hygienist, and racist concepts in Portuguese society in the first half of the 20th century. The Galtonian eugenics perspective was not only known in Portugal as it also impacted the intellectual, university and medical elites. However, the eugenicist theories and practices were not strong enough to be translated, what happened in other European countries, the institutionalization of radical eugenics measures. The hygienist tradition, Catholic opposition, and the reduced acceptance of eugenics in liberal-conservative and progressive circles in Portugal conditioned the acceptance of these eugenic theories and practices in the country. This reality, similar in many respects to what has occurred in other Latin countries with a Catholic origin. Nevertheless, they have some specific features which require an explanation. Particularly, the singularities of the relations between science, society, and political projects present at the reception of the different models of eugenia. Its methodology has been essentially analytical-bibliographic.

Keywords: Eugenics. Hygienism. Racism. Modernisation. Colonialism

Resumo

Com este artigo pretendemos destacar a influência e divulgação das concepções higienistas, eugenistas e racistas na sociedade portuguesa na primeira metade do século XX. A perspetiva eugenista galtoniana não só era conhecida em Portugal, como teve impacto nas elites intelectuais, universitárias e médicas. No entanto, as teorias e práticas eugenistas nunca foram suficientemente fortes para se terem traduzido, como aconteceu noutros países europeus, na institucionalização de medidas eugénicas radicais. A tradição higienista,

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a oposição católica e a reduzida aceitação da eugenia nos círculos liberais conservadores e progressistas de Portugal acabaram por condicionar a recepção das teorias e práticas eugénicas no país. Esta realidade, semelhante, em muitos aspetos, ao que se verificou noutros países latinos de origem católica, tem, no entanto, algumas características específicas que exigem explicação. Em particular, as singularidades das relações entre a ciência, sociedade e projetos políticos em presença no momento da recepção dos diferentes modelos de eugenia. A metodologia utilizada foi essencialmente analítico-bibliográfica.

Palavras-chave: Eugenismo. Higienismo, Racismo. Modernização. Colonialismo.

Introduction

The eugenics movement, as a social philosophy, developed in the context of the scientific and positivist paradigm, benefiting from the intersection with other areas of knowledge on the rise in the early twentieth century (medicine, psychiatry, biology, statistics, anthropology, and demography). Even so, recent research on different countries, using a comparative methodology, has shown that eugenics is far from being a homogeneous and coherent scientific movement. On the contrary, it developed as a “multiform archipelago”¹, where the articulation between scientific positions and the political measures proposed by eugenicists varied greatly, both between states and within each one, and even over time².

As a result, the eugenics movement has many differences in acquiescence, being similar only in the maintenance of some scientific misconceptions, such as the biologization of imminently social factors. It was, in essence, an optimistic and totalitarian doctrine regarding the power of science and heredity. It is possible that this reason, eugenics has always been seen by its critics as a biased way to use the triumph of reason and science. And as a biopolitical project, it ended up fuelling some of the darkest imperialist and racist utopias in the 20th century.

¹ WEINGART, Peter. «Science and Political Culture. Eugenics in Comparative Perspective» In *Scandinavian Journal of History*, v. 24, n. 2, 1999, pp. 163-177.

² KEVLES, Daniel J. *In the Name of Eugenics: Genetics and the Uses of Human Heredity*. Cambridge: Harvard University Press, 1995; BASHFORD, Alison; LEVINE, Philippa (Eds.). *The Oxford Handbook of the History of Eugenics*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2010; TURDA, Marius. *Modernism and Eugenics*. Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan, 2010; TURDA, Marius; GILLETTE, Aaron. *Latin Eugenics in Comparative Perspective*. London: Bloomsbury, 2014.

Despite the centrality of heredity, it was “social and personality traits such as intelligence, criminality, alcoholism, schizophrenia, and manic-depressive insanity” which led to eugenic political and social interventions³. Moreover, they were wrongly convinced that these features were genetically determined⁴. Where these mistakes were extreme, eugenics became a powerful political technology in which the power and well-being of the person were determined by the selective reproduction of the “fittest”. And, in the radicalism of its convictions, by eliminating the “unfit” and “impure racists”⁵. This “scientific racism”, based on an ideology that differentiates races, classes, and cultures has fed some of the most dangerous imperialist utopias⁶.

The different scientific paradigms do not succeed each other in isolation from the historical circumstances that produce them. There is a close relationship between the science that is produced, the society that supports and legitimizes it, and the political projects that emanate from here. An eugenics global understanding, in its different manifestations and national specificities (which, as an unsystematized idea, precedes in some of its principles and purposes the theory coined in 1883 by Francis Galton), and requires a close connection with the particular history of each country. Most of all, when we know today that, although eugenics in its most negative effects is associated with Nazism, it has served various powers, right and left, from dictators and totalitarian regimes to liberal regimes. Belief in the possibility of creating improved future generations by manipulating human genetics passed by the reforming minds. In this sense, the eugenics movement, rather than a clear set of scientific principles, ended up placing a new path, discussing social and political problems in the public arena and in the hands of the state. This biopolitical perspective, spearheaded by doctors and men of science, where hygienists, eugenicists, and different forms of nationalism intersected, was indeed a new idea in a new and troubled time⁷. It even sought, as some authors recognize, not only scientific authority but a certain classical humanitarian lineage. Many saw themselves as worthy bearers of a new idea, based on a certain perspective of modernity. Moreover, secure in their belief, few

³ ALLEN, Garland E. «Eugenics and Modern Biology: Critiques of Eugenics, 1910-1945» In *Annals of Human Genetics*, n. 75, 2011, p. 314.

⁴ Idem, *Ibidem*.

⁵ Idem, *op. cit.*, pp. 314-325.

⁶ BASHFORD; LEVINE, *op. cit.*

⁷ On the concept of biopolitics, cf. FOUCAULT, Michel. *Microfísica do Poder*. 23, Ed. S. Paulo, Graal, 2004.

doubted the serious ethical and political problems that their theories and practices would raise.

We will understand how in Portugal the eugenist theory was received. Firstly, to understand how the defenders of eugenics set out to perfect “the race” in a cultural and ideological environment in which the causes of Portuguese decadence were contrary to eugenicist proposals. The regeneration of the nation, in which the “race” was seen as the “raw material” subject to historical constraints, required more education than eugenicist interventions⁸.

In methodological terms, we will use secondary sources preferably, seeking to bring new interpretations to how the eugenics project confronted other cultural and ideological movements that also aimed to regenerate the “race” and the nation. And so, in point one, we address the way eugenics was received. In point 2, we will analyze the main political, cultural, and ideological barriers that conditioned the acceptance of the eugenics movement. Finally, in point 3, we will focus on how the Catholic hierarchy positioned itself, especially in the 1930s and in an authoritarian and corporatist political context, in the face of the advance of eugenicist ideas.

The reception of eugenics in Portugal

Such as in other Latin countries with a conservative and Catholic culture, the eugenic theory and practices were not passively received in the Portuguese society. On the contrary, the political and social conceptions of peripheral country were assimilated (economically and culturally) in the world. However, centralist power in respect to the colonial empire. In the first half of the 20th century, the eugenics movement found its defenders in Portugal, but its social philosophy never seduced the different proposals for a national regeneration, either on the left or on the right. The political – ideological confrontations, in the first half of the 20th century in Portugal, in the context of the crisis of demolitionism, focused on two models of development able to overcome modernity which the intellectual and political elites considered imperfect and/or unfinished. For some, the secularization of society and the rationalist, enlightenment, demoliberal legacy had already gone too far, and it was important to return to the pre-liberal period, establishing a new conservative and authoritarian Catholic corporate order. For others, on the

⁸ CATROGA, Fernando. Antero de Quental. História. Socialismo. Política. Lisboa: Editorial Notícias, 2001, pp. 125-146.

other hand, need to promote the modernity, secularization, democracy, and socialism advance.

It was within this social framework here simplified which in practice opposed those in Portuguese society who defended the cultural heritage inherited from the Enlightenment to those who wanted to overcome it, and that eugenics was received in Portugal. The most significant research carried out to date on eugenics in Portugal is unanimous in considering that eugenics was known and discussed in relevant institutions such as at the University⁹. It also had defenders who were well politically and professionally positioned and able to disseminate their ideas, both in specialized newspapers and through the Portuguese Society of Eugenic Studies (SPEE), created in 1937. Even so, the eugenic theory of the improvement of the breed, coined by Francis Galton, not only left no trace of political institutionalization, but also was not included in the main political projects, either on the left or the on the right, mobilizing the Portuguese between the two world wars. It is a fact that the supposed superiority of races, underlying eugenicist theory, helped to legitimize the narrative of the “civilizing action” of the Portuguese over the colonized people, considered as inferior¹⁰. The Portuguese colonial nationalism took advantage of this perspective with a State ideology during the First Republic. With an even greater ideological strength under the Estado Novo (The New State), especially after the approval of the “Colonial Act” in 1930, and with Armindo Monteiro as Minister for the Colonies (1931-1935).

The political rise of Oliveira Salazar within the military dictatorship and the beginning of the Estado Novo (The New State) (1933) was undoubtedly taken advantage of by the most fervent eugenicists to embed the idea to purify the Portuguese race, which has always been seen as decadent, in the corporatist authoritarianism of the new regime and O Homem Novo (The New Man) to create. But their eugenicist proposals, on the one hand, were not seen as a credible alternative to the strong hygienist tradition in the field and, on

⁹ CLEMINSON, Richard. *Catholicism, Race and Empire. Eugenics in Portugal, 1900-1950*. Budapest: Central European University Press, 2014; _____. «Eugenics in Portugal, 1900-1950: setting a research agenda» In *East Central Europe*, v. 38 n. 1, 2011, pp. 133-154; MATOS, Patrícia Ferraz de. «Aperfeiçoar a ‘raça’, salvar a nação: eugenia, teorias nacionalistas e situação colonial em Portugal» In *Trabalhos de Antropologia e Etnologia*, v. 50, 2010, pp. 89-111. NINHOS, Cláudia. «A discussão em torno da eugenia em Portugal» In PIMENTEL, Irene Flunser; NINHOS, Cláudia. *Salazar, Portugal e o Holocausto*. Lisboa: Temas e Debates, 2013, pp. 209-242; PEREIRA, Ana Leonor. *Darwin em Portugal (1865-1914)*. Filosofia. História. Engenharia Social. Coimbra: Almedina, 2001; WEBER, Maria Julieta. «eugenia latina em Portugal e no Brasil (primeira metade do século XX)» In *Trabalhos de Antropologia e Etnologia*, v. 63, pp. 205-217.

¹⁰ ALMEIDA, Miguel Vale de. «Longing for oneself: hybridism and miscegenation in colonial and postcolonial Portugal» In *Etnográfica*, v. 1, 2002, pp. 181-200.

the other, they were not entirely consistent about what they considered to be the “problems of mestizaje” and “cross-breeding”, which they saw as forms of the decadence of the nation and the race¹¹.

Eusébio Tamagnini, a lecturer at the University of Coimbra and the first president of the SPEE, who was greatly influenced by German eugenics, had no doubts about the superiority of races. He believed and defended that the strongest races were endowed with a superior culture and would therefore be “better equipped” to take over vast territorial spaces¹². He believed and defended that the strongest races were endowed with a superior culture and would therefore be “better equipped” to take over vast territorial spaces. This supposedly scientific narrative not only legitimised all kinds of imperialism and colonialism, but was supposed to lead Portugal, like Nazi Germany, to adopt eugenic practices that would prevent the “Portuguese race” from decaying. We can thus see that eugenics had its defenders in Portugal (Eusébio Tamagnini, Mendes Correia, Barahona Fernandes, José Aires de Azevedo, to name a few), involving doctors, scientists, and anthropologists. However, even in the 1930s, when imperialist/colonialist nationalism struggled with the aspiration of a New Man. Eugenia never had political impact for Salazarism to adopt eugenic formal measures.

Eugenics as biopolitics: the political and cultural barriers which conditioned its reception in Portugal

Eugenics emerges depending on a theory of heredity that underpins a conception of the population biological evolution much centered on the physical, intellectual, and moral decline of the human species¹³. In Portugal, as we have already mentioned, although there were several eugenics defenders and its institutionalization, some of them with a clear German influence, the truth is that these ideas ended up not being politically materialized into eugenic laws. Richard Cleminson, in his work *Catholicism, Race and Empire: Eugenics in Portugal, 1900-1950*, gives three fundamental reasons to explain the weak impact of eugenics in Portugal: 1) a low level of institutionalization of eugenic practices; 2) opposition from Catholics; 3) the conservative nature of the Estado Novo Corporativo¹⁴. The same author adds that, in Portugal,

¹¹ NINHOS, op. cit., pp. 209-242.

¹² Idem. Ibidem.

¹³ CLEMINSON, op. cit., *Catholicism, Race and Empire...*

¹⁴ Idem, Ibidem.

science and the eugenics movement were limited to three main areas of debate: individualized studies on mental health, often from a biotypological perspective; a particular position on racial miscegenation in the context of the colonial empire; and a diffuse model of social hygiene, maternity, and childcare¹⁵.

The aforementioned author, in another of his studies, also sought to critically evaluate Portugal's inclusion in what he considered to be the two great international currents on eugenics: the "Latin eugenics" model and the "Germanic eugenics". Concluding that, although Germanic influences were audible in Eusébio Tamagnini, José Aires de Azevedo and Leopoldina Ferreira de Paulo, along with Portugal's weak involvement in the International Latin Federation of Eugenics Societies¹⁶ the eugenics model that dominated was decidedly environmentalist, less focused on "racial hygiene" and more on pronatalist family hygiene¹⁷. In other words, what happened in Portugal "was an ebb and flow of influences from different types of eugenics, which varied according to location and personal and institutional contexts"¹⁸. While Eusébio Tamagnini in Coimbra was pro-German, Almeida Garrett in Porto coincided with Latin eugenics forms. While anthropology in Coimbra was largely Germanic, in Porto, where Mendes Correia pontificated, neo-Lamarckism dominated and the influential field of social hygiene shared similarities with Latin eugenics¹⁹.

In other words, despite the singularities of a peripheral country, the deep-rooted and strong tradition of public hygiene, based on eclecticism and neo-Lamarckism, was always dominant in Portugal²⁰. Thus bringing the

¹⁵ Idem, *Ibidem*.

¹⁶ In August 1937, a meeting of the Latin Federation of Eugenics Societies was held in Paris, with very limited participation from Portuguese eugenicists, represented only by Dr Almerindo Lessa. Although the conference proceedings mentioned that a Portuguese eugenics society was in the process of being established, there is no indication of any formal involvement by the Sociedade Portuguesa para o Estudo da Eugenia, which had already been officially established in 1934. Cf. TURDA; GILLETTE, *op. cit.*

¹⁷ Idem. *Ibidem*.

¹⁸ Idem, *ibidem*, p. 85.

¹⁹ TURDA; GILLETTE, *op. cit.*

²⁰ For a better understanding of the influences of Darwinism or Lamarckism on Portuguese eugenic thought, cf. PEREIRA, Ana Leonor. «Eugenia em Portugal?» In *Revista de História das Ideias*, Vol. 20, 1999, pp. 531-60; PEREIRA, *op. cit.*, Darwin em Portugal...; MATOS, *op. cit.* Aperfeiçoar a 'raça', salvar a nação..., pp. 89-111; PIMENTEL, Irene Flunser. «A assistência social e familiar do Estado Novo nos anos 30 e 40» In *Análise Social*, n.151-152, 1999, pp. 477-508; _____. «O aperfeiçoamento da raça: a eugenia na primeira metade do século XX» In *História*, n. 3, 1998, pp.18-27.

Portuguese reality closer to what has become common in the international literature known as “Latin eugenics”.

In this sense, as different authors have noted, the French cultural and scientific influence and the neo-Lamarckist conceptions of eugenics among the elites directly linked to this issue ended up being decisive for the eugenic model that took hold in Portugal. Indeed, the influence of German eugenics was more vocal and dominant in the SPEE, but this was never enough to prevent the hygienist tradition — Almerindo Lessa, considered the representative of “Latin Eugenics” in Portugal and a disciple of Abel Salazar, represented this tradition — from being dominant. This eclectic, neo-Lamarckist perspective of eugenic ideas indicates something that somehow singularises the Portuguese reality, even within the framework of “Latin eugenics”: the clear subordination of eugenics to hygienism²¹. The latter ended up constituting, in practice, not only an alternative model to the various forms of eugenics but above all a strong theoretical and scientific conditioning to how the debate on eugenics took place in Portuguese society.

The eugenics movement, as we have already mentioned, understood from a biopolitical perspective, is part of a process that accompanies the development of science and needs institutions and political projects to involve it at all times. It is, in fact, this need that essentially explains the differences in its reception and development. In the Portuguese case, as we have also seen, the eugenics movement never had the necessary political support from the state. Neither during the First Republic (1910-1926), nor during the Military Dictatorship (1926-1933) or the Estado Novo (1933-1974) did the various powers see eugenics as a useful tool to develop their projects. Even in the 1930s, a period in which the Salazar dictatorship made no secret of its totalitarian ambition to create a New Man, the regime’s elites refused to include any negative eugenics measures in their political project. They even refused the eugenic temptation of “perfecting the race”, based on the authentic social engineering proposed by the eugenicists.

One of the structural components of Portuguese ideological culture, especially among the elites, was the politically instrumental and operative use of the indissociable binomial decadence/regeneration. Any interpretation of the present and how to change it was somehow “decadent”. On the other side, all the victorious political movements that succeeded it, assumed the status of promoters of the necessary regeneration. The same happened with

²¹ MATOS, op. cit., Aperfeiçoar a “raça”, salvar a nação...; NINHOS, op. cit., pp. 209-242.

the victory of liberalism (1820-1834) over absolutism. The same happened with the establishment of the Republic in 1910, with the end of the Republic (1926) and the establishment of the Estado Novo (1933), which also included Portugal's regeneration in its narrative. However, no other period experienced the nation's sense of decadence so clearly (which was nothing more than the perception of the country's backwardness in relation to more developed countries) than the one that ended up celebrating the iconoclastic generation of the 1870s (Antero de Quental, Oliveira Martins, Eça de Queirós)²². It is important to remember, as an important aspect of the issue of eugenics, that the root causes of our decadence as a people and as a nation were not biological and/or hereditary, but cultural and moral. For the more progressive sectors, it was the lack of education and the fact that we did not take the whole Enlightenment legacy further which explained our backwardness. The more conservative and anti-liberal sectors blamed the entire legacy of the French Revolution for our decadence.

Although eugenics as a practice and legal formalization was known and disseminated by a minority of doctors and scientists at conferences and in specialized newspapers, presenting it as a technology able to "improve the race", it was never influential and attractive enough to be included in the main political strategies dominant in the first half of the 20th century. The explanation for our decadence and the crisis of liberalism in the inter-war period, especially in the 1920s, mobilized Portuguese elites politically and intellectually. But eugenics was practically ignored by the cultural and ideological movements that hegemonized the debate in Portuguese society, on both the left and the on the right. We found nothing relevant about eugenics in the magazine *Seara Nova* (1921)²³, which the left hegemonized the political, cultural, and ideological debate in the 1920s and 1930s, into a space where there were several polemics on practically all contemporary political, scientific, and cultural currents²⁴. This obliviousness on the part

²² CATROGA, op. cit.

²³ The seareiros, fully committed to neo-Enlightenment rationalism in defence of modernity, based their entire struggle on the primacy of culture, political action, and the efficacy of ideas in transforming societies. They prioritised, with an assumed intellectual vanguardism, the improvement of elites through education and knowledge as a solution for the regeneration of Portugal, rejecting positivism and materialist philosophical conceptions. This stands in stark contrast, as we can see, to the social engineering proposals advocated by the eugenicists. Regarding the seareiro movement and the Seara Nova journal, Cf. AMARO, António Rafael. *A Revista Seara Nova nos anos vinte e trinta: Memória, Cultura, Poder* (1921-1939). Viseu: Universidade Católica Portuguesa, 1995.

²⁴ On culture, politics, and science in the 1920s-30s, we highlight only the most significant debates involving António Sérgio: the controversies with António Sardinha, leader of the integralist movement;

of the Seareiros intellectuals, who were always so aware of current cultural and scientific developments, could be explained by one of two reasons: a) eugenics and scientific and biopolitical issues were unknown among the Seareiros, which is hard to believe given the group's sensitivity to issues of this nature; b) or, more likely, eugenics in Portugal remained very institutionally circumscribed, within a very limited scientific framework.

Our investigation on the main government bodies of the conservative and anti-modernist movements linked to Lusitanian Integralism, which on the right brought together the anti-Enlightenment elites and defenders of corporatist authoritarianism, yielded a result that was in every way similar to the one we have already mentioned for *Seara Nova*: a surprising silence on eugenics and, even when the issue was the "Race/Nation" and their regeneration (always seen as an unity), the solutions presented did not go beyond the hereditary route. The regeneration needed was more cultural than biological, more institutional than hereditary.

Does this mean that eugenics had no advocates in Portugal? Of course not. As we have already mentioned, there are countless examples of doctors, university professors, and researchers who publicized and defended eugenics as a solution to be taken into account for the physical and intellectual elevation of the Portuguese. These personalities held positions of the utmost importance, and it is enough to look at those who, at the beginning of the 1930s (1934, when the Statutes were approved), took part in the formation of the SPEE²⁵. Professor Eusébio Tamagnini, Minister of Public Instruction

with Cabral Moncada, a law professor at the University of Coimbra, regarding the concept of history; with Abel Salazar, on the dissemination of science, framed by neo-positivism; with Bento de Jesus Caraça, on science and culture, among others. Cf. FITAS, Augusto; PRÍNCIPE, João (Eds). *A Seara Nova e os Debates Contemporâneos*. Lisboa: Caleidoscópio, 2022.

²⁵ As founders of the Portuguese Society of Eugenic Studies, in 1934, the following stand out a) linked to the University of Coimbra as professors, namely José Alberto dos Reis, Director of the Faculty of Law (1916-1920 and 1922-1927) and future President of the National Assembly of the Estado Novo Corporativo (1935-1938; 1938-1942; 1942-1945); Alberto Pessoa, Alberto Rocha Brito (Director of Dermatology Service); Álvaro de Matos (Founder of the Coimbra Maternity Hospital), all professors at the Faculty of Medicine; The doctor and professors, Henrique Jardim de Vilhena, were elected responsible for the Lisbon section of SPEE (between 1925-1926, he was rector of the University of Coimbra and published several works on anatomy and anthropology). Henrique João Barahona also belonged to the Lisbon section, graduated from the Lisbon Faculty of Medicine in 1930, and who would become a scholarship holder, between 1934-1936, from the National Education Board in Nazi Germany. As responsible for the Porto section of SPEE, António Mendes Correia (1888-1960), graduated in medicine, was elected in 1911. Despite having a degree in medicine, António Mendes Correia stood out as a professor of History, Geography and Ethnology at the Faculty of Letters of Porto and Full Professor at the Faculty of Sciences in the same city. He was Director of the Institute for Scientific Research in Anthropology at the Faculty of Sciences of Porto (1923), Director of the Escola Superior Colonial, which later became known as Instituto Superior de Estudos Ultramarinos (1946), and President of the Lisbon Geography Society (1951), among other positions.

(1934-1936), should be highlighted for his social and political significance. Although he did not register his interests, as a minister he approved the SPEE Statutes, which he would later direct.

Only three years after SPEE's foundation it was possible to have their own buildings, precisely at the Anthropology Institute of the University of Coimbra where Eusébio Tamagnini was the director. If we look at the ambitious goals of the SPEE Statutes, which aimed to "promote the study of heredity and eugenics, with a view to the physical and intellectual improvement of the Portuguese", what create "in public opinion an environment advantageous to eugenics", able to take it to schools, the family and to corporations and associations, in line with the corporatist matrix of the regime, perhaps we can say that its impact on Portuguese society fell short of the ambitious intentions of the main signatories²⁶.

Even so, the effects on Portuguese society of the emergence of new protagonists linked to scientific development (doctors, scientists, researchers linked to biology and population studies) who, in some way, rivaled and progressively dethroned the elites linked to the humanities, should be highlighted. These new actors were given the authority by the new sciences, seen as the debate on the decline of the nation and the "race" from a completely different perspective: it was not history, culture, or mentality that explained everything about people's success but by the new knowledge brought by maths, engineering, economics, demography, biology and genetics.

From what we have said above, it is not surprising that the eugenics movement found it difficult to gain acceptance in Portuguese society. From the outset, eugenics found it very difficult to position itself as an alternative to the dominant environmental hygienism, to the political-cultural reformism and mentalities in common with political projects on the left and on the right, and quite naturally, to the anti-modernity matrix of the Catholic Church. The eugenics proposal was part of a long journey of Enlightenment, secularisation, and rationalist worldviews that Catholics had always fought against. And so they allied themselves, albeit for different reasons, with all the sectors on the left and on the right that rejected eugenicist biopolitics as an instrument to regenerate the "race" and the nation. The weight of the historical-cultural tradition explaining Portuguese decadence thus also ended up conditioning how eugenicist theories were received. In effect, the eugenicist reform

²⁶ For a better understanding of the content of the Statutes of the Portuguese Society for Eugenic Studies, cf. PORTUGAL. Portaria 7948, Diário do Governo, I Série, n.º 293, de 14 de dezembro de 1934. (<https://files.diariodarepublica.pt/gratuitos/1s/1934/12/29300.pdf>)

agenda was confronted with a narrative of a Portuguese nation cleansed of its multiethnicity (Celts, Phoenicians, Carthaginians, Jews, Arabs, Africans)²⁷, in which only the “flagrant traces” left by the Germans were recognized, devaluing the Semitic or African presence²⁸.

The weight of a historical-literary culture (as opposed to a so-called exact sciences culture) to explain the causes of Portuguese decadence and the existence of an important neo-Lamarckist tradition in hygiene and public health, practices greatly conditioned the biosocial acceptance of eugenics with its strong hereditary slant²⁹. The position of the Catholic Church was always closer to this perspective, as we will see below.

The Catholic Church's opposition to eugenics

Eugenics was known, discussed, and disseminated in circles closely linked to health and the university, but it is worth to recognize that its proposals never took a center stage in a public debate. Firstly, for scientific, social, and political reasons. Portugal was far from having scientists and scientific institutions linked to eugenics with the weight and capacity to put eugenic theory and practices at the center of the discussion on their own. This claim was jeopardized from the outset by the fact that the most influential political elites, linked to the various regenerative political projects in Portuguese society in the first half of the 20th century, did not include eugenic biopolitical therapies in their decadent diagnoses. The fact that a large part of public social assistance was very dependent on the role of institutions linked to the Catholic Church, where there was a hygienist tradition with evidence of persistent social practice, conditioned the debate and the degree of eugenics acceptance. The hygienist perspective of disease prevention and the eradication of social problems such as alcoholism and prostitution, as well as the subordination of the hereditary response to the neo-lamarckist paradigm that had been known and practiced for a long time, may help to explain how the weak public debate among the political elites at stake. It should be noted, in this regard, that the neo-Lamarckist perspective in a

²⁷ It should be remembered that António Sardinha (1887–1925), founder and principal ideologue of Integralismo Lusitano, did not even acknowledge the influence of the Arabs. Despite the historical evidence of the many peoples who inhabited the Iberian Peninsula, for him, the “purity of the race” remained unaltered.

²⁸ MATOS, op. cit., *Anthropology, Nationalism and Colonialism...*; _____, op. cit., *Aperfeiçoar a “raça”, salvar a nação...*

²⁹ PEREIRA, op. cit., *Eugenia em Portugal?*, pp. 531-60.

scientific and secularising context, which imposed new challenges to the role of the Church in society and family, was easier to accept among Catholics.

Even so, in Portugal, the hierarchy of the Catholic Church followed the debates on eugenics, which, it should be noted, had well-known lay Catholic supporters, without any official public controversy worthy of note. No formal stance on eugenics is known to have been taken by the Catholic hierarchy (nor is any official stance known to have been taken by Oliveira Salazar's government), although the Pope's doctrinal guidelines were well known. The papal encyclical "Casti connubii" (December 1930) re-established the Church's position and its authority in the "sacralized" sphere of the family, marriage, and sexuality. At a time when, in some Protestant countries, gaps were opening up towards the acceptance of positive and negative eugenic practices, Pius XI's encyclical reiterated his opposition to any form of birth control, sterilization, or abortion. The red lines, ere drawn, moved away from the Anglican Church which, in August 1930, at the Lambeth Conference, had recognized artificial birth control. This is an unacceptable principle among Catholics, namely the interference of science in marriage and reproduction. Admitting this, as the eugenicists argued, was not only a denial of the sacredness of marriage but also an intrusion into the domain of sexuality and the family.

In the aforementioned encyclical "Casti connubii" it is reaffirmed at one point:

"With too much solicitude for eugenic ends, they not only give certain salutary advice so that the health and vigor of future offspring may be easily achieved – which is certainly not contrary to right reason – but they go so far as to put the eugenic end before any other, even of a higher order, and desire that marriage be forbidden by public authority to all those who, according to the processes and conjectures of science, believe that they should give birth to defective offspring because of hereditary transmission, even though they are fit to marry"³⁰.

As far as we can tell, the Catholic Church was opposed to all forms of negative eugenics, and, above all, it was concerned about the interference of science and the state in an institution like the family. In Portugal, Catholics not only followed this doctrine, but were also attentive to its evolution in its Portuguese society. In June 1933, the *Jornal Novidades* (The News), the official organ of the Portuguese bishops, warned Catholics to take "the necessary

³⁰ PIO XI. Carta encíclica casti connubii do Papa Pio XI sobre o matrimónio Cristão.

precautions to consider this new science”³¹. From their point of view, they should not see eugenics as a “simple medical chapter, harmless and specialized because, under the cover of the scientific spirit, a philosophy of materialist absolutism is being propagated (compare man with the animal), a policy of state absolutism (the right of the state to intervene in the intimate lives of citizens)”³².

The concerns about eugenics, it is curious to note, were not directly related to the Portuguese reality, but to the publication of a book by Tristão de Athayde (pseudonym of Alceu Amoroso Lima), a Brazilian catholic writer and intellectual³³. The Portuguese Catholic journalist, defining the orientation of the newspaper *Novidades*, took advantage of the publication of the book *Ensaio de Biologia*, by the aforementioned Brazilian author, of criticizing the writer Bernard Shaw (Irish playwright, and defender of eugenics) accusing him of conveying ideas that present “the eugenic transformation of humanity” as “the only one that counts”, devaluing what could be achieved through “modifications to political, social or religious institutions”³⁴.

In Portugal too, regretted the same writer of the main newspaper of the Portuguese episcopate, it was possible to feel “the invasion of eugenicist tyranny treading the Portuguese land, blown from all sides as a medicine against our social backwardness”³⁵. And sharing Tristão de Athayde’s ideas to Brazil, he concluded: “like him, we believe that the worst evil to fight is not barbarism, as is usually said, but so-called civilization”. At the same time, trying to see in the supposed scientific modernity of eugenics no more than “an old pagan idea”, he criticized the “freaks that are sought to be introduced as discoveries and progress achieved by new lights”³⁶. From his point of view, “eugenics, in its essence, is as old as paganism”³⁷. And, once again quoting the Brazilian Catholic intellectual Tristão de Athayde, who in turn used the

³¹ NOVIDADES, n.º 11 759, 24 de junho, 1933, p. 1.

³² Idem. *Ibidem*.

³³ On the impact of Tristão de Athayde’s book, «Ensaio de Biologia», Livraria Católica, 1933, and, from the same author, «Limites da Eugenia» In *Ensaio de Biologia*, Livraria Católica, 1933, see GIESBRECHT, Daniel F. «Divus contra Galton: o debate eugênico a partir da produção intelectual católica brasileira na década de 1930» In *ARIES Anuario de Antropología Iberoamericana*, pp. 1-6, 2023. (<https://aries.aibr.org/articulo/2023/27/4897/divus-contra-galton-o-debate-eugenico-a-partir-da-producao-intelectual-catolica-brasileira-na-decada-de-1930>)

³⁴ NOVIDADES, *op. cit.*

³⁵ Idem. *Ibidem*.

³⁶ Idem. *Ibidem*.

³⁷ Idem. *Ibidem*.

Greek poet Teognis (who wrote six centuries BC), the writer for the newspaper *Novidades* pays a special attention to the following passage:

“We worry about having good donkeys and horses because we know that good comes from good; however, a healthy man doesn’t refuse to marry a sick woman if she has money. It’s money that weakens the race. There’s no wonder if it declines, since the bad crosses paths with the good”³⁸.

The eugenicist idea that pretended to be new, in the end, had nothing modern about it except in its materialist aspect. Materialism is present in all its conceptions “that seek to elevate ‘eugenic superhumanism’ to the status of a 20th century gospel”³⁹. And to try to lump political philosophies and Lutheran religions into the same unacceptable bag, he concludes saying “that the fanatics of eugenics are divided between the supporters of a superhumanism, materialist in philosophy and communist in politics, and the idealist reformers coming out from the religious extravagances in which Lutheran evangelism is dissolved today”⁴⁰.

On both sides of the Atlantic, Catholics were united in the same faith and in the fight against eugenics. In both countries (more so in Brazil than, despite everything, in Portugal) the Catholic Church felt the pressure of the modernity challenges in which the whole eugenicist scientific and biopolitical project was embedded. There or here, the church would become an obstacle to the institutionalization of eugenics, due to the social power it represented. The French-influenced neo-Lamarckist paradigm prevailed in both countries, with the specificities of each one, more focused on the promotion of hygiene and disease prevention⁴¹.

Conclusion

It is undeniable that during the first half of the 20th century, hygienist and eugenicist conceptions, as well as issues related to race, clashed in

³⁸ Idem. *Ibidem*.

³⁹ Idem. *Ibidem*.

⁴⁰ Idem. *Ibidem*.

⁴¹ STEPAN, Nancy Leys. «Eugenia no Brasil, 1917-1940» In HOCHMAN, Gilberto; ARMUS, Diego (Orgs). *Cuidar, Controlar, Curar. Ensaios Históricos sobre Saúde e Doença na América Latina e Caribe* [online]. Fiocruz, Rio de Janeiro, pp. 330-391; WEBER, op. cit., pp. 205-217; TURDA; GILLETTE, op. cit.; PEREIRA, op. cit., Eugenia em Portugal?, pp. 531-60; PEREIRA, op. cit., Darwin em Portugal... CLEMINSON, op. cit., Between Germanic and Latin eugenics..., pp.73-91.

Portugal. Eugenics, as an institutionalized practice, was never accepted in its negative aspects, but it had many persistent defenders. Its defense as a theory and practice in Portugal, as in most countries, was based on a conception of the decadence of the “race”, and its progressive degeneration, requiring urgent responses to reverse the situation, in other words, the seriousness of the situation (decadence) demanded biopolitical responses only within the reach of eugenics. Thus, the question posed does not aspire to disguise the undisguisable: “racial” superiority, on the one hand, and the imperative need of people, who want to be strong and healthy, to do whatever possible to create “good generations”. Therefore, within this scientific and social framework, in which hygienist, eugenicist and racist proposals intersected, the movement in favor of eugenics as the savior of “good offspring” developed in Portugal.

However, ideas with social, scientific, or pseudo-scientific implications always need institutions, in other words, a culture that is favorable or unfavorable to their acceptance and dissemination. In turn, the societies in which these ideas are disseminated are far from being mere passive receptacles. This is what happened to some extent in Portugal, as a country that received eugenic theories, which became conditioned by the institutional conditions (norms, rules, laws, practices) imposed at that time and period to their reception.

Although we can follow the moments of reception and dissemination of the eugenics movement in Portugal, there will always be a grey side to this journey, which is constantly being illuminated by new researches. This is also what we have endeavored to do, to surprise the path of eugenics in a very specific political and social time. In this sense, it was easy to see that, as we progressed through the 20th century, eugenics was gaining favor, especially among a small elite of doctors, university professors, anthropologists, and scientists. However, not even during its heyday in the 1930s did eugenics manage to establish itself as a central idea in Portuguese society. In other words, eugenics never became a scientific, political, cultural or even religious issue in Portugal, forcing the main areas of public debate (magazines, newspapers, political parties, parliaments) to come out in support and/or opposition. The debate existed and has been analyzed in detail by various studies, but it was confined to a very restricted circle of new protagonists who, due to a lack of scale and audience, found it very difficult to break out of the shell from which they sought to disseminate their ideas.

Therefore, we do not find eugenics outside of academic circles and specialized medical newspapers and, although we can find some of its defenders in political or academic positions of any kind of relevance, they never found the political conditions to mobilize their ideas towards institutionalization. The influences and knowledge of what was being practiced in other countries, particularly in France, Germany, England, and Brazil, were extensive. But they all were a result of a set of ideas that, although Germanic traits remained very evident in figures such as Eusébio Tamagnini and many of those who founded the SPEE with him, it was always the environmentalist aspect that set the tone for eugenics in Portugal.

The social, political, and institutional conditions were therefore lacking for the advocates of more negative eugenics to succeed. It wasn't for lack of endeavor that this did not happen. In 1934, Professor Eusébio Tamagnini, in his inaugural lecture at the University of Coimbra, seemed to believe in the power of eugenics as a mean of ethnic purification. However, these ideas, apparently mobilizing, did not find the necessary cultural, political, and ideological broth in Portuguese society to make them take off. Neither during the First Republic (1910-1926), nor in the context of the Military Dictatorship (1926-1933), nor the more favorable environment of the creation of Salazar's "New Man" (1933-1968), did any project for national regeneration that brought with it hereditary eugenic solutions gain dominant prominence in the main political-ideological movements.

National regeneration on both the left and on the right never placed the issue of eugenics at the center of the debate, as happened elsewhere, which was confined, while maintaining a certain tension, to university and public health institutions. The existing alternative models of national regeneration and the role of the Catholic Church in defending environmental and social hygiene practices seem to have been strong enough barriers to prevent the institutionalization of hereditary eugenics practices. The strong neo-Lamarckist tradition of environmental public hygiene, the weight that the Catholic Church had in institutions linked to social protection and public health, became so dominant that, after the Second World War, Germanic eugenics, which was so popular with certain figures in Portugal, ceased to be a topic and, in some cases, its defense was even erased from some biographies.

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The belief in the moral and intellectual inferiority of poor children in Portugal: a turning point

A crença na inferioridade moral e intelectual das crianças pobres em Portugal: um ponto de viragem

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Abstract

In Portugal, the fight against poverty in childhood was considered essential not only to combat “social ills”, and consider new hygienist precepts, but as a defence, a concept of race improvement. The moralization of the poor from childhood was then imposed a State responsibility which forced to create social and hygienic educational assistance institutions based on scientific and pedagogical concepts which did not escape Darwinist and eugenic influences. The then dominant adopted the same corrective pedagogy as responses focused on the field of moral and therapeutic education to curb childhood poverty, mainly when of their shortcomings were social and environmental. This study aims to explain the urgent social policy and trajectory to tackle poverty in childhood, invoking the central role of policymakers receive ideas, science, and knowledge produced about childhood during the First Republic in Portugal. Specifically, the aim here is to highlight the social, political, and cultural context of the urgent Child Protection Law of May 27, 1911. We intend to establish convergences or divergences between the theoretical influences of Herbert Spencer’s social Darwinism and the opportunity to create a Law that is still considered significant and a historic landmark in terms of children’s rights and protection.

Keywords: Poverty in Childhood. Hygiene. Social Darwinism. Family Regeneration.

Resumo

Em Portugal, o combate à pobreza na infância era entendido como essencial, não só para debelar os “males sociais”, à luz dos novos preceitos higienistas, mas também como defesa de uma conceção de aperfeiçoamento da raça. A moralização dos pobres desde a infância impunha-se, então, como uma

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responsabilidade do Estado, obrigando à criação de instituições de assistência educativa social e higiénica, tendo por base concepções cientistas e pedagógicas que não escapavam às influências darwinistas e eugénicas. Vão no mesmo sentido as pedagogias corretivas então dominantes, centradas em respostas no domínio da educação moral e terapêutica para crianças em situação de pobreza, quando muitas das suas insuficiências eram sociais e ambientais. O propósito deste trabalho pretende explicar a emergência e a trajetória das políticas sociais de combate à pobreza infantil invocando o papel central dos políticos na receção das ideias, da ciência e do conhecimento produzido sobre a infância durante a I República em Portugal. Concretamente, pretende-se aqui colocar em evidência o contexto social, político e cultural de emergência da Lei de Proteção da Infância de 27 de maio de 1911. É nossa intenção estabelecer convergências ou divergências entre as influências teóricas do darwinismo social de Herbert Spencer e a oportunidade de criação de uma Lei que ainda hoje é considerada significativa e um marco histórico em matéria de direitos e proteção das crianças.

Palavras-chave: Pobreza Infantil. Higienismo. Darwinismo Social. Regeneração da Família.

Introduction

Poverty and the welfare practices developed in Portugal from the modern period to the present and have received many researchers' attention, yet this topic remains far from fully be explored. The social and political perspectives underlying most of the studies are an important anchor for understanding the user profile to institute resources — in the form of the deserving and undeserving poor — and for highlighting the plans of the central government to combat poverty and their contrast with the intervention of civil society.

The searches for solutions to put an end to poverty has marked several centuries of history, bringing to prominence intellectuals and personalities from different fields, such as Thomas Chalmers, Jeremy Bentham, Robert Owen, William Pitt (18th-19th centuries), and more recently, Jane Addams (USA), Alice Salomon (Germany), Ilse Arlt (Austria), Marie Muller-Louis (France), and more recently, Jane Addams (USA), Alice Salomon (Germany), Marie-Thérèse Vieillot (France), Ilse Arlt (Austria), Marie Muller-Lulofs (Holland), Kalliopi Pouboura (Greece), among many others (19th and 20th

centuries)¹ whose debate has made society aware on the problem of poverty in capitalist societies. Charity and philanthropy also evolved through the creation of *Charities Organisations Societies* and the *Settlements* movement. In the political sphere, landmark legislative measures emerged, such as the Speenhamland Act² (1795) or the *Allowance System*, regarded by Karl Polanyi as a significant social innovation with which they defend the right to life³.

On the Portuguese scene, the historical support for conceptions of poverty and the social devices that assist in an institutional context emerges in the work of several authors such as Maria Antónia Lopes⁴, Laurinda Abreu⁵, Alcina Martins⁶ e Rosa Tomé⁷. Based on the results of many of these investigations, we intend to explain the urgent and trajectory social policies on poverty childhood, invoking the central role of politicians in the reception of ideas, science, and knowledge produced about childhood during the First Republic in Portugal. Specifically, the aim is to highlight the social, political, and cultural context in which the Law for the Protection of Children (LPI) of 27 May 1911 emerged. The theoretical influences of Herbert Spencer's social Darwinism convergence and divergence and the opportunity to create a law that, still today, is considered significant and a landmark in terms of children's rights and protection will be addressed. This law represents a paradigm shift in our understanding of child poverty, impacting the intervention models and welfare practices adopted by governments. The moralization of the poor from childhood onwards was then imposed as a responsibility of the state, forcing

¹ The decision regarding the selection of the personalities listed as examples was based on the following readings: POLANYI, Karl. *A Grande Transformação*. Lisboa: Edições70, 2012 [1944]; SOTELO, Ignacio. *El Estado Social. Antecedentes, origen, desarrollo y declive*. Madrid: Editorial Trotta, 2010; HERING, Sabine; BERTEKE Waaldijk (Eds.). *History of Social Work in Europe (1900-1960). Female Pioneers and their influence on the development of International Social Organizations*. Opladen: Leske+Budrich, 2003.

² On 6 May 1795, during a period of widespread poverty, the judges of Berkshire convened in Speenhamland and decided to implement supplementary subsidies to wages. These subsidies were distributed according to a table indexed to the price of bread, aiming to ensure a minimum income for the poor that was not dependent on their earnings. The poor were entitled to assistance, even if employed, provided their wages were below the guaranteed household income assigned to them by the table. POLANYI, op. cit., p. 222.

³ Idem, *Ibidem*.

⁴ LOPES, Maria Antónia. "Pobreza, Assistência e Política Social em Portugal nos sécs. XIX e XX - perspectivas historiográficas" In *A Cidade e o Campo. Colectânea de estudos*. Coimbra: Centro de História da Sociedade e da Cultura, 2000, pp. 63-83.

⁵ ABREU, Laurinda. *O Poder e os Pobres. As Dinâmicas Políticas e Sociais da Pobreza e da Assistência em Portugal (Sécs. XVI-XVIII)*. Lisboa: Gradiva, 2014.

⁶ MARTINS, Alcina. *Génese, Emergência e Institucionalização do Serviço Social Português*. Lisboa: Fundação Calouste Gulbenkian e Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia, 1999.

⁷ TOMÉ, Maria Rosa. *A Criança e a Delinquência Juvenil na Primeira República*. Lisboa: Centro Português de Investigação em História e Trabalho Social, 2003.

the creation of social and hygienic educational assistance institutions, based on scientific and pedagogical concepts that did not escape to Darwinist and eugenic influences.

This article is divided into two parts considered central to understand the subject. At first, we will take a depth look at the influence that the social Darwinism and eugenics may have had on the construction of ways of fighting poverty in childhood in the early 20th century, during a republican government. Secondly, we detail the innovative features of the law for that time and identify similarities or dissonances between these theoretical orientations and the letter of the law.

Social Darwinism and eugenics determined ways to fight poverty in childhood

In 1883, Eugenics, a term introduced by the British statistician Francis Galton, from the Greek *eu + genēs*, meaning “well-born”, as defined by the American Charles Davenport “in 1911” as the science of perfecting the human race through a better reproduction. In terms of social and economic change, eugenics was raised because of issues of race, class, and sexuality, reflecting an optimistic faith in science that would solve complex problems of heredity and human behavior, in rational planning in order to wonder a better society and in state action with programs implementations, would guarantee public welfare and national progress⁸.

Eugenics is often portrayed as an elitist ideology aligned with nazi racial hygiene, in which some saw themselves as fit and defined the unfit as “the others” in terms of race, ethnicity, and social class. The opposition would be between a superior race based on the Nordic, blond, and blue-eyed ideal that the eugenics movement glorified and urban immigrants, poor whites, blacks, Mexicans, Jews, criminals, alcoholics, the mentally ill and anyone else who did not look like a dominant race⁹. As historian Frank Dikötter wrote in 1998, eugenics was not so much a clear set of scientific principles as a modern way to approach social problems in biologizing terms¹⁰. It took on different expressions according to regional and national contexts, but all over the world,

⁸ LADD-TAYLOR, Molly. *Fixing the poor: eugenic sterilization and child welfare in the twentieth Century*. Baltimore: Johns Hopkins University Press, 2017, p. 4.

⁹ Idem, *Ibidem*.

¹⁰ Idem, *Ibidem*.

it was a crucial element of modernization and nation-building¹¹. However, in Portugal, the manifestation of eugenic precepts to improve the genetic quality of the human population or attempts to prevent people reproduction with undesirable features were not extensive or institutionalized, namely through government policies and systematic practices. Eugenic ideas in Portugal were more closely associated with academic debates and public health policy proposals, to emphasize hygiene and disease control rather than to implement coercive eugenic measures¹².

The social Darwinism perspective, advocated by Herbert Spencer, poverty in childhood was often seen as the result of children and their families' "inferiority" or "weakness"¹³. The idea was propagated that many of the features linked to unfitnes — the propensity to idleness, criminality, prostitution, and alcoholism — were transmitted from generation to generation by heredity, (such as hair and eye colour) and would lead to more serious forms of crime or delinquency unless measures were taken to prevent it.

Social Darwinism and eugenics significantly influenced the approach to poverty in childhood policies in the 19th and 20th centuries. Both movements had visions of society that influenced social policies and practices, often in harmful and discriminatory ways. There are many examples in which the defense of these ideologies allowed for situations of justified discrimination and abuse, such as the people mentally or physically incapacities forced sterilization, eugenic marriage laws, genocide, and embryo selection, among other human rights violations¹⁴.

Although it could be argued that we are dealing with ideologies that are considered obsolete nowadays, the interest to study the relationship between these theories and the development of public policies lies, recognise and reflect on the policies evolutionary trajectory been linked to precepts that have acted as determinants of the success or failure of childhood protection measures. In other words, policy measures arise from a decision-making process that determines the choices for a particular government action program, which unfolds within a specific context and timeframe that begins

¹¹ TURDA, Marius. "Legacies of eugenics: confronting the past, forging a future" In *Ethnic and Racial Studies*, v. 45, n. 13, 2022, p. 2471.

¹² CLEMINSON, Richard Mark. "Entre a eugenia germânica e a latina: Portugal, 1930-1960 Analysis" In *Hist. Ciências da Saude-Manguinhos* 23 (Suppl1), Dez 2016.

¹³ MARTÍNEZ, Manuel Moix. *Introducción al Trabajo Social*. Madri: Trivium, 1991, pp. 177-188.

¹⁴ Idem, *Ibidem*.

before the formulation or policies implementation. Government decisions are based on the need to establish priorities within the set of problems detected. In this way, at least two factors can interfere in this decision: ideological criteria, which establish a kind of “should be” or desirable, according to the politically prioritized ends or those considered philosophically more valuable, and technical decisions that guide decision-making, also taking into account the fact that resources are scarce or limited¹⁵.

It is our central aim, with this revisit, to breathe new life into the construction of the of Portuguese policies’ history to assist poor children and families, reviving the commitment to the values of equality, justice, and respect for human dignity, in a continuous and vigilant effort against discriminatory ideologies and practices. Social history is fertile with examples of attitudes that blamed poor people for their situation and justified policies or practices aimed at reducing poverty through eugenic selection, approaches that prioritized assistance only for the most “fit” or “deserving” and discriminated against those considered less capable or worthy of help, including poverty in childhood, or even to create policies that limited access to education for certain groups considered less fit or less able to contribute to society, such as children with intellectual or physical disabilities who were segregated and received limited or inadequate education¹⁶.

Positivist republican scientism recognized the child as a careful subject and then education needed, therefore made it compulsory to guarantee them through the vigilant action of their family, a tutor, or, ultimately, the state. As a preventive and regenerative ideology for with care of needs, monitorization, protection, and education these aspects of children’s rights and public and private duties’ relationship to organize the “construction” of the citizen¹⁷. Children became the social and political concern of crucial importance for the regeneration of the Portuguese nation, both to promote their development and to control the danger that any deviations could pose to social order and peace¹⁸.

According to Fernando Catroga¹⁹, the Portuguese republicans, influenced by positivism and social Darwinism, built a new type of nationalism

¹⁵ GUERRA, Joana. “Sinergias entre a Intervenção Social e as Metodologias de Análise de Implementação de Políticas Sociais” In FIALHO, Joaquim (Org.). *Manual de Intervenção Social*. Lisboa: Sílabo, 2021, pp. 121-140.

¹⁶ LADD-TAYLOR, op. cit., pp. 1-10.

¹⁷ TOMÉ, op. cit., pp. 27-36.

¹⁸ Idem, *Ibidem*, p. 33.

¹⁹ CATROGA, Fernando. *O Republicanismo em Portugal. Da formação ao 5 de outubro de 1910* (I e II vols. Coleção

based on a collective, an altruism, and a solidarity sense. It was based on the belief of a people's history and culture ability to regulate itself when facing the rules of life struggle or the natural selection of the fittest. Far from leading to racist doctrines, the most influential Portuguese doctrinaires, such as Bernardino Machado, Miguel Bombarda, and Afonso Costa, increased Darwinism, built a nationalism with a universalist tendency towards the evolution and progress of humanity, which integrated the nation into the civilized world, into humanity, giving a genuinely Portuguese stamp to the formulation and justification of their programs²⁰.

Afonso Costa invokes the work of Herbert Spencer, entitled *De l'éducation intellectuelle, morale et physique* (1888), to affirm that

[sic] the power of education, which encompasses instruction at all levels, is unlimited. It teaches us to follow the best line of behavior in all of life's situations; to look after the body, to direct the intellect, to govern business, to lead the family. It teaches us the duties of a citizen. It teaches us to take advantage of the pleasures that nature has placed within our reach, to use our faculties to achieve our happiness and the happiness of others, in short, to live a complete life²¹.

Patriotism, duty, solidarity, and responsibility appear as the result of a pedagogical practice aimed at the child's intelligence and emotions, in such a way that citizen is the subject of rights become an object of duties.

[sic] Now, if the loaves do not and cannot know how to educate, if the individuals themselves do not and cannot carefully complete their education, is it because of a lack of will, or because the sloppiness of the public authorities has spread throughout the social body, insinuating dangerous pedagogical norms and letting all the criminal causes run amok against the unfortunate, already deprived of the bread of the body, and thus also deprived of the bread of the spirit?²²

It is very well mentioned in chapter II – The principles of the Socialist School, as outlined in Afonso Costa's aforementioned work, clearly

Estudos). Coimbra: Faculdade de Letras, 1991.

²⁰ Idem, *Ibidem*, pp. 41-58.

²¹ COSTA, Afonso. *Commentario ao Código Penal Portuguez. Introdução: escolas e princípios de criminologia moderna*. Coimbra: Impr. da Universidade, 1895, p. 255.

²² Idem. *Ibidem*, p. 256.

emphasize the importance of education and instruction, while advocating for socialist reforms that call for the establishment of legislation to protect the ‘underprivileged’, with a significant role for the state.

The defense of intervention possibility with poor populations is much more oriented to ethical and moral education from childhood; the promotion of family and community environments that reinforce ethical behavior; the adoption of public policies that encourage the moral virtues practices and train moral development programs to individuals of any age, than the defense of interventions on physical factors related to heredity.

Education for a job and education through practice was the guide-line behind the support programs for the most disadvantaged, abandoned, and delinquent. As bourgeois virtues, the child should learn to be a “sober, active and clean citizen, not proud, irascible or frivolous, while should have good feelings, virtues, and character, respect the environment, preserve the health of body and soul and foster the cult of work and energy and the socialization of an optimistic and Promethean ethic”²³.

The social, hygienic, and educational assistance schemes aimed at poor children developed with a dual purpose: on the one side, as a matter of law and social justice, and on the other side, as the only mean to face disease and crime. In Rosa Tomé’s view, the centrality of poverty issues as the cause of social ills made poor families in cities a privileged object of intervention that was now required not only on political grounds but also on scientific ones²⁴.

Children’s education then had the dual function of prevention and scholastic, ethical, and aesthetic training, subsidized by the development of pedagogy and experimental psychology. The end of repressive and punitive educational practices was called for, replaced by indications of the duty to love, protect, treat, instruct, and stimulate, with the total exclusion of inhumane punishments. At this stage, the importance of the pedagogues contributions, such as Friedrich Fröbel and Maria Montessori spread with new precepts and methods of children’s education. In Portugal, the work carried out by Father António Oliveira took the risk of proclaiming the removal of children from the Penal Code and their rightful place in the Portuguese education system.

The Republicans’ concern led to a strong investment in working-class families and children who interpreted, in terms of social danger, had become

²³ CATROGA, Fernando. “A Importância do Positivismo na consolidação da Ideologia Republicana em Portugal” In *Biblos*, 1997, p. 263.

²⁴ TOMÉ, op. cit., pp. 61-86.

the favored target of a surveillance and control policy, marked by a strong institutional presence, aimed to protect those most deprived as early as possible. Education and pedagogy were the flagships of regeneration²⁵, in the case of poor children by a system of surveillance underlying their school career. In all the measures presented below, the expression of pedagogical optimism is the cornerstone that supports the ideological dimension of the children protection measures.

Historical and legal background for the creation of the 1911 Child Protection Act

The historical and legal background that we intend to present is a contribution to understand the social and political relevance that poverty in childhood and childcare represented in Portugal. It is a question to recognize the decision-making process regarding the choices made for a given government action program, which took place in a period before the formulation of the law in question. Exposing the genesis of the Child Protection Law²⁶ takes us back to forums other than the public sphere, since the background of this law in terms of children's protection is practically non-existent. Even so, in the public sphere, we are left with a mention of the Constitutional Charters of 1826 and 1836, since they refer charity to the state administration, as a public and municipal service. It was the Constitutional Charter of 1826 that laid down the right to public assistance under the heading "The provisions and guarantees of the civil and political rights of Portuguese citizens": "The Constitution also guarantees public assistance" (art. 145 § 29), also stating that "Primary education is free to all citizens" (§ 30)²⁷. The Portuguese Constitution of 1838 (1838-1842) once again included public assistance in the "Rights and Guarantees of the Portuguese": "Article 28 — The Constitution also guarantees: 1. Free primary education; 2. Establishments where the sciences, letters, and arts are taught; 3. Public assistance; [...]"²⁸.

On 6 April 1835, a decree created by the General Charity Council, responsible for a national program to eliminate begging, with the fundamental

²⁵ See the preamble of the Law. PORTUGAL. *Decreto com força de lei de 29 de março, reforma o ensino infantil, primário e normal*. Diário do Governo n.º 73. Ministério do Interior, Lisboa, 1911a.

²⁶ PORTUGAL. *Decreto com força de lei de 27 de maio, cria instituições de protecção às crianças e regula a respectiva organização*. Diário do Governo n.º 137. Ministério da Justiça, Lisboa, 1911b

²⁷ LOPES, Maria Antónia. "Os socorros públicos em Portugal, primeiras manifestações de um Estado-Providência (séculos XVI-XIX)" In *Estudos do Século XX*, v. 13, Coimbra, 2013, p. 260.

²⁸ Idem, *Ibidem*.

principle of the value of work as a regenerator of character. It aimed to centralize and coordinate all charitable and social assistance activities, creating a unified structure to manage charities, hospitals, and other assistance organizations. Recognizing the need to protect the “indigent”, organizations such as asylums, Kindergartens, nursing homes, and night shelters were set up^{29 30}. This program managed to help hundreds of “indigents” across the country, but in light of the seriousness of the poverty problem in Portugal, it was far from being extinguished. Beggars were arrested, and the disabled were supported, but the root causes of poverty and begging were not tackled, so this serious social problem lasted. The infant mortality rate was extremely high, with approximately 19 percent of newborns being abandoned or left orphaned, often placed in the care of charities or public institutions³¹. During this period, Portugal had one of the highest rates of illegitimate births in Europe and the scenario of the breakdown of preorganized public and private assistance revealed a lack of child protection^{32 33}.

In 1851, the General Charity Council was reorganised and given the task of running pious establishments and hospitals. By decree of 4th October 1899, it was incorporated into the General Directorate of Health and Beneficence, reorganised and regulated. In this context, in 1901, the General Regulation of Public Health and Charity Service had to supervise and administer health and charity services assigned to the state. Regarding this regulation, the Superior Council of Charity was tasked to study the organization and improvement of public assistance services and institutions, proposing reform plans, organizing medical and charitable home care, and leaving the state with the role of supervisor³⁴.

We cannot fail to note that it was during this period that began political incursions into the field of public health. The frequent confrontation with serious epidemic outbreaks of infectious and contagious diseases and the proliferation of epidemiological studies on social diseases highlighted the importance of hygienic conditions and environmental sanitation

²⁹ LOPES, Maria Antónia. “Políticas assistenciais em Portugal no ‘Despotismo Iluminado’ e na Monarquia Liberal”. Comunicação apresentada no IX Congresso da Associação de Demografia Histórica. Ponta Delgada, 2010, p. 16.

³⁰ MARTINS, op. cit., p. 90.

³¹ Ibid, p. 57.

³² TOMÉ, op. cit., p. 70.

³³ LOPES, Maria Antónia. *Crianças e jovens em risco nos séculos XVIII e XIX. O caso português no contexto europeu*, 2002, p. 7.

³⁴ MARTINS, op. cit., p. 95.

in substantially reducing morbidity and mortality³⁵. In this process, the configuration of the hygienist state became clear, it represented a turning point in relations between society and the state. The hygienist state aimed to protect society as a whole in the name of the collective interest or public good³⁶. The public authorities did not hesitate to intervene in situations of epidemic outbreaks, even though liberalism was theoretically suspicious of state intervention in different sectors of society.

A new attempt to regulate and reorganize public assistance came about in 1903 with Bill 32-B. One of the main features of this proposal was the decentralization of the organization of public assistance and the mandatory collaboration between public and private assistance. Assistance included children's protection and the elderly home care. Its functions were limited to give advice and promote compliance with laws related to education, vaccination, health, and hygiene. Those who did not want to work, alcoholics, professional beggars, and prostitutes were excluded from this support. According to Alcina Martins, "assistance is associated with a function of surveillance of the poor, counselling, education of customs and moralization of behavior"³⁷. This law never got off the drawing board and in 1905, Lisbon's public charity services were created, tasked with organising requests for help and formulating, by means of the most rigorous enquiries, an opinion on whether each applicant deserved help.

On 25 May 1908, the Chamber of Deputies was asked to reintroduce the bill aimed to protect pregnant women and early childhood. Responsibility to implement this legislation on the ground lay with the government, but also with local councils, with the direct collaboration of the health and administrative authorities. The proposed measures included free medical care, the creation of maternal and child dispensaries, subsidies and financial benefits for poor mothers and families, helping to guarantee minimum living conditions and nutrition for children, and health education programmes for mothers, teaching good hygiene, nutrition, and childcare practices. Despite the good intentions and the obvious need for such measures, the 1908 bill faced several barriers that prevented its enactment. The political instability of that time in Portugal, the resistance of conservative sectors who did not

³⁵ GUERRA, Joana. "Políticas de Saúde em Tempos de Crise(s)" In ALBUQUERQUE, Cristina (Org.). *Políticas Sociais em Tempos de Austeridade*. Lisboa: Pactor, 2016, p. 179.

³⁶ GARNEL, Maria Rita, "Os médicos, a saúde pública e o Estado improvidente (1890-1926)" In *Estudos do Século XX*, v. 13, pp. 281-308, 2013.

³⁷ MARTINS, op. cit., p. 97.

see public health and social assistance as a priority for the state and the country's economic limitations were all factors that once again led to the postponement of government action in line with the social and economic reality of the early 20th century. Despite everything, it can be considered that the foundations were laid for future political initiatives to create measures and reforms to improve maternal and childhood care and their conditions of living for children and mothers in Portugal.

It is therefore worth noting that the state and the monarchical-liberal regime played an important role in public assistance and that the charitable institutional network was not only not supervised or funded by the Catholic Church, but that it practically did not employ members of the clergy and that private charities were subsidised by the central government³⁸. In fact, as far as children's protection is concerned, it is within civil society that we can find actions with the greatest capacity to intervene on poor children's realization. The illustrative example, we can allude to the French-inspired Casas de Asilo movement in Portugal (*salles d'asile*, founded by Jean-Frédéric Oberlin from 1769), which aimed to provide children with both protection, education and instruction³⁹. Since the constitutional monarchy, the Sociedade das Casas de Asilo da Infância Desvalida de Lisboa (SCAID) has been an example of this welfare⁴⁰. SCAID's aim was to:

to protect, educate and instruct poor children of both sexes, from the time they left the mother's milk diet until the age of 7, thus allowing their parents to freely indulge in their daily occupations, indispensable for earning the pecuniary means with which they had to meet the expenses that their daily needs obliged them, convinced that their children were under the shelter of an institution that would advantageously replace their care⁴¹.

In fact, the Portuguese Asylum Houses were distinguished from their French and English counterparts by the dual purpose of combining social or welfare purposes on pedagogical or educational goals.

³⁸ LOPES, op. cit., "Os socorros públicos em Portugal...", pp. 259-280.

³⁹ FERNANDES, Rogério. "Orientações Pedagógicas das 'Casas de Asilo da Infância Desvalida' (1834-1840)" In *Cadernos de Pesquisa*, n. 109, 2000, pp. 89-114.

⁴⁰ GOMES, Joaquim Ferreira. *A Educação Infantil em Portugal*. Coimbra: Instituto Nacional de Investigação Científica. Centro de Psicopedagogia da Universidade de Coimbra, 1986.

⁴¹ Internal regulations of the Asylum Houses for Destitute Early Childhood, 1851, art. 1, p. 3, taken from FERNANDES, op. cit., p. 99.

This extract refers the entry of poor children up to the age of 7 as the favoured recipients of these Asylum Houses. This determination is significant if we remember that child labour was a common practice and widely accepted due the economic need, families and educational lack alternatives. In 18th century Europe, there were no official regulations or minimum age for child labour. Children started working at a very young age, often as young as 5 or 6, in hard working conditions and with no access to formal education. It was not until the 19th century that the first legal stipulations began to appear and decreed a minimum age for starting work, as in the case of the Factory Act of 1833 in the United Kingdom. The definitive ban on child labour came in 1973, decreed by Convention 138 on Minimum Age for Admission to Employment, convened by the Governing Body of the International Labour Office⁴².

A second comment on this excerpt expresses the legitimacy of the intervention of these welfare and educational institutions, arguing that the aim is to create opportunities so that parents could to work fully and both guarantee their family's livelihood. Parents, fearful but attracted by the offer of protection and food for their children while they were at school, gradually joined the new educational and welfare project.

In Lisbon, the first Casa de Asilo (Asylum House), the Escola de Ensaio (Rehearsal School) was home to just 21 children, who had been recruited from poor neighbourhoods thanks to the efforts of Ana Mascarenhas de Ataíde, who had knocked on doors to convince needy families to hand over their children to this charitable establishment⁴³.

The asylums provided them free hospitality, education, and instruction to the poorest children of both sexes, who were of the age and in the circumstances determined by special regulations (Article 2 of the Statutes of the Coimbra Charity Society for Asylums for Destitute Children). The Casas

⁴² Legal antecedents of Convention No. 138 — Minimum Age for Admission to Employment: the Minimum Age (Industry) Convention of 1919, the Minimum Age (Sea Work) Convention of 1920, the Minimum Age (Agriculture) Convention of 1921, the Minimum Age (Trimmers and Stokers) Convention of 1921, the Minimum Age (Non-Industrial Employment) Convention of 1932, the Revised Minimum Age (Sea Work) Convention of 1936, the Revised Minimum Age (Industry) Convention of 1937, the Revised Minimum Age (Non-Industrial Employment) Convention of 1937, the Minimum Age (Fishermen) Convention of 1959, and the Minimum Age (Underground Work) Convention of 1965. PORTUGAL. 58th General Conference of the International Labour Organization: Convention No. 138 - Minimum Age for Admission to Employment. Geneva, International Labour Office Governing Body, 6 June 1973. Available at: https://gddc.ministeriopublico.pt/sites/default/files/documentos/instrumentos/convencao_138_oit_idade_minima_admissao_emprego.pdf

⁴³ FERNANDES, op. cit., p. 95.

de Asilo's educational and welfare project was forged under the precepts to protect, educate and instruct. The Houses' Internal Regulations set out what was meant by each of these actions:

Protection meant supporting and sheltering children, keeping them clean, and promoting the progressive development of their faculties, keeping them away from all dangers through continuous vigilance. Education, on the other hand, would consist of strengthening in children the habits of cleanliness, order, obedience, decency, and respect, considered to be the mainstays of life in all social classes, and developing in their hearts, through a childhood habit, the fundamental bases of the Christian virtues; namely, love for God, continuous respect for his presence, and brotherly love for other people. Finally, the instruction would center on teaching pupils the fundamental truths of Christian doctrine, elements of sacred history, elements of reading and arithmetic, as well as a "stockpile" of useful and customary notions, especially maxims and moral precepts "within the reach of the first age". As for the girls, they would also be taught the manual labour considered appropriate for their sex and age⁴⁴.

In the 1910-1911 school year, there were 12 Asilos in Lisbon (Menino Deus, Junqueira, Calafates, Sant'Ana, Lapa, Santa Quitéria, Ajuda, Arroios, S. Vicente, Esperança, Santa Engrácia, Olivais) that cared for 1,520 children. In Lisbon, Asilos da Infância Desvalida were set up in various cities across the country, such as the Asilo da Infância Desvalida in Coimbra, founded on 10th April 1836. In effect, the Asylum Houses for poor children played a vital role in the structure of social assistance in Portugal, offering an institutionalized solution to the problem of child neglect and extreme poverty among children. Their work was guided by the principles of Christian charity, which emphasized the importance of formal education and discipline as vital tools for character development and preparation for adult life. They encouraged to work as a means to achieve self-sufficiency and promoted moral values and good manners and cultivate morally responsible citizens. These institutions played a significant role in the context of social welfare, before the implementation of more comprehensive public policies and structured social protection systems that would emerge throughout the 20th century.

⁴⁴ Idem, *Ibidem*, pp. 100-101.

The fall of the monarchy and the establishment of the republic brought with it a series of social and political changes in Portugal. Among these changes was the need of a reform in institutions and laws, including those related to child protection.

In the social field, the legislation enacted by the Minister of the Interior, António José de Almeida, aimed to restructure public assistance services, creating a national fund aimed primarily to help the indigent and reduce begging. Thus, the 1911 legislation established official and free education for all children at infant and primary level and compulsory schooling between the ages of 7 and 10, with up-to-date methods and subjects compared to other European countries. Temporary mobile schools were also created, especially for teaching adults⁴⁵. A new regime required far-reaching changes considered essential for the modernization of the country and their impact on building a psychological barrier between the monarchical past and the republican present.

In 1911, two significant milestones in legislation contributed to the expansion of state intervention in the fields of health and social assistance: the right to public assistance was recognized in the Constitution of the Republic, by Article 29, and the creation of the Directorate-General for Health. The 1911 Child Protection Law was a significant step for Portugal in aligning itself with international concerns about the children's rights and welfare. Portugal took an European legislation as examples [the Guizot Law in France (1833), the Factories Act in the United Kingdom (1833), and the Patronage of Children Act in Spain (1904) to enact its child protection law.

A new period in the fight against poverty in childhood in Portugal

Shortly after the proclamation of the Portuguese Republic on 5 October 1910, it was the 1911 Child Protection Law that significantly marked a fundamental change in the country's approach to children's rights⁴⁶ and protection and was presented as "the broadest and easiest path to the patriotic dream of regenerating the Portuguese family, which aims to educate, purify

⁴⁵ SOUSA, Fernando de.; PEREIRA, Conceição Meireles. *Os Primeiros-Ministros de Portugal 1820-2020*. Imprensa Nacional, 2021, p. 51.

⁴⁶ CASTRO, José; FERREIRA, Jorge Manuel Leitão; CAPUCHA, Luís. "Uma análise histórica do sistema de proteção de crianças portugueses: que lições para o futuro?" In *Sociologia, Problemas e Práticas*, n. 102, pp. 59-78, 2023.

and harness the child”⁴⁷. We are facing a new period in the evolution of the fight against poverty in childhood in Portugal, with reforms that introduced regenerative policies inspired by reason, equity, and science and distinctive of the constitutional monarchy era.

Afonso Costa, in charge of the Ministry of Justice in the Provisional Government, commissioned Father António de Oliveira to draw up draft laws for the protection of minors in moral danger, perverted or delinquent, in order to preserve and reform⁴⁸. Recognizing Father António d’Oliveira’s experience and his astute pedagogical vision of destitute, abandoned or delinquent children turned him into the mentor and main proponent of the 1911 Child Protection Law. The jurist and the writer Sousa Costa was appointed by Afonso Costa to help draft the bill and in one of his works, he describes Fr António Oliveira’s powers as follows:

[...] [sic] But he knew everything that, in the family unit, causes the infection and illness of the members in physical and moral formation; but he knew everything that, in the meanderings of the city, drags minors devoid of soul goods, education and will, to the scoundrel and crime; but he knew everything, from science acquired in the laboratory and in the infirmary, which should be applied to them as a preventive resource and as a curative medication. He was a free master and a chaplain at the University of Life. So when he had to climb Mount Sinai to pass on the Law to his people, he, who knew nothing of what was in the codes and grammars, saw it, grasped it, absorbed it overnight in the light of the burning bush of genius⁴⁹.

On the occasion of his death in 1923, Catanho Meneses asked the Senate of the Republic for a vote of regret, saying the following:

[...] [sic] dedicated himself extraordinarily to the protection of destitute children. Until 1911, little attention had been paid to childcare in Portugal, and it was Father Oliveira who drafted the decree, or at least provided the necessary elements for the drafting of the first decree, which was of 27 May 1911, which

⁴⁷ PORTUGAL. *Diário do Governo*, n.º 137, de 14 de junho de 1911, p. 2530.

⁴⁸ GOMES, Joaquim Ferreira. “O Padre António de Oliveira (1867-1923), Grande Educador” In *Interações Sociedade e as novas modernidades*, n. 1, 2002, p. 114.

⁴⁹ Idem, *Ibidem*, p. 121.

created this remarkable institution called the Tutoria da Infância (Tutiring of Childhood)⁵⁰.

It is undeniable that the construction of this law was the responsibility of a recognized man, a priest, and a pedagogue, with a vast experience in children's protection contexts. His legacy became a timeless and a very important contribution to the humanization of educational institutions and legal institutions. Perhaps that is why Sousa Costa ends his description by saying: "Father António makes his Love Poem, the Law of 27 May..."⁵¹

While reading the preamble to the LPI⁵² carries with it the expression of the scientific principles of Law and Pedagogy that could lead to the improvement of children, increasing their knowledge, capacity for work, discipline, and morality. But "it is a decree in which, in many of its articles, the heart replaces intelligence – the heart, aided by the memory of facts, carefully analyzed and thought about"⁵³.

The justification to put child protection on the political agenda was the horror of the extreme poverty experienced by families begging on the streets of Portuguese cities:

Every night, as we leave the theatres, and especially on cold and rainy nights, we find on the street corners, slumped on the ground, ragged women with five or six little children around them, crying and begging - they are, in most cases, rented children, whose display each night provides a living for two families⁵⁴.

Because of the high infant mortality rates, the high number of children abandoned and left to their own devices, involved in prostitution, vagrancy, and begging, and children left to parents who, due to their poverty, were unable to educate them and provide a healthy physical and moral environment.

The 1911 IPL proposes normative solutions based on the following precepts:

⁵⁰ REPÚBLICA PORTUGUESA. *Diário do Senado*, Sessão n.º 75 (Extraordinária), em 26 de setembro de 1923, p. 3.

⁵¹ Idem, *Ibidem*, p. 121.

⁵² PORTUGAL. *Diário do Governo*, n.º 137, de 14 de junho de 1911, p. 2530.

⁵³ Idem, *Ibidem*.

⁵⁴ Idem, *Ibidem*.

[sic] Only with children educated in a disciplined school system, with scrupulous moral hygiene, instructed in the knowledge of things and in the practice of the sentimental laws that form characters, of the social laws that form positive activities, will it be possible to constitute a society that joins the salubrity of customs with the fruitful anxieties of knowledge and work⁵⁵.

The triple purpose to protect, regenerate, and make it useful will be the foundation of a decree made up of 184 articles and which essentially created the following institutions: the Children's Guardianship⁵⁶ (or Juvenile Court) (articles 1 to 16) and the National Federation of Friends and Defenders of Children (articles 112 to 131). Inherently, the remaining articles are dedicated to the different forms of disqualification from parental or guardianship powers (Articles 17 and 25); minors in moral hazard (Articles 26 and 27); abandoned minors (Articles 28 and 38); poor minors (Articles 39 and 40); ill-treated minors (Articles 41 and 57); unloved minors (Articles 41 and 57). Art. 41 and 57); destitute: idle, vagrants, beggars, or libertines (Art. 58 and 61); juvenile delinquents, miscreants, or criminals (Art. 62 and 68); undisciplined (Art. 69 and 72); pathological abnormalities (Art. 73 and 75)⁵⁷.

The creation of children's guardianships is a historic milestone, as it essentially removes poor, destitute, or abandoned children from a legal environment (sentences, sanctions, and enforcement of penalties) intended for adults, under the Civil and Criminal Procedure Codes, which did not include an interpretation of childhood as distinct from adulthood. "This new body behaves like a good family father, in love with truth and justice, and always in the children's interest [sic]"⁵⁸. The idea is reinforced that the purpose of child tutoring is more to prevent, and heal, than to punish in the true sense of the word. "It prescribes a process of a moral therapy to prevent hygiene

⁵⁵ Idem, *Ibidem*.

⁵⁶ For a more specific reading on the influence of hygienic and eugenic thought on the actions of the Porto Children's Tutelage, consult WEBER, Maria Julieta.; MATOS, Patrícia Ferraz de. "Melhorar a Espécie Humana desde a Infância: eugenia e higiene mental no Brasil e em Portugal (primeira metade do século XX)" In *Zero-a-Seis*, Florianópolis, v. 25, n. 47, Universidade Federal de Santa Catarina, jan/jun., 2003, pp. 16-40..

⁵⁷ POIARES, Carlos Alberto. *Edição Comemorativa da Lei de Protecção da Infância*, 27 maio 1911. Lisboa: Instituto da Segurança Social, 2010.

⁵⁸ PORTUGAL. *Diário do Governo*, n.º 137, de 14 de junho de 1911, p. 2530.

against crime, before the crime, and of curative hygiene against the consummated crime, to avoid its repetition”⁵⁹.

It is within this framework of responsibility for abandoned, poor, and mistreated children that the state’s commitment arises to protect them for as long as they are unable to declare themselves emancipated through work and responsibilities and to remove them from environments considered harmful to their development.

This decree provides solutions for each circumstance, providing measures to preserve the child, such as supervised liberty, placement in foster families, internment by sentence, and promotion and education services choice; punishment to adults responsible for causing any children’s harm; participation of legal guardians in the process to approach educational and corrective action, the inhibition of parental authority more broadly, thus minimizing the damage caused by family environments. This decree marks a decisive shift towards a differentiated right, of a preventive, tutelary and an eminently subjective nature, but essentially rescues the condition of a poor child justified by family, social, and environmental conditions, making any reference to physical factors or heredity disappear⁶⁰.

To finalize, it should be said that the enthusiasm with which the 1911 Child Protection Law was received led to a subsequent effect on Portuguese legislation. The number of pieces of legislation that, from 1911 onwards, regulated the organization and competence of children’s courts, the measures applicable to minors, the exercise of parental authority and related institutes, the constitution and functioning of both the central services and the establishments dependent on the Directorate-General, the ways of filling the various posts on the staff lists, among others, multiplied⁶¹.

Although this decree represented a breakthrough in the chapter on criminal law for minors compared to the previous period, the subsequent legislation failed to completely emancipate itself from the repressive spirit that animated the old institutions, making suffering, the feeling of social disapproval, or moral responsibility where the minor prevail⁶².

⁵⁹ Idem, *ibidem*.

⁶⁰ Cf. Lei de Proteção à Infância, Menores em perigo moral - artigo 26º in POIARES, op. cit..

⁶¹ Preamble of the Decree-Law n.º 44287, 20 de abril de 1962. PORTUGAL. *Decreto-Lei n.º 44287, promulga a reforma dos serviços tutelares de menores*, Diário do Governo n.º 89/1962, 1º Suplemento, Série I de 1962, pp. 479-512.

⁶² Idem, *ibidem*

Conclusion

The implementation of the entire republican legislative apparatus in favor of the regeneration relied on a bureaucratic and judicial apparatus built up throughout the 19th century. In the case of the Child Protection Law, it was possible to see that the role of the State when determined public intervention benefited from the experiences of civil society and private institutions supporting poor children and families. Although eugenic measures appeared to be the solution to the social problems caused by the degeneration of the race, the Portuguese political decision-makers of the First Republic defended the idea of a preventive function of intervention in children, the power of education for regeneration and the existence of differentiated institutions according to the case-by-case nature of the problems. We had the opportunity to analyze a law that, despite the enormous advance it represented in legal and pedagogical terms regarding the child's conception, persisted, in the look of the present eyes, with a stigmatizing dimension to poverty, since it was seen as a determinant of misconduct and crime. Although there was an understanding that the reasons for poverty were environmental, the subject (children and families) was always the epicentre of the diagnosis and treatment of the effects of that same poverty, and so the focus of intervention on the real causes of poverty of a macro-social nature very weak. In addition, the process of categorizing children, enshrined in the law and intended to define the predictability of phenomena, ended up to standardize intervention scenarios. Many other study variables about the situation of the child and their family would be dispensed with, jeopardizing an adequate diagnosis of poverty in childhood conditions at the beginning of the 20th century in Portugal.

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As good as so good: Afro-Brazilian speeches, racism, and nation-building in Bahia (1889–1937)¹

Tão bom como tão bom: discursos afro-brasileiros, racismo e projeto de nação na Bahia (1889–1937)

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Abstract

This article aims to discuss how Afro-Brazilians positioned themselves between 1889 and 1937, in the face of racist practices and discourses. At this time, the construction of a national project that was incompatible with the large contingent of non-whites that made up the Brazilian demographic picture was discussed. The first forty-eight years of the republican regime in Brazil was the period in which the ruling classes, as part of their project for the nation, put into practice racist ideas and a series of eugenicist measures, with the aim of leading the Brazilian population to a physical and behavioral type closer to those of Europeans. The choice of Bahia as the geographical landmark of this work was due to the fact that it was the unit of the federation with an Afro-Brazilian majority in the period, and because it had an important pole that irradiated racist ideologies in the country, the first Faculty of Medicine, in Salvador. From journalistic sources, literary texts, articles and academic productions of the period it was possible to discuss and analyze racial ideologies, as well as how Afro-Brazilians reacted to them from their discourses, social practices and strategies to confront racism.

Keywords: History. Race Relations. Culture and Society. Bahia. Brazil.

Resumo

Este artigo discute o posicionamento dos afro-brasileiros face às práticas e discursos racistas. O marco cronológico do artigo refere-se a um período de

* PhD in History from the Universidade Federal Fluminense (UFF). Postdoctoral studies in History at the Universidad de Las Palmas de Gran Canaria. Full Professor at the Universidade Estadual de Santa Cruz (UESC). E-mail: fgsantos@uesc.br.

¹ This text is a modified excerpt from the master's dissertation: DOS SANTOS, Flávio Gonçalves. *Os discursos afro-brasileiros face às ideologias raciais na Bahia — 1889/1937*. Dissertação (Mestrado em História). Salvador: Universidade Federal da Bahia, 2001. The phrase As good as so good was very common among former slaves after the abolition of slavery, used to assert their equality with other sectors of Brazilian society, as if May 13th were the pure and simple marker of their freedom. “[...] As good as so good is the phrase continually on the lips of individuals of low condition’ — as an author wrote in 1894 [...]”. SILVA, Eduardo. *As Queixas do Povo*. Rio de Janeiro: Paz e Terra, 1988, p. 78.

discussão de um projeto de nação que excluía a população afro-brasileira. O marco geográfico do artigo definiu-se pelo fato da Bahia abrigar um grande contingente de afro-brasileiros e ser, também, um polo de produção e difusão de ideologias raciais, a partir a Faculdade de Medicina e da atuação de intelectuais com Nina Rodrigues. O foco no posicionamento dos afro-brasileiros tem por finalidade evidenciar suas percepções do racismo científico e suas estratégias para invalidá-lo. Utilizou-se como fontes periódicos e trabalhos acadêmicos de afro-brasileiros e de ideólogos do racismo do período.

Palavras-Chave: História do Racismo. Relações Raciais. Cultura e Sociedade. Bahia. Brasil.

Introduction

In Brazil, between 1889 and 1937, the construction of a national project that was incompatible with the large contingent of non-whites that made up the Brazilian demographic picture was discussed. The initial forty-eight years of the Brazilian republican regime was the period in which the ruling classes, as part of their project for the nation, put into practice racist ideas and a series of eugenicist measures, with the aim of bringing the Brazilian population to a physical and behavioral type closer to those of Europeans.

How did Afro-Brazilians position themselves in the face of such racist ideas of the period?

This was the question that permeated the research. In the process of the investigation, two types of response were noted: one linked to popular culture — understood here as the interpenetrations, in Brazil, of cultures of African, indigenous and European matrices reread and manifested by the common sense of the population — and the other to bourgeois culture and science — understood here as the approximations and rereading's made in Brazil, by the dominant classes, of the Judeo-Christian, rationalist, scientific and capitalist models of Western societies, in particular the French, Germanic and Anglo-Saxon.

The choice of Bahia as the geographical landmark of this work was due to the fact that it was a unit of the federation with an Afro-Brazilian majority in the period, and because it had an important center for the dissemination of racist ideologies in the country, the first Faculty of Medicine, in Salvador. Figures such as Nina Rodrigues, Afrânio Peixoto and other ideologues of scientific racism of the nineteenth and twentieth centuries passed through it.

The text will stick to the academic discourses of Afro-Brazilians and, with the reader's permission, will evoke the memory of three characters who helped in the journey in search of answers. The first is a fictional character of Jorge Amado, Pedro Arcanjo from Tenda dos Milagres, the other two are Manoel Raymundo Querino and Édison Carneiro. It is possible to discuss and categorize his actions from the Gramscian concept of organic intellectuals, but this is not the main objective of this article and this would imply exploring other conceptual categories that would make the text longer and perhaps denser, which is not the purpose for which it is intended at the moment.

Putting ideas in place

At the end of the nineteenth century until the first decades of the twentieth century, there was a discussion in Brazil of a national project and the disputes around the constitution of a hegemonic class, as a result of the end of slavery and the monarchy. For this reason, the term “ruling classes” is understood in this text as a group of people who, having access to the various instances of power — political, economic, ideological — monopolize the State and other institutions for their own benefit. According to Gramsci:

[...] that a class is dominant in two ways; it is both ‘leading’ and ‘dominant.’ It leads allied classes and dominates opposing classes. Therefore, a class, even before coming to power, can be ‘leading’ (and it must be), and once it attains power, it becomes dominant while also continuing to be ‘leading.’².

Cardoso also clarifies that a dominant class, that is, “the one that controls the State and imposes themselves on the other classes through the juridical-political apparatus” become a leader when, in addition to controlling the State, “it establishes organic relations with civil society”, and at the same time acquiring the capacity to be dominant and leading, hegemonic³.

And although capable of joining actions, this group is heterogeneous — in its formation, interests, and expectations — to the point of conflict with each other for to prevail of their political purpose. He finds his amalgam in opposition in most of the majority subordinate to him.

² GRAMSCI, Antonio. *Quaderni del carcere: edizione critica a cura di Valentino Gerratana*. Torino: Einaudi, Q 1, § 44, 1977, p. 41.

³ CARDOSO, Franci Gomes. “Classes sociais e construção da hegemonia das classes subalternas” In *Revista de Políticas Públicas*, v. 22, pp. 403-418, 2018, p. 408.

Thus, when one enunciates ruling classes accompanied by an adjective — such as republican, national, or regional — one wants to highlight the distinction of intellectual, social and cultural project of this group in relation to the others, in the dispute for hegemony in society.

However, it is necessary to state that most of the Nation projects discussed in the period did not include the significant contingent of Afro-Brazilians in the country. The reason for such negligence must be attributed to the hegemony of racist ideas and ideologies in the political thought of the national ruling classes.

the black race in Brazil, no matter how great its countless services to our civilization have been, will always form one of the factors of our inferiority as a people [...] we consider the immediate or mediate supremacy of the black race harmful to our nationality⁴.

The prevalence of racist ideologies can be understood based on the science and the mindset of those times as a strategy of the central colonialist countries (France and England) subordinating peripheral countries, located in Latin America, Asia and Africa⁵. These ideologies were used to justify the technological gap of these countries based on internal demographic issues, such as, the large population contingents of non-Europeans and the high rates of miscegenation. The central colonialist countries presented themselves as a model to be followed. On the other hand, so that this subordination of the peripheral countries to be effective, it was required the acceptance of these racist theses by national ruling classes.

In the specific case of Brazil, adherence to ideologies was almost immediate. The ruling classes differed in detail due to their heterogeneity of education, education and interests, but they always positioned themselves in accordance with these racial ideologies.

The motivations for such prompt adhesion are anchored in the issues raised with the enactment of the Eusébio de Queiroz Law, which determined the end of the slave trade in 1850. The end of the slave trade meant for Brazil not only a crisis in the system of production based on compulsory labour,

⁴ RODRIGUES, Raimundo Nina. *Os africanos no Brasil* [online]. Rio de Janeiro: Centro Edelstein de Pesquisas Sociais, 2010, pp. 14-15. [https://doi.org/10.7476/9788579820106]

⁵ QUIJANO Aníbal. “Colonialidad del poder, eurocentrismo y América Latina” In LANDER, Edgardo. (Org.). *La colonialidad del saber: eurocentrismo y ciencias sociales*. Buenos Aires: CLACSO/UNESCO, 2000.

but also a threat to the system of social hierarchies structured on the basis of social relations and slave production.

The Brazilian ruling classes rushed to create social hierarchies that would maintain the already established order. And, because they condemn the same contingent subordinated by slave relations, racial ideologies were used systematically and were perfectly suited to this purpose. The same obstacles imposed by slavery for the integration and social ascension of Afro-Brazilians in Brazilian society were replicated by racial ideologies. They endorsed social and institutional practices that depreciated Afro-Brazilians, based on their presumed biological and cultural inferiority in relation to whites. In fact, racial ideologies have not only maintained the status quo, but have increased the mechanisms and excuses to prevent not only the ascension, but also the social inclusion of non-whites.

However, with the same attributes and stereotypes with which Afro-Brazilians were classified within the country, Brazil was classified by the central colonialist countries — England, France, Germany — on a global scale. This fact provoked a deep malaise in the Brazilian ruling classes. Hence, the adoption of eugenicist policies, which, between 1870 and 1930, had as their main instrument the immigration of European labour subsidized by the Union and state governments.

To justify the exclusion of Afro-Brazilians from social activities, including work, numerous studies were produced during this period, trying to demonstrate the corrupt and degenerate character of Afro-Brazilians. Marco Aurélio Luz reminds us that:

To the extent that blacks are considered citizens, and not semovents, the inequality circumscribed in the legal sphere gains a formidable ideological reinforcement to give a 'scientific' basis to racism⁶.

Lilia Schwarcz argues that originality of Brazilian intellectuals was manifested by the ability to accommodate the two current models in force at that time and opposites in essence, liberalism, that proposed respect for the individuality of men, and racial theories, which proposed the difference between men based on physical and biological features. Joining them with their gaps, to give shape to a national project, these intellectuals created an

⁶ LUZ, Marco Aurélio. *Agadá: a dinâmica de uma civilização africano-brasileira*. Salvador: Conselho Editorial e Didático da UFBA/SECENEB, 1995, p. 259.

effective mechanism of control and subordination portion on the population who was under the rule of slavery and other forms of domain⁷.

Another point that was widely discussed at the time was public health and sanitation in cities. Racial theories and hygienist ideas were consensual at the beginning. Afro-Brazilians were, by definition, the sick who compromised the health of cities and the progress of the country. Sanitizing has removed them from urban areas.

Thomas Skidmore gave an example of the thinking of part of the Brazilian ruling classes when he reported the position of Monteiro Lobato in relation to the figure of a “caboclo” (a Brazilian indigenous representation, of coppery skin and physical features of the European white man), in his work *Preto no Branco: raça e nacionalidade no pensamento brasileiro* [Black on white: race and nationality in Brazilian thought].

Monteiro Lobato idealized his Jeca Tatu as a metaphor for the Brazilian who gained national notoriety in a 1919 presidential campaign, Rui Barbosa used it to denounce the country’s socioeconomic crisis. Lobato’s character functioned as a herald of those who defended the adoption of eugenicist measures, believing that they would solve the public health problems for themselves.

However, the advancement of scientific research in the sanitation area made Lobato promote the raising of his Jeca Tatu, who, after the visit of some doctors, was healed of his diseases, turning himself into a hard-working and intelligent man. According to Skidmore, the principle that led to Monteiro Lobato’s conversion was that “Jeca Tatu was not like that, he was like that. Science had come to rescue the country”⁸.

This was an idea manifested since the first half of the 19th century, as shown in the work *A morte é uma festa* [Death is a party] by João Reis⁹. In this work, the author identifies the commitment given by doctors in urban sanitation in the belief of a redemptive science and guardian of civilization.

These doctors, [...] believed themselves able to carry out the ‘progress of the homeland’ because they had the knowledge

⁷ SCHWARCZ, Lília Moritz. *O Espetáculo das raças: cientistas, instituições e questão racial no Brasil, 1870-1930*. São Paulo: Companhia das Letras, 1993, p. 17.

⁸ SKIDMORE, Thomas E. *Preto no branco: raça e nacionalidade no pensamento brasileiro*. Rio de Janeiro: Paz e Terra, 1976, pp. 193-204.

⁹ REIS, João José. *A morte é uma festa: ritos fúnebres e revolta popular no Brasil do século XIX*. São Paulo: Companhia das Letras, 1991.

to do so. The political highlight they had evidences a group in the struggle for the imposition of an ideology that included the country's urban sanitation, although it is not confined to this¹⁰.

Iraneidson Santos Costa analysed in more detail the relationship of Bahian doctors regarding the population of colour of Salvador city, at the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th. His study is about the formation of a school of Forensic Medicine in Bahia and its relationship with the theses of Criminal Anthropology in Europe. In this work, the use of deterministic racial theories related to Criminal Anthropology in Bahia is discussed and analysed the actions of nationally and internationally renowned intellectuals, such as Nina Rodrigues, Oscar Freire and Estácio de Lima. These characters were committed to establish the criminal potential of Afro-Brazilians and preached eugenicist measures intended to rid society from the imminent danger of racial degeneration, represented in the figure of the mestizos¹¹.

However, it was well evident the unfeasibility of these eugenicist measures. Firstly, they were very long-term investments, making the financial cost extremely heavy for the state coffers. Secondly, these investments were not having the expected effect, since they were based on false premises, such as the infertility of mestizos or the biological inferiority of the non-whites.

Realizing the little effect of these eugenicist policies, the ruling classes converted the discourse in a prejudiced and conservative way, exalting the melting pot of the three races (indigenous, white and black) for the formation of the Brazilian people, thus creating the myth of racial democracy, associated with the idea that from miscegenation the Brazilian would be converting in the long term into a new race. The conditions for this change in position on the issue of race were also closely linked to a change in the course of the international policies of the central colonialist countries.

With the rise of Nazi-fascism in Germany and Italy, ideologically constructed from the notion of biological superiority and inferiority of the races, as well as in the establishment of racial hierarchies that had the Aryan race as their ideal model, there is a dispute between these “new central countries” and the “old” ones. These disputes resulted in the World War II (1939-1945).

¹⁰ Idem, p. 252.

¹¹ Idem, p. 182.

The former central countries, France and England, promoted the softening of the racial ideological discourse, choosing the strand that privileged cultural racism, thus emptying the idea of a supposed biological superiority indifferently on the race. The notion of superiority or inferiority came to be focused in cultural terms, measured from technological development. This way, the Nazi-fascist discourse was also emptied.

In Brazil, from the 1930s onwards, the tropicalist theses of Gilberto Freyre began to be adopted by the ruling classes. It was during the government of Getúlio Vargas that they were widely disseminated to the entire body of the society. From then on, miscegenation was assumed and ideologically reconstructed in scientific, literary and artistic areas, being considered a mechanism for the cultural elevation mechanism of populations of African and indigenous origin to reach the level of Europeans. This new view, although intolerant of the African demographic and cultural presence, was not compatible with previous racial postulates that saw miscegenation as a sign of backwardness and incivility¹². However, it did not favour non-whites or modify their insertion in Brazilian society. On the contrary, there was intolerance towards their costumes and practices. The national ruling classes intended that mestizos or those with fair skin to their similarity, that is, a European behaviour is adopted. The hierarchization of races and the internal colonization of whites over non-whites perpetuated in Brazil the same principles of the colonial and slave hierarchical structure.

Science at the service of racism

Concerned by the glaring Africanization of Brazilian customs, the ruling classes used racism, sometimes disguised as an aura of search for civilization, as an expedient to contain the imminent “immediate or mediate supremacy of the black race”, considered “harmful to the [...] nationality”¹³.

The term race, an European creation par excellence, in Brazil, was used not to compromise the current social hierarchies. Although in some strongholds of society, such as the academia or the Parliament, the concept of race has been used explicitly, most of the time it has been associated,

¹² SCHWARCZ, op. cit., pp. 235-250.

¹³ RODRIGUES, op. cit., p. 7. Regarding the apprehension of Bahian elites regarding the Africanization of customs, see: VIEIRA FILHO, Rafael. *A africanização do carnaval de Salvador, BA – a recriação do espaço carnavalescos (1876 - 1930)*. Dissertação (Mestrado em História). Pontifícia Universidade Católica de São Paulo, 1995 e FERREIRA FILHO, Alberto Heráclito. “Desafricanizar as ruas’: elites letradas, mulheres pobres e cultura popular em Salvador” In *Afro-Ásia*, n. 21-22, 1998.

confused or even replaced by another term also in vogue in the same period: the concept of civilization. Generally, racist attitudes manifested by the press, spokesmen pretended the extinction of primitive habits for the interests of the ruling classes, associated with those who had left captivity.

The national ruling classes proposed, in the name of civilization and progress, the cultural and demographic elimination of the Afro-Brazilian elements from the country. Their presence was considered a great shame for the nation. In his point of view, Brazil was doomed to backwardness as long as it did not go through a process of racial cleansing.

If the term (civilization) “expresses the consciousness that the West has of itself”, the Brazilian ruling classes did not like the consciousness they had in their country and unconsciousness of themselves¹⁴. From their point of view, there was nothing to be proud of. Brazil was considered by Europeans as a primitive country and equated to African continent. This was an unbearable prospect for a group that held itself in high regard and was ashamed of the indigenous and African blood which flowed in the veins of their members, but not of having made a fortune by indulging in the compulsory labour of Africans and their descendants.

Thus, the frustration of the Brazilian ruling classes when compared to the populations of European nations was fed and, at the same time, fed racist considerations. From such ideas, widely disseminated among the educated sectors of that time, Brazilian intellectuals began to reflect on the country. To solve specific problems of Brazilian society or to propose some kind of public policy to improve the country’s demographic profile, scientists, linked to the interests of the ruling classes, adapted to the Brazilian reality considerations made by social Darwinism or by the geographical determinism of Ratzel and Buckle, thus contributing with racist theoretical formulations and concepts¹⁵.

The notion of race has influence all considerations about Brazil, its society, its population and especially its development. These reflections began within the Medical Universities, Law, Geographical and Historical Institutes, in short, in the institutions in which intellectuals gathered to reflect on Brazilian society. The issue of races in Brazil was seen, above all, as a public health issue, which urgently needed to be taken from epidemics to criminal acts, according

¹⁴ ELIAS, Norberto. *O processo civilizador* (volume 1). Rio de Janeiro: Jorge Zahar, 1994, p. 23.

¹⁵ Friedrich Ratzel (1844–1904) was a German ethnologist and geographer, now regarded as one of the leading figures of Modern Geography and recognized as the founder of Geographical Determinism. Henry Thomas Buckle (1821–1862) was a British positivist historian whose work *History of Civilization in England* had a significant influence on Brazilian intellectuals in the 19th century.

to the current thought of that time, the racial issue was at the centre of the discussion: diagnosis and dosage¹⁶.

Science, personified in the figure of doctors, showed its deep uneasiness in relation to the Brazilian demographic composition – already with a high degree of miscegenation. Doctors did not shy away from interfering in the various sectors of society to supported their theses¹⁷.

It is in no other way that Nina Rodrigues criticized the jurists and legislators who drafted the Penal Code of 1890. She even stated that the focus of attention of the Penal Code was wrong because it should not be focused on the crime itself, but on the criminal. He wrote a book in which he argued that punishments should be differentiated for each race and, perhaps, for each region, according to its position on the evolutionary scale.

In such a country (Brazil), the germ of criminality – fertilized by the degenerative tendency of miscegenation, by the dominant impulsiveness of inferior races, still marked by the infamous stigma of slavery recently extinguished, by the general consciousness, about to be formed, of the inconsistency of the penese doctrines founded on free will – sown in such fertile and carefully tilled soil, will force to produce crime in luxuriant vegetation, truly tropical.

III. I may delude myself, but I am profoundly convinced that the adoption of a single code for the whole republic was a serious mistake that greatly undermined the most elementary principles of human physiology.

Due to the marked difference in its climatology, the conformation and physical aspect of the country, its diverse ethnic population, which is already so pronounced and threatens to become even more pronounced. Brazil must be divided, for the purposes of criminal legislation, at least into its four great regional divisions, which, as I demonstrated in chapter 4, are so natural and profoundly distinct¹⁸.

It is clear that Nina Rodrigues used an argument based on both evolutionary doctrines and climate determinism. Her criticism of the Brazilian legislators who drafted the Penal Code of 1890 focuses on two aspects: I – The non-observance of the principles of human physiology; II – The adoption of

¹⁶ SCHWARCZ, op. cit., p. 191.

¹⁷ Idem, p. 182.

¹⁸ RODRIGUES, Raimundo Nina. *As raças humanas e a responsabilidade penal no Brasil* [online]. Rio de Janeiro: Centro Edelstein de Pesquisa Social, 2011, p 76.

penal principles based on ideals of free will. A mistake in Nina Rodrigues' opinion, as these are principles that admit that all men have the same ability to evaluate their actions. According to his ideals, this would be the same as comparing an adults' judgment capacity as a child. In other words, he believed that blacks, indigenous people, and mestizos were evolutionarily like children, just as the Aryan races were like adults. Hence, his struggle for the variation of the degree of criminal imputability, taking into account the racial origin of the individual¹⁹.

Nina Rodrigues was one of the first Brazilian intellectuals to be interested in the influence of former slaves and their descendants in the formation of Brazilian society. So he founded what can be known as the first Criminal Anthropology School in the country. This school proposed the framing of individuals in scales of marginality and dangerousness based on their physical features. The further away from the European type – Aryan – the more “intense” to civilization and the more socially dangerous²⁰.

The selection of races in an electoral context

One of the confrontations between the oligarchies of Bahia and those of São Paulo and Minas Gerais, in an attempt to put Bahia back in a more evident position in the national political scenario and perhaps get out of the abandonment to which it was relegated by the coffee and milk policy, took place at the same time as the presidential election in 1919.

Epitácio Pessoa and Ruy Barbosa would compete the election. In the Bahian newspapers, there was a whole climate of antagonism. Ruy Barbosa is acclaimed “The national candidate”, while preaching the ineligibility of Epitácio Pessoa. In this electoral dispute, what drew the most attention, and which is of particular interest to this work, is the emphasis given to the racial issue.

The ineligibility of Epitácio Pessoa is publicized because of his participation in the Peace Conference that took place in Versailles, where he defended, together with the President of the United States, Woodrow Wilson, the inequalities of the human races. In Brazil, the reactions to this attitude were of widespread dissatisfaction. It is always said: [...] we cannot deny the juridical equality of races, simply to please our American friends,

¹⁹ Idem, p. 49.

²⁰ COSTA, op. cit., pp. 41-49.

who voted against it [...] ²¹. Although this reveals an apparent paradox, since Epitácio Pessoa's vote could be considered consistent with the belief, and even with the public policies adopted by the elites of that period, some sectors of the elites led by Ruy Barbosa, Miguel Calmon and some other politicians and intellectuals, transformed Epitácio Pessoa's vote into one of their banners of struggle and electoral campaign. Protest rallies proliferated across the country. From blacks and workers, to sectors of the high intelligentsia demonstrated in newspapers and in the public square against the vote given by Epitácio Pessoa.

Ruy Barbosa knew that, if he wanted to be elected, it was necessary to position himself in relation to the constructed image of Bahia as a land of degenerate mestizos. To do so, he used Jeca Tatu, the character of Monteiro Lobato, as a way of denouncing the country's crisis and, at the same time, criticizing the governing political group for its incompetence in dealing with the issue ²². The character extracted from the pages of *Urupês* was a metaphor for the Brazilian people, mestizo, lazy and degenerate. Their few qualities were attributed to their European heritage and what was understood as vicious behaviours, was attributed to their indigenous matrix. The African was definitely not part of his anatomical-cultural constitution. Jeca Tatu will thus serve, both to demarcate Ruy Barbosa's position in the field of "public health" issues, to denounce the country's crisis and, mainly, to remind the people of Minas Gerais and São Paulo that they were as mestizo as the Bahians.

The strategy was not successful and the candidate of the hardline defence of Brazil's whitening won the victory. Despite all the movement against the vote of Epitácio Pessoa at the Congress of Versailles, the coffee and cattle raising oligarchies of the South managed to impose their candidate.

Far from being homogeneous, the national ruling classes did not have only one project for the nation. They gave another demonstration of their divergences on the racial issue, on the occasion of the vote of the Brazilian representation at the Congress of Versailles. In fact, they feared that Brazil would suffer a colonization process similar to those in developing countries, on the African and Asian continents, but they could not reach an agreement.

[...] But the evil vote to which he refers is precisely the inequality of races and peoples, one before another; from which it must be inferred, since if the Japanese, strong, armed, numerous

²¹ O IMPARCIAL. "Sem título", Salvador, 22 de abril 1919, p. 1.

²² SKIDMORE, op. cit., pp. 193-204.

and efficient people, are inferior to the people of the United States, the mass of the Brazilian population, a virile and hopeful offspring, but recent and not yet armed and prepared, of various races, whose fusion only presumed ignorance and scolding would not know here, cannot claim a better qualification when confronted [...]”²³.

The way to avoid this daunting possibility was to try to civilize the country—read: whiten the country, or rather, to intensify the process that had already been underway since the mid-19th century. With the figure of Emperor Dom Pedro II no longer present—the scholar, the man of science, who projected a favourable image of Brazil in Europe and, in their eyes, represented a son bringing enlightenment to the wilderness—there was a fear that the country might lose its sovereignty²⁴. It was urgent to civilize the nation, to get rid of the remnants of the colonial past, whether in architecture, traditions, hygiene habits, in short, in everyday uses and customs considered backward and uncivilized, attributed to blacks and mestizos.

In Bahia, this concern was even more pronounced. In every street, in every corner, in every building in the city, you could see the remnants of a past that you would like to forget. The streets were still a space of Afro-Brazilians experiences and survival, who were already beginning to dispute this space with families who wanted to adopt French style. And the newspapers were already shouting:

[...] The streets and squares of the city, without exception, besides the grass, are daily, and to our shame they are full of all the debris, all the dirt, everything that speaks to uncleanness [...] the residents of Bahia get used to the electric tram, the garden without railings, the up-to-date fashions, everything good and bad, that comes to us from abroad, and takes time to subject to the good practices of good hygiene. Compared to certain capitals of Brazil, large and small, Bahia looks like a backyard. And a Bahian house backyard [...] The backyard here, a kind of so-called kitchen leftover of primitive men, is like the sewers of Paris to receive everything [...]”²⁵.

²³ O IMPARCIAL. “Sem título”, Salvador, 18 de maio 1919, p. 1.

²⁴ SCHWARCZ, op. cit., p. 31.

²⁵ DIÁRIO DE NOTÍCIAS. “Sem título”, Salvador, 25 de outubro 1912, p. 5.

While other capitals were modernizing, “[...] Salvador remained inert, paralysed in time, preserving memories of colonial times [...], both habits of population and materially [...]”²⁶. The waves of civilized Europeans did not arrive in their territory. At the same time, the action of São Paulo agents within their hinterlands was witnessed, seducing the sertanejos to go to São Paulo, to get job careers in regions where Europeans refused to go, further aggravating their labour crisis. In 1933, Antônio Vieira de Mello criticized the secundarization of the national workers in the north of the country in favour of the European settlers, in his words²⁷:

[...] several foreign owners, were all unanimous in sustaining the superiority of the Brazilian by resistance, fidelity to commitments, agility of learning and the spirit of order [...]²⁸.

Meanwhile:

[...] it is universal knowledge — that Brazilians always have the heaviest work of felling, and that foreigners find flattened ground in their roughest lines. The farmers, after using the northerner for the heavy, dismiss him to make room for the European settler [...]²⁹.

This article by Antônio Vieira de Mello could well be an aside in the defenses made about a project of agrarian policy for Brazil. He adopted, in this debate, conservative positions favorable to the current landowner model, differing, however, in the definition of who would serve as labor in the country’s productive activity. Alberto Torres³⁰, for instance, proposed the use of the “national element”, thus approaching the new racial paradigm, which did not see the need of promoting whitening of the population, as he believed in the adaptability of Afro-Brazilians to the tropics³¹. Oliveira Viana, in turn, considered it not only necessary to maintain the landowner model, but also remained faithful to the previous racial postulates, considering the

²⁶ Idem, p. 51.

²⁷ A lawyer and journalist, promoter of the work of Alberto Torres and a member of the Society of Friends of Alberto Torres, he took part in the expedition that would lead to Armando Magalhães Correia’s book *Os Sertões Cariocas*, published in Rio de Janeiro by the National Press in 1936.

²⁸ O IMPARCIAL. “Sem título”, Salvador, 17 de novembro 1933, p. 4.

²⁹ Idem.

³⁰ Alberto de Seixas Martins Torres was Governor of Rio de Janeiro from 1897 to 1900, a journalist, and one of the few intellectuals of the late 19th and early 20th centuries who did not criticize Brazil’s racial composition and identity.

³¹ TORRES, Alberto. *A organização nacional*. São Paulo: Ed. Nacional, 1978, pp. 114-147.

use of European labour necessary³². Thus, although the divergence regarding the definition of the labour to be used in Brazil was not new, it dated back to at least 1870, the year the Law of Free Womb was signed, resisting until the 1930s. It placed the northeastern and southern landowners in opposite camps³³.

In the acceleration of the urbanization process, this problem was not restricted only to rural workers, but also transcended to the sphere of urban work with the beginning of the country's industrialization process³⁴.

Although the sharp clash, the Brazilian ruling classes was accentuated with the increase in the importance of the cities, with the emergence of the workers' movement, the shock of the Bolshevik revolution in Russia and with the white European socialist and anarchist contingent, until the 1930s the main attention was devoted to the maintenance of an agro-export model of development and, therefore, to the problems faced by rural landowners.

Issues of Brazil labour and racial profile were closely linked, the arrival of European workers was expected so that they could improve the racial composition of Brazil. In the dispute for arms for their crops, Bahian rural landowners were doubly excluded from the process. First, they had to move to their labour force to the southeast region and, second, because they knew that the scarce resources of the State would not be able to face without the support of the Union's resources, their lands colonized.

Nina Rodrigues had stated that "[...] the existing blacks will soon be diluted in the white population and everything will be finished [...]". Afrânio Peixoto predicted that:

These passing sub-races tend to disappear, reintegrating the white race into an exclusive possession of the land. There was also a Portuguese advantage: the interbreeding with the black, exterminating them in the successive dilutions of white blood in which they would drown, with the African slave trade ceasing once and for all. In more than three hundred years, we will all be white³⁵.

³² OLIVEIRA VIANNA, Francisco J. *Evolução do povo Brasileiro*. São Paulo: 1930, pp. 185-186.

³³ ANDRADE, Manoel Correia de. *Abolição e Reforma Agrária*. São Paulo: Ática, 1987, p. 26.

³⁴ HASENBALG, Carlos Alfredo. *Discriminação e desigualdade racial no Brasil*. Rio de Janeiro: Editora Graal, 1979, pp. 166-167.

³⁵ PEIXOTO, Afrânio Júlio. *A esfinge*. Rio de Janeiro: Livraria Francisco Alves, 1919, p. 400.

Miscegenation was one of the ways pointed out to solve the racial issue in Brazil. However, the Bahian ruling classes were facing with another problem: how to civilize the State of Bahia without the introduction of European settlers? There was a risk that would resemble even more to the Coast of Africa.

And what about blacks and mestizos, Afro-Brazilians, so often disliked and marginalized because of their descent and the inheritance of a slave past? How did they get involved with public policies that directly affected them? How were their habits and social interactions shaped in the name of an idea of “civilization”?

Fresh out of slavery, they had a very bold proposal. They sought to imprint their forms of relationship, their work relations, in short, their features on Brazilian society. In this situation of cultural contact, they were seduced by their customs and were seduced, partially or entirely, by the same ideals and practices that aimed at their social exclusion, but not necessarily with the same perspective as the ruling classes.

Their practices and their discourses were interspersed with vagueness, contradictions and reformulations. The advances and setbacks were evidenced by the fact that they were cultural manifestations and, as such, suffered the effects of a cultural circularity and underwent new elaborations³⁶.

In my opinion, the intellectuals presented below have a lot in common. They were Afro-Brazilians who dedicated themselves to the study of preservation of the Afro-Brazilian culture; all of them had a militancy on the side of the working class and placed them as intellectuals at the service of the people³⁷.

Pedro Arcanjo, as a character of Jorge Amado, is a literary amalgam of many individuals' experiences such as Luís Anselmo da Fonseca, Manoel Querino and Édison Carneiro. Afro-Brazilian intellectuals who opposed slavery and racism. He, as a character, responds to Jorge Amado's desire to position himself in relation to the discussions of the 60s about a “dialectical critique of popular culture”. In this moment of criticism, there is an appreciation of the concept of alienation, and popular beliefs were seen as obstacles to the humanization of the masses because they were alienating factors. They would

³⁶ The concept of cultural circularity is used here with the same connotation given by Mello e Souza, Laura de. *O diabo e a Terra de Santa Cruz: feitiçaria e religiosidade popular no Brasil colonial*. São Paulo: Companhia da Letras, 1986.

³⁷ See: GRAMSCI. Antonio. *Os intelectuais e a organização da cultura*. Trad. de Carlos Nelson Coutinho. 7ª ed. – Rio de Janeiro: Civilização Brasileira, 1989.

be wrapped in a fatalistic and passive mysticism, which would subject the masses to economic yoke and bourgeois domination.

Thus, in the logic of these intellectuals of the 60s, in order to defend themselves, the people had to distance themselves from their irrational beliefs and traditions. “Reason” imposed this distance. However, in Tenda dos Milagres [Tent of Miracles], what stands out are precisely those elements that its authors consciously criticized that task as an amalgam of popular solidarities.

When Arcanjo became a leader leading his people and exercising this role, it went through a process of estrangement or at least distancing himself from the beliefs of the people he claimed to represent and/or defend. However, without being able to break the bond he had with these beliefs, it was through this bond that he was recognized and respected.

In the same way as Pedro Arcanjo, some Afro-Brazilian intellectuals were also part of a great variety of social media, involved in various social struggles, throughout their lives. Some of these, today “illustrious Bahians”, also committed themselves to the defense of the culture and values of “their people”, sometimes as selflessly as the character of Jorge Amado. Manoel Querino and Edison Carneiro are two good examples, each in their own time tried to demonstrate African civilization contribution and sought to understand its role in the Brazilian formation process. They, as Arcanjo, dialogued with the two cultural universes of Bahian society, the popular and the academic; with the knowledge of the Houses of Saints and the circles of literates.

Manoel Querino was linked to the Bahian labour movement of the late 19th and early 20th centuries, and his trajectory as a militant of the working class still needs a more in-depth study. Édison Carneiro was a militant of the Brazilian Communist Party (PCB) persecuted by the Vargas Government and lived in hiding several times. Jorge Amado’s character was involved in the Circular Strike, which earned him the role of leader of the movement and a resignation that threw him into indigence and oblivion³⁸.

³⁸ A movement that took place in the city of Salvador, beginning with a strike by workers of the Circular de Bondes tram company, which later evolved into a widespread protest movement against rising costs of living. It is also known as the “Quebra-bonde” [Tram Break] and is related to the 1930 Revolution and the 15 years of federal intervention in the State of Bahia. See: Negro, Antônio Luigi; Brito, Jonas. “Insurgentes incendiavam a cidade da Bahia. O Quebra Bondes e a Revolução de 30” In *Estudos Históricos (Rio de Janeiro)*, 33(71), pp.579-599, 2020. [<https://doi.org/10.1590/S2178-14942020000300008>].

However, before addressing the contribution of these Afro-Brazilians, it is necessary to point out what this process of estrangement in relation to the culture of origin represents, which is not just a literary resource used by Jorge Amado. He was also present outside of fiction and affected Manoel Querino and Édison Carneiro.

The life trajectory of the historical and fictional characters is marked by being on the borderline, where the dialogue with bourgeois culture and sciences leave marks on their beliefs and ways of acting. For this reason, they cease to be “believers and convinced” to become intellectuals at the service of the poor people.

The appropriation of bourgeois culture and science worked and still works as a form of resistance. Knowing the language and diacritics of the other is a manifestation of power. It is to have a strategy that allows you to use that same language and signs for your own benefit; to construct discourses of oneself, about oneself and about one’s own, having discursive control over one’s own identity. In short, it allows Afro-Brazilians to cease to be the object of the discourse of others, to become producers of discourses about themselves and about the world, based on the formalities and conventions of bourgeois culture and sciences.

Objectively, the fact is not ignored, as already indicated, that this appropriation opened loopholes for co-optation. In the specific case of Querino and Carneiro, the negotiated values were incorporated and began to influence reading these Afro-Brazilian intellectuals about their way of life and customs and popular classes. However, this co-optation is punctual and not exclusive, not least because bourgeois culture and sciences also merge with popular and Afro-Brazilian culture, blending, in the agreements they establish among themselves, what is conventionally called common sense.

The speech of Afro-Brazilian intellectuals

The approaching of Afro-Brazilian intellectuals to the pattern of bourgeois culture and science was one of the ways of insertion in society and the development of strategies to deconstruct stereotypes around themselves. However, the use of these diacritics was not without criticism and ridicule. The most immediate reaction was to disavow and mock the Afro-Brazilian who dared to issue an opinion that was not at least consensual.

This was the purpose of the newspaper *O Tempo* [The Time] when it published a note of repudiation of the article *A Bahia Caloteira!* [Bahia the deadbeat], published by the newspaper *A Tarde* [The Afternoon]. The article protested against the non-payment of salaries to primary school teachers and said, among other things:

The principle of tyranny has always been cruelty, the sacrifice of freedom, the elevation of servility, the love of darkness, and hatred of the teacher of childhood. Sad misfortune that forces me to despair of life to scream: I am condemned to starvation because I am not paid long months from 1918 to 1919!³⁹.

The newspaper *O Tempo* launches itself into fury to refute the article *A Bahia Caloteira!* without, however, rebutting with arguments the accusations of delay in teachers' salaries. He chose to deal with the issue by pointing the finger at Professor Cincinnato da Franca, personifying the dispute, and then disavowing and demoralizing him. This behaviour exemplifies an intolerant attitude from Brazilian society towards criticism. Illustrative of this posture is the way in which the newspaper *O Tempo* begins the text of the repudiation note:

Any idiot, really pernestic and, like all of them, with no composure, with no grammar, devoid of sense, devoid of criteria, got a tremendous discomposure in Bahia yesterday afternoon. The anagosado style, however, flagrantly betrays the author of the mystify, a black girl, taken from the know-it-all, who wants to take revenge in Bahia on the boos with which the cheerful kids mark their passage through the streets, pointing, harassing, harassing the – Fessô⁴⁰.

To disqualify Professor Cincinnato da Franca, the newspaper *O Tempo* used some words that function as stigmas, insignia launched that will disqualify any relatively educated Afro-Brazilian. In this strategy of disqualification it is recognized some mastery of the diacritical signs of bourgeois culture and science but in a clumsy way. Expressions such as pernestic and “taken from the know-it-all” are used, suggesting a diminished dominance that the Afro-Brazilian makes a point of exaggerating and trumpeting to the winds.

³⁹ Idem.

⁴⁰ O TEMPO. *A fama do Cincinnato*, Salvador, 15 de outubro 1919, p. 2.

What could be more annoying to a republican and post-slavery ruling classes than a “Slash” Afro-Brazilian, that is, who possesses and competently uses the diacritical marks and information of bourgeois culture and science?

It is in this full of conventions environment and expectations regarding the conduct of Afro-Brazilians that Édison Carneiro and Manoel Querino develop their research and write their works. In their own way, each of them tried to demonstrate the importance of Afro-Brazilians in the Brazilian sociocultural formation.

Édison Carneiro (1912–1972)

An intellectual with a degree in Law and ever-diligent to include a more scientific character to his studies, Édison Carneiro was led from an early age to attend the Santo festivities in Salvador. Here he found in his own father the example and the guide for his incursions into the world of Afro-Brazilian culture and traditions⁴¹.

Édison Carneiro, Couto Ferraz and Reginaldo Guimarães organized, in Salvador, the II Afro-Brazilian Congress in 1937. Unlike the First Afro-Brazilian Congress in Recife, the Bahian edition congress, the depositories of Afro-Brazilian culture were on the same level as national and foreign scholars on the subject, with a speech of authority, using the diacritical signs of the dominant culture, ceasing to be just an object of others speech and becoming a producer of speeches about themselves⁴². This, perhaps, was the greatest contribution for the young Édison Carneiro and Afro-Brazilians did not figure in this event only as an object of science.

In a particular way and which concerns too different from those of Manoel Querino, Édison Carneiro sometimes did not spare him criticism. He was more sympathetic to Nina Rodrigues⁴³. What was Édison Carneiro looking for with his studies?

Before trying to answer this question, it would be better to try to understand what are their concerns and considerations in relation to Afro-Brazilians. In other words, what did Édison Carneiro believe?

⁴¹ OLIVEIRA, Waldir Freitas; LIMA, Vivaldo da Costa. *Cartas de Édison Carneiro a Artur Ramos: de 4 de janeiro de 1936 a 6 de dezembro de 1938*. São Paulo: Corrupio, 1987, pp. 25-26.

⁴² Here, diacritical marks are understood as elements that serve to distinguish and define space and forms of coexistence between two groups.

⁴³ Édison Carneiro was, alongside Arthur Ramos, one of the most active members of the so-called Nina Rodrigues School, meaning he was a perpetuator of the ethnographic studies left by Nina Rodrigues.

Like every ethnologist of his time, Édison Carneiro believed that the phenomena and manifestations he dedicated himself to his studies were about to disappear; therefore, it was urgent to record and analyse them in order to have a future reminder. He did not believe that reason imposed distancing himself from popular culture. Before that, with a keen eye, he sought to see the resistance and class struggle in the cultural manifestations he studied and. When he did not find them, he did not measure criticism. For example, in an article on samba published in 1936, when analysing the lyrics of some “sambas de roda” [Dancing the samba in a circle], Édison Carneiro seems to be impatient:

The singing, I said, is monotonous. In general, there is only one verse for the solo, one verse for the choir, always in the same sound. Sometimes, but only sometimes, the soil is richer, but samba remains poor in terms of music⁴⁴.

Moments later, he “rejoices” when he finds elements that can be analysed by class conflicts. The tone of his statements reveals what he was looking for:

In addition to the fact that this samba gives us the satisfaction of the Negro for the misfortune of the master, the Negro wants to see the fire working in the sugarcane field and rejoices at the loss of the burning of molasses, — class struggle, exactly!⁴⁵

The samba to which Édison Carneiro refers is the following, and according to himself, it is the “most interesting that he can record due to the reminiscences of slavery, of work in the sugarcane fields and in the mills of the Recôncavo”⁴⁶:

Set fire to the sugarcane ...
- In Canaviá!
I want to see work ...
- In Canaviá!
Look at the ripe cane ...
- In Canaviá!
Ella is green, she is ripe...
- In Canaviá!
To make rapadura ...

⁴⁴ O ESTADO DA BAHIA. “Sem título”, Salvador, 20 de maio 1936, p. 5.

⁴⁵ Idem.

⁴⁶ Ibid.

- In Canaviá!
The mill caught fire...
- In Canaviá!
Burned the molasses ...
- In Canaviá!⁴⁷

And, Édison Carneiro continues his analysis of this samba: we still have here material life giving shape to intellectual forms, — Marx’s superstructure, — corroborating the thesis of historical materialism⁴⁸.

Édison Carneiro’s intention is to connect the elements of resistance, perceived by him in Afro-Brazilian culture, to the Marxist model of explanation. The possibility of successfully carrying out this intent would have transformed the samba into a question of the most interesting and, therefore, worthy of record.

In this aspect, Édison Carneiro approaches the character of Pedro Arcanjo. He “entered into the secret of fortune-telling.” That is, he was an intellectual who dialogued with the two cultural universes: the popular and that of bourgeois culture and science. Therewith, he committed himself to a cause: the socialism, an ideology with an European origin.

For this reason, his ethnologist gaze was concerned with the preservation of the values of tradition, not with the role of Afro-Brazilians in the construction of a new process and dynamic and active cultural elements in the society in which they lived in. It was necessary to record this universe in order to highlight the disobedience of the slave to the plantation owner, from capoeira and candomblé to police repression.

In short, Édison Carneiro was an Afro-Brazilian intellectual who described a path used to be suitable for an European pattern of thought-form than to the Afro-Brazilian, but who nevertheless became, like Pedro Arcanjo, an intellectual for the poor ones, a scholar who gets involved, made a scholar by virtue of his involvement.

Manoel Querino (1851–1923)

When analysing the work of Manoel Querino, we noticed the existence of two recurring ideas. The first is the idea of the cultural and material contribution of Africans to the formation of Brazil. The second is

⁴⁷ Ibid.

⁴⁸ Ibid.

the statement that there is no incompatibility between the ex-captives and the ideal of civilization aspired by Brazilian society. Before that, they had contributed significantly to the formation of the Brazilian culture.

In the case of the article *O colono preto como fator da civilização brasileira* [The black settler as a factor of Brazilian civilization]⁴⁹, published for the first time in 1918, Manoel Querino analysed colonization which places the African contribution to Brazilian civilization on an equal footing relating to other contributions. In doing so, he also positioned himself in the sense of deconstructing the romanticized image of the Portuguese navigator and colonizer. In the exercise, Manoel Querino produces a lucid and still current critique of what would have been the motivating impulses of the Lusitanian awakening for his colony in America. This criticism of the form of colonization also works as an answer to those who claim to defend Brazilian Latinity, forgetting to look at the flagrant African demographic and cultural presence in the formation of Brazilian society.

The historical moment in which Querino writes is very delicate for matters related to issues of recognition of racial contributions. The national and regional ruling classes did not want to see themselves at the head of a country that was considered by Europe as “typically mixed”. It is in this context that Manoel Querino’s article presents a new historical picture, in which the Afro-Brazilian presents themselves no longer as a foreigner, but as an active and constant contributor in the formation of Brazilian society and history.

Using excerpts such as Latino Coelho, Manoel Querino leads the reader to perceive the failure of the Portuguese colonial enterprise as the result of an administrative incompetence⁵⁰:

We legislate, as if Portuguese overseas were the pariahs of the metropolis. We govern, as if Brazil were just an estate, where we brought agages and oppressed day laborers [...]⁵¹.
We declared by attempt that only one press would timidly shed its light in those darkened regions. We condemn literary

⁴⁹ QUERINO, Manoel. “O colono preto como fator da civilização brasileira” In *Afro-Ásia*, n. 13, 1980.

⁵⁰ In a footnote, Manoel Querino indicates that he extracted the quotation from LATINO COELHO, José Maria. *Elogio Histórico de José do Bonifácio*. Lisboa: Typographia da Academia, 1877. Entretanto, ele não informa as páginas de onde retirou o texto.

⁵¹ An expression derived from the French “à gage,” meaning “contracted”. Thus, the phrase was interpreted as: “where we would bring in contracted and oppressed day laborers”.

societies as subversive. We fear that the slightest illustration of thought would rob us of the emancipated colony.

And the same writer added:

What we have left in glory as daring and fortunate navigators, we dwindle in the reputation of energetic and farsighted colonizers.

We conquered India so that strangers could get it⁵².

Manoel Querino goes on to quote the Portuguese writer on half a page, introducing the idea that Portuguese were not able to maintain their conquests. They were the first to arrive in Africa and Asia, making the Lusitanian name known as far as Japan, losing, however, their possessions to other less inert and remissive people who disputed them, took them and enjoyed the benefits that the Portuguese were not able to enjoy.

After situating his reader in the reasons that led the Lusitanians to turn their hopeful eyes to Portuguese America, Manoel Querino once again reinforces the initial idea of Portuguese carelessness with illustration for the benefit of adventure and the sword. To this end, he uses another long quote, this time from General Abreu e Lima⁵³.

The Portuguese were good soldiers and good enterprisers, brave and brave sailors, but they were never known except as conquerors [...]

Of the more distant regions we knew only the riches which served as a stimulus to the covetousness of the new Argonauts; we knew nothing that might be of interest to the sciences and arts, until other peoples also partook of their spoils: it was then that we were able to know the productions of nature in those varied climates⁵⁴.

Querino uses three authors, two of them with a Portuguese origin, to corroborate his perception of the Portuguese colonizer. In the excerpts extracted above, it is noticeable the criticism of Portuguese inability to manage its colonies, the little predisposition to contribute to the construction of knowledge and circulation of information and the inability to maintain the conquests in Asia and Africa. The Portuguese were left with Brazil,

⁵² QUERINO, op. cit., p. 143.

⁵³ Manoel Querino's second critique of Portuguese colonisation was based on a passage from the book *Esboço Histórico, Político e Literário do Brasil*, authored by General Abreu e Lima. However, Querino does not provide details on the page number, location, or year of publication of this book.

⁵⁴ QUERINO, op. cit., p. 144.

Querino observes, through which Portugal had decided to ensure for itself “a prosperous future”.

The words of the authors quoted were used by Querino, within this context, with two interspersed intentions. The first is to support his criticism, to demonstrate that his thought was not isolated. Praxe in the academic environment. With this, he exempted himself from being accused as the author of “nonsense”. The second is to demonstrate his erudition.

His analysis of colonization begins with the relationship established between the settlers and the indigenous people. According to Querino:

Once colonization began with the worst elements of the metropolis, the unsubmitive Indian rebelled against the tyranny and injustice of which he had been a victim, with the exploitation of his activity in the work of the fields⁵⁵.

In the second chapter of his article, Querino dedicates himself to the technical skills that Africans brought to Brazil. According to the author, these skills were acquisitions that came from Arab influence. Brought to Brazil to “replace” the indigenous slaves, considered to be “very fickle and less secure, as it was a very controversial property between the colonists and the authorities”, the Africans were employed to replace Portuguese who came here and, because of their inability to resist the rigour of the tropics or because of their pretensions as nobility, they avoided work of any kind⁵⁶.

In Querino’s argument, it can be seen the maintenance of his criticism from the form and motivation of Portuguese colonization in Brazil. On the other hand, there is also the use of principles of climate determinism to explain the use of the “powerful arm of the African to boost and intensify the production of cereals and sugar cane and to dig up diamonds and precious metals from the heart of the earth”⁵⁷. This line of argument was used both by Europeans to justify slavery, and to later defend racist ideas that justified the backwardness and degeneration of the populations of the tropics.

Querino was unable to resist this deterministic explanation of the conditioning factors for the use of Africans as slaves, in vogue in his time. And he adds:

⁵⁵ Ibid., p. 144-145.

⁵⁶ Ibid., p. 146.

⁵⁷ Ibid., pp. 145-146.

Without this [African slavery], it was difficult if not impossible to catch colonization in the country with the European element, all the more so when it began, apart from the servants of the high administration, the first waves were of exiles, vicious individuals and prison soldiers⁵⁸.

With this statement, Querino suggested that not only was the colonization enterprise feasible with the use of Africans, but also that their coming to Portuguese America was an element of neutralization of the vices brought by the Europeans.

In the excerpt that follows the above quote, Querino tried to demonstrate the influence of the slave on the economic progress of the colony, associating this fact with his personal qualities.

the first gold leaflet found on the bank of the Funil River, in Ouro Preto [Black Gold], by a black gold digger; as well as the discovery of the diamond 'Estrela do Sul' [Star of the South]. Industrious as he was, even with his body addicted by the whips of the overseer, the black slave was always obedient to his determinations⁵⁹.

Stoic, industrious and fulfilling their obligations. It is this image that Manoel Querino built of the slaves. In principle, it can confuse this picture set up by him as a certain passivity of the slave in relation to his oppressors. After all, why would a slave tyrannized by his master be so diligent in fulfilling his tasks?

It would be better to perceive this construction of Querino's speech as a rhetorical resource. He showed a picture of contrasts, an interesting picture to highlight the imperfections of the white settlers and highlight the virtues of the "black settlers", even with little altered colour and the insubmissions and rebellions were softened, but not disregarded.

In analysing forms of collective resistance, Querino continued to seek to highlight the qualities of the "black settlers". He made the choice for the quilombola people, especially Palmares. Once again, he established a somewhat anachronistic comparison between Africans and Europeans.

Greek slaves were instructed both in public games and in literature, advantages that the African enslaved in America was

⁵⁸ Ibid., p. 147. I added the expression African slavery in brackets to situate the context to which the author was referring.

⁵⁹ QUERINO, Ibid., p. 148.

unable to possess, since the rigor of captivity, which did not allow the slightest mental preparation, dulled his intelligence. However, he showed himself superior to the anguish of suffering, and had memorable gestures of revolt seeking to organize himself into independent governments. He knew the warrior organizations and was prepared for the defense of his citadel of Palmares [...]

The Greek or Roman slave, abandoning his mastership, did not think of organizing himself into a regular society of territory that he might seize; he lived wandering or in bands given over to plunder⁶⁰.

In table 1, assembled from the argument of Manoel Querino, it can be seen the main oppositions between Africans and Europeans, identified by him in his article. From this identification, it is possible to note the author's intention to deconstruct two ideas, that the "white European" was superior to other races, as was boasted at the time, and, as a result of this premise, that the presence of the black race was an element of degeneration and social and economic backwardness in the country. Establishing a comparison, Manoel Querino highlighted the contribution of Afro-Brazilians in a different way from what Nina Rodrigues did years earlier.

Table 1: Comparing Africans and Europeans experiences according to Manoel Querino

Europeans and Portuguese	X	Africans and Mestizos
Conquerors and adventurers	X	Settlers
Unprepared as colonial administrators	X	Prepared for Work in America
Unprepared for the climate of the tropics	X	Prepared for the climate of the Tropics
Addicted and not very fond of work	X	Stoic and industrious
Tyrannical	X	Obedient
Slaves Instructed in Public Games	X	Slaves with blunted intelligence
European slaves: when free, wandering marauders	X	Black slave: founder of organized and regular societies

Source: Prepared by the author.

⁶⁰ Ibid., pp. 151-152.

If for Nina Rodrigues the black presence in the Brazilian social composition was an obstacle to the country's development, to Querino, the conclusion is the opposite and more radical. Listing the names of several Afro-Brazilians who somehow shone on the national scene, either for their achievements or for their intellectual competence, Manoel Querino aimed to deconstruct the idea of an intellectual incapacity and the incompatibility of Afro-Brazilians with civilization. That is, stating, unlike Nina Rodrigues, that it is from the black and mestizo presence that the country has become so great.

Querino concluded his article by cheering for freedom of the soil and the mestizo's talent. And, with a very significant verse, especially for the period in which the article was written, it defines the engine of the History of Brazil.

Whoever rereads history
You will see how it was formed
The nation, which has only glory
The African who imported⁶¹.

Final remarks

In the confrontation with racist ideas, the Afro-Brazilian intellectuals addressed in this article did not have, unlike their contenders, the purpose to state the thesis of superiority or inferiority. On the contrary, they preferred to affirm that their contributions to the formation of society were as important as those of the other human groups that made up the Brazilian demographic picture. In the construction of their speeches, they made it clear that the contributions could have been of a different order, but that with equal importance. It was from this understanding that Manoel Querino and Édison Carneiro set up their works. Leading even Querino to make his intention explicit when he said:

Our investigations included the Africans themselves and extended to their most direct descendants, individuals who knew the religious practices of their ancestors. Undoubtedly, African fetishism has exerted a notorious influence on our customs; and we will consider ourselves well paid if the reduced material we have gathered can contribute to the study of national psychosis in the individual and in society⁶².

⁶¹ Ibid.

⁶² QUERINO, Manoel. *Costumes Africanos no Brasil* (volume 15). Rio de Janeiro: Civilização Brasileira, 1938, p. 22.

In this excerpt, Manoel Querino reveals not only his purposes, but also his understanding of the Afro-Brazilian culture role in the formation of the Brazilian society. However, this perception was also involved in a political nature, despite a certain apparent acquiescence to the racial theses of the period, by stating that the features credited to Afro-Brazilians are not exclusive to them:

And, we take the opportunity, we leave here our protest against the contemptuous and unfair way in which they try to depress the African, constantly accusing them of being stupid and rude, with congenital qualities and not a simple circumstantial condition in common, moreover, to all unevolved races. No. Originally, all people were susceptible to this stupidity and were subjugated to the tyranny of slavery, created by the oppression of the strong against the weak⁶³.

Thus, I tried to demonstrate the three main constitutive elements of the Afro-Brazilians speeches related to racial ideologies. The appropriation of the standard of bourgeois culture and science, the deconstruction of the discourse of white superiority and the equalization of the experience of Afro-Brazilians and whites.

The first is the principle of seeking instruments and arguments in the universe of bourgeois culture and science. This stratagem is recurrent and perceptible in both the production of popular and erudite Afro-Brazilian speeches. It worked, on the one hand, to denounce the fragility of prejudiced discourse and, on the other, to demonstrate knowledge of the signs of bourgeois culture and science and scientific concepts.

At this point, the first constitutive element of the Afro-Brazilians speech is associated with the second, that is, the deconstruction of the discourse of white superiority, to affirm theses favourable to Afro-Brazilians. In contact with this bourgeois culture and science, Afro-Brazilians selected the elements who best suited the construction of their own arguments. In fact, with the chosen elements, he reaffirmed his mastery of bourgeois culture and science and the relevance of his arguments. Played as central counterpoints to racist ideology. Most of the time, the categories of analysis, interpretations and arguments were extracted from the theses of scientific racism themselves.

However, the speeches were always nuanced as elements that made up the Afro-Brazilian repertoire and conferred additional rhetorical force.

⁶³ Idem.

Such as, joining in the same discourse evolutionist arguments that suggest the existence of superior and inferior races with a demonstration that “African fetishism exerted a notorious influence” on the customs of a Brazilian society, to conclude that this society found only its glory – its evolution – through the action of the supposed inferior races.

From this point on, the third element, that of equivalence, takes shape. In their speeches, Afro-Brazilian intellectuals defend the thesis that there was an equivalence of the contribution of the three races in the formation of Brazil, that their cultural and religious experiences, their way of life, have the same value as the European experience.

Finally, whether among intellectuals, religious leaders or carnival artists, the statement of Afro-Brazilians has always been the same: “We are as good as we are as good”!

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